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Invertebrate and Ichnofauna of the Upper Campanian Wenonah Formation, Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain, New Jersey and Delaware, USA

By

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ERRATA

Version 2 corrects several issues found in Version 1 after publication. These changes include:

- Added a Wenonah specimen of Asteroidea, f. 11A.
- Fixed spelling of genus *Pyrgoion* to *Pyrgopolon*.
- Removed the section on *Pachydiscus* including figure 161. The specimen is not *Pachydiscus*, but instead a *Menuites*.
- Removed the section on *Placenticerias placenta* (DeKay, 1828), including figure 163. Kennedy and Cobban (1994A) p. 98-99 described several small specimens of *Placenticerias* as being juveniles of *P. placenta*. Weller (1905A1) p. 333 and Weller (1905A2) p. 141 also listed *P. placenta* from the Wenonah. Continued extensive collecting in the Wenonah formation by members of MAPS has failed to yield any *Placenticerias* specimens larger than an adult *Placenticerias minor* Kennedy and Cobban, 1994. As adult *P. placenta* specimens are normally much larger, it is the authors' opinion that the *P. placenta* specimens described by these authors are more likely varieties of *P. minor* or a closely related undescribed species. Updated the synonyms of *Placenticerias minor* Kennedy and Cobban, 1994 to reflect these changes.
- Under phylum Cnidaria Hatschek, 1888, the class that contains the order Scleractinia Bourne, 1900 was incorrectly listed as Anthozoa Ehrenberg, 1834. It has been corrected to be Hexacorallia Haeckel, 1896.
- Added *Turritella vertebroides* Morton 1834, figure 116A.
- *Faujasia chelonium* Cooke, 1953 corrected to *Domechinus chelonium* (Cooke, 1953).
- Fix the caption on figure 27, *Cardium wenonah* Weller 1907.
- Fix the caption on figure 34, *Solyma lineolatus* Conrad, 1871.
- Fix the caption on figure 44 to be *Lima reticulata* (Lyell, Forbes, 1845) from *Pseudolimea reticulata* (LYELL, FORBES, 1845).
- Fix the caption on figure 1: *Etea carolinensis* Conrad, 1875.
- Addition of Figure 97A: *Veniella conradi* (Morton, 1833).
- Fix the caption on figure 2, *Pterocerella* sp.

- Fix the caption on figure 3, *Mataxa elegans* Wade, 1916.
- Addition of figure 149A: *Turbinella alabamensis* (Gabb, 1860).
- Fix the misspelling, *Luisogalateha* on figure 171, *Luisogalatheia cretacea* (Stenzel, 1945).
- Add figure 174A, *Hoploparia gabbi* Pilsbry, 1901.

INTRODUCTION

It has been over 60 years since Horace G. Richards (and others) published the 2-part bulletins describing the fossil invertebrates found within the Late Cretaceous strata of the New Jersey portion of the Atlantic Coastal Plain. Since that time numerous papers and several websites have been dedicated to describing and discussing vertebrate fossils from these strata, but little new work has been done regarding the invertebrates. This current work is an effort to update and augment this very important invertebrate fauna from the Wenonah formation of the Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain (NACP) Late Cretaceous section. The NACP includes Late Cretaceous deposits which outcrop in Central and Southern New Jersey, Northern Delaware and Eastern Maryland.

This work is largely due to the efforts of the Monmouth Amateur Paleontologists' Society (MAPS), its founder Ralph Johnson, and the Delaware Valley Paleontological Society. It is hopefully intended that additional volumes will be forthcoming regarding the invertebrate faunas of other Late Cretaceous formations of the NACP.

The Wenonah Formation consists of fine-grained quartz sand, mica, glauconite and potassium feldspar with small bits of lignite. It is dark to medium gray, usually massive to thick-bedded, but locally thin-bedded and/or cross-bedded. The Wenonah is very micaceous and bioturbated with numerous burrows of the trace fossil *Ophiomorpha nodosa*. These burrows are attributed to the work of callianassid crustaceans.

The Wenonah Formation outcrops in a narrow belt that runs from Sandy Hook Bay in the northeast to just southwest of Oldman's Creek, Salem County, where it pinches out. It is approximately 10 meters thick in Monmouth County and gradually thins to the southwest. The Wenonah is conformable with the underlying Marshalltown formation. Gallagher (1993) describes the Wenonah as grading conformably upward into the overlying Mount Laurel Formation, in the southern portion of the state, and discusses the difficulty in separating the two units, by lithology, for mapping purposes. He previously (Gallagher et al., 1986) suggested

the two units be united into a single unit. Others, (Martino and Curran, 1990 for example) describe the Wenonah/Mt. Laurel contact as transitional. The Mt Laurel and Wenonah formations are largely lacking in fossils in their southwestern outcrops and are difficult to distinguish but in the area of the Crosswicks basin and northeastward both have an extensive and very distinct invertebrate fauna. The respective lithology between the two formations also becomes more distinct. The respective ammonite faunas from the Wenonah below, and Mt. Laurel above indicate a substantial amount of time missing between them.

The term Wenonah was first used by Knapp (1899) to describe a silt and sand unit overlying the Marshalltown formation and underlying the Mt. Laurel formation. Kummel and Knapp (1904) considered the Wenonah to be late Cretaceous in age. Spangler and Peterson (1950) revised the Wenonah formation as a member of the

Matawan Group. Figure 1 shows the relationship of the Late Cretaceous Formations of New Jersey as viewed along strike from the Northwest.

Index fossils include the bivalve *Flemingostrea subspatulata* (Forbes, 1845) reported by Weller (1907) and the ammonites *Placentoceras minor* Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A, *Baculites texanus* Kennedy and Cobban, 1999, *Trachyscaphites pulcherrimus* (Roemer, 1841). Other ammonites include *Menuites portlocki* (Sharpe, 1853), *Didymoceras binodosum* (Kennedy and Cobban, 1994B) and *Nostoceras colubriformis* Stephenson, 1941. These all indicate an upper but not uppermost Campanian age. Wolfe (1976) placed the Wenonah microflora in his CA5A assemblage, considered to be of late Campanian age. Other discussions of the Wenonah formation can be found in Gallagher (1984), Gallagher (1993) and Brown (2019).

FIGURE 4: STRATIGRAPHY OF THE NORTHERN ATLANTIC COASTAL PLAIN CRETACEOUS SHOWING THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE WENONAH FORMATION WITH THE UNDERLYING MARSHALLTOWN FORMATION AND THE OVERLYING MOUNT LAUREL AND NAVESINK FORMATIONS. (FENCE DIAGRAM COURTESY OF MATTHEW GARB).

FIGURE 5: RALPH JOHNSON POINTING OUT THE WENONAH / MT. LAUREL CONTACT ON AN OUTCROP ON RAMANESSIN BROOK, HOLMDEL, NJ

INSTITUTIONAL / COLLECTIONS ABBREVIATIONS

ANSP – Academy of Natural Sciences Philadelphia, AMNH – American Museum of Natural History, CZ – Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, BZ – Invertebrate Natural History Museum, London, CCPM – Cumberland County Prehistory Museum, EML – Ed Lauginiger Collection, KS – Shankle Collection, MAPS – Monmouth Amateur Paleontologists’ Society, NJSM – New Jersey State Museum, UC – University of Chicago, USNM – United States National Museum, USGS – United States Geological Survey, WFIS – Wagner Free Institute of Science

FORMATION ABBREVIATIONS

Tht – Hornerstown, Kt – Tinton, Kne – New Egypt, Krb – Red Bank, Ksv – Severn, Ks – Navesink, Kml – Mount Laurel, Kw – Wenonah, Kmt – Marshalltown, Ket – Englishtown, Kwb – Woodbury, Kmv – Merchantville, Kcq – Cheesequake, Kmg – Magothy, Kr – Raritan, ALKr – Ripley (Alabama), TNKr – Ripley (Tennessee), MSKr – Ripley (Mississippi), GAKr – Ripley (Georgia), NCKr – Ripley (North Carolina), ARKn – Nacatoch Sand (Arkansas), NCKb – Black Creek (North Carolina)

The authors have attempted to provide a comprehensive review of all works on the Cretaceous invertebrates of the NACP. Works from the 19th century include Morton (1830A), Morton (1830B), Morton (1832A), Morton (1832B), Morton (1834), Conrad (1853A), Conrad (1853B), Cook (1868), Whitfield (1886) and Whitfield (1892). These early works, however, used terms for the formations of the NACP like Ferruginous Sands, Lower, Middle and Upper Marls among others. The NACP formations nomenclature accepted today started to appear in the works of Clark (1897), Knapp (1899), Kummel and Knapp (1904). These works, however, still used a mix of the “older” names and the currently accepted names for the NACP formations. Weller (1907) was the first author to use formations listed in Figure 4. For this reason, this review relies on works starting with Weller (1907) which have reported specimens from the Wenonah, with one exception.

Groot, Organist, Richards (1954) identified the Wenonah as occurring in Delaware along the CD Canal and some of those Wenonah attributions are included in Richards, Groot, Germouth (1957), Richards (1958), Howell (1958), Richards and Ramsdell (1962) Subsequent authors such as Jordan (1962), Jengo (1982), Lauginiger and Hartstein (1983), Lauginiger (1988) and DGS (1992) agree that the Wenonah does

not outcrop in Delaware. For this reason, Wenonah species reported by Richards, Groot, Germouth (1957), Richards (1958), Howell (1958), Richards and Ramsdell (1962) are not included in the official Wenonah list, unless the species was reported by other authors. This list of dubious Wenonah species is provided at the end of this paper.

For each species listed, type information, where available, is provided as well as a complete listing of references and specimens from the Wenonah formation. A brief listing of synonyms is also provided but not a list of occurrences for the species from other formations. Photos of specimens from the Wenonah formation are provided where possible. If no Wenonah specimen photo was found, then photos of specimens from other formations are provided. The systematic paleontology is based primarily on the online database MolluscaBase (2020).

NOTE: Several researchers have reported certain species in the Wenonah formation but failed to provide documentation of these occurrences with repositied specimens, photos or locality descriptions. Furthermore, extensive long-term collecting by the authors of this publication have failed to confirm these undocumented occurrences and we therefore regard them dubious. For the record we include a list of these species dubious species at the end of this publication.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

PHYLUM BRYOZOA Ehrenberg, 1831

CLASS GYMNOLEAEMATA Allman, 1856

ORDER CHEILOSTOMATIDA Busk, 1852

FAMILY CHIPLONKARINIDAE TAYLOR AND GORDON,
2007GENUS BASSLERINELLA TAYLOR AND MCKINNEY,
2006*Basslerinella prismatica* (Canu and Bassler, 1926)*Conopeum prismaticum* Canu and Bassler in Wade,
1926: p. 33, pl. 4, f. 7-10, USNM 69967.*Basslerinella prismatica* (Canu and Bassler, 1926).
Taylor and McKinney, 2006: p. 71, pl. 45, f. 1; UNSM
644358; BZ 5081.**Types** – *Conopeum prismaticum* Canu, Bassler in
Wade, 1926: p. 33, pl. 4, f. 9, Lectotype: USNM
69967 (TNKr); Paralectotype: Taylor and McKinney,
2006: p. 71, pl. 45, f. 1, UNSM 644358.**Wenonah Specimens** – MAPS A3955a**Description** – “The zoarium is free, bilamellar, with
fiabellate fronds; the lamellae are separable and
formed of facettes of zooecia prismatic inferiorly. The
zooecia are distinct, separated by a deep furrow,
elongated, elliptical, deep, prismatic, fitted one in the
other, independent and separable; the mural rim is
thin, very oblique; the termen commonly bears short,
flat, scattered spicules. The opesia have the same
form as the zooecia. The interopesia cavities are
small, triangular. The septulae are multiparous.” -
*Canu and Bassler (1926) p. 33.***FIGURE 6: BASSLERINELLA PRISMATICA (CANU AND BASSLER,
1926) A: MAPS A3955A B: MAPS A3556A (CLOSE UP
VIEW) (Kw)***Basslerinella* sp.**Wenonah Specimens** – MAPS A3956a**FIGURE 7: BASSLERINELLA SP. A: MAPS A3956A (Kw)**

GENUS HETEROCONOPEUM VOIGHT, 1983

Heteroconopeum ovatum (Canu and Bassler, 1926)*Conopeum ovatum* Canu and Bassler in Wade, 1926:
p. 32, pl. 4, f. 1-4, USNM 69964; McKinney and
Taylor, 2016: p. 66.*Conopeum parviporum* Canu and Bassler in Wade,
1926: p. 32, pl. 4, f. 5-6, USNM 69965.*Conopeum wadei* Canu and Bassler in Wade, 1926: p.
32, pl. 4, f. 11, USNM 69953.*Conopeum ramosum* Toots and Cutler, 1962: p. 84,
pl. 18, f. 1-4.*Solenophragma ovatum* Voight, 1962: p. 34, pl. 18, f.
1-3; Shaw (1967) pl. 179, f. 3.*Heteroconopeum ovatum* (Canu and Bassler, 1926).
Taylor and McKinney, 2016: p. 66; McKinney and
Taylor, 2016: p. 66.**Types** – *Conopeum ovatum* Canu, Bassler, 1926 in
Wade, 1926: p. 32, pl. 4, f. 1-4, Lectotype USNM
69964 (TNKr); *Conopeum parviporum* Canu,
Bassler, 1926 in Wade, 1926: p. 32, pl. 4, f. 5-6,
Syntype USNM 69965; *Conopeum wadei* Canu,
Bassler, 1926 in Wade, 1926: p. 32, pl. 4, f. 11,
Syntype USNM 69953.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3952c

Description – “The zoarium is free, subcylindrical or somewhat compressed, bifurcated in the same plane. The zooecia are distinct, separated by a deep furrow, elongated, oval; the distal wall is very oblique and bears a large median, septula and two lateral septulae visible exteriorly; the mural rim is thin, somewhat enlarged at the base with the termen sharp or slightly denticulated; the opesium is oval. The interopesia cavities are large, lozenge-shaped, much elongated; they contain in many specimens a kind of avicularium with special walls and without a pivot.” - *Canu and Bassler (1926) p. 32.*

FIGURE 8: *Heteroconopeum ovatum* (Canu and Bassler, 1926) A: MAPS A3952c (Kw)

FAMILY DYSNOETOPORIDAE VOIGHT, 1971

GENUS *DYSNOETOPORA* CANU AND BASSLER, 1926
***Dysnoetopora celleporoides* Canu and Bassler, 1926**

Dysnoetopora celleporoides Canu and Bassler in Wade, 1926: p. 37, pl. 6, f. 10-17; Voight, 1962: p. 21 pl. 4, f. 2-5; Voight, 1971: f. 1A-D, 2C-E, 3A-E, 4A-D, 8A, 10A-B; Taylor and McKinney, 2006: p. 186 pl. 139-141; ANSP 80356 (Kml).

Types - *Dysnoetopora celleporoides* Canu, Bassler in Wade, 1926: p. 37, pl. 6, f. 10-17, pl 7, f.10-12, Lectotype USNM 69960 (TNKr); Paralectotype USNM 528934 (TNKr), Taylor and McKinney, 2006: pl. 139-141.

Wenonah Specimens - MAPS A3950f

Description – “The zoarium is free, cylindrical, branched; it is very light and floats on water. The surface is garnished with several kinds of pores, including (1) salient and orbicular peristomes (nonnal zooecia) 1 (2) salient peristomes furnished with a small adventitious internal tube (proliferating zooecia), (3) irregular polygonal pores (zooecia not entirely developed), (4) peristomes little salient and very small (bases of new zooecia), and (5) large orifices elongated in the form of avicularia with lateral teeth. Diameter of aperture, 0.13 millimeter; diameter of peristomes, 0.20 millimeter; length of avicularia, 0.45.” - *Canu and Bassler (1926) p. 37.*

FIGURE 9: *Dysnoetopora celleporoides* Canu and Bassler, 1926 A: MAPS A3950A (Kw)

PHYLUM ANNELIDA Lamarck, 1809
 CLASS POLYCHAETA Grube, 1850
 GENUS DIPLOCONCHA CONRAD, 1875
Diploconcha harbisonae Howell, 1943

Hamulus? sp. Weller, 1907: p. 311, pl. 19, f. 3-4.

Non Serpula cretacea Stephenson, 1923: p. 67, pl. 9, f. 8, 9 (not pl. 9, f. 1-7, 10-12 = *Serpula cretacea*, Stephenson, 1923).

Diploconcha harbisonae Howell, 1943: p. 159 pl. 20, f. 6-8; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 55-57; Howell, 1958: p. 41, pl. 5, f. 11-12.

Types – *Diploconcha harbisonae* Howell, 1943: p. 159, pl. 20, f. 6-8, Holotype: NJSM 7677 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Howell, 1958: p. 41 pl. 5, f. 11, NJSM 7677.

Description – “This species is based entirely on the tube fillings and the moulds of the exterior of the tube, and the structure of the tube can therefore only be inferred. If, as Stephenson believed, the tube was similar in composition to that of *Diploconcha cretacea* Conrad, it was made up of a number of thin layers, arranged as a series of truncated cones which fitted, one within another, so that the wall of the tube was relatively thick. The tube was large and tapered slowly. Those parts of it which we know about from the incomplete fillings available to us were straight or almost straight. The inner surface of the tube was smooth, the outer surface was ornamented with a series of coarse, parallel, encircling ridges. The only part of the tube known is the larger end. As *Diploconcha cretacea* bears similar, though smaller, ridges on the anterior portion of its tube, but only less prominent ones on the rest of the surface, it is probable that the ridges in *D. harbisonae* were also smaller nearer the apex than toward the aperture.” - Howell (1943) p. 159.

FIGURE 10: *DIPLOCONCHA HARBISONE* HOWELL, 1943 A: NJSM 7677 (Kw); B: RICHARDS, 1958 PL. 5 F. 11 (NJSM 7677) (Kw)

ORDER SABELLIDA Latreille, 1825
 FAMILY SERPULIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815
 GENUS PYRGOPOLON DE MONTFORT, 1808
Pyrgopolon wenonahanus (Howell, 1943)

Hamulus wenonahanus Howell, 1943: p. 157, pl. 20, f. 1-3; Howell, 1958: p. 38-39, pl. 4, f. 2,8; Kuehne, 1999: p. 62.

Genus *Hamulus* is unaccepted and replaced with *Pyrgopolon*. See Jager (2004).

Types – *Hamulus wenonahanus* Howell, 1943: p.157 pl. 20, f. 1-3, Holotype: NJSM 9680 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens - *Hamulus wenonahanus* Howell, 1943: p.157 pl. 20, f. 1-3; Howell, 1958: p. 38 pl. 4, f. 2,8; NJSM 9680, NJSM 21036.

Description – “Tube fillings similar to those of *H. falcatus* in size and form except that the portion of the filling nearer the apex is less curved. The fillings taper about as they do in *H. falcatus*; and as is the case with that species, this tapering distinguishes even fragments of the fillings of *H. wenonahanus* from fragments of the tube fillings of “*Hamulus lineatus*,” which taper almost imperceptibly.” - Howell (1943) p. 157.

FIGURE 11: *PYRGOPOLON WENONAHANUS* HOWELL, 1943 A:
NJSM 21036 (Kw); B: NJSM 9680 (Kw)

Pyrgopolon sp.

Wenonah Specimens –Kuehne (1999) p. 64

PHYLUM **CNIDARIA** Hatschek, 1888
 CLASS **HEXACORALLIA** Haeckel, 1896
 ORDER **SCLERACTINA** Bourne, 1900
 FAMILY **CARYOPHYLLIDAE** DANA, 1846
 GENUS **TROCHOCYATHUS** MILNE-EDWARDS AND
 HAIME, 1848
Trochocyathus woolmani Vaughan, 1900

Parasmilia? balanophylloides Bolsche, 1870. Wells, 1933: p. 222; Squires, 1958: p. 1.

Non Platytrochus speciosus Gabb and Horn, 1860. Johnson 1898, p. 265, 462.

Trochocyathus woolmani Vaughan, 1900: p. 436, f. 1-3; Johnson, 1905: p. 4; Weller, 1907: p. 268 pl. 5, f. 5-7; Wells, 1933: p. 213 pl. 27, f. 4-7; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 33-35; Wells, 1958: p. 34 pl. 3, f. 4-6; Gallagher, 1984: p. 12; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 64; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2106: p. 108, pl. 1, f. 4; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 62.

Types – *Trochocyathus woolmani* Vaughan, 1900 p. 436, f. 1-3, Holotype: ANSP 685 (Kwb).

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne, 1999: p. 64

Description – “Corallum short, attached, inversely conical, transverse outline circular. Wall rather thick, naked, ornamented externally by 24 costae, corresponding to all cycles of septa, and showing a fairly regular alternation of larger and smaller-i.e., there are 12 larger costae of the same size corresponding to the septa of the first and second cycles, and 12 smaller corresponding to the septa of the third cycle; near the calice they are prominent, with acute edges and broad bases, as the base of the corallum is approached they decrease in prominence; they possess granulations along their edges, and some scattered granulations on the sides. Septa arranged in three cycles, divided into six systems; the septa of the first cycle are appreciably larger than the others, and pass directly from the corallum wall to the columellar space without forming any part of any septal group; the septa of the third cycle bend towards the members of the second, and fuse to the sides of the latter below the level of the calice ; the

septal margins project very slightly above the upper edge of the corallum wall; the septal faces are ornamented with distant subconical granulations. The inner end of each of the primary septa is thickened, the thickening apparently representing a palus, and before each group of the members of the second and third cycle is what appears to be a slender palus, therefore, there apparently are slender pali before the septa of the first and second cycles. The columella is fasciculate, not large, with a papillary upper termination. The calicular fossa shallow.” – Weller (1907) p. 268.

**FIGURE 12: *TROCHOCYATHUS WOOLMANI* VAUGHAN, 1900
 A-B: ANSP 80702 (KWB)**

Trochocyathus sp.

Wenonah Specimens –MAPS A3978f

FAMILY **MICRABRACIIDAE** VAUGHAN, 1905
 GENUS **MICRABACIA** MILNE-EDWARDS AND HAIME,
 1849
Micrabacia cribraria Stephenson, 1916

Non Micrabacia americana Meek, 1864. Weller, 1907: p. 271 pl. 5, f. 14-17.

Micrabacia cribraria Stephenson, 1916: p. 118, pl. 20, f. 1-3; Stephenson, 1923: p. 66 pl. 9, f. 15-17; Wells, 1933: p. 244; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 37-40; Wells, 1958: p. 33 pl. 3, f. 1-2; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer, 1986: p. 10; Kuehne, 1993: p. 66; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 9; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 108, t. 1, pl. 1, f. 5a, b; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 62.

Micrabacia? cribraria Stephenson, 1916. Wade, 1926: p. 27 pl. 1, f. 9-10.

Types – *Micrabacia cribraria* Stephenson (1916) p. 117, pl. 20, f. 1-3, Holotype: USNM 31996 (Black Creek Formation, N.C).

Wenonah Specimens — *Micrabacia americana* Meek, 1864: Weller, 1907: p. 271 (not of Meek, 1864); *Micrabacia cribraria* Stephenson, 1916: Wells, 1958: p. 33, f. 1.

Description – “Corallum solitary, cupoloid, free, with flat or slightly concave base; diameter of base about 7 mm.; height 2-2.25 mm.; ratio of height to diameter about 30:100. Costae relatively narrow, slightly wider or slightly narrower than interspaces, with small, transversely acute granulations at each synapticular junction. Centrally costae and synapticulae form a meshwork. Costae in five complete cycles (96), unequal in length, those of the last or fifth cycle having a length-basal 33 diameter ratio of 14:100 to 21:100. Septa in five complete cycles, alternating in position with the costae.” – Stephenson (1916) p. 117.

FIGURE 13: *MICRABACIA CRIBRARIA* STEPHENSON, 1916 A-B: RICHARDS, 1958 PL. 3 F. 1,2 (KWB)

***Micrabacia hilgardi* Stephenson, 1916**

Micrabacia hilgardi Stephenson, 1916: p. 120 pl. 22, f. 166; Richards, 1943: p. 4; Sohl, Mello 1970: p. 48.

Types – *Micrabacia hilgardi* Stephenson, 1916: p. 120 pl. 22, f. 166, Holotype: USNM 32001.

Wenonah Specimens - MAPS A3975b

Description – “Corallum somewhat variable, but in general moderately high, subdiscoidal, with steep, only slightly convex sides, suggesting a truncated

cone; base fiat, slightly convex or slightly concave; axial depression small and about 1 millimeter deep in the type, with steep sides. Dimensions of the type: Diameter 5.5 millimeters, height 3 millimeters. The costae on the base or wall start with six and by successive bifurcations reach 96 on the periphery; they alternate with the septa. Each of the six original costae (first cycle) is the focus of a group; the original divides near the center into two (second cycle); these split about 0.5 millimeter from the center to form four (third cycle); the four split 1.25 to 1.5 millimeters from the center to form eight (fourth cycle); and finally, the eight splits on the periphery to form 16 (fifth cycle). The bifurcations of each cycle are at rather markedly irregular distances from the center. Up to the fourth cycle the costae are coarsely denticulate; those of the last cycle are thin, sharp, and finely denticulate, and form a narrow band bordering the periphery; they project slightly beyond the periphery. In the narrow intercostal loculi are synapticulae numbering 12 in the loculi extending to the center, separated by slightly elongated perforations; the intercostal synapticulae and perforations are arranged in concentric rows. The septa are thin and are separable into six groups, each group occupying the interspace between two of the six primaries. Total number of septa 96. The secondaries extend to the columella; the tertiaries are fused against the secondaries near the columella; the two outer quaternaries of each group are fused against the tertiaries nearer the center than the two inner ones; and the two outer quaternaries of each subgroup formed about the tertiaries are fused against the quaternaries nearer the center than the two inner ones. The primary septa are slightly higher than the secondaries, and their inner edges descend steeply to the top of the columella; the members of each of the succeeding cycles are slightly lower than those of the preceding cycles. Margins of the septa finely denticulate, the denticulations numbering about twelve to 1 millimeter. Sides of septa with striae, tubercles, and synapticulae radiating fanlike from a point near the base of the columella. Each septum is joined to the wall (base) by synapticulae that connect with the intercostal synapticulae; these are separated by perforations that connect with the intercostal perforations. Columella elliptical, spongy, trabecular, certain of the trabeculae terminating above in more or less scattered, irregularly

distributed papillae; length of the cross section a little less than one-fifth the diameter; width a little less than one-tenth the diameter.” – Stephenson (1916) p. 120.

**FIGURE 14: *MICRABACIA HILGARDI* STEPHENSON, 1916 A:
MAPS A3975B (KW)**

PHYLUM ECHINODERMATA Bather, 1899

CLASS ASTEROIDEA Blainville, 1830

ORDER FORCIPULATIDA Perrier, 1884

FAMILY ASTERIIDAE GRAY, 1840

Wenonah Specimens — MAPS A3701a – The authors believe this is an undescribed species of a Cretaceous Starfish in the family Asteriidae requiring more research.

FIGURE 11A: ASTERIIDAE - A: MAPS A3701A (Kw)

CLASS ECHINOIDEA Leske, 1778

ORDER CLYPEASTEROIDA A. Agassiz, 1872

FAMILY FAUJASIIDAE LAMBERT, 1905

GENUS **DOMECHINUS** KIER, 1962

Domechinus chelonium (Cooke, 1953)

Faujasia chelonium Cooke, 1953: p. 14 pl. 4, f. 11-14; Cooke, 1955 p. 96.

Domechinus chelonium (Cooke, 1953): Kier, 1962: p. 141, pl. 18, f. 1-5.

Types – *Faujasia chelonium* Cooke, 1953: p. 14 pl. 4, f. 11-14, Holotype: USNM 108377.

Wenonah Specimens: MAPS A3610A, MAPS A3610B.

Description - Test medium-sized; upper surface tumid, lower surface slightly concave, expanded and turned down at the margin; horizontal outline semicircular in front, sides straight, V-shaped behind; margin sharp. Apical system central, mono basal (plates fused), with four genital pores. Petals lanceolate, nearly equal in length, extending little more than halfway to the margin; poriferous zones nearly closed at the outer ends, somewhat wider open at the inner ends; pores conjugate, those of outer row slightly elongate, inner row circular, zygopores oblique with respect to the median suture of the petal. Peristome central; bourrelets long and pointed like those of *Hardouinia*; phyllodes longer than wide. Periproct transversely elongated, small, terminal, indenting the margin as viewed from above but turned slightly downward." – Cooke (1953) p. 14.

FIGURE 15: *DOMECHINUS CHELONIUM* A-B: MAPS A3610A - DORSAL AND VENTRAL (Kw); C: MAPS A3610B (Kw)

GENUS HARDOUINIA HAIME IN D'ARCHIAC AND HAIME, 1853

Hardouinia mortonis emmonsii (Stephenson, 1927)

Cassidulus? berryi Twitchell, 1915: p. 220, pl. 101, f. 3a-d.

Hardouinia berryi (Twitchell, 1915). Lambert and Thiery, 1921 p. 363.

Cassidulus emmonsii Stephenson, 1927: p. 7, pl. 3, f. 3-8, pl. 4, f. 1-5.

Hardouinia? stetsoni Stephenson, 1936: p. 37, pl. 1, f. 2-4.

Hardouinia mortonis emmonsii (Stephenson, 1927).
Cooke, 1953: p. 20 pl. 5, f. 22-24; Cooke, 1955: p. 99; Cooke, 1958 p. 49 pl. 46, f. 4; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986 p. 30.

Types – *Cassidulus emmonsii* Stephenson, 1928: p. 7, pl. 3, f. 3-8; pl 4., f. 1-5, Holotype: USNM 73423 (Pee Dee Formation, N.C.); Paralectotype: USNM 73424; *Hardouinia stetsoni* Stephenson, 1936: Holotype: CZ 3516.

Wenonah Specimens - MAPS A3608a, MAPS A3608b, MAPS 3608c, ANSP 30488, Cooke, 1958: p.49 pl. 46, f.1; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer, 1986: p. 30.

Description – “Differs from typical *Hardouinia mortonis* in its smaller size and lower, more conical form.” - Stephenson (1928) p. 7.

Description of *H. mortonis* – “Test medium-sized to large, upper surface variably inflated, lower surface slightly concave, margin angular to acutely rounded, horizontal outline semi-circular in front, nearly straight posterolaterally, produced downward behind. Apical

system having four genital pores located beyond the inner ends of the petals and outside of the large central madreporite, which extends between the posterior oculars. Petals lanceolate, extending more than halfway to the ambitus; poriferous zones closed at inner end, nearly closed and much wider at outer end; zygopores consisting of a circular inner pore conjugated with a slot-shaped outer pore of variable length. Peristome central, circular, tubular, surrounded by five strong, pointed hollow bourrelets covered with scalelike small tubercles and separated by deep pits. Phyllodes short, broad, depressed, very conspicuous. Periproct small, circular, located between the ends of the posterior petals, sunken in a conical tube that widens into a straight-sided sulcus, which extends to and slightly indents the ambitus. Upper surface covered with small sunken tubercles. Lower surface having a bare calluslike area extending backward from the floscelle; remainder covered with larger tubercles set at the outer edge of large semilunate scrobiculi.” - Stephenson (1928) p. 7.

FIGURE 16: *HARDOUINIA MORTONIS EMMONSI* (STEPHENSON 1927) A: MAPS A3608A (Kw); B: MAPS A3608c (Kw)

PHYLUM **MOLLUSCA** Linnaeus, 1758
 CLASS **BIVALVIA** Linnaeus, 1758
 ORDER **ADAPEDONTA** Cossman and Peyrot, 1909
 FAMILY **EDMONDIIDAE** KING, 1850
 GENUS **UNICARDIUM** D'ORBIGNY, 1850
Unicardium umbonata (Whitfield, 1885)

Sphaeriola umbonata Whitfield, 1885: pl. 19, f. 17-18;
 Johnson, 1905 p. 14.

Unicardium umbonata (Whitefield, 1885). Weller,
 1907: p. 569, pl. 62, f. 16-17; Groot, Organist and
 Richards, 1954: p. 46, pl. 5, f. 9; Richards, 1958: p.
 195, pl. 30, f. 5; Richards, 1968: p. 93; Sohl and
 Mello, 1970: p. 42; Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 8, f.9;
 Kuehne, 1999: p. 62, 64 ,68; Gallagher and
 Hanczaryk, 2019: p. 51.

Types – *Sphaeriola umbonata* Whitfield, 1885 pl. 19,
 f. 17-18, Holotype: ANSP 18748.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2405d, MAPS A2405e.

Description - "The dimensions of a large left valve are
 length, 57 mm.; height, 54 mm.; convexity, 18.5 mm.
 Shell very thin, subcircular or slightly
 subquadrangular in outline. Cardinal margin arcuate,
 edentulus; anterior margin broadly rounded, its most
 anterior point being at or below the middle, rounding
 below into the basal margin; basal margin curving
 upward at each end, straighter in the middle;
 posterior margin usually a little shorter than the
 anterior, regularly rounded or sometimes a little
 straightened in the middle. Beaks strongly incurved,
 pointing forward, situated at the middle or a little
 back of the middle of the cardinal margin; umbones
 prominent, much elevated above the hinge-line.
 Valves strongly convex or ventricose, the anterior
 slope somewhat more abrupt than the posterior,
 slightly compressed towards the cardinal extremities.
 Surface of the shell marked only by concentric lines of
 growth which are more or less irregular in the
 strength of their development." - Weller (1907) p.
 569.

**FIGURE 17: UNICARDIUM UMBONATA (WHITFIELD, 1885) A-
 B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 19 FIG. 17-18 (ANSP 18748,
 HOLOTYPE) ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); C-D: MAPS A2405E
 (Kw)**

FAMILY **HIATELLIDAE** GARY, 1824
 GENUS **PANOPEA** DE LA GROYE, 1807
Panopea decisa Conrad, 1853

Panopea decisa Conrad, 1853A: p. 275 pl. 24, f.19;
 Gabb, 1861A, p. 211; Meek, 1864: p. 15.; Whitfield,
 1885, p. 181 pl. 24, f. 5-8; .; Whitfield, 1886, p. 181
 pl. 24, f. 5-8; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898:
 p. 179, 186; Whitfield, 1899: p. 162; Whitfield and
 Hovey, 1901: p. 422; Kummel and Knapp, 1904: p.
 77; Johnson, 1905: p. 18; Weller, 1907: p. 646, pl.
 73, f. 4, 5; Miller, 1911: pl. 5, f. 7; Stephenson, 1914:
 p. 24, f. 2,5,8,9; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954:
 p. 48 pl. 5, f. 11; Richards, 1956: p. 71,72; Richards,
 1958: p. 256, pl. 38, f. 8, pl. 39, f. 5; Richards, 1968:
 p. 44; Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 8, f. 11; Sohl and
 Christopher, 1983: p. 8; Gallagher, 1984: p.
 13,14,15,18,27; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 90;
 Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne,
 1999: p. 60,61,64,69; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27;
 Lauginiger, Parris and Pellegrini, 2014: p. 175;
 Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 20; Kuehne
 and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Glycymeris decisa (Conrad, 1853A). Gabb, 1859 p. 12;
 Gabb, 1861A: p.181; Conrad, 1868 p. 727.

Panope decisa Conrad, 1853A. Gardner, 1916: p. 721;
 Wade, 1926: p. 98 pl. 32, f. 8-9; Sohl and Mello,
 1970: p. 37,42; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59.

Types – *Panopea decisa* Conrad, 1853A, Holotype: ANSP 16380.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller, 1907: p. 646 pl. 73, f. 4; Richards, 1958: p. 256.

Description – “The dimensions of a large specimen are length, about 80 mm.; height, 51 mm.; thickness, 35 mm. Shell more or less subelliptical in outline, widely gaping behind and closed in front. Beaks central or a little in front of the center of the shell, moderately large and incurved. Hinge-line nearly straight; anterior margin rounded, its greatest extension below the middle; basal margin nearly straight or gently convex; usually subparallel with the hinge-line; posterior margin curving more or less abruptly upward and backward from the basal margin, obliquely truncate below, rounding into the cardinal margin above. Valves rather ventricose, with a rounded, oblique, anterior, umbonal ridge becoming broader and more or less obsolete below; from the umbo the surface slopes rather abruptly in front and gently behind; from the posterior side of the beak a rather broad, shallow, indefinite sinus extends obliquely backwards towards the postero-basal angle, usually becoming obsolete in the outer portion of large individuals. Surface of the shell marked by strong, more or less irregular, concentric undulations.” – Weller (1907) p. 646

Discussion - The authors have never encountered *P. decisa* in the Wenonah, but because Weller (1907) has illustrated a specimen reportedly from the Wenonah, *P. decisa* has been left in the official Wenonah species list.

FIGURE 18: PANOPEA DECISA CONRAD, 1853 A: INTERNAL CAST OF THE RIGHT VALVE, WELLER 1907 PL. 73 F. 4 (Kw)

ORDER ARCIDA Stoliczka, 1871

FAMILY ARCIDAE LAMARK, 1809

GENUS NEMOARCA CONRAD, 1869

***Nemoarca cretacea* Conrad, 1869**

Nemoarca cretacea Conrad, 1869F: p. 97, pl. 9, f. 21; Whitfield, 1885: p. 86 pl. 12, f. 8-10; Whitfield, 1885: p. 86 pl. 12, f. 8-10; Whitfield, 1899 p. 161; Johnson, 1905: p. 9; Weller, 1907: p. 413, pl. 30, f. 25-26; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 76,77; Richards, 1958 p. 87 pl. 14, f. 4; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018 p. 61, 62, pl.4.

Types – *Nemoarca cretacea* Conrad, 1869F: p. 97, pl. 9, f. 21, Holotype: ANSP 18724 (Kwb).

Wenonah Specimens - *Nemoarca cretacea* Richards, 1958: p. 87

Description – “Shell small, seldom attaining more than half an inch in extreme length, trapezoidal in form, the transverse diameter being nearly once and a half the height. Valves very ventricose, with large, strongly inflated, prominent beaks, situated nearly opposite the middle of the length. Hinge-line straight and low; area narrow, the length a little less than the greatest length of the body of the shell. Hinge-plate narrow, marked by about 12 short, oblique teeth which diverge from the center on each side, and two or three transverse teeth nearly parallel to the hinge-line at the posterior end. Muscular imprints too faint to be observed on well-preserved casts of the interior. No internal rib bordering the posterior scar. Surface marked by from four to six fine radiating ribs on the posterior slope, and 24 to 26 on the body of the shell and anterior end. Strongest on the posterior part of the body of the shell and gradually decreasing in size anteriorly. On some individuals one or more of the ribs on the posterior slope appear to be divided, while all are strongly elevated and rather sharp and narrow interspaces. On the matrix there are remains of distinct elevated concentric lines at regular distances crossing the radiating lines” – Whitfield (1885) p. 86.

Discussion - The authors have never encountered *N. cretacea* in the Wenonah, but because Richards (1958) has listed the specimen from two Wenonah sites, *N. cretacea* has been left in the official Wenonah species list.

FIGURE 19: NEMOARCA CRETACEA CONRAD, 1869 A-B:
ANSP 81154 (HR) C: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 15 F.4, ANSP
18724 (KWB)

FAMILY CUCULLAEIDAE STEWART, 1930

GENUS CUCULLAEA LAMARCK, 1801

***Cucullaea antrosa* Morton, 1834**

Cucullaea antrosa Morton, 1834: p. 65, pl. 13, f. 6; Gabb, 1859: p. 10; Meek, 1864: p. 8; Johnson, 1905: p. 8; Weller, 1907: p. 391, pl. 32, f. 7-9; Gardner, 1916: p. 534; Stephenson, 1923: p. 87, pl. 12, f. 5-6; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 85-87; Richards, 1956: p. 71; Dorf and Fox, 1957: p. 4,8; Richards, 1958: p.77 pl. 11, f. 13,14; pl. 12, f. 1; Richards, 1968: p. 32; Gallagher, Paris and Spamer, 1984: p. 13, 14,16, 20, 64, 66, 68; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64,66, 68; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 14; Kuehne an Kuehne, 2106: p. 54, App. B pl. 1.

Non *Cucullaea neglecta* Gabb, 1861C. Gabb, 1862A: p. 326 in part.

Idonearca antrosa (Morton, 1834). Conrad, 1868: p. 725; Conrad, 1872: p. 54; Whitfield, 1885: p. 96, pl. 13, f. 6-11; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179.

Idonearca? *antrosa* Morton, 1834. Gabb, 1876: p. 315.

Types – *Cucullaea antrosa* Morton, 1834: p. 65, pl. 13, f. 6, Holotype: ANSP 2272 (Kt).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2457m

Description - "Shell subcircular in outline, or very slightly ovate from being a little prolonged at the posterobasal angle, very slightly oblique with a straight hinge line, which is about half as long as the greatest length of the shell. Beaks large, erect, and

slightly incurved, but not projecting beyond the edge of the proportionally small ligamental area, which is marked by oblique grooves, as in all species of the group. Surface of the shell slightly angulated along the postero-umbonal slope and very convex; marked by numerous strong concentric lines of growth at irregular distances; no radiating striae. Hinge-plate narrow in small and medium sized specimens and the teeth small, but barely bent down at their inner extremity and few in number, the denticulations along the middle of the hinge vertical and small. On large individuals the outer teeth are strong, from four to five in number on each side, according to the size of the individual; slightly declining outwardly, and the bent portion usually nearly half as long as the horizontal portion, the bending being at an angle within ninety degrees, the denticles on the middle part of the hinge being small and numerous. Muscular scars, as seen on the casts, strongly marked; the impression of the ridge deep, strongly arched, and situated pretty well up on the posterior slope; surface of the cast marked by rather strong vascular lines. The outer margin of the cast is bordered by a strong keel, indicating the great thickening of the valves along the pallial line, which extends around three sides, being broadest on the anterior." – Weller (1907) p. 391.

FIGURE 20: CUCULLAEA ANTROSA MORTON, 1834 A-C:
MAPS A2457M (Kw)

***Cucullaea litteli* (Gabb, 1876)**

Idonearca litteli Gabb, 1876: p. 316; Richards, 1968: p. 62.

Cucullaea litteli (Gabb, 1876). Johnson, 1905: p. 9; Weller, 1907: p. 400, pl. 33, f. 1-2; Wade, 1926: p. 45, pl. 9, f. 5; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 82,83; Richards, 1958: p. 79 pl. 12, f. 2, pl. 13, f. 6, 9; Gallagher, 1984: p. 20; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 70.

Idonearca (Cucullaea) litteli Gabb, 1876. Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57.

Types – *Idonearca litteli* Gabb, 1876, Holotype: ANSP 18764 (GaKr).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2513b.

Description – “Shell very large, the dimensions of a large internal cast being length 115 mm., height 89 mm., thickness 100 mm. Anterior margin regularly rounding from the anterior extremity of the hinge-line into the convex ventral margin; postero basal margin rather bluntly rounded; posterior margin obliquely subtruncate, slightly convex; hinge line arcuate. Beaks large and prominent, widely separated and much elevated above the hinge-line in the cast. Valves strongly ventricose, the umbonal ridge broadly rounded, the postero-dorsal slope abrupt, the posterior surfaces of the two valves meeting at the posterior margin in nearly a plane. Indentation of the posterior muscular ridge strong and very deep, 12 mm. in the type specimen. Hinge characters not observed.” – Weller (1907) p. 400.

FIGURE 21: *CUCULLAEA LITTELI* (GABB, 1876) A-D: MAPS A2513B (Kw)

FAMILY GLYCYMERIDIDAE DALL, 1908**GENUS GLYCYMERIS DA COSTA, 1778*****Glycymeris microdentus* (Weller, 1907)**

Axinea microdentus Weller, 1907: p. 416, pl. 35, f. 10-11; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 71,72.

Glycymeris microdentus (Weller, 1907). Richards, 1958: p. 91, pl. 14, f. 10.

Glycymeris cf. microdentus (Weller, 1907). Gallagher, Camburn, Camburn and Hanczaryk, 2014: p. 67; Gallagher and Hanczaryk, 2019: p.51.

Types – *Axinea microdentus* Weller, 1907: p. 416, pl. 35, f. 10-11, Holotype: NJSM 7672 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller, 1907: p. 416, pl. 35, f. 10-11; Richards, 1958: p. 91 pl. 14, f. 1; NJSM 7672

Description – “Shell subcircular, attaining a length and breadth of 21.5 mm. each in the largest specimen observed, the convexity of each valve from one-fourth to three-tenths the diameter. The internal casts somewhat compressed about the free margins, the margin very faintly or not at all crenate. Beaks moderately elevated, pointed, and slightly oblique, their lateral slopes meeting at an angle of about 90; the impression of the hinge-plate of moderate width, with n or 12 teeth on each side of the beak, with several less distinct ones in the middle beneath the beak; the individual teeth on each side are slightly oblique to the inner margin of the hinge-plate, the anterior and posterior rows are nearly straight or slightly convex, meeting beneath the beak in a rounded angle. Both muscular impressions moderately developed. The external surface of the shell, as indicated by impressions, is marked by fine, regular, radiating costae, and by more or less irregular concentric lines of growth. The beaks are approximate and the cardinal areas small.” – Weller (1907) p. 416.

FIGURE 22: *GLYCYMERIS MICRODENTUS* (WELLER, 1907) A-B: WELLER (1907) PL. 35 F. 10, 11 (Kw)

GENUS **POSTLIGATA** GARDNER, 1916***Postligata crenata* Wade, 1926**

Postligata crenata Wade, 1926: p. 48, pl. 11, f. 3-4;
Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 5, pl. 2, f. 5; Sohl
and Mello, 1970: p. 46; Pickett, 1972: p. 20, pl. 7, f.
2; Carrey, 1976: p. 226, pl. 12, f. 5; Lauginiger,
1988: p. 21, f. 9; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57.

Types – *Postligata crenata* Wade, 1926: p. 48, pl. 11,
f. 3-4, Holotype: USNM 32731 (TnKr).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2537d

Description – “Shell small and strong; sub circular in outline, lenticular; umbones small, submedial in position, nearly flat with little inflation, prosogyrate; lunule and escutcheon absent.; dorsal margins sloping gently but curved so as not to break the circular outline of the shell; external surface very finely and regularly striated concentrically from the umbones to the base, with strongly defined resting stages common; ligament opisthodontic, lodged in three to five grooves oblique to the dorsal margin; hinge taxodont but obtusely angular and slightly interrupted directly beneath the umbone; teeth V-shaped, subequal, about 12 in number in the anterior series and 16 in the posterior series; adductor scars elliptical, subequal in number, situated on faint buttresses along the medial horizontal, the anterior slightly higher than the posterior one; pallial line simple and distinct; inner ventral margins crenate. Latitude, 9 millimeters; elevation, 9 millimeters.” – Wade (1926) p.48.

FIGURE 23: *POSTLIGATA CRENATA* WADE, 1926; A: MAPS A2537D (KW); B-C: USNM 32731 (WADE (1926) PL. 11, FIG. 3,4 (ALKR)

The type specimen, USNM 32731 from the Ripley Formation, is shown for comparison because the Wenonah specimen, MAPS A2537d, is an internal mold only.

***Postligata* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 65

FAMILY NOETIIDAE STEWART, 1930

GENUS **STRIARCA** CONRAD, 1862***Striarca congesta* (Conrad, 1875)**

Trigonarca (Breviarca) congesta Conrad, 1875A: p. A3, pl. 1, f. 2; Conrad, 1875B: p. A14; Boyle, 1893: p. 289.

Axinea congesta (Conrad, 1875A). Weller, 1907: p. 418, pl. 35, f. 12-19.

Striarca congesta (Conrad, 1875A). Stephenson, 1923: p. 112, pl. 20, f. 9, 10 10a, 11-13; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 77, 78; Richards, 1958: p. 89, pl. 12, f. 5; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65.

Types – *Trigonarca (Breviarca) congesta* Conrad, 1875A, Holotype lost; Paratypes: USNM 7707, 31916, 31917.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller, 1907: p. 419 (*Axinea congesta*); Richards, 1958: p. 90.

Description - “Shell small, equilateral or very slightly oblique, longer than high, subelliptical in outline; the dimensions of the largest specimen observed are: length, 12 mm. ; height, 10.5 mm. ;convexity, 3 mm. Valves moderately and evenly convex ; hinge line nearly straight, arched downward on each side, the cardinal extremities rounding into the general subelliptical outline of the entire shell ; internal casts scarcely compressed about the free margins, not crenate; the beak central, prominent, rounded, a little produced beyond the hinge-line in the casts, impressions of the exterior show a small vertically striated cardinal area; impression of the hinge-plate rather broad, with 7 or 8 larger teeth at each end set obliquely to the inner margin of the hinge-plate, the median portion beneath the beak with smaller, nearly vertical teeth ; the central half of the entire row of teeth is straight, the outer one-fourth on each side being slightly arched downward. Surface of the casts smooth, the muscular impressions inconspicuous. External surface, as indicated by impressions, marked

by narrow radiating costae, narrower than the interspaces, and by more or less inconspicuous concentric lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 418.

FIGURE 24: *STRIARCA CONGESTA* (CONRAD, 1875) A:
WELLER, 1907 PL. 35 FIG. 19 (KWB)

Striarca sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64

FAMILY PARALLELODONTIDAE DALL, 1890

GENUS NEMODON CONRAD, 1869

Nemodon angulatum (Gabb, 1861)

Leda angulatum Gabb, 1861C: p. 95, pl. 2, f. 12;
Richards, 1968: p. 32.

Leda subangulatum Gabb 1861A: p. 133.

Nuculana subangulatum (Gabb, 1861A). Meek, 1864:
p. 8.

Nuculana angulatum (Gabb, 1861C). Conrad, 1868: p.
725.

Nemodon angulatum (Gabb, 1861C): Gabb, 1876: p.
316; Whitfield, 1885: p. 84, pl. 12, f. 6-7; Whitfield,
1886: p. 84, pl. 12, f. 6-7; Whitfield, 1899: p. 161;
Johnson, 1905: p. 9; Weller, 1907: p. 388, pl. 30, f.
15; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 92-93; Richards, 1958: p. 72,
pl. 11, f. 10; Kuehne, 1993: p. 69; Kuehne 1999: p.
68.

Nemodon cf. angulatum (Gabb, 1861C). Kuehne,
1995: p. 84.

Types – *Leda angulatum* Gabb, 1862 p. 95, pl. 2, f. 12,
Holotype: ANSP 18723.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2423d

Description – “Shell small, the dimensions of the type
specimen being length, 15.5 mm.; height, 8 mm.;
thickness, 5 mm. Beaks rather prominent, situated at

about the anterior third of the shell. Anterior margin
broadly curved from beneath the beak to the antero-
basal region, where it curves more abruptly into the
nearly straight ventral margin, postero-basal margin
produced and subangular, posterior margin truncate,
meeting the posterior extremity of the hinge-line in
an obtuse angle, dorsal margin nearly straight, sloping
gently backward from the beak to the posterior hinge
extremity. From the beak a subangular umbonal ridge
passes obliquely backward to the postero-basal
angle, and a broadly flattened or slightly sinuate area
passes downward from the beak to about the middle
of the ventral margin. The surface markings and hinge
characters not preserved on the type specimen,
which is an internal cast.” – Weller (1907) p. 388.

FIGURE 25: *NEMODON ANGULATUM* (GABB, 1861) A-D:
MAPS A2423d (Kw)

Nemodon brevifrons Conrad, 1875

Nemodon brevifrons Conrad, 1875A: p. A4, pl. 1, f. 15;
Whitfield, 1885: p. 85 pl. 12, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1885:
p. 85 pl. 12, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1899: p. 161; Weller,
1905: p. 333; Johnson, 1905: p. 9; Weller, 1907: p.
389, pl. 30, f. 12-14; Stephenson, 1923: p. 91 pl. 13,
f. 1-4; Richards, 1958: p. 73, pl. 11, f. 12; Richards,
1968: p. 35; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8;
Kuehne, 1993: p. 69; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84;
Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 63.

Nemodon cf. brevifrons Conrad, 1875A. Sohl and
Christopher, 1983: p. 8.

Types – *Nemodon brevifrons* Conrad, 1875: p. A4, pl.
1, f. 15, Holotype: ANSP 2301 (NcKr).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller, 1907: p. 389 pl. 30, f. 13; Richards, 1958: p. 74 pl. 11, f. 12.

Description – “Shell of moderate size, the dimensions of a very perfect right valve being length, 23 mm.; height, 13 mm.; length of hinge-line, 15 mm.; convexity, 6 mm. Shell sub-rhomboidal in outline, rather strongly convex. Beaks incurved, the umbo rather broad and prominent, and produced above the hinge-line. Hinge-line straight. Anterior margin meeting the hinge-line in an obtuse angle, broadly and evenly rounded, passing with a regular curvature into the gently convex ventral margin, posteroventral margin rather broadly rounded and passing into the obliquely subtruncate posterior margin above, which meets the hinge-line in an obtuse angle. The umbonal ridge prominent, broadly rounded or somewhat inflated, the posterior slope being narrow and somewhat abrupt. Surface of the shell marked by concentric lines of growth, and in some specimens by faint radiating lines, which are more conspicuous upon the anterior portion of the shell. The anterior hinge-teeth are three in number, rather short and slightly curved, but nearly parallel with the hinge-line, the posterior teeth are also three in number, perhaps a little longer than the anterior ones, straight and subparallel with the hinge line.” - Weller (1907) p. 389.

FIGURE 26: *NEMODON BREVIFRONS* (CONRAD, 1875) A: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 11 FIG. 12 (Kw)

***Nemodon* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2506a; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer, 1986: p. 30.

ORDER CARDIIDA Ferussac, 1822

FAMILY CARDIIDAE LAMARCK, 1809

GENUS CARDIUM LINNAEUS, 1758

Scott (1978) p. 894 erected the genus and subgenus combinations of *Pleuriocardia* (*Pleuriocardia*) and *Pleuriocardia* (*Dochmocardia*) and suggested several NACP species of “*Cardium*” might be placed into these taxa. *Cardium whitfieldi* Weller, 1907, *Cardium ripleyanum* Conrad 1858A in the sub genus *Pleuriocardia*. *Cardium Wenonah* Weller, 1907, *Cardium longstreeti* Weller, 1907, *Cardium cliffwoodensis* Weller, 1907 and *Cardium lorillardensis* Weller, 1907 in the sub genus *Dochmocardia*. The authors have decided to not follow these suggested changes.

***Cardium eufaulense* Conrad, 1860**

Cardium eufaulense Conrad, 1860: p. 28, pl. 46, f. 12; Gabb, 1861A: p. 162; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 12; Gardner, 1916: p. 664.

Cardium (*Trachycardium*) *eufaulense* Conrad, 1860. Conrad, 1868: p. 726; Conrad, 1875B: p. A15; Gabb, 1876A: p. 310.; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46

Acanthocardium eufaulense (Conrad, 1860). Stoliczka 1871: p. 271.

Cardium eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). *not* Whitfield, 1885: p. 132 pl. 20, f. 17 = *Cardium whitfieldi* Weller, 1907; *not* Whitfield, 1886: p. 132 pl. 20, f. 18,19 = *Cardium tenuistriatum* Whitfield, 1885; Clark, 1897: p. 335; Clark, 1898: p. 185; Weller, 1907: p. 577 pl. 63, f. 17-20; Richards, 1958: p. 200 pl. 33, f. 1,6,7; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 7.

Cardium cf. eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Minard, 1974A: p. 23 tb. 4.

Trachycardium eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Kummel 1908: p. 69; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 139, 141, 143, 147, 150, 153, 159, 162; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Rindsberg, 1998; Kosnick, 2002; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54 App B pl. 1.

Granocardium eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Hartstein, 1986: p. 90.

Pleuriocardia (*Dochmocardia*) *eufaulensis* (Conrad, 1860). Kuehne, 1999: p. 76,77,79.

Types – *Cardium eufaulensis* Conrad, 1860, Holotype: ANSP 19597 (AlKr).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 577 pl. 63, f. 20.

Weller lists the species from the Wenonah near Crawford's Corner, Holmdel, NJ. and Richards (1958) p. 200 repeats Weller's description of the species but does not list the species as occurring in the Wenonah and provides no explanation.

Description - The dimensions of an internal cast are height, 44 mm.; width, 37 mm.; thickness, 35 mm. Large examples sometimes attain a height of over 60 mm. Shell irregularly subovate in lateral view and cordate in end view. Hinge-line arcuate; anterior and basal margins, from the extremity of the hinge-line to the middle of the basal margin, describing a nearly regular, arcuate curve; post basal margin curving more sharply around the postero-basal extremity of the shell into the posterior margin; posterior margin much straighter than the anterior, usually gently convex but sometimes nearly or quite straight. Beaks situated at about the middle of the hinge-line, rather prominent, elevated, pointed and incurved, considerably more prominent in the casts than in the specimens with the shell preserved. Valves gibbous, most prominent, but not angular, along a line from the beaks to the postero-basal extremity, the posterior slope more abrupt than the anterior. Muscular impressions rather large, the posterior ones scarcely impressed and often scarcely distinguishable upon the casts; the anterior ones more strongly impressed. Each valve with a strong, somewhat curved cardinal tooth beneath the beak, with a pit for the reception of the tooth of the opposite valve; in each valve is a single anterior and posterior, rather strong, lateral tooth, somewhat remote but nearly equidistant from the cardinal tooth. The inner free margin of the valves is crenate. Externally the shell is marked by flat, radiating costae wider than the interspaces; from the interspaces rise rows of laterally compressed spinules or tubercles which are longer and stronger upon the anterior and posterior slopes towards the hinge extremities; on the central portion of the shell each third row of processes is more conspicuous than the two intervening rows, the spines being longer and larger, one of them occupying the space of two or three of the smaller ones of the intervening rows, the smaller ones sometimes being scarcely more than tubercles but little elevated above the surface of the ribs of the shell; upon the anterior

and posterior slopes of the shell the rows of larger and smaller spines alternate, there being but a single row of smaller spines between the larger ones." – Weller (1907) p. 592.

FIGURE 27: *CARDIUM EUFAULENSE* (CONRAD, 1860) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 63 FIG. 20 (KW); B-D: MAPS 2843A (KS); E: ANSP 80474 (KWB)

***Cardium ripleyanum* Conrad, 1869**

not Cardium ripleyense Conrad, 1858A: p. 326.

Cardium ripleyanum Conrad, 1869F: p. 96, pl. 9, f. 6; Whitfield, 1885; p. 132, pl. 20, f. 14; Whitfield, 1886; p. 132, pl. 20, f. 14; Whitfield, 1899: p. 155; Johnson, 1905: p. 15; Weller, 1907: p. 582, pl. 65, f. 4-6; Richards, 1956: p. 73; Richards, 1958: p. 205, pl. 32, f. 4; Richards, 1968: p. 81; Gallagher, 1984: p. 16; Gallagher, 1986: p. 11; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B pl. 1.

Pleuriocardia (Pleuriocardia) ripleyanum (Conrad, 1869F). Scott, 1978: p. 889.

Granocardium cf. ripleyanum (Conrad, 1869F). Kuehne, 1999: p. 65.

Types – *Cardium ripleyanum* Conrad (1869), Holotype: ANSP 18794 (Kwb).

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999)
(*Granocardium ripleyanum*) p. 65.

Description - The dimensions of an internal cast are height, 4.5 mm.; width, 4 mm.; thickness, 3 mm. The height of one of the largest individuals observed is 5.3 mm. Shell subcircular in outline, slightly higher than wide, cordate in end view. Hinge line relatively long, a little arched; anterior, basal, and posterior margins rounded. Beaks rather prominent, elevated above the hinge-line, incurved. Umbones prominent, the surface sloping rather abruptly both in front and behind; shell compressed towards the cardinal extremities, more so behind than in front. Surface of the shell marked with about 22 subangular, radiating ribs, slightly narrower than the interspaces, also by fine, concentric, sublamellose lines." – Weller (1907) p. 583.

FIGURE 28 *CARDIUM RIPLEYANUM* (CONRAD, 1858) A: RICHARDS, 1958 PL. 32 FIG. 4 - ANSP 18794 (KWB); B-D: WELLER, 1907 PL. 35 FIG. 4-6 (KWB)

***Cardium tenuistriatum* (Whitfield, 1885)**

Cardium eufaulensis Whitfield, 1885: p. 132, pl. 20, f. 18-19 (not pl. 20, f. 17 = *C. whitfieldi* Weller, 1907); Whitfield, 1886: p. 132, pl. 20, f. 18-19 (not pl. 20, f. 17 = *C. whitfieldi* Weller, 1907).

Cardium (Criocardium) dumosum Whitfield, 1885: p. 133 pl. 20, f. 10-12 (not pl. 20, f. 9, 13 = *Granocardium dumosum* Conrad, 1871), Whitfield, 1886: p. 133 pl. 20, f. 10-12 (not pl. 20, f. 9, 13 = *Granocardium dumosum* Conrad, 1871).

Cardium (Criocardium) multiradiatum Whitfield, 1885: p. 135, pl. 21, f. 1-3 (not *C. multiradiatum* Gabb, 1860B), Whitfield, 1886: p. 135, pl. 21, f. 1-3 (not *C. multiradiatum* Gabb, 1860B).

Fragum tenuistriatum Whitfield, 1885: p. 139, pl. 20, f. 15,16; Whitfield, 1886: p. 139, pl. 20, f. 15,16.

Cardium tenuistriatum (Whitfield, 1885). Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Weller, 1907: p. 591, pl. 65, f. 13, 17-19; Gardner, 1916: p. 669; Wade, 1926: p. 84, pl. 26, f. 4; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 47, pl. 5, f. 5, 6; Richards, 1956: p. 71, 72; Dorf and Fox, 1957: p. 6; Richards, 1958: p. 211, pl. 32, f. 10; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 7; Gallagher, 1984: p. 13-15, 18, 20, 27; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 17; Gallagher, 1991: p. 31; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64, 69; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Brister and Young, 2007 p. 59.

Cardium (Fragum) tenuistriatum (Whitfield, 1885). Whitfield, 1899: p.155.

Cardium (Granocardium) tenuistriatum (Whitfield, 1885). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36.

Granocardium tenuistriatum (Whitfield, 1885). Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 8, f. 5,6; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 62-66, 79.

Granocardium cf. tenuistriatum (Whitfield, 1885). Kuehne, 1999: p.79.

Types – *Fragum tenuistriatum* Whitfield, 1885, Holotype Lost?. Weller (1907) pl. 65, f. 13 is labelled as the type from Wenonah sand near Marlboro but does not provide a catalogue number.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller, 1907: p. 591 pl. 65, f. 13; Richards, 1958: p. 211.

Description – “The dimensions of an internal cast are height, 44 mm.; width, 37 mm.; thickness, 35 mm., large examples sometimes attain a height of over 60 mm. Shell irregularly subovate in lateral view and cordate in end view. Hinge-line arcuate; anterior and basal margins, from the extremity of the hinge-line to the middle of the basal margin, describing a nearly regular, arcuate curve; posterior basal margin curving more sharply around the postero-basal extremity of the shell into the posterior margin; posterior margin much straighter than the anterior, usually gently convex but sometimes nearly or quite straight. Beaks

situated at about the middle of the hinge-line, rather prominent, elevated, pointed and incurved, considerably more prominent in the casts than in the specimens with the shell preserved. Valves gibbous, most prominent, but not angular, along a line from the beaks to the postero-basal extremity, the posterior slope more abrupt than the anterior. Muscular impressions rather large, the posterior ones scarcely impressed and often scarcely distinguishable upon the casts; the anterior ones more strongly impressed. Each valve with a strong, somewhat curved cardinal tooth beneath the beak, with a pit for the reception of the tooth of the opposite valve; in each valve is a single anterior and posterior, rather strong, lateral tooth, somewhat remote but nearly equidistant from the cardinal tooth. The inner free margin of the valves is crenate. Externally the shell is marked by flat, radiating costae wider than the interspaces; from the interspaces rise rows of laterally compressed spinules or tubercles which are longer and stronger upon the anterior and posterior slopes towards the hinge extremities; on the central portion of the shell each third row of processes is more conspicuous than the two intervening rows, the spines being longer and larger, one of them occupying the space of two or three of the smaller ones of the intervening rows, the smaller ones sometimes being scarcely more than tubercles but little elevated above the surface of the ribs of the shell; upon the anterior and posterior slopes of the shell the rows of larger and smaller spines alternate, there being but a single row of smaller spines between the larger ones." - Weller (1907) p. 591.

FIGURE 29: *CARDIUM TENUISTRATIUM* A: WELLER (1907) PL. 65 FIG. 13 (Kw); B: NSJM 21024 (KMR); C-E: NJSM 21024 (KMR)

***Cardium wenonah* Weller, 1907**

Cardium wenonah Weller, 1907: p. 576 pl. 63, f. 14-16 (not pl. 63, f. 10-13 = *Ethmocardium welleri* (Stephenson, 1941); Richards, 1958: p. 199; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 7.

Pleuriocardia (Dochmocardia) wenonah (Weller, 1907). Scott, 1978: p. 894.

Types – *Cardium wenonah* Weller, 1907: p. 576 pl. 63, f. 14-16; Cotypes: NJSM 7676 (Kw) and UC 18066 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 576 pl. 63, f. 14-16; Richards (1958) p. 211, pl. 32, f. 1; ANSP 81162; NSJM 7676.

FIGURE 30: *CARDIUM WENONAH* WELLER 1907 A-C: WELLER (1907) PL. 63 F. 14-16 (Kw); D: ANSP 81162 (Kw)

Cardium sp.

Wenonah Specimens – ANSP 81162

GENUS *ETHMOCARDIUM* WHITE, 1880
Ethmocardium welleri (Stephenson, 1941)

Non *Cardium wenonah* Weller, 1907: pl. 63, f. 10-13 (not pl. 63, f. 14-16 = *Cardium wenonah* Weller, 1907).

Cardium (Ethmocardium) welleri Stephenson, 1941: p. 195, pl. 34, f. 13-17.

Ethmocardium welleri (Stephenson, 1941). Wollenben, 1977: p. 386; Kuehne, 1993: p. 69.

Granocardium (Ethmocardium) welleri (Stephenson, 1941). Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 257, 258, f. 231, 232.

Ethmocardium sp. Tandon, Moyer and Garb: 2016: p. 9, f. 14, 19.

Types – *Cardium (Ethmocardium) welleri* Stephenson, 1941: pl. 34, f. 13, Holotype: USNM 76600 (ArKn), Paratypes: USNM 76001-76003 (ArKn).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 576 pl. 65, f. 10-13; MAPS A2544c, MAPS A2544e, MAPS A2544f

Description – “Shell small for the genus, broadly subovate in outline, slightly elongated in the direction of the umbonal ridge, moderately ventricose. Beaks only moderately prominent, strongly incurved, approximate, prosogyrate, situated a little in advance of the midlength. Umbonal ridge broadly rounded below, becoming more sharply rounded to subangular toward the beak. Anterior slope moderately steep, flattening out a little toward the

anterior margin and becoming slightly excavated toward the anterodorsal margin; posterior slope steep, becoming a little excavated toward the margin. Although many individuals, many of the individuals in the collection have separated from the hard concretionary matrix in such a way as to show the external features perfectly, the hinges are not well exposed in any of them. The hinge plate appears to be rather narrow, and the dentition normal. As seen on internal molds the anterior adductor scar is small, subovate, and situated high in the shell; the posterior scar is larger, more elongate, and extends to much lower in the shell. The inner surface of the shell within the pallial lines exhibits radial rows of pits corresponding in position to the intercostal channels of the exterior, the pits numbering 1 to 3 to the millimeter; these pits were filled with matrix and appear on the internal mold as rows of nodes; many of the pits penetrate the shell and appear on the exterior as rows of perforations in the intercostal channels. The pits do not become conspicuously developed until the adult stage is reached and may appear to be wanting on younger stages. Serrations on the margin of the shell mark the ends of the costae. Dorsal margin of shell arched; anterior and ventral margins broadly and evenly rounded; posterior margin subangular below, very broadly rounded above, meeting the dorsal margin in a very broad, subobtuse angle. The surface is ornamented with about 32 distinct spineless ribs; laterally these are squarish to the broadly rounded on their crests and are separated by slightly narrower interspaces with squarish bottoms; on the anterior slope the ribs become narrower and the interspaces wider; on the posterior slope the ribs are low, triangular in cross section, and show a tendency to become bifid on their crests. The internal pits appear as rows of perforations in the intercostal channels as already explained.” – Stephenson (1941) p. 195.

FIGURE 31: *ETHMORCARDIUM WELLERI* (STEPHENSON, 1941)
A-F: MAPS A2544c (Kw)

GENUS *FULVIA* GRAY, 1853
Fulvia tenuis Whitfield, 1885

Fulvia tenuis Whitfield, 1885: p. 139 pl. 20, f. 8;
Whitfield, 1886: p. 139 pl. 20, f. 8; Whitfield, 1899:
p. 158; Weller, 1907: p. 597 pl. 66, f. 8; Richards,
1958: p. 215 pl. 33, f. 11.

Lenearia tenuis is used in some contexts, but the
authors can find no definition of this genus.

Types – *Fulvia tenuis* Whitfield, 1885, p. 139 pl. 20, f.
8, Holotype: NJSM 7588 (Kns or Kml).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2444f

Description - "Shell rather small, but little exceeding
an inch in length by about half that height;
transversely elliptical in outline, and but moderately
convex. Beaks very small, appressed, and but very
slightly projecting beyond the hinge margin. Anterior
end of the shell the shortest, obtusely pointed, or
sharply rounded at its extremity, which is situated
much above the middle of the height; posterior end
more broadly rounded; basal line strongly arcuate
and rapidly ascending toward the anterior part.
Hinge-line but little declining on either side of the

beak. Surface of the valve marked by radiating
plications which are very fine at the anterior end, and
gradually increase in strength to the extreme
posterior margin, where they must have been fully
one-sixteenth of an inch wide (the shell being broken
at this point). Plications flattened obliquely, so as to
give the anterior side a much greater abruptness and
only about one-third the width of the posterior side.
A few concentric undulations mark the surface, and
very fine concentric striae cover the entire shell."
Whitfield (1886) p. 139.

FIGURE 32: *FULVIA TENUIS* WHITFIELD, 1885 A-C: MAPS
A2444f (Kw)

GENUS *GRANOCARDIUM* GABB, 1869
Granocardium dumosum (Conrad, 1871)

Cardium (Criocardium) dumosum Conrad 1871: p. 75;
Whitfield, 1885: p. 133 pl. 20, f. 9, 13 (not pl. 20, f.
10-12 = *Cardium tenuistriatum* (Whitfield, 1885);
Whitfield, 1886: p. 133 pl. 20, f. 9, 13 (not pl. 20, f.
10-12 = *Cardium tenuistriatum* (Whitfield, 1885);
Whitfield, 1899: p. 155.

Criocardium dumosum (Conrad, 1871). Conrad, 1875:
p. A15.

Cardium dumosum (Conrad 1871). Clark, 1897: p.
330, 335; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 185; Johnson, 1907:
p. 15; Stephenson, 1907: p. 138, 150; Weller, 1907:
590 (not pl. 65, f. 7-10, see Stephenson, 1923 p.
293); Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2; Gardner, 1916:
p. 668; Stephenson, 1923: p. 293 pl. 72, f. 5-8;
Wade, 1926: p. 83 pl. 26, f. 2-3; Stephenson, 1941:
p. 199-200, 202; Groot, Organist and Richards,
1954: p. 47; Richards, 1956: p. 47, 79; Richards,
1958: p. 210 pl. 32, f. 8, 9, 11; Richards, 1963: p. 7;
Richards, 1968: p. 47; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36;
Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Elder,

1996: p. 258, f. 6.1-6.3; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B pl. 1.

Cardium (Grandocardium) dumosum (Conrad 1871).
Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 42,46.

Grandocardium dumosum (Conrad 1871). Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61.

Grandocardium (Criocardium) dumosum (Conrad 1871). Elder, 1996: p. 258, f. 6.1-6.3; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 257, 258, f. 231, 232.

Types – *Cardium (Criocardium) dumosum* Conrad 1871: p. 75, Holotype ANSP 20012.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 591; Richards (1958) p.210.

Description -The dimensions of a large individual are height, 18 mm.; width, 18 mm.; convexity of one valve, 6 mm. Shell subcircular in outline, but slightly inequilateral, moderately convex. Beaks situated at about the middle of the hinge-line, rather small and incurved; umbones prominent, the anterior and posterior cardinal slopes about equally steep; shell slightly compressed at both cardinal extremities. Surface of the shell marked with about 54 rounded radiating costae, with interspaces of about equal width; from the bottom of every third interspace on the central portion of the shell, there arises a row of laterally flattened spines one to two millimeters in length, their distance apart being about equal to the space occupied by two costae; the two intervening interspaces are occupied by rows of much smaller tubercles a little compressed laterally, situated at intervals about one-third the distance between the spines in each row. On the anterior and posterior slopes of the shell several rows of spines alternate with single rows of tubercles. The longest spines occur upon the posterior cardinal slope." – Weller (1907) p. 590.

FIGURE 33: GRANOCARDIUM DUMOSUM (CONRAD, 1871) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 20 FIG. 9 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); B: ANSP 80479 (KWB)

***Granocardium* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64-65; MAPS A2443k; KS 2238

GENUS TRACHYCARDIUM MORCH, 1853

***Trachycardium longstreeti* (Weller, 1907)**

Cardium longstreeti Weller, 1907: p. 579, pl. 63, f. 21-22; Stephenson, 1907: p. 122, 126, 127, 129, 130, 136, 148, pl. 63, f. 21-22; Stephenson, 1923: p. 289; pl. 71, f. 4-8; Stephenson, 1927: p. 20; Stephenson, 1936: p. 377, pl. 2, f. 1; Richards, 1958: p. 201 pl. 32, f. 2,12; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36

Cardium (Trachycardium) longstreeti Weller, 1907. Stetson, 1949: p. 9; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40.

Cardium cf. longstreeti (Weller, 1907). Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 47, pl. 5, f. 7.

Trachycardium cf. longstreeti (Weller, 1907). Pickett, 1972: pl. 3, f. 7; Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 8, f. 7.

Pleuriocardia (Dochmocardia) longstreeti (Weller, 1907). Scott, 1978: 894.

Trachycardium longstreeti (Weller, 1907). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 9, table 2; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 30; Brown and Morano, 2019: f. 26.

Types – *Cardium longstreeti* Weller, 1907., Holotype: NJSM 7673 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 579 pl. 63, f.2; Richards (1958) p. 201 pl. 32, f. 2, 12; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2454b, MAPS A2454c; NJSM 7673

Description - The dimensions of the internal cast of a left valve are height, 33 mm.; width, 31 mm.; convexity, 10 mm. Shell obliquely subovate in outline. Hinge-line arcuate; anterocardinal margin nearly straight, sloping downward from the beak to the anterior hinge extremity, curving below without break into the anterior margin; anterior and basal margins rounding with a regular, slightly decreasing curvature from the anterior hinge-extremity to the postero-basal extremity; posterobasal extremity subangular, situated considerably above the base of the shell; posterior margin obliquely truncate, rounding above to the posterior hinge-extremity. Beaks small, acute, incurved, moderately elevated above the hinge-line, pointing slightly backward at their tips. Valves with an umbonal prominence passing obliquely from the beak to the postero-basal extremity, in the casts it is subangular, but in the shell itself more rounded; the most prominent portion of the shell lies in front of this umbonal ridge; posterior slope narrow, somewhat flattened or concave; anterior slope gently convex across the middle of the shell, becoming more abrupt towards the anterior margin. The inner free margins of the shell strongly crenate, and the radiating ribs present upon the internal casts halfway or more to the beaks. Muscular impressions inconspicuous upon the casts. Surface of the shell marked by about 38 rather high, angular ribs with small, more or less distant nodes along their summits; these ribs grow regularly larger in passing from the anterior cardinal extremity to the postero-basal angle, those upon the posterior slope are notably thinner and more sharply angular than those upon the central and anterior portion of the shell, and one, about the second or third from the postero-cardinal extremity, is much higher and more conspicuous than the others." – Weller (1907) p. 579.

**FIGURE 34: *TRACHYCARDIUM LONGSTREETI* (WELLER, 1907)
A-B: MAPS A2454B (KW); C: NJSM 7673 (KW); D-F:
MAPS A2454C (KW)**

FAMILY TELLINIDAE Blainville, 1814

GENUS LINEARIA CONRAD, 1860

***Linearia metastriata* Conrad, 1860**

Linearia metastriata Conrad, 1860: p. 279; pl. 46, f. 7; Gabb, 1861A: p. 193; Lea, 1862: p. 15; Meek, 1864: p. 14; Conrad, 1871: p. 73, pl. 3, f. 11; Conrad, 1875B: p. A16; Whitfield, 1885: p. 165, pl. 23, f. 6-7; Whitfield, 1886: p. 165, pl. 23, f. 6-7; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 159; Harris, 1900: p. 296, pl. 50, f. 7; Weller, 1905: p. 333; Johnson, 1905: p. 16; Stephenson, 1907: p. 126, 128, 130; Weller, 1907: p. 618, pl. 70, f. 9; Gardner, 1916: p. 699; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2, 8; Stephenson, 1923: p. 329, pl. 84, f. 1-5; Wade, 1926: p. 93, pl. 31, f. 1-2; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 48, pl. 5, f. 8; Richards, 1956: p. 71; Richards, 1958: p. 231, pl. 35, f. 3-5; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 8; Afshar, 1969: p. 58, pl. 24, f. 12-15; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 40, 46; Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 8, f. 8; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8; Gallagher, 1984: p. 16; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 139, 144, 147, 150, 153, 156, 160, 162; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 11, 16; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 59, 60, 64, 65, 74; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 60; Lauginiger, Parris and Pellegrini, 2014; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B pl. 1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61, 70, pl. 3.

Linearia cf. metastriata Conrad, 1860. Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 42; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitely, 2016: p. 110, t. 1, pl. 2, f. 9.

Types – *Linearia metastriata* Conrad, 1860, Holotype: ANSP 294 (MsKr).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 618 pl. 70, f. 9; Richards (1958) p. 231; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65.

Description - The dimensions of a large individual are length, 25 mm.; height, 16 mm. Shell subelliptical in outline, depressed convex. Beaks small, appressed, but little elevated above the hinge-line, situated nearly centrally. Hinge-line a little arcuate; anterior and posterior cardinal margins meeting at the beak in an angle of about 145; anterior and posterior margins both rounded, the anterior a little higher than the posterior; basal margin broadly convex. Valves nearly regularly convex, the surface sloping more abruptly to the cardinal margin. Surface of the shell marked by fine concentric ribs increasing regularly in size and separated by sharply depressed furrows about equaling the ribs in width; also by radiating furrows which cut through the concentric ridges, giving them more or less the appearance of rows of discontinuous nodes, the radiating furrows are much stronger and more conspicuous upon the anterior and posterior portions of the shell, becoming fainter or sometimes almost obsolete upon the central portion, the furrows on the anterior part are further apart than upon the posterior portion of the shell. “– Weller (1907) p.618.

FIGURE 35: *LINEARIA METASTRIATA* CONRAD, 1860 A: NJSM 21942 (KWB); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 70 FIG. 9 (KW)

Linearia sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2559b

FIGURE 36: *LINEARIA* SP.; A-B: MAPS A2559B (KW)

GENUS **SOLYMA** CONRAD, 1871***Solyma lineolatus* Conrad, 1871**

Solyma lineolatus Conrad, 1871: p. 75, pl. 3, f. 9; Gabb, 1876A: p. 305; Tyron 1884: p. 134, pl. 105, f. 11-13; Whitfield, 1885: p. 182, pl. 25, f. 11-13; Whitfield, 1886: p. 182, pl. 25, f. 11-13; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 48; Richards, 1958: p. 237, pl. 35, f. 10; pl. 37, f. 5; Richards, 1968: p. 16; Carey, 1976: p. 228, pl. 13, f. 11; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 68.

Solyma lineolata (Conrad, 1871): Whitfield, 1885: p. 182, pl. 25, f. 11-13; Whitfield, 1886: p. 182, pl. 25, f. 11-13; Whitfield, 1899: p. 164; Johnson, 1905: p. 701; Weller, 1907: p. 629, pl. 71, f. 3-6; *not* Gardner, 1916: p. 701 pl. 36, f. 20, 21 = *Solyma gardnerae* Stephenson, 1941.

Solyma cf. lineolatus Conrad, 1871. Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 16; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27.

Types – *Solyma lineolatus* Conrad, 1871, Holotype: ANSP 16327.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 629; Richards (1958) p. 237. .

Description - The dimensions of the type specimen are length, 26 mm.; height, 15.5 mm. Shell subquadrangular in outline, a little broader behind than in front; beaks broad, rather strongly elevated above the hinge-line, nearly central in position and directed anteriorly. Hinge-line nearly straight, the anterior and posterior portions sloping very gently on each side of the beak; antero-cardinal margin concave; anterior margin rounding from the cardinal into the basal margin; basal margin nearly straight or slightly convex in the middle, curving upward a little more abruptly in front than behind; postero-basal extremity rounded; posterior margin nearly vertically truncate; post-cardinal extremity obtusely subangular; post-cardinal margin straight. Valves moderately convex, with an obscure, rounded, umbonal ridge along both the anterior and posterior umbonal slopes; the cardinal margins inflected both in front and behind the beaks. Surface of both valves in the casts marked by rather fine, more or less irregular, concentric lines of growth. – Weller (1907) p. 630.

FIGURE 37: *SOLYMA LINEOLATUS* CONRAD, 1871 : RICHARDS, 1958 PL. 37 FIG. 5 (ANSP 16327) (KWB); B: RICHARDS, 1958 PL. 35 FIG. 10 (KMR); C, D: WELLER, 1907 PL 71 FIG. 3, 6 (KWB); E: WELLER, 1907 PL. 71 FIG. 5 (KMR)

GENUS **TELLINA** LINNAEUS, 1758***Tellina gabbi* Gardner, 1916**

Peronaeoderma georgiana Gabb, 1876A: p. 308; Johnson, 1905: p. 16; Weller, 1907: p. 617: pl. 70, f. 4-6.

Tellina (Acropagia) gabbi Gardner, 1916: p. 694, pl. 42, f. 2.

Tellina gabbi Gardner, 1916. Richards, 1958: p. 230, pl. 35, f. 2, pl.36, f.6,7; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 139, 143, 147, 150, 156; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl 1.

Tellinimera gabbi (Gardner, 1916). Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 141; Kuehne, 1999: p. 79.

Types – *Tellina (Acropagia) gabbi* Gardner, 1916, Holotype: ANSP 18792 (NCKr).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 617 pl. 70, f. 5 (*Peronaeoderma georgiana*); Richards (1958) pl. 36, f. 7 (NJSM 7690); ANSP 81028.

Description. -" Shell small, thin, flattened; elongate, beaks subcentral in one case in the middle, in another a little posterior; cardinal margins sloping about equally towards both ends. Anterior end prominently

and narrowly rounded; posterior rounded, subtruncate; base broadly and regularly convex. Surface marked by fine, regular concentric lines. Hinge composed of minute teeth. Length 1.2 in, width 0.8 in." - Gabb, 1876A.

"Shell rather large for the genus, compressed, ovate, trigonal in outline ; umbones flattened, inconspicuous, not over-topping the dorsal margins, slightly posterior; umbonal angle approximately 135; dorsal margins oblique, the anterior very gentle, the posterior moderately steep; anterior lateral margin broadly and smoothly rounded, the posterior obscurely truncate ; base line broadly arcuate : external surface sculptured with very thin, concentric lamina? their dorsal edges free, but closely appressed; ligament external, opisthodontic, mounted on a nymph almost half the length of the dorsal margin; hinge concentrated, that of the right valve armed with two short, divergent cardinals and an anterior lateral; hinge of left valve and characters of adductor scars and pallial sinus: unknown." – Gardner (1916) p. 694.

FIGURE 38: *TELLINA GABBI* GARDNER, 1916 A: WELLER (1907) PL. 7 FIG. 5 – LEFT VALVE (KW) (NJSM 7690); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 7 FIG. 4 – IMPRESSION OF OUTSPREAD VALVES (KW) (NJSM 7690); C: ANSP 81028 (KW)

***Tellina gabbiana* Gabb, 1876**

Tellina gabbiana Gabb, 1876A: p. 307; Johnson, 1905: p. 16; Weller, 1907: p. 615, pl. 70, f. 1-2; Richards, 1958: p. 229, pl. 36, f. 4, 5; Richards and

Shapiro, 1963: p. 8, pl. 2, f. 12a-b; Richards, 1968: p. 53; Carey, 1976: p. 228, pl. 12, f. 12; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 147; Rindsberg, 1998.

Tellina (Acropagia) georgiana Gabb, 1876A. Gardner, 1916: p. 692.

Tellina cf. georgiana Gabb, 1876A. Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85.

Types – *Tellina georgiana* Gabb, 1876, Holotype: ANSP 18791 (NCKr).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 615 pl. 70, f. 1-2; Richards (1958) p. 229 pl. 36, f. 4, 5 (NJSM 9758).

Description – “The dimensions of two specimens are: length, 32 mm. and 46 mm.; height, 16 mm. and 23 mm. Shell very broadly subtriangular in outline, the beaks nearly central, and pointing a little backward, the greatest anterior extension at about the mid-height of the shell, the greatest posterior extension considerably below the middle. The anterior and posterior cardinal margins meeting at the beak in an angle of about 140 to 150, curving gently downward in front and behind; anterior margin rather sharply rounded; ventral margin very long and gently convex; postero-basal extremity sharply rounded or subangular; posterior margin nearly vertically subtruncate below, curving forward above and passing into the cardinal margin. Valves depressed convex, with a subangular umbonal ridge extending from the beak to the postero-basal extremity, the surface sloping with a very gentle convex curve to the anterior, posterior and ventral margins; curving much more abruptly to the cardinal margins, but just before reaching the margin the surface is deflected in the casts so as to form a rather narrow flattened area extending from the beak in each direction and gradually dying out before reaching the anterior and posterior extremities of the shell; just beneath the beak this flattened area bears the impressions of the hinge-teeth. Surface of the casts smooth except for a few very faint and indistinct radiating costae just above the postero-cardinal slope of the valves. Pallial sinus very deep, extending beyond the middle of the shell. Hinge-teeth small and weak, situated just beneath the beak, a single one in the left valve with a socket on either side, and two in the right valve with a deep socket between.” – Weller (1907) p. 615.

FIGURE 39: *TELLINA GEORGIANA* GABB, 1876 A: WELLER (1907) PL. 70 FIG. 1; RICHARDS (1958) PL. 36 FIG. 4, 5 (NJSM 9758) (Kw)

Tellina sp

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) pl. 70, f. 3,7; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65; MAPS A2531b; MAPS A2531d

FIGURE 40: *TELLINA* SP. A1, A2: BOTH SIDES OF LEFT VALVE MAPS A2531B (Kw); B1, B2: BOTH SIDES OF RIGHT VALVE MAPS A2531B (Kw); C: MAPS A2531B (Kw); D: MAPS A2531D (Kw)

GENUS *TELLINIMERA* CONRAD, 1860

Tellinimera eborea Conrad, 1860

Tellina (*Tellinimera*) *eborea* Conrad, 1860: p. 278, pl. 46, f. 14; Gabb, 1861A: p. 229; Meek, 1864: p. 14.

Tellinimera eborea Conrad, 1860: Conrad, 1868: p. 727; Tyron, 1884: p. 169, pl. 112, f. 100; Whitfield, 1899: p. 165; Johnson, 1905: p. 16; Weller, 1907: p. 621: p. 621, pl. 70, f. 14-23; Gardner, 1916: p. 695, pl. 42, f. 5-6; Wade, 1926: p. 92; Richards, 1958: p. 235, pl. 36, f. 9, 10; Kuehne, 1993: p. 63; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 77; Brister and Young, p. 59.

Tellimera eborea (Conrad, 1860). Conrad, 1871: p. 73, pl. 3, f. 11; Whitfield, 1885: p. 164, pl. 23, f.12-13; Whitfield, 1886: p. 164, pl. 23, f.12-13; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179.

Tellina eborea (Conrad, 1860). Richards, 1968: p. 47.

Linearia (*Tellinmera*) *eborea* (Conrad, 1860). Afshar, 1969: p. 58, pl. 24, f. 9-10.

Types - *Tellina eborea* Conrad, 1860, – Holotype: ANSP 18769 (Kwb).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 621 pl. 70, f. 14-16, 19-20; Richards (1958) p. 235 pl. 36, f. 10 (NJSM 7696).

Description – “The dimensions of an average specimen are length, 13.5 mm.; height, 9 mm.; convexity, 2 mm. Shell triangularly subovate or very broadly subtriangular, depressed convex. Beaks small, appressed, situated considerably back of the middle of the shell. Anterior and posterior cardinal slopes meeting at the beak in an angle of about 140; anterior margin rounded; basal margin broadly convex; posterior margin subtruncate below. A rounded ill-defined umbonal ridge extends from the beak to the postero-basal extremity; the posterior slope short, more or less abrupt, often somewhat flattened; the anterior slope very long and gently convex, becoming somewhat abrupt towards the antero-cardinal margin. Surface of the shell marked by fine, concentric, impressed lines at regularly increasing distances apart, which are bent abruptly upward in crossing the umbonal ridge.” – Weller (1907) p. 621.

FIGURE 41: *TELLINIMERA EBOREA* CONRAD, 1860 A: WELLER (1907) PL.70 FIG. 20 (Kw); B: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 36 FIG. 10 (NJSM 7696) (Kw); C-D: WELLER (1907) PL.70 FIG. 14-16 (NJSM 7696) (Kw)

ORDER CARDITIDA Dall, 1889

FAMILY CRASSATELLIDAE FERUSSAC, 1822

GENUS CRASSATELLA LAMARCK, 1799

Crassatella cuneata (Gabb, 1861)

Non *Crassatella pteropsis* Conrad, 1860: p. 279, pl. 46, f. 9.

Non *Crassatella pteropsis* Gabb, 1860B: p. 395, pl. 68, f. 28.

Crassatella cuneata Gabb, 1861A: p. 168-169 [new assignment for *Crassatella cuneata* Gabb, 1860, not of Conrad, 1860]; Whitfield, 1885: p. 118, pl. 17, f. 18-20; Whitfield, 1886: p. 118, pl. 17, f. 18-20; Wingard, 1993: p. 59-60.

Crassatella gabbi Safford, 1864: p. 368 [new assignment for *Crassatella pteropsis* Gabb, 1860, not of Conrad, 1860]; Harris, 1896: p. 63, pl. 5, f. 7-11; Gardner, 1933: p. 151-152; Palmer and Brann, 1965: p. 100-101; Toulmin 1977: p. 147-148, pl. 2, f. 1, 2.

Crassatellites cuneatus (Gabb, 1861A): Weller, 1907: p. 556, pl. 61, f. 11-12; Richards, 1958: p. 185, pl. 31, f. 2.

Types – *Crassatella cuneatus* Gabb, 1860, Holotype: ANSP 533 (ALKr).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 556; Richards (1958) p. 185.

Description - "Shell small, the dimensions of a nearly complete internal cast are length, 16 mm.; height, 10.5 mm.; thickness, 6.5 mm. Subovate in outline, cuneate behind. Beaks erect, rather prominent, situated about one-third the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Antero-cardinal margin sloping forward from the beak; anterior margin rounding into the basal margin; basal margin convex in front and straight or slightly concave posteriorly; posterior margin short, truncate; post-cardinal margin long, sloping backward from the beak and meeting the posterior margin at the extremity of the hinge-line in an obtuse angle. An obtusely subangular umbonal ridge passes in a nearly straight or slightly concave line from the beak to the postero-basal extremity; the postero-cardinal slope flat or slightly concave, the cardinal margin inflected. Surface of the shell marked with rather strong, regular, concentric lines of growth. In well preserved internal casts, the post-cardinal margin and the truncate posterior margin are not sharply differentiated, the posterior extremity of the shell being rather sharply rounded. The muscular scars prominent in the casts. When the internal casts are well preserved to the margin of the shell, the free margins are finely crenate." – Weller (1907) p. 557.

FIGURE 42: *CRASSATELLA CUNEATA* (GABB, 1861) A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL 17 FIG. 19-20 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS") C: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 31 FIG. 2 (KMV)

***Crassatella hodgei* (Stephenson, 1923)**

Non *Crassatella pteropsis*? Conrad, 1875A: p. A6, pl. 1., f. 25 (not of *Bathytormus pteropsis* (Conrad, 1860)).

Crassatellites hodgei (Stephenson, 1923): p. 271, pl. 67, f. 4-8; Richards, 1958: p. 187, pl. 31, f. 3, 4; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64.

Crassatellites roodensis Stephenson, 1923: p. 271, pl. 68, f. 1-4; Stephenson, 1926: p. 246, pl. 90, f. 5.

Crassatellites cf. pteropsis (Conrad 1875): Richards, 1950, p. 74, f. 61b, 61c (not of *Bathytormus pteropsis* (Conrad, 1860))

Crassatella hodgei (Stephenson, 1923). Richards, 1954: p. 2, text fig. 1; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 7; Wingard, 1993: p. 76, pl. 2, f. 7, 8, 10, 11, pl. 4, f. 1-10, pl. 5, f. 2, 7, 9, 10, 12, pl. 6, f. 1-6; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Rindsberg, 1998.

Crassatellites cf. hodgei (Stephenson, 1923). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 7.

Crassatella roodensis (Stephenson, 1923). Wingard, 1993: p.76, pl. 4, f. 10, 18.

Crassatella cf. hodgei (Stephenson, 1923). Elder, 1996: p. 258, f. 5, 9; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 246, f. 219.

Types – *Crassatellites hodgei* Stephenson, 1923, pl. 67, f. 5, 6, Holotype: USNM 31930; *Crassatellites hodgei* Stephenson, 1923, pl. 67, f. 7, Paratypes: USNM 31931; USNM 31749.

Wenonah Specimens – Richards (1958) p. 187.

Description.— “Shell equivalve, inflation shallow to fairly convex; maximum convexity at midpoint of height; shell flattens across umbo region as viewed from ventral or dorsal margins parallel to plane of commissure; adults vary from trigonally suboval to obtusely trigonal in outline; nepionic outline subcircular; juveniles rapidly assume adult shape; inequilateral; beak position highly variable, ranging from anterior one-quarter to near midlength of shell; early stages of shell prosogyrous; adult appears weakly prosogyrate to nearly orthogyrate as viewed perpendicular to plane of commissure. Anterior dorsal margin slightly concave to slightly convex at maximum width of lunule; margin slopes steeply away from beak; lunule well developed on left valve of adults with sharp ridge defining area, less well defined on right valve with no distinct ridge; anterior margin smoothly rounded. Posterior dorsal margin straight to slightly concave near end of escutcheon; slope of margin varies from steep to gentle depending on posterior elongation; escutcheon elongate, well defined on right valve with area defined by ridge, less well defined on left valve with ridge absent; posterior ridge varies from sharp raised carinate forms preceded by depression in shell surface to forms with simple ridge marked by bend in growth lines; posterior margin varies from pointed to quadrilaterally truncate on adults. Ventral margin gently curved anteriorly, flattened to rounded below beak, strongly incurved to flattened below posterior adductor. Ornamentation begins at beak as evenly spaced coarse raised ribs with broad interspaces reduced to raised sharp lines in posterior area, gradually shifts to closely spaced finer ribs at later stages, and in some cases fades entirely; comarginal threads begin near beak and continue across entire shell surface, including ribs, interspaces, and

posterior area; lower portions of shell may show deep broad undulations of surface; stage at which shift in ornamentation occurs is highly variable. Hinge angle variable, average 113 degrees; moving from posterior lateral ridges across hinge plate to anterior lateral ridges, dentition noted as follows: Right Valve 0 1 0-R 010 -101 Left Valve 1 0 I-R(O) 1010 (1)-0 1 0 Right valve dentition consists of one posterior lateral ridge, separated by edentulous space from resilifer (R); resilifer originates at beak on platform formed by rear wall of a trigonal socket below and slightly anterior to resilifer; opening of resilial platform to umbonal cavity is incompletely obstructed by position of trigonal socket; trigonal socket may have vertical grooves on rear wall of socket; one large cardinal tooth lies anterior to beak, some with transverse grooves on sides of tooth; two anterior lateral ridges present, separated by groove. Left valve dentition consists of two posterior lateral ridges, separated by groove; resilifer originates at beak; opening of resilial area to umbonal cavity restricted by depression at base of posterior slope of cardinal; two well defined cardinals separated by socket, some with transverse grooves on sides of cardinals; forward of anterior most cardinal is narrow groove followed by short ridge; one anterior lateral ridge present. Resilifer shaped like elongate teardrop. Juveniles display well-developed hinge characters at early stages. Isomyarian adductor muscle scars; anterior reniform; posterior subcircular to suboval. Anterior pedal retractor present. Pallial line distinct, entire. Crenulations present from end of anterior lateral ridge ventrally to posterior lateral ridge on adults; development begins anteriorly early in ontogeny so young specimens may have complete marginal crenulations. Prodissoconch not known." – Wingard (1993) p. 76

FIGURE 43: *CRASSATELLA HODGEI* STEPHENSON, 1923 A-B:
RICHARDS (1958) PL. 3 FIG. 3-4 (KWB)

Crassatella transversa Gabb, 1862

Crassatella transversa Gabb, 1862C: p. 364-365; Meek, 1864 p. 11; Conrad, 1868: p. 726p; Whitfield, 1885: p. 122, pl. 17, f. 16-17; Whitfield, 1886: p. 122, pl. 17, f. 16-17; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156; Richards, 1968: p. 90; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 30; Wingard, 1993: p. 60; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64, 65.

Crassatellites transversus (Gabb, 1862C): Johnson, 1905: p. 14; Weller, 1907: p. 555, pl. 61, f. 5; Stephenson, 1923: p. 274; Richards, 1958: p. 185, pl. 29, f. 8.

Types – *Crassatella transversa* Gabb, 1862, Holotype: ANSP 18744 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens –Weller (1907) p. 555 pl. 61, f. 5; Richards (1958) p. 185 pl. 29, f. 8 (ANSP 18744); Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65; MAPS A2523a; MAPS A2523b.

Description - The dimensions of an internal cast are length, 49 mm.; height, 32 mm.; thickness, 20 mm. Shell very inequilateral, higher in front than behind, the beaks pointed in the internal casts and nearly erect, situated about one-third the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Anterior margin convex in front, rounding to the hinge-line above and into the basal margin below; basal margin convex anteriorly and concave posteriorly; postero-basal margin sharply rounding into the obliquely subtruncate posterior margin, which rounds into the dorsal margin above. Valves with an umbonal ridge extending in a nearly straight line from the beak obliquely backward to the postero-basal extremity of the shell, becoming more angular posteriorly. The postero-cardinal slope rather narrow, flat, slightly concave or slightly convex. Surface of the shell marked with somewhat regular, rather strong, concentric lines of growth which are less conspicuous back of the umbonal ridge. In internal casts the muscular impressions are conspicuous and of about equal size. Free margin of the shell crenate. Weller (1907) p. 555.

FIGURE 44: *CRASSATELLA TRANSVERSA* GABB, 1862 A: WELLER (1907) PL. 61 FIG. 5 (Kw); B-E: MAPS A2523B (Kw)

GENUS *SCAMBULA* CONRAD, 1869

Scambula perplana Conrad, 1869

Scambula perplana Conrad, 1869E: p. 47, pl. 9, f. 7, 8; Conrad, 1872: p. 51 pl. 1., f. 2; Whitfield, 1885: p. 123-124, pl. 18, f. 8-10; Whitfield, 1886: p. 123-124, pl. 18, f. 8-10; Whitfield, 1899: p. 163; Weller, 1907: p. 562, pl. 61, f. 13-14; Wade, 1926: p. 82, pl. 25, f. 11, 12, 15, 16; Chavan, 1939: p. 32; Stephenson, 1941: p. 183; pl. 26, f. 11-12; Shimer and Shrock, 1944: p. 419, pl. 167, f. 6,7; Stephenson, 1955: p. 118, pl. 18, f. 3-5; Richards, 1958: p. 192, pl. 31, f. 9; Richards, 1968: p. 75; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 139, 162; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Wingard, 1993: p. 89, pl. 2, f. 6, pl. 20, f. 2, pl. 21, f. 1, 5, 7, 9; Rindsberg, 1998; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 249, f. 222; Brister and Young, 2007, p. 59.

Crassatella perplana (Conrad, 1869). Stoliczka, 1871: p. 294, 295.

Crassatellites (*Scambula*) *perplana* (Conrad, 1869). Johnson, 1905: p. 14.

Anthonya (*Scambula*) *perplana* (Conrad, 1869). Stewart, 1930: p. 147.

Scambula widmeri Richards, 1962. p. 204, pl. 93, f. 19,20.

Types – *Scambula perplana* Conrad, 1869, Holotype: ANSP 18740 (Kwb); *Scambula widmeri* Richards, 1962, Holotype ANSP, 30750. Plesiotype: USNM 128142, USNM 76572.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 553 pl. 61, f. 14; Richards (1958) p. 187.

Description — Shell equivalve, flat; outline of shell triangular, adults posteriorly elongate, juveniles approaching equilateral. Inequilateral; beak position of adults at approximately anterior two-fifths shell length, juveniles closer to midlength of shell; beak high, pointed, opisthogyrous. Anterior dorsal margin straight to slightly convex, slopes steeply down to ventral margin; lunule extremely narrow, elongate; anterior margin turns abruptly to ventral margin. Posterior dorsal margin concave, slopes steeply away from beak, levels out above anterior termination of posterior adductor; escutcheon elongate, narrow, flattened; raised posterior ridge absent, posterior area demarcated by bend in ornament alone; posterior margin truncate. Ventral margin broadly rounded; shell material thickened at edge. Ornament consistent across shell surface; fine ornament of comarginal growth threads overlies dominant ornament of rounded raised ribs, separated by incised fine lines; lamellae of ribs may extend past dorsal margins giving rugose appearance. Hinge angle approaches right angle; moving from posterior lateral ridges across hinge plate to anterior lateral ridges, dentition noted as follows: Right Valve 010 (I)-R(I) 010 (I)-(O) (1) 0 1 Left Valve 1 0 1 (O)-R 101 (O)-(I) (O) 1 0 Right valve dentition consists of one sharp raised posterior lateral ridge extending from beak to above posterior adductor, separated by shallow furrow from second faint posterior lateral ridge that fades into resilifer area; elongate, narrow, triangular resilifer originates at beak, extends to edge of hinge platform, curves posteriorly; anteriorly very narrow trigonal socket separated from resilifer by low, sharp, narrow ridge; ridge almost bifurcation of posterior edge of cardinal; one strong medial cardinal tooth anterior to beak, curves posteriorly, vertical striations present on sides of tooth; deep, narrow, elongate socket separates strong medial cardinal from faint, narrow, low anterior ridge, which blends ventrally into hinge platform; one short anterior lateral ridge, separated by groove from long anterior lateral ridge, extends length of anterior dorsal margin to above anterior adductor. Left valve dentition consists of two sharp posterior lateral ridges, separated by deep groove; both posterior lateral ridges extend from above

posterior adductor to beak but interior-most ridge fades slightly near beak; elongate, narrow, triangular resilifer originates at beak, extends to edge of hinge platform; two narrow cardinals separated by deep narrow socket, all curve posteriorly; anterior-most cardinal slightly broader; anterior-side of posterior cardinal and both sides of anterior cardinal covered with vertical striations; faint anterior lateral ridges continuous with edge of hinge platform, separated by groove from sharp anterior lateral ridge extending from beak along anterior dorsal margin to above anterior adductor. Edge of hinge platform continuous with umbonal cavity; cavity beneath hinge platform absent. Two subequal shallow adductor muscle scars, anterior oval, posterior subelliptical. Anterior and posterior pedal retractor scars independent, small, subcircular, located above adductor scars. Pallial line faint, entire. Fine, sharp marginal crenulations present from anterior lateral ridges ventral to posterior lateral ridges. Prodissoconch not seen." – Wingard (1993) p. 90.

FIGURE 45: *SCAMBULA PERPLANA* CONRAD, 1869 A-C: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 18 FIG. 8-10 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS" – HADDONFIELD, NJ)

ORDER LIMIDA Moore, 1952

FAMILY LIMIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS LIMA BRUGUIÈRE, 1797

Lima monmouthensis (Whitfield, 1885)

Nucula monmouthensis Whitfield, 1885: p. 102, pl. 11, f. 1; Whitfield, 1886: p. 102, pl. 11, f. 1; Whitfield, 1899: p. 161.

Lima monmouthensis (Whitfield, 1885). Weller, 1907: p. 494, pl. 54, f. 9; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 189-191; Richards, 1958: p. 145, pl. 22, f. 11

Types – *Nucula monmouthensis* Whitfield, 1885, Holotype: NJSM 9731 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Whitfield (1886) p. 102 pl. 11, f. 1; Weller (1907) p. 494 pl. 54, f. 9; Richards (1958) p. 145 pl. 22, f. 11 (NJSM 9731).

Description – "Shell small, the dimensions of the type specimen being height, 12 mm.; length, n mm.; convexity of one valve, 3 mm. Valves oblique, moderately convex, subovate in outline not gaping; hinge-line short, arcuate, edentulous; beaks near the center of the hinge line, auriculations absent. Surface of valves marked only by faint, concentric lines of growth." – Weller (1907) p. 494.

FIGURE 46: *LIMA MONMOUTHENSIS* (WHITFIELD, 1885) A: NJSM 9731 (Kw); B: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 11 FIG. 1 (NJSM 9731) (Kw)

Lima reticulata (Lyell and Forbes, 1845)

Ctenoides reticulata (Lyell and Forbes, 1845). Gabb, 1859: p. 10; Gabb, 1861A: p. 171.

Lima reticulata Lyell and Forbes, 1845: p. 62, f. 1, 2; Meek, 1864: p. 7; Stephenson, 1907: p. 136, 140, 143, 153, 154, 156, 163; Weller, 1907: p. 492, pl. 54, f. 3-4; Gardner, 1916: p. 600, pl. 34, f. 12, 13;

Stephenson, 1914; p. 24, t. 2-8; Stephenson, 1923: p. 213, pl. 58, f. 10-15; Wade, 1926: p. 66, pl. 20, f. 12; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 193-195; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 44; Richards, 1958: p. 144, pl. 22, f. 9-10; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40, 46; Sohl and Christopher 1983: p. 8; Sohl and Koch, 1987 p. 146, 159; Kuehne, 1993: p. 66; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 63, 68, 70-72; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 58; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016 p. 54, App. B pl. 1.

Radula reticulata (Lyell and Forbes, 1845). Conrad, 1868: p. 728; Stoliczka, 1871: p. 416; Whitfield, 1885: p. 63, 64, pl. 9, f. 8,9; Whitfield, 1886: p. 63, 64, pl. 9, f. 8, 9; Whitfield, 1899: p. 163.

Lima auctilineata Conrad, 1858A. Whitfield, 1885: p. 62; Whitfield, 1886: p. 62.

Limea (Pseudolimea) reticulata (Lyell and Forbes, 1845). Dhondt, 1989: p. 107; Elder, 1996: p. 257, f. 4.15-4.17; Rindsberg, 1998.

Types - *Lima reticulata* Lyell, Forbes 1845, Holotype Lost.

Wenonah Specimens – Richards (1958) p. 144.

Description - "Shell small, moderately oblique, strongly ovate and inflated. Hinge short, beaks proportionately strong and projecting beyond the cardinal line. Valves nearly equal; anterior margin straight and not at all gaping; auriculations small but distinct, rectangular or very slightly pointed at their outer angles, Surface radiately ribbed, those of the anterior and posterior slopes faintly marked or obsolete, ribs (about 30) distinct, with five or more indistinct on each side; subangular on the middle of the valves and rounded toward the sides, crenulate or subspinose on the larger specimens when well preserved, but often appearing nearly smooth. Entire surface marked by concentric lines which give a roughened surface when perfect, giving the reticulated character indicated by the specific name." – Whitfield (1886) p. 63.

FIGURE 47: *LIMA RETICULATA* (LYELL, FORBES, 1845) A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL 9 FIG. 8-9 ("LOWER GREEN SANDS – FREEHOLD NJ); C: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 22 FIG. 9 (NJSM 9942) (KMV); D: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 22. FIG. 10 (NJSM 9636) (KMT)

***Lima whitfieldi* Weller, 1907**

Radula pelagica Whitfield, 1885: p. 61, pl. 9, f. 4 (not pl. 9, f. 3, 5 =?); Whitfield, 1886: p. 61, pl. 9, f. 4 (not pl. 9, f. 3, 5 =?).

Lima whitfieldi Weller, 1907: p. 491, pl. 54, f 8; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 195-196; Richards, 1958: p. 143, pl. 24, f. 13; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer 1986: p. 30.

Types – *Lima whitfieldi* Weller, 1907: pl. 54, f 8, Holotype: NJSM 7601 (Kmt).

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30.

Description – "The dimensions of the type specimen are extreme length, 25 mm.; greatest width, 21.5 mm.; length of hinge line, 8 mm.; convexity of one valve, 7 mm. In general form and proportions this shell is essentially identical with *R. pelagica*, but it has not been observed to attain so large a size as that species and differs fundamentally in the character of the surface markings. In this species the plications and interspaces are always rounded and lack entirely the secondary riblets which are present in the bottom of the interspaces in *R. pelagica*. In addition to the ribs the shell is entirely covered with fine concentric markings." – Weller (1907) p. 491.

FIGURE 48: *LIMA WHITFIELDI* WELLER, 1907 A-B: NJSM 7601 (HOLOTYPE) (KMT); C: WHITFIELD (1886) PL 9 F. 4 (KMT) (*RADULA PELAGICA* = *L. WHITFIELDI*); D: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 24 FIG. 13 (NJSM 7601) (KMT)

ORDER MYALINIDA Paul, 1939

FAMILY INOCERAMIDAE GIEBEL, 1852

GENUS INOCERAMUS J. SOWERBY, 1814

Inoceramus proximus Toumey, 1854

Inoceramus proximus Toumey, 1854: p. 171; Gabb, 1861A: p. 185; Meek, 1864: p. 10; Meek, 1876: p. 53, pl. 12, f. 7a-b; Smith, 1905: p. 636; Stephenson, 1907: p. 140, 143; Weller, 1907: p. 424, pl. 40, f. 1-6; pl. 41, f.1; Kummel, 1908; Wade, 1926: p. 49 pl. 12, f. 2; Richards, 1943: p. 24, pl. 6, f. 1; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 124-125; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 42; Richards, 1958: p. 95, pl. 15, f. 6,7; Richards, 1963: p. 25; Carey, 1976: p. 214, pl. 6, f. 8; Gallagher, 1984: p. 14; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 57, 60, 64, 65; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57; Lauginiger, 2014; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B. pl. 1.

Non *Inoceramus sagensis* Owen, 1854. Whitfield, 1885: p. 76, pl. 15, f. 5, pl. 15, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1886: p. 76, pl. 15, f. 5, pl. 15, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1899: p. 159.

Inoceramus aff. I. proximus Toumey 1854: Cobban, Landis and Dane, 1974: p. 279. 280.

Types - *Inoceramus proximus* Toumey, 1854, Holotype -Lost? (MSKr?).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) pl. 40, f. 3; Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65.

Description – “Shell in large examples attaining a height of 100 mm. or more, and a length of 120 mm. or more. The valves subovate in outline, moderately convex, the hinge line about two-thirds the length of the shell, the beak but little elevated above the hinge-line. The anterior margin sloping forward from the beak and rounding gradually into the broadly rounded basal margin, posterior margin broadly rounded and meeting the hinge line in an obtuse angle. Surface of the shell marked by more or less rounded or subangular, concentric undulations, which are often somewhat irregular in the strength of their development and in their distances apart. In addition to the undulations the surface of the shell is marked by fine concentric striae separated by intervals of 1 mm. or less.” – Weller (1907) p. 424.

FIGURE 49: *INOCERAMUS PROXIMUS* A-D: NJSM 21010 (MR)

Inoceramus sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2467e; MAPS A2476i; MAPS A2467p

FIGURE 50: *INOCERAMUS* SP. A: MAPS A2467P (KW); B -E: MAPS A2467E (KW)

ORDER MYIDA Stoliczka, 1870

FAMILY CORBULIDAE LAMARCK, 1818

GENUS *CAESTOCORBULA* VINCENT, 1910

Caestocorbula crassiplica (Gabb, 1860)

Corbula crassiplica Gabb, 1860A: p. 394, pl. 68, f. 25; Gabb, 1861A: p. 166; Safford, 1869: p. 416; Whitfield, 1885: p. 178, pl. 23, f. 30; Whitfield, 1886: p. 178, pl. 23, f. 30; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156; Johnson, 1905: p. 17; Stephenson, 1907: p. 136, 140, 143; Weller, 1907: p. 641, pl. 72, f. 27-28; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2-8; Gardner, 1916: p. 713, pl. 43, f. 6-7; Wade, 1926: p. 96, pl. 31, f. 9, 13; Stephenson, 1941: p. 234-235, pl. 44, f. 16-17; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 48; Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957: p. 11; Richards, 1958: p. 251, pl. 38, f. 6; Gallagher, 1984: p. 16; Gallagher, 1986: p. 11; Kuehne, 1993: p. 61; Perrilliat, Vega and Corona, 2000: p. 22, f. 7.23; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54, 60; Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 14; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B pl. 1.

Corbula crassiplicata (Gabb, 1860A). Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 15; Conrad, 1868: p. 727; Conrad, 1875B: p. A16; Richards, 1956: p. 73.

not *Corbula perbrevis* Conrad, 1875A: App. A, pl. 2, f. 5. Only Weller, 1907, p. 641 lists *C. perbrevis* as a

synonym but Stephenson, 1923, p. 346 does not agree with this assignment.

Caestocorbula crassiplica (Gabb, 1860A). Vokes, 1944: p. 614, pl. 1, f.3; Haribson, 1945: p. 80; Stephenson, 1955: p. 56; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 42, 46; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 7; DeCauwer, 1985: p. 186; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 62, 65, 71, 79; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012, f. 7; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 110, t. 1, pl. 2, f. 2a,b; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61, 62, 72, pl. 4.

Caestocorbula (*Parmicorbula*) *crassiplica* (Gabb, 1860A). Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 404, f. 385.

Caestocorbula (*Caestocorbula*) *crassiplica* (Gabb, 1860A).

Types – *Corbula crassiplica* Gabb, 1860, Holotype: Lost?, **Plesiotype**: USNM 76730.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 641; Richards (1958) p. 251; Kuehne (1999) p. 65.

Description – “The dimensions of a right valve are length, 6 mm; height, 5 mm. Shell subtriangular in form. Beaks large, inflated and enrolled, situated a little in front of the middle of the shell. Hinge-line arcuate; antero-cardinal margin sloping rather abruptly forward to the anterior extremity of the shell below the middle; basal margin convex anteriorly through the greater portion of its length, becoming concave behind; postero-basal extremity angular; posterior margin short, vertically truncate, curving rather abruptly above into the long sloping postero-cardinal margin. Right valve strongly ventricose, with an angular umbonal ridge which is faint or obsolete towards the beak, becoming conspicuous as it approaches the postero-basal angle of the shell; in front of the umbonal ridge in the lower half of the shell is a rather narrow but distinct sinus which forms the posterior sinuosity in the basal margin; the post-umbonal slope concave. Surface of the valve marked with nine or ten strong, rounded, elevated, concentric costae, which continue from the anterior margin of the shell to the sinus in front of the umbonal ridge, the interspaces about equaling the ribs in width. On the umbo the concentric markings are reduced rather abruptly from the strong costae to fine concentric lines; passing over the umbonal ridge and down the posterior slope, are rather fine, sublamellose, concentric lines of growth. Left valve much less

ventricose than the right and the beak much less produced, the surface marked only with more or less irregular concentric lines without the strong costae.” – Weller (1907) p. 641.

FIGURE 51: CAESTROCORBULA CRASSIPLICA GABB, 1860 A: WELLER (1907) PL. 72 FIG. 28 (KWB); B-C: NJSM 21929 (KWB); D: NJSM 19072 (KWB); E: WOODBURY SPECIMEN (COURTESY OF JOHN WHITLEY)

ORDER MYTILIDA Rafinesque, 1815

FAMILY MYTILIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS BOTULA MORCH, 1853

***Botula ripleyana* (Gabb, 1862)**

Lithophagus ripleyannus Gabb, 1862A: p. 326; Meek, 1864: p. 10; Ruhoff, 1980: p. 468, 608; Kleemann, 1983: p. 21, 27, 31.

Lithophagus affinis Gabb, 1862A: p. 327; Meek, 1864: p. 10; Conrad, 1868: p. 726; Twenhofel, 1924: p. 74; Ruhoff, 1980: p. 127, 608; Kleeman, 1983: p. 1, 28, 31.

Lithodomus affinis (Gabb, 1862A). Whitfield, 1885: p. 66-67, pl. 17, f. 2,3; Whitfield, 1886: p. 66-67, pl. 17

f. 2,3; Stoliczka, 1871: p. 375; Kleemann, 1983: p. 21.

Lithophaga ripleyana (Gabb, 1862A). Gabb, 1876: p. 311-312; Johnson, 1905: p. 13; Weller, 1907: p. 512, pl. 56, f. 9-12; Gardner, 1916: p. 618, pl. 36, f. 6; Wade, 1926: p. 70, pl. 23, f. 5,6; Stephenson, 1941: p. 155,156, 633; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 230-231; Stephenson, 1952: p. 86, 222, 224; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 45, pl. 4; Richards, 1958: p. 156, pl. 25, f. 11; Carey, 1976: p. 216: pl. 7, f. 7; Carter, 1978: p. 85; Kleeman, 1983: p. 5; Gallagher, 1984: p. 27; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 16, 17; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Andrews, 1995: p. 290; Bien, Wendt and Alexander, 1999: p. 300, 301; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 58; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 110, t. 1.

Lithophaga affinis (Gabb, 1862A). Gabb, 1876A: p. 311-312; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156; Johnson, 1905: p. 13; Gardner, 1916: p. 619; Wade, 1926: p. 70; Stephenson, 1952: p. 86, 219, 222; Richards, 1958: p. 157, pl. 25, f. 12.

Lithodomus ripleyana (Gabb, 1862A). Whitfield, 1885: p. 67, pl. 17, f. 4-5; Whitfield, 1886: p. 67, pl. 17, f. 4-5; Clark, 1897: p. 335; Clark, 1898: p. 185; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156.

Botula ripleyana (Gabb, 1862A). Stephenson, 1952: p. 86; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 146.

Botula affinis (Gabb, 1862A). Kleemann, 2007: p. 5, pl. 1, f. 7a, b.

Types – *Lithophagus ripleyannus* Gabb, 1862A, Holotype: ANSP 19580 (Kmv).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 512; Richards (1958) p. 156.

Description – “Shell more or less subcylindrical, sometimes curved downward posteriorly, attaining a length of 15 mm. to 20 mm. in full grown specimens, the width and thickness usually about one-half the length. Anterior extremity of the shell bluntly rounded, the beaks blunt, anterior or nearly terminal in position; posterior extremity of the shell compressed. Dorsal margin marked by an impressed line between the valves. Surface of the shell, which is rarely preserved, marked by lamellose, concentric lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 512.

FIGURE 52: *BOTULA RIPLEYANA* (GABB, 1862) A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 17 F. 4-5 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); C: WELLER (1907) PL. 56 FIG. 11 (KNS); D: CAREY (1976) PL. 7 FIG. 7 (KML)

GENUS *INOPERNA* CONRAD, 1875
Inoperna carolinensis Conrad, 1875

Inoperna carolinensis Conrad, 1875A: p. A5, pl. 1, f. 22; Stephenson, 1907: p. 140; Kummel, 1908: p. 69; Clark, Miller, Stephenson, Johnson and Parker, 1912: p. 140; Stephenson, 1923: p. 239, pl. 62, f. 14; Wade, 1926: p. 53, pl. 13, f. 10; Stenzel, Krause and Twinning, 1957: p. 74; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer 1986: p. 30; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 68, 79; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 59, f. 59; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B pl. 1.

Types – Holotype: *Inoperna carolinensis* Conrad, 1875, USNM 31927 (NCKr).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2514b; MAPS A2514c.

Description - "Shells slightly arcuate towards the posterior end, much compressed, gradually expanding to the posterior extremity, which is rounded. "The shorter outline and larger ribs distinguish this species from the allied forms. The compression of the valves may be owing to pressure, one valve being perfectly flat." – Conrad (1875A) p. A5.

"Shell thin, greatly elongated, curved forward below mid-height, slightly convex. Beak and hinge not preserved and internal characters not uncovered. The

greatest dimension of the specimen is about 80 mm. and its greatest width at right angles to the elongation is about 21 mm. Anterior margin a little convex near the upper extremity, below which it becomes nearly straight to a point a little below the midheight, where it curves pronouncedly forward; ventral margin short and sharply rounded; posterior margin broadly convex from the lower extremity to a point a little below the midheight, above which the margin is nearly straight. Surface strongly plicated concentrically with major and minor folds on the posterior slope and on the entire surface below the midheight; anterior slope above the midheight smooth except for fine-growth lines and very gentle plications." – Stephenson (1923) p. 240.

FIGURE 53: *INOPERNA CAROLINENSIS* CONRAD, 1875 A: MAPS A2514c (Kw); B: MAPS A2514c -DORSAL AND VENTRAL VIEW (Kw); C: MAPS A2514b (Kw)

GENUS *MODIOLUS* LAMARCK, 1799

According to ICZN the genus *Modiolus* is the accepted genus over *Volsella*.

Modiolus wenonah (Weller, 1907)

Modiola wenonah Weller, 1907: p. 507, pl. 55, f. 11.

Volsella wenonah (Weller, 1907). Ramsdell, 1948: p. 237; Richards, 1958: p. 155, pl. 25, f. 8.

Types –*Modiola wenonah* Weller, 1907, Holotype: NJSM 7681 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 507 pl. 55 f. 11 (NJSM 7681); Richards (1958) (*Volsella*

wenonah) p. 155 pl. 25, f. 8 (NJSM 7681); MAPS A2454b.

Description – “Shell small, the dimensions of the type specimen being length, 15 mm.; width, 8 mm.; convexity, 3.5 mm. The hinge-line a little more than one-half the length, the beaks nearly anterior, umbo rather prominent with a somewhat broadly rounded umbonal ridge extending to the posterobasal margin. Anterior margin rather broadly rounding into the nearly straight basal margin, which is slightly sinuate back of the middle, postero-basal margin rather sharply rounding into the long, oblique, slightly convex upper portion of the posterior margin which meets the posterior extremity of the hinge-line at an angle of about 125. Surface of the internal cast marked by indistinct concentric lines of growth. This species is based upon a single individual from the top of the Wenonah sand near Marlboro. It differs from all other members of the genus in the New Jersey Cretaceous faunas, in the conspicuous postero-basal extension of the shell with the long oblique posterior slope above.” – Weller (1907) p. 507.

FIGURE 54: *MODIOLUS WENONAH* (WELLER, 1907) A: NJSM 7681 (Kw); B: MAPS A2454A (Ks)

GENUS *MYTILUS* LINNAEUS, 1758
Mytilus oblivius Whitfield, 1885

Mytilus oblivius Whitfield, 1885: p. 65, pl. 17, f. 1; Whitfield, 1886, p. 65, pl. 17, f. 1; Whitfield, 1899: p. 161; Weller, 1905: p. 333; Weller, 1907: p. 503, pl. 55, f. 5-8; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 232-233; Richards, 1958: p. 152, pl. 25, f. 4.

Types –*Mytilus oblivius* Whitfield, 1885, Holotype: NJSM 9733 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Whitfield (1886) p. 64 pl. 17, f. 1 (NJSM 9733); Weller (1907) p. 503 pl. 55, f. 5-6 (NJSM 9733); Richards (1958) p. 152 pl. 25, f. 4 (NJSM 9733).

Description - "Shell small, erect, or but very slightly curved on the buccal margin, beaks terminal, projecting and acute. Hinge line sloping at an angle of about 60 to the buccal margin; posterior margin subparallel to the anterior, and the extremity rather sharply rounded. Anterior face abrupt, and the surface of the valve gradually sloping from the umbonal angle to the posterior margin. Surface apparently marked by fine lines of growth as indicated on the cast." -Whitfield (1886) p. 64

FIGURE 55: *MYTILUS OBLIVIOUS* A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 17 FIG. 1 ("LOWER GREEN SANDS"); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 55 FIG. 5 (Kw); C: NJSM 9733 (Kw)

ORDER NUCULANIDA CARTER, CAMPBELL, CAMPBELL
2000

FAMILY NUCULANIDAE ADAMS AND ADAMS, 1858

GENUS NUCULANA LINK, 1807

Nuculana marlboroensis (Weller, 1907)

Leda marlboroensis Weller, 1907: p. 374, pl. 29, f. 18-23.

Nuculana marlboroensis (Weller, 1907). Ramsdell, 1948: p. 106-107; Richards, 1958: p. 62, pl. 10, f. 9, 10.

Nuculana cf. marlboroensis (Weller, 1907). Owens, Miller and Mello, 1970: p 40, t. 6.

Types – *Leda marlboroensis* Weller, 1907, Cotypes: NJSM 9686 (Kw), 9687 (Kw), UC 18660 (Kw).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 375 pl. 29, f. 18-23; Richards (1958) p. 62 pl. 10, f. 9, 10 (NJSM 9686); NJSM 9686; NJSM 9687; UC 18660.

Description – “Shell small, the dimensions of a small internal cast being length, 6 mm.; height, 3.5 mm.; convexity, 1.5 mm. The dimensions of a larger individual are length, 13.5 mm.; height, 7.5 mm.; convexity, 2 mm. Beaks rather prominent, directed backward, situated about twice the length of the shell from the anterior end. Anterior portion of the shell in front of the beaks, subsemielliptical in outline, somewhat inflated; posterior portion compressed, rostrate, the postero-dorsal margin concave, the posterior extremity sharply and narrowly rounded, the postero-ventral margin gently convex. Hinge-line elongate, the anterior row of teeth straight, about 12 in number; posterior row slightly concave, with 16 or 18 teeth. Surface of the shell as shown in impressions of the exterior, marked by fine, regular, concentric costae.” – Weller (1907) p. 375.

FIGURE 56: *NUCULANA MARLBOROENSIS* (WELLER, 1907) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 29 FIG. 21 (Kw)

Nuculana rostratruncata (Gardner, 1916)

Leda rostratruncata Gardner, 1916: p. 516, pl.19, f. 8, 9.

Nuculana rostratruncata (Gardner, 1916). Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 139, 141, 143, 146, 153, 156, 159; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 73, 77, 79.

Nuculana cf. rostratruncata (Gardner, 1916). Kuehne, 1995: p. 84.

Types – *Leda rostratruncata* Gardner, 1916, Holotype: USNM 131897 (Ks).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2478b.

Description – “Shell very thin and fragile, transversely elongated, moderately convex, umbones small, not very prominent, incurved and opisthogyrate, placed a little in front of the median horizontal; anterior end a little shorter than the posterior, broadly rounded distally; posterior end strongly rostrate, the rostrum squarely truncated, and isolated by a broad and shallow depression in front of it; lunule narrow but well defined; escutcheon strongly differentiated, outlined by a low ridge, persistent to the extremity of the keel; external surface sculptured with thirty to forty fine, concentric rugae, regular in size and spacing over the entire disk but absent upon the tips of the umbones and the lunule and escutcheon; teeth arranged in two discrete series, becoming finer toward their point of convergence beneath the umbones; anterior series numbering approximately twenty - five denticles, the posterior twenty - eight; pallial line and muscle scars obscure. Dimensions. - Right valves, longitude 18.5 mm, 8.5 mm.; left valve of another individual, longitude 14.5 mm., altitude 7 mm.” – Gardner (1916) p. 517.

FIGURE 57: *NUCULANA ROSTRATRUNCATA* (GARDNER, 1916)
A: MAPS A2478A (Ks); B: MAPS A2478B (Kw)

***Nuculana stephensoni* Richards, 1958**

Perrisonota protexta Conrad, 1869A: p. 98, pl. 9, f. 24; Conrad, 1875B: p. A14; Whitfield, 1885: p. 110, pl. 11, f. 14, 15; Whitfield, 1886: p. 110, pl. 11, f. 14, 15; Whitfield, 1899: p. 163; Weller, 1907: p. 379, pl. 30, f. 1, 2; Gardner, 1916: p. 522; Stewart, 1930: p. 52; Stephenson, 1941: p. 79; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 111-112; Richards, 1968: p. 78; Sohl and Koch, 1987: p. 141, 143, 146, 153, 156, 159; Kuehne, 1999: p. 70.

not *Leda protexta* (Conrad, 1869A = *Perrisonota*) Johnson, 1905: p. 8; Stephenson, 1941: p. 79

Nuculana stephensoni Richards, 1958: p. 66, pl. 11, f. 1-2; pl. 2, f. 2; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 5, pl. 2, f. 2; Richards, 1968: p. 86; Carey, 1976: p. 226, pl. 12, f. 2; Gallagher, 1984: p. 17, 27; Gallagher, 1986: p. 17; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Rindsberg, 1998; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Perrisonota stephensoni (Richards, 1958). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46.

Types – *Nuculana stephensoni* Richards, 1958, Holotype: ANSP 18728 (Kwb).

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 379; Richards (1958) p. 66.

Description - "Shell small, ensiform, extremely elongated posteriorly, and gradually narrowed from the beaks. Valves depressed convex with very small inconspicuous beaks, which are curved backward, and with an obsolete carination extending from them backward to the postero-basal angle. Anterior end broadest, sharply rounded; posterior end narrowly rounded, longest above the middle. Hinge-line arched upward in front of the beaks, and gently concave posteriorly throughout the entire length of the shell. Basal line moderately curved, more prominent just in advance of the beaks. Surface of the shell polished or marked by very fine concentric lines of growth, except on the posteriorcardinal slope, where they unite and form a few inconspicuous folds." (Whitfield.) The impression of the hinge-plate in internal casts shows the presence of 60 or more fine, straight teeth posterior to the beaks, and about 12 much larger and decidedly) -shaped teeth in front. The dimensions of a large internal cast are length 26 mm., height 8mm." – Richards (1958) p. 66.

FIGURE 58: *NUCULANA STEPHENSONI* RICHARDS, 1958 A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 11 FIG. 14 (*PERRISONOTA PROTEXTA*); B-C: WELLER (1907) PL. 30 FIG. 1, 2 (KRB); D: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 11 FIG. 15 – CLOSEUP OF HINGE

***Nuculana whitfieldi* (Gardner, 1916)**

Nuculana pinnaformis Whitfield, 1885: p. 108 pl. 11, f. 8 (not pl. 11., f. 7 = *Nuculana pinnaformis* (Whitfield, 1885); Whitfield, 1886: p. 108 pl. 11, f. 8 (not pl. 11, f.7 = *Nuculana pinnaformis* (Whitfield, 1885).

Leda pinnaformis (Whitfield, 1885). Weller, 1907: p. 373, in part (not pl. 29, f. 27 = *Leda pinnaformis* (Whitfield, 1885)).

Leda whitfieldi Gardner, 1916: p. 516, pl. 19, f. 10-12; Wade, 1926: p. 41.

Nuculana whitfieldi (Gardner, 1916). Richards, 1958: p. 66, pl. 18, f. 7-9; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 137, 139, 141, 143, 146, 150, 153, 156, 159, 162; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64, 65, 70, 71, 73, 79; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 110, t. 1, pl. 2, f. 12a, b; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61, 70; pl. 3.

Nuculana cf. whitfieldi (Gardner, 1916). Kuehne, 1995: p. 84.

Nuculana (Leda) whitfieldi (Gardner, 1916). Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57.

Types – *Leda whitfieldi* Gardner, 1916, Holotype Lost.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65.

Description.—“Shell small, convex, cuneate dorsally, arcuate ventrally, forming roughly a sector of 120°; posterior end more produced than the anterior and sharply rostrate; anterior end evenly rounded; umbones inflated, flattened upon their summits; incurved, proximate; external adult sculpture of twenty to thirty concentric rugae, strongest and most crowded toward the ventral margin, altogether absent upon the umbones and evanescent in the slightly depressed area directly in front of the rostrum; teeth fine but sharp, becoming increasingly finer and convergent beneath the umbones; both anterior and posterior series numbering from thirteen to seventeen; ligament pit trigonal, minute, subumbonal; muscle scars small, placed at the distal ends of the hinge; pallial line running close to the ventral margin; pallial sinus short, steeply ascending, squarely truncate. Dimensions. — Altitude 3.7 mm; latitude 6.5 mm.” – Gardner (1916) p. 516.

FIGURE 59: *NUCULANA WHITFIELDI* (GARDNER, 1916) A: NJSM 21949 (KWB); B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 11 FIG. 8 (KWB); C: GARDNER 1916 PL. 19 FIG. 10-11 (“MONMOUTH GROUP”)

ORDER NUCULIDA Dall, 1889

FAMILY NUCULIDAE GRAY, 1824

GENUS NUCULA LAMARCK, 1799

***Nucula percrassa* Conrad, 1858**

Nucula percrassa Conrad, 1858A: p. 327, pl. 35, f. 4; Gabb, 1859: p. 14; Gabb, 1861A: p. 205; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 8; Conrad, 1875B: p. A14; Gabb, 1876A: p. 318; Whitfield, 1885: p. 102, pl. 11, f. 4-6; Whitfield, 1886: p. 102, pl. 11, f. 4-6; Whitfield, 1899: p. 161; Johnson, 1905: p. 7; Weller, 1907: p. 369, pl. 29, f. 1-5; Kummel, 1908: p. 69; Miller, 1911: pl. 5, f. 9; Stephenson, 1914: t. 2-6; Wade, 1926: p. 39, pl. 8, f. 1-4; Roberts, 1931: p. 404, pl. 68, f. 1,2; Stephenson, 1955A: p. 106, pl. 15, f. 4-7; Richards, 1958: p. 59, pl. 10, f. 1-2; Richards, 1968: p. 74; Speden, 1970: p. 33, pl. 2, f. 4-11; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 45; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 139, 141, 143, 146, 150, 153, 156, 159; Wingard and Sohl, 1990: p. D12-D16, pl. 1, f. 1-10, pl. 2, f. 1-11, pl. 3, f. 1-10, pl. 4, f. 1-10, pl. 5, f. 3, 10, pl. 6, f. 1, 2, 4-16, pl. 7, f. 1, 2, 4-11; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65, 66; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 44, 62, 71, 73; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54, 57; Sessa, Larina, et. al., 2015: p. 15563, f. 1h; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 110, t. 1, pl. 2, f. 11a, b; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B. pl. 1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61,70, pl. 3.

Leda slackiana Gabb, 1860B: p. 397, pl. 69, f. 36; Gabb, 1861A: p. 189; Richards, 1968: p. 84.

Nuculana slackiana (Gabb, 1860B). Meek, 1864: p. 8; Conrad, 1868; p. 725; Clark, 1897: p. 330, Clark, 1898: p. 179; Weller, 1905: p. 333; Sohl and Mello, 1970; p. 46; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84.

Donax fordii Conrad, 1869F: p. 102, pl. 9, f. 25; Whitfield, 1885: p. 102, pl. 23, f. 1; Whitfield, 1886: p. 102, pl. 23, f. 1; Whitfield, 1899: p. 157; Johnson, 1905: p. 17; Richards, 1958: p. 60, pl. 10, f. 4; Richards, 1968: p. 51.

Nucula slackiana (Gabb, 1860B). Gabb, 1876A: p. 318; Whitfield, 1885: p. 103, pl. 11, f. 2-3; Whitfield, 1886: p.103, pl. 11, f. 2-3; Whitfield, 1899: p. 161; Johnson, 1905: p. 8; Gardner, 1916: p. 511, pl. 19, f. 1-4; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 98-100; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 40; Richards, 1958: p. 59, pl. 10, f. 3, 5, 6; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89, pl. 1, f. 17; Wingard and Sohl, 1990: p. D14, pl. 2, f. 1, 2, 3; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 61, 63, 64; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B. pl. 1.

Nucula aff. *Nucula percrassa* Conrad, 1858. Stephenson, 1907: p. 126-130, 143.

Nucula cibolensis Stephenson, 1941: p. 72, pl. 8, f. 10; Wingard and Sohl, 1990: p. D1; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 47, f. 20.

Nucula chatfieldensis Stephenson, 1941: p. 73, pl. 8, f. 11, 12; Wingard and Sohl, 1990: p. D2; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 47, f. 20.

Nucula tippahensis Haribson, 1945: p. 77, pl. 2, f. 10; Wingard and Sohl, 1990: pl. 1, f. 7-10, pl. 2, f. 7, 8, 10, 11.

Nucula cf. *slackiana* Gabb, 1876A. Kuehne, 1999: p. 73, 74.

Types – *Nucula percrassa* Conrad, 1858A, Holotype: ANSP 16710; *Leda slackiana* Gabb, 1860B, Holotype: ANSP 18796; *Donax fordii* Conrad, 1869F, Holotype: ANSP 19700; *Nucula cibolensis* Stephenson, 1941, Holotype: USNM 76291; *Nucula chatfieldensis* Stephenson, 1941, Holotype: USNM 76293; *Nucula tippahensis* Haribson, 1945, Holotype: USNM 103751.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64; ANSP 81027.

Description – “Shell moderately convex, attaining a large size for the genus, the largest observed being length 32mm, and height about two-thirds the length. Shell subelliptical in outline, the beaks situated at

about the anterior third of the shell, the greatest length of the shell at about the mid-height. Anterior margin obliquely subtruncate above, the anterior extremities of the shell usually regularly rounded, sometimes more or less obscurely obliquely subtruncate in front and sometimes somewhat straightened ventrally; posterior margin more or less sharply rounded; the postero-dorsal margin gently convex or nearly straight. Valves regularly convex, anterodorsal slope rather abrupt, passing into the rather large lunular depression. Surface of the shell marked by more or less irregular concentric lines of growth, and by fine, regular, radiating costae, narrower than the interspaces, which are more strongly developed on the anterior portion of the shell. The shell substance thick. Teeth strong, about 20 posterior and 8 or 10 anterior to the beak, both series diminishing in size as they approach the beak. Well preserved internal casts preserve strongly defined muscular impressions and pallial line and are strongly crenate about the free margin.” - Weller (1907) p. 370.

3 cm

**FIGURE 60: *NUCULA PERCRASSA* CONRAD, 1858
A: ANSP 81027 (Kw)**

***Nucula whitfieldi* Weller, 1907**

Nucula whitfieldi Weller, 1907: p. 371, pl. 29, f. 6-12; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 100-101; Richards, 1958: p. 61, pl. 17, f. 1-2; Sohl and Mello, 1970; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 7.

Types – *Nucula whitfieldi* Weller, 1907; Cotypes: NJSM 7685, 7732.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 371, pl. 29, f. 6-9; Richards (1958) p. 61, pl. 17, f. 2.

Description – “Shell triangularly subovate in outline, with moderately convex valves ; the beaks pointed, situated from one fifth to one-fourth the length of the shell from the anterior extremity; postero-dorsal margin moderately convex from the beak to the somewhat sharply rounded posterior extremity of the shell which is below the midheight; ventral margin convex throughout, curving upward more rapidly in front than behind anterior margin rounded; antero-dorsal margin sloping somewhat abruptly from the beak. Hinge-line with 20 to 25 teeth posterior to the beak and 10 or 12 in front, with a few small ones directly beneath the beak. Surface of the shell marked by somewhat regular concentric lines. Surface of the casts usually smooth and without marginal crenulations. The dimensions of a rather large individual from the Wenonah sand are length, 21 mm; height, 15.5 mm.: - Weller (1907) p. 370.

FIGURE 61: *NUCULA WHITFIELDI* WELLER, 1907 A-B: WELLER (1907) PL. 29 FIG. 7-8 (Kw); C: NJSM 21652 (Kns); D: NJSM 21145 (Kmv); E: NJSM 7685 (Kw)

ORDER **OSTREIDA** Ferussac, 1822

FAMILY **BAKEVELLIDAE** KING, 1850

GENUS **GERVILLIOPSIS** WHITFIELD, 1885

***Gervillioopsis ensiformis* (Conrad, 1858)**

Gervillia ensiformis Conrad, 1858A: p. 328, pl. 34, f. 10; Gabb, 1859: p. 12; Gabb, 1861A: p. 180; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 9; Conrad, 1868: p. 726; Conrad, 1875B: p. A15; Frech, 1902; p. 615; Stephenson, 1907: p. 136, 143; Richards, 1956: p. 73; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Rindsberg, 1998; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitely, 2016: p. 111, t. 1.

Gervillioopsis ensiformis (Conrad, 1858A). Whitfield, 1885: p. 73, pl. 15, f. 8-11; pl. 16, f. 5; Whitfield, 1886: p. 73, pl. 15, f. 8-11; pl. 16, f. 5; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 158; Johnson, 1905: p. 10; Weller, 1907: p. 421, pl. 37, f. 4-5, pl. 38, f. 1-3; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2; Wade, 1926: p. 51, pl. 13, f. 1-3; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 118-119; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 42, pl. 3, f.3; Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957: p. 11; Richards, 1958: p. 94, pl. 15, f. 4, pl. 17, f. 8; Carey, 1976: p. 214, pl. 6, f. 3; Gallagher, 1984: p. 11, 16, 17, 27; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 17; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 61, 70, 71; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 93, 94, f. 65-66; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B pl.1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61, 62.

Dalliconcha ensiformis (Conrad, 1858A). White, 1887: p. 35, pl. 2, f. 6.

Gervillia (Gervillioopsis) ensiformis (Conrad, 1858A). Brister and Young, 2007, p. 54,57.

Types – *Gervillia ensiformis* Conrad, 1858; Holotype?

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 421; Richards (1958) p. 94; Kuehne (1999) p. 64; NJSM 7685.

Description - "Shell of moderately large size and thickened, falciform, very oblique; the body of the shell finally becoming parallel to the hinge or even slightly recurved, narrowing posteriorly and flattened on the surface. Hinge-line straight, short, not more than one-fourth the length of the shell in grown individuals; posterior wing only moderately elevated, and the posterior margin rapidly sloping backward from its extremity to the body of the shell, anterior wing very slight, the anterior end of the shell being

squarely truncate at right angles to the hinge. Beak of the shell small and terminal, elevated above the wing and continuing in a ridge to the surface of the valve. Greatest width of the shell opposite the posterior extremity of the hinge. Surface of the shell lamellose, and marked by numerous concentric varices of growth, and on the basal portion of the right valve indications of fine radiating lines occur. Hinge area moderately wide, marked by several transverse ligamental pits, arranged at a little more than one-fourth of an inch apart, and also by numerous oblique corrugations. Muscular imprints large and obliquely situated. Substance of the shell highly nacreous throughout and iridescent." – Whitfield (1886) p. 73.

"The dimensions of a large, nearly perfect individual illustrated by Whitfield, are extreme length, 190 mm.; length of hinge line 48 mm.; height at posterior extremity of hinge-line, 44 mm.; greatest width of body of shell, 35 mm." – Weller (1907) p. 421.

FIGURE 62: *GERVILLIOPSIS ENSIFORMIS* (CONRAD, 1858) A: NJSM 21937 (KWB); B: ANSP 80698 (KWB); C: WELLER (1907) PL. 38 FIG. 1 (KMT)

FAMILY GRYPHAEIDAE VIALOV, 1936

GENUS *EXOgyra* SAY, 1820

Exogyra ponderosa erraticostata Stephenson, 1914

Exogyra ponderosa erraticostata Stephenson, 1914. Stephenson, 1907: p. 130; Stephenson, 1914: p. 49-50, pl. 15, f. 4, pl. 16, f. 1,2; Stephenson, 1923: p. 171, pl. 47, f. 1; Stephenson, 1936D: p. 375, pl. 1, f. 10; Richards, 1958: p. 116, pl. 20, f. 2; Young, 1963: p. 129, pl. 78, f. 1,8, pl. 79, f. 4; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 42; Carey, 1976: p. 216, pl. 7, f. 2; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8; Bernstein, 1986: p. 4-12;

Kuehne, 1993: p. 60; Elder, 1996: p. 257, f. 5.2, 5.5, 5.11; Rindsberg, 1998; Dietl, Alexander and Bien, 2000: p. 221; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 178, f. 148; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 44, 54, App B pl. 1.

Types – *Exogyra ponderosa erraticostata* Stephenson, 1914; Holotype USNM 31225.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2470d; MAPS A2470e.

Description – "In all its characters except the surface ornamentation of the left or lower valve is essentially like the typical *Exogyra ponderosa* Romer. The surface of the left valve is characterized by the presence of fairly well defined, sharp to rounded, ridged, radiating costae or plications which differ from the costa on *Exogyra costata* Say in the generally weaker development and in their striking irregularity as regards size, shape, and distribution. In proximity to the beak the shell is usually ornamented with small, regularly arranged costae extending backwards over the shell one-half to three-fourths of an inch and merging into the irregular costae just described, which characterize the variety. The irregular costae extend backward 3 to 5 inches from the beak, becoming weaker in the direction of the margin; in the larger individuals there is usually a considerable part of the surface bordering the margin on which the costae are either very faint or are entirely absent." – Stephenson (1914) p. 49.

FIGURE 63: *EXOgyra PONDEROSA ERRATICOSTATA* STEPHENSON 1914 A-B: MAPS A2470E (INTERNAL MOLD) (KW); C: MAPS A2470E (IMPRESSION) (KW); D: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 20 FIG. 12 (KWB)

Exogyra sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2560b

FIGURE 64: *EXOGYRA* SP. A-B: MAPS A2560B (KW)
(INTERNAL CASTS)

FAMILY FLEMINGOSTREIDAE STENZEL, 1971

GENUS *AGEROSTREA* VIALOV, 1936*Agerostrea falcata* (Morton, 1827)

Ostrea falcata Morton, 1827: p. 50, pl. 1, f.2; Morton, 1828A: p. 92; Morton, 1830A: p. 284, pl. 3, f. 19-20; Morton, 1830C: p. 203, pl. 1, f. 2; Morton, 1832A: p. 293; Morton, 1834 p. 50 pl. 3, f.5, pl. 9, f. 6,7; Lyell, 1845B: vol. 1; Owen, 1860: pl. 7, f. 5; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Weller, 1907: p. 444, pl. 43, f. 3-6; Miller, 1911: p. 95, pl. 5, f. 6; Stephenson, 1923: p. 154, pl. 39, f. 1-10; Stephenson, 1941: p. 111, pl. 14, f. 7-8; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 151-153; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 42, pl. 3, f. 13; Dorf and Fox: 1957, p. 6; Richards, 1958: p. 108-109, pl. 19, f. 2; Minard, Owen and Todd, 1861: p. C66; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 34; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, t. 5; Carey, 1976: p. 214, pl. 6, f. 13; Gallagher, 1984: p. 19.

Non *Ostrea larva* Lamarck, 1819. Gabb, 1859: p. 15; Gabb, 1861A; p. 209; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Cook, 1868: p. 375, text fig.; Credner, 1870: p. 226; Gabb, 1876A: p. 320; Whitfield, 1885: p. 34, pl. 3, f. 5-6 (not pl. 7 = *Ostrea mesenterica* Gabb, 1861); Whitfield, 1886: p. 34, pl. 3, f. 5-6 (not pl. 7 = *Ostrea mesenterica* Gabb, 1861); Hill, 1887: p. 6; Clark, 1897: p. 179; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Hill and Vaughn, 1898: p. 44, f. 2c - not f. 2a,2b; Whitfield, 1899; p. 162; Harris, 1900: p. 293, pl. 49, f. 3; Hill, 1901; p. 335, 338, 355, pl. 48, f. 5, 6a; Johnson, 1905: p. 11; Stephenson, 1907: p. 148,

149, 153, 156; Wade, 1926: p. 250, pl. 92, f. 4; Dane, 1929: p. 138, pl. 25, f. 3,4.

Ostrea unguate Coquand, 1869: p. 58, pl. 31, f. 11,12 according to Stephenson, 1941: p. 111.

Ostrea (Alectryonia) larva Gabb, 1859. White, 1884: p. 296, pl. 42, f. 8.

Ostrea larva var. falcata Gardner, 1916: p. 552, pl. 22, f. 4

Ostrea cf. larva Gab, 1859. Hill, 1889: p. 6.

Arctostrea falcata (Morton, 1827). Bobkova, 1961.

Agerostrea falcata (Morton, 1827). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 7; Gallagher, 1984: p. 18-20; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 153, 156; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 62, 64-66, 68, 70; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 213, f. 184; Aberhan, 2010; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: p. 67, f. 7.

Lopha falcata (Morton, 1827). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46, t. 8, p. 42, t. 7, p. 40, t. 6; Minard, 1974A: p. 24, tb. 4.

Agerostrea cf. falcata (Morton, 1827). Kuehne, 1999: p. 68.

Agerostrea (Ostrea) falcata (Morton, 1827). Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54, 57.

Types – *Ostrea falcata* Morton, 1827; Holotype: ANSP 16710.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65; MAPS A2468f; KS2236; KS2241; KS2242.

Description – “Shell of medium size, laterally arcuate. The dimensions of an average specimen are length along the arcuate median line from beak to posterior extremity, 47 mm.; distance between beak and posterior extremity, 28 mm.; width of shell at middle, 16 mm.; length of hinge-line, 20 mm. Shell usually more or less strongly auriculate, the ears subequal or with one ear somewhat larger than the other. Hinge-line straight. Shell marked with from seven to ten deep plications which originate along the lower or convex margin and extend nearly to the beak, not leaving a conspicuous non-plicate central area, the plications towards the anterior hinge extremity decreasing regularly in size; along the upper or concave margin the shell is marked by a series of

short, marginal plications. Lower valve moderately convex, with a small scar of attachment; upper valve much flatter, its plications similar to those of the lower valve." – Weller (1907) p. 445.

FIGURE 65: *AGEROSTREA FALCATA* (MORTON, 1830) A-B: MAPS A2468F (Kw); C: NJSM 22586 (KML); D: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 3 FIG. 6; E-G: WELLER (1907) PL. 43 FIG. 3-5 (KMT)

GENUS FLEMINGOSTREA VREDENBURG, 1916

***Flemingostrea subspatulata* (Forbes, 1845)**

Ostrea subspatulata Forbes, 1845: p. 61-61, text f. pp. 61, 62; Conrad, 1857: p. 155, pl. 10, f. 3a, 3b; Gabb, 1861A: p. 210; Meek, 1864: p. 6; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Coquand, 1869: p. 43, pl. 32, f. 1-3; Gabb, 1876A: p. 320; White, 1884: p. 301, pl. 37, f. 1, 2; Whitfield, 1885: p. 32, pl. 3, f. 14; Whitfield, 1886: p. 32, pl. 3, f. 14; Cragin, 1893: p. 208; Whitfield, 1899: p. 162; Veatch, 1906: pl. 11, f. 3, 3a; Stephenson, 1907: p. 130, 137, 148-150, 154-156; Weller, 1907: p. 440, pl. 42, f. 15; Gardner, 1916: p. 561, pl. 23, f. 3, pl. 24, f. 1; Stephenson, 1923: p. 158, pl. 40, f. 1,2, pl. 41, f. 1-5; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 164-165; Ramsdell, 1958: p. 106, pl. 16, f. 10; Black, 1980: p. 73; Gallagher, 1986: p. 30.

Ostrea owenana Shumard, 1861: p. 200; Meek, 1864: p. 6; White, 1884: p. 298; Deussen, 1924: p. 33, pl. 11, f. 3,3a; Adkins, 1928: p. 35, 101; Stephenson, 1923: p. 159; Deussen, 1924: p. 33, pl. 11, f. 3,3a; Adkins, 1928: p. 35, 101; Dane, 1929: p. 133, 136,

pl. 24, f. 1,2; Stephenson, 1941: p. 103: pl. 15, f. 1,2 pl. 16, f. 1-3.

Ostrea glabra Meek & Hayden, 1860. Bose, 1906: p. 41-42, pl. 2, f. 5; Bose, 1913: p. 43-45, pl. 23, f. 3, pl. 24, f. 1.

Ostrea sigmoidea Imlay, 1937: p. 1824, pl. 8, f. 6, 9, pl. 9, f. 2-6, pl. 10, f. 2-4.

Flemingostrea sp. Myers, 1968: p. 59, pl. 11, f. 7.

Flemingostrea subspatulata (Forbes, 1845). Wollenben, 1977: p. 384, pl. 2, f. 3, 6, 9, 12; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64, 77; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 202, 204, f. 173, 175.

Types – Holotype Lost? *Ostrea subspatulata* Forbes, 1845; South Washington, N.C.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 440 pl. 42, f. 15; Richards (1958) p. 106 pl. 16, f. 10 (NJSM 7688); Kuehne (1999) p. 64; MAPS A2409a; MAPS A2409b; MAPS A2409c.

Description – “Shell subovate in outline, higher than wide, usually widest below the middle, the dimensions of a nearly complete cast of the interior of a lower valve are length, 45 mm.; width, 31 mm. Lower valve strongly arcuate longitudinally, the cast nearly smooth or with a few obscure concentric undulations, the muscular impression large, situated in the lower left-hand quarter of the cast. The impressions of the exterior of the shell show rather strong concentric undulations.” – Weller (1907) p. 441.

Figure 66: *Flemingostrea subspatulata* (Forbes, 1845) A: Whitfield (1886) pl. 3 fig. 14; B: Weller (1907) pl. 42 fig. 15 (Kw); C, E: MAPS A2409a (Kw); D, F, G: MAPS A2409b (Kw) h: MAPS A2409c (Kw)

FAMILY OSTREIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS CUBITOSTREA SACCO, 1897

Cubitostrea tecticosta (Gabb, 1860)

Ostrea tecticosta Gabb, 1860A: p. 403, pl. 68, f. 47-48; Gabb, 1861A: p. 210; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 6; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Coquand, 1869: p. 50, pl. 17, f. 10, 11; White, 1884: p. 301, pl. 1, f. 3, 4; Whitfield, 1885: p. 33, 34, pl. 3, f. 1, 2; Whitfield, 1886: p. 33, 34, pl. 3, f. 1, 2; Clark, 1897: p. 335; Clark, 1898: p. 185; Whitfield, 1899: p. 162; Johnson, 1905: p. 10; Stephenson, 1907: p. 128, 136, 150, 153 - 155, 157; Weller, 1907: p. 443, pl. 43, f. 17-19; Gardner, 1916: p. 560, pl. 24, f. 2-4; Stephenson, 1923: p. 143, pl. 38, f. 1-9; Stephenson, 1926: p. 250, pl. 92, f. 5; Wade, 1926: p. 54, pl. 14, f. 4-5; Adkins, 1928: p. 102; Dane, 1929, 93, 133; Stephenson, 1941: p. 107, pl. 14, f. 5-6; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 165-167; Ramsdell, 1958: p. 107, pl. 16, f. 13, 14; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40;

Feldman, 1977: p. 90; Black, 1980: p. 73; Gallagher, 1985: p. 29; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 198, 199, f. 169, 170; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57; Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B. pl. 1.

Ostrea pusilla Gabb, 1876A: p. 321.

Cubitostrea cf. tecticosta (Gabb, 1860A). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 7, t. 2.

Cubitostrea tecticosta (Gabb, 1860A). Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 139, 141, 143, 146, 150, 153, 156, 159; Sohl and Kollman, 1985: p. 162; Rindsberg, 1988; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 62, 64, 70, 71, 76; Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B.

Ambigostrea tecticosta (Gabb, 1860A). Malchus, 1990; Kosnick, 2002.

Types – *Ostrea tecticosta* Gabb, 1860; Cotypes – ANSP 18761, 18808 (Tennessee)

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 443 pl. 43, f. 17-19; Richards (1958) p. 107.

Description - "Shell small, elongate, oval, ovate or irregularly elliptical in outline, slightly curved, with a small, strongly-twisted beak and moderately sized ligamental area on the lower valve. The lower valve usually shows a large, cicatrized area of attachment and is strongly plicated, the plica being usually sharply rounded and very rugose from concentric lamellose lining. The inner margins of the valves are also crenulated on the upper half or two-thirds of their length, and more minutely so on the inner border at the junction of the valves just below the ligamental area. Muscular scar large, but only moderately marked. Upper valves slightly convex and destitute of plications except near the border." - Whitfield (1886) p. 33.

FIGURE 67: CUBITOSTREA TECTICOSTATA (GABB, 1860): A: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 16, F. 13-14 (ANSP 18761) (THT) B-D: WELLER (1907) PL. 43 F. 17-19 (KW)

GENUS STRIOSTREA VIALOV, 1936

***Striostrea plumosa* (Morton, 1833)**

Ostrea plumosa Morton, 1833: p. 293; Morton, 1834: p. 51, pl. 3, f. 9; Gabb, 1861A: p. 153; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 6; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Coquand, 1869: p. 61, pl. 32, f. 9; Gabb, 1876A: p. 320; White, 1884: p. 299, pl. 37, f. 5, 6; Whitfield, 1885: p. 31,32, pl. 3, f. 12, 13; Whitfield, 1886: p. 31,32, pl. 3, f. 12, 13; Cragin, 1893: p. 206, pl. 35, f. 3; Harris, 1900: p. 293, pl. 49, f. 4; Johnson, 1905: p. 10; Stephenson, 1907: p. 128, 130, 137, 149, 154, 156-158; Weller, 1907: p. 439, pl. 42, f. 16-18; Gardner, 1916: p. 556-557; Stephenson, 1923: p. 147, pl. 38, f. 14-17, pl. 39, f. 11-15; Wade, 1926: p. 53, pl. 14, f. 1-3, 7; Dane, 1929: p. 56, pl. 27, f. 4-6; Stephenson, 1941: p. 108, pl. 16, f. 4-6; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 161-163; Richards, 1958: p. 111, pl. 17, f. 9, 10, pl. 19, f. 4; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46; Cobban, Landis and Dane, 1974: p. 281; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 139, 153, 155; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 62, 66, 72; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Ostrea denticulifera Conrad, 1858A: p. 330, pl. 34, f. 1, 8; Gabb, 1860B: p. 398; Gabb, 1861A: p. 152; Meek, 1864: p. 6; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Safford, 1869: p. 419; Coquand, 1869: p. 50; White, 1884: p. 295; Whitfield, 1885: p. 29, pl. 3, f. 8, 9; Whitfield, 1886: p. 29, pl. 3, f. 8, 9; Johnson, 1905: p. 10;

Weller, 1907: p. 436, pl. 43, f. 1, 2; Richards, 1958: p. 111, pl. 18, f. 3, pl. 19, f.5-6.

Non *Ostrea crenulimarginata* Gabb, 1860. Whitfield, 1885: p. 30, pl. 3, f. 10-11; Whitfield, 1886: p. 30, pl. 3, f. 10-11; Clark, 1897: p. 335; Clark, 1898: p. 185; Weller, 1907: p. 441, pl. 42, f. 12, 13.

Non *Anomia argentaria* Morton, 1833. Whitfield, 1885: p. 42 pl. 4, f. 9 (not pl. 4., f. 10-11 = *A. argentaria* Morton, 1833); Whitfield, 1886: p. 42 pl. 4, f. 9 (not pl. 4, f. 10-11 = *A. argentaria* Morton, 1833).

Striostrea plumosa (Morton, 1833). Rindsberg, 1998.

Ostrea cf. plumosa Morton, 1833. Kuehne, 1999: p. 75.

Types – Holotype: *Ostrea plumosa* Morton, 1833; ANSP 18807.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 439 pl. 42, f.18; Richards (1958) p. 111.

Description - "Shell small, ovate, ovate-triangular or elongate-spatulate, thin and, somewhat fragile irregularly convex on the upper valve, often subangulate longitudinally, either along one side or the other, beak of the upper valve thin, sharp and pointed; the ligamental area small and inconspicuous in most cases, though sometimes of moderate size. Exterior of the upper valve marked by obscure plications in all the type specimens, which cross the valve obliquely in either direction from right to left or oppositely; also, by fine radiating striae which obscurely diverge from a more or less median line and pass toward the margin on either side. On the interior the margin of the valve near the apex is more or less crenulate. The muscular scar is small and lateral. Lower valve not yet observed." - Whitfield (1886) p. 31.

"The dimensions of a rather small individual are length, 32 mm.; width, 16.3 mm." – Weller (1907) p. 439.

FIGURE 68: *STRIOSTREA PLUMOSA* (MORTON, 1833) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 3 FIG. 8-9 (KWB); B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 3 FIG. 10-11 (KNS); C: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 3 F. 13; D: WELLER (1907) PL. 42 FIG. 12-13 (KNS); E: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 19 FIG. 5-6 (ANSP 18760) (KWB)

FAMILY PTERIIDAE GRAY, 1847

GENUS PTERIA SCOPOLI, 1777

Pteria petrosa (Conrad, 1853)

Avicula petrosa Conrad, 1853A: p. 274, pl. 24, f. 15; Gabb, 1859: p. 10; Gabb, 1861A: p. 158.

Avicula linguaeformis Evans and Shumard, 1854: p. 163; Gabb, 1859: p. 10; Meek, 1859: p. 183, pl. 1, f. 7; Gabb, 1861A: p. 102.

Pteria petrosa (Conrad, 1853A). Meek, 1864: p. 9; Whitfield, 1885: p. 68, pl. 14, f. 10; Whitfield, 1885B: p. 31; Whitfield, 1886: p. 68, pl. 14, f. 10; Whitfield, 1899: p. 163; Weller, 1905: p. 333; Stephenson, 1907: p. 10, 140, 428, pl. 42, f. 1-2; Kummel, 1908: p. 69; Miller, 1911: p. 96; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2; Gardner, 1916: p. 548, pl. 21, f. 10; Stephenson, 1923: p. 131, pl. 27, f. 5-6; Wade, 1926: p. 51, pl 13, f. 7; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 135-136; Richards, 1958: p. 100, pl. 16, f. 2; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 57; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 110, t. 1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Pteria linguiformis (Evans and Shumard, 1854). Meek, 1864: p. 9; Meek, 1876: p. 32, pl. 16, f. 1a-1d; White, 1879: p. 180, 197, 205; Whitfield, 1880: p. 384, pl. 7, f. 2-3.

Pteria cf. petrosa (Conrad, 1853A). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36.

Types – Holotype Lost: *Avicula petrosa* Conrad, 1853.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 429; Richards (1958) p. 100.

Description – “Shell oblique, winged in front and behind, the hinge-line straight with the beaks in front of the middle. Both valves rather strongly convex, but the left a little more so than the right. Posterior wing compressed, of moderate length, pointed behind, its posterior margin concave; anterior wing narrower, pointed in front, less compressed than the other, its free margin nearly straight or slightly concave; in the right valve it is separated from the body of the shell by a narrow and shallow sulcus which extends from the anterior side of the beak downward and usually a little obliquely backward to the antero-ventral margin; just in front of the marginal extremity of this sulcus the surface is slightly bulged so as to leave a byssal opening between the valves. The antero-ventral margin slopes obliquely backward from the anterior extremity of the hinge-line; it is slightly concave to the base of the anterior wing beyond which point it becomes slightly convex, curving more and more below into the rounded postero-basal margin; the posterior margin oblique below and sinuate above. Surface of the shell marked only by concentric lines of growth which are inconspicuous on the internal casts. The dimensions of a large specimen are length from the anterior extremity of the hinge-line to the postero-basal margin, 51 mm.; length of hinge-line, 37 mm.; distance of beak from the anterior extremity of hinge-line, 12 mm.; convexity of right valve, 10 mm.” – Weller (1907) p. 430.

FIGURE 69: *PTERIA PETROSA* (CONRAD, 1853) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 14 F. 10 (KMG); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 42 FIG. 1 (KW); C: WELLER (1907) PL. 42 FIG. 2 (KMG); D: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 16 FIG. 2 (NJSM 7786) (KMG); E: NJSM 23012 (Kmv)

Pteria sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64; MAPS A2519b; MAPS A2519c

FIGURE 70: *PTERIA* SP. A-B: MAPS A2519c (KW)

ORDER **PANDORIDA** Stewart, 1930
 FAMILY **LATERNULIDAE** HEDLEY, 1918
 GENUS **ANATIMYA** CONRAD, 1860
Anatimya anteradiata CONRAD, 1860

Anatimya anteradiata Conrad, 1860: p. 276, pl. 46, f. 3; Meek, 1864: p. 14; Weller, 1907: p. 519, pl. 57, f. 12; Dane, 1929: p. 109, pl. 20, f. 5; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 238-239; Richards, 1958: p. 162, pl. 27, f 3,5; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 142; Gallagher, 1986: p. 30; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 67, 77; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 7; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B pl. 1.

Pholadomya anteradiata (Conrad, 1860). Gabb, 1861A: p. 220.

Anatimya aff. *Anatimya anteradiata* Conrad, 1860. Dane, 1929: p. 109, pl. 20, f. 5.

Types – Holotype: *Anatimya anteradiata* Conrad, 1860; ANSP 20835.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 519 pl. 57, f.12; Richards (1958) p. 162 pl. 27, f. 3, 5 (NJSM 7667); Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2450b.

Description – “The dimensions of a right valve are length, 56 mm.; height, 31 mm. Shell subelliptical in outline, the beaks small, subcentral in position, scarcely elevated above the hinge line, pointing posteriorly, fissured. Antero-cardinal margin straight and horizontal in front of the beak, curving downward anteriorly; anterior margin broadly rounding from the cardinal to the basal margins; basal margin curving upward in front and behind, nearly straight in the middle, subparallel with the dorsal margin; posterior margin most produced near the cardinal line, curving broadly to the basal margin and more sharply to the cardinal extremity; post-cardinal margin concave just behind the beaks, becoming nearly straight posteriorly. Valves depressed convex, a little gaping behind. Surface of the shell in front of the beaks, marked by rather strong, more or less irregular concentric undulations, and by fine, more or less irregular lines of growth; posterior half of the shell marked by more or less inconspicuous concentric markings, and by about 10 or 12 narrow, angular, radiating costae, the most anterior of which extends nearly vertically downward from the beak to the

ventral margin, being slightly bowed forward; back of this is a rather broad smooth space beyond which the costae reappear, the intervals between them gradually becoming wider posteriorly, the most posterior one reaching the posterior margin of the shell near the middle, leaving a smooth area for some distance below the cardinal border." – Weller (1907) p. 530.

FIGURE 71: *ANATIMYA ANTERADIATA* CONRAD, 1860 A: WELLER (1907) PL. 57 FIG. 12 (Kw); B-C: MAPS A2450B (Kw)

***Anatimya lata* (Whitfield, 1885)**

Pholas? lata Whitfield, 1885: p. 189: pl. 25, f. 17; Whitfield, 1886: p. 189: pl. 25, f. 17; Whitfield, 1899: p. 164.

Anatimya lata (Whitfield, 1885). Weller, 1907: p. 521, pl. 57, f. 13; Wade, 1926: p. 74; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 239-240; Richard, 1958; p. 163, pl. 27, f. 4; Gallagher, 1986; p. 30; Kuehne, 1999; p. 69, 79; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59.

Types – Holotype: *Pholas lata* Whitfield, 1885; NJSM 7670.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 521 pl. 57, f. 13; Richards (1958) p. 163 pl. 27, f. 4 (NJSM 7670); Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2404a; MAPS A2404d; MAPS A2404e.

Description - "Shell large and proportionally very broad between dorsal and basal margins, the relative height and length being about as two to three, respectively. The general outline is slightly ovate, widest at the anterior end and gradually narrowing

posteriorly, the beak being a little in advance of the middle and showing somewhat above the cardinal line in the slightly compressed and somewhat crushed specimen of an internal cast of a left valve, the only one yet seen. Anterior and posterior ends rounded, the latter one most narrowly so; basal line slightly emarginate just behind the middle of its length; cardinal line apparently arcuate throughout. Surface of the shell, as shown on the cast, convex, with a broad sulcus passing across the valve from beak to base, reaching the latter behind the middle. Anterior to the sulcus the surface is radiately ribbed, the rays being somewhat alternate in size over a portion of the space. At the bottom of the broad sulcus there is a single larger and stronger rib, which passes from the beak directly to the base of the shell, which it reaches at the point of greatest emargination. Posterior to this larger rib the surface is destitute of radiating lines, the surface being marked only with broad, irregular, concentric sulci, which extend over the entire surface parallel to the margin of the shell." – Whitfield (1886) p. 189.

FIGURE 72: *ANATIMYA LATA* (WHITFIELD, 1885) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 57 FIG. 13 (Kw); C, F: MAPS A2404D (Kw); B, D: MAPS A2404E; E: MAPS A2404A (Kw)

GENUS *Laternula* RODING, 1798*Laternula jerseyensis* (Weller, 1907)

Anatina jerseyensis Weller, 1907: p. 516, pl. 57, f. 1-4; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 243-245; Richards, 1959: p. 159, pl. 25, f. 13-14; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61, 62, 68, pl. 2.

Anatina Lamarck, 1818 is an invalid junior homonym of *Laternula* Roding, 1798.

Types – Cotypes: *Anatina jerseyensis* Weller, 1907; NJSM 7740, 9737.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 516; pl 57, f. 3 (NJSM 9737); Richards (1958) p. 159 pl. 25, f. 13 (NJSM 9737).

Description – “The dimensions of a nearly complete internal cast are length, 44 mm.; height, 29 mm.; thickness, 11 mm. Shell subovate in outline, a little gaping posteriorly, much broader in front than behind; beaks transversely fissured, situated back of the middle, pointing posteriorly. Antero-cardinal margin straight and nearly horizontal in front of the beak, curving gradually downward in front; anterior margin broadly rounded from the cardinal to the basal margins; basal margin nearly straight in the middle, curving upward at each end; posterior margin with its greatest extension above the middle of its height, curving into the basal margin below and the cardinal margin above; post-cardinal margin strongly concave. Valves depressed convex, most prominent in the umbonal region, abruptly compressed towards the postero-cardinal extremity, the anterior and ventral slopes gently convex. Shell marked by more or less irregular concentric lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 516.

FIGURE 73: *Laternula jerseyensis* (WELLER, 1907) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 57 FIG. 1-2 (NJSM 7740) (Kmv); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 57 FIG. 3 (Kw); C: NJSM 21912 (Kwb); D: ANSP 8070 (Kwb); E-F: NJSM 9737 (Kw)

Laternula robusta Stephenson, 1941

Laternula? robusta Stephenson, 1941: p. 160, pl. 25, f. 7-9.

Laternula robusta Stephenson, 1941. Sohl and Koch, 1987: p. 157; Kuehne, 1999: p. 69; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 381, 382, f. 363, 364.

Types – Holotype: *Laternula robusta* Stephenson, 1941; USNM 76505.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2435c.

Description – “Shell of medium size, depressed convex, inequivalve, subequilateral; anteriorly the two valves appear to be slightly gaping, and posteriorly they are markedly separated; posteriorly the shell is slightly bent to the right. Beaks low, broad, slightly prominent, incurved, opisthogyrate, the beak of the right valve rising above, and slightly overtopping that of the left valve; the beaks appear to be situated slightly in advance of the midlength and are fissured obliquely backward. A rather sharp radial sulcus back of the fissure, fades out about halfway between the beak and the posterior extremity; the posterodorsal slope is broadly excavated on each valve. Hing and internal features not uncovered. Anterodorsal margin broadly arched; anterior margin rather sharply and evenly rounded; ventral margin very broadly rounded; posterior margin imperfect, but appears to be sharply rounded below, becoming

subtruncated above. The surface, as impressed on the internal mold, is ornamented with numerous small, somewhat irregularly developed, close spaced concentric ridges. Dimensions of the holotype: length 52+ mm., height 36mm., thickness 6.5mm.” – Stephenson (1941) p. 160.

FIGURE 74: *LATERNULA ROBUSTA* STEPHENSON, 1941 A:
MAPS A2345c (Kw)

ORDER PECTINIDA Gray, 1854

FAMILY ANOMIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS ANOMIA LINNAEUS, 1758

Anomia argentaria Morton, 1833

Anomia argentaria Morton, 1833: p. 293, pl. 5, f. 10; Morton, 1834: p. 61, pl. 5, f. 10; Gabb, 1859: p. 10; Gabb, 1861A: p. 150; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 6; Conrad, 1868: p. 724; Conrad, 1875B: p. 13; Gabb, 1876A: p. 319; Whitfield, 1885: p. 42, pl. 4, f. 10-11 (not pl. 4, f. 9 = *Striostrea plumosa* (Morton, 1833); Whitfield, 1886: p. 42, pl. 4, f. 10-11 (not pl. 4, f. 9 = *Striostrea plumosa* (Morton, 1833); Clark, 1897: p. 335; Clark, 1898: p. 185; Johnson, 1905: p. 12; Weller, 1907: p. 496, pl. 54, f. 11-14 (not pl. 54, f. 15 = *Anomia tellinoides* Morton, 1833); Stephenson, 1907: p. 127, 128, 130, 138, 148-150, 154-157, 160; Gardner, 1916: p. 608, pl. 35, f. 1,2; Stephenson, 1923: p. 226, pl. 60, f. 10-14; Adkins, 1928: p. 134; Dane, 1929: p. 73, 93, 150, pl. 27, f. 7, 8; Stephenson, 1934: p. 273; Stephenson, 1941: p. 148, pl. 24, f. 1-4; Richards, 1943: p. 24, pl. 5, f. 12; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 179-182; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 45; Richards, 1956: p. 71; Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957: p. 45; Richards, 1958: p. 147, pl. 22, f.14-15; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 6; Richards, 1968: p. 33; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40, 42, 46; Cobban, Landis and

Dane, 1974: p. 281; Black, 1980: p. 73; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 7; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 139, 141, 143, 146, 150, 153, 156, 159; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 88; Gallagher, 1984: p. 13, 14; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64, 69; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60-63, 70, 71, 73, 76, 79; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 159, f. 129; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54,58; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B, pl. 1.

Anomia selleformis Conrad, 1858A: p. 330, pl. 34, f. 6.

Non *Diploschiza cretacea* Conrad, 1866D. Whitfield, 1885: p. 43, pl. 4, f. 4-5, (not pl. 4, f. 6-9 = *D. cretacea* Conrad, 1866D); Whitfield, 1886: p. 43, pl. 4, f. 4-5, (not pl. 4, f. 6-9 = *D. cretacea* Conrad, 1866D); Whitfield, 1899: p. 157; Weller, 1907: p. 497.

Anomia? argentaria Morton, 1833. Bose, 1906: p. 38, pl. 1, f. 8.

Non *Anomia? subtruncata* D’Orbigny, 1850. Bose, 1913: p. 41, pl. 5, f. 1.

Non *Anomia tellinoides* Morton, 1833. Wade, 1926: p. 69, pl. 3, f. 3-4.

Anomia cf. argentaria Morton, 1833. Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 42; Feldman, 1977: p. 90.

Types – Holotype: *Anomia argentaria* Morton, 1833; ANSP 19888.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 496; Richards (1958) p. 147; MAPS A2446e.

Description – “Shell subcircular, more or less irregular in outline, the larger individuals attaining a diameter of 25 mm. or more. Upper valve depressed convex, with the apex marginal, or nearly marginal, the surface marked by more or less irregular, sometimes sublamellose, lines of growth, and sometimes by more or less distinct radiating costae. Lower valve flat, concave or convex, often irregular in contour, the perforation rather large and situated near or at some distance from the margin.” – Weller (1907) p. 497.

FIGURE 75: *ANOMIA ARGENTARIA* MORTON, 1833 A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 4 F. 9-10; C-E: ANSP 8071 (KWB); F: MAPS A2446A (KMT); G MAPS A2446E (KW)

FAMILY NEITHEIDAE SOBETSKI, 1960

GENUS NEITHEA DROUËT, 1825

Weller (1907) pl. 51, f. 7-8 *Neithea quinquecostata* (Sowerby, 1814) is an illustration from Whitefield (1886) who attributed the specimen to Holmdel, NJ. Whitefield listed the formation as the "Lower Green Sands" and Weller identifies the formation as Wenonah on the plate, however in the list of locations for this species in Weller (1907) p. 481 no Wenonah formations are listed. The specimen is most likely from one of the many Navesink formation sites in the Holmdel area.

FAMILY PECTINIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS *CAMPTONECTES* AGASSIZ, 1864

Camptonectes bellisculptus Conrad, 1869

Camptonectes bellisculptus Conrad, 1869F: p. 99, pl 9, f. 11; Kummel, 1908: p. 69; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 40, 42; Wright, 1973; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 62, 77.

Non *Camptonectes (Amusium) burlingtonensis* Whitfield, 1885: p. 53, pl. 8, f. 3-6, 9; Whitfield, 1886: p. 53, pl. 8, f. 3-6, 9.

Pecten bellisculptus (Conrad, 1869F). Johnson, 1905: p. 11; Stephenson, 1923: p. 193, pl. 54, f. 10-11; Adkins, 1928: p. 124; Groot, Organists and Richards, 1954: p. 44; Richards, 1958: p. 129, pl. 23, f. 10, pl. 22, f. 4; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 143, f. 115; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 9; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B, pl. 1; Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 14; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B, pl. 1.

Non *Pecten argillensis* Conrad, 1860. Weller, 1907: p. 472, pl. 49, f. 1-3; Gardner, 1916: p. 588, pl. 34, f. 3-5; Wade, 1926: p. 62.

Pecten? bensoni Knicker, 1919: p. 16, pl. 1 f. 7-13; Stephenson, 1923: p. 193.

Pecten (Camptonectes) bellisculptus (Conrad, 1869F). Stephenson, 1941: p. 132.

Types – *Pecten bellisculptus* Conrad, 1869F; Holotype: ANSP 18755.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 472 (*Pecten argillensis*); Richards (1958) p. 129, MAPS A2512c; KS2106.

Description - Conrad described the species as follows: "Ovate, compressed, thin and fragile; divaricating radii distinct; concentric lines extremely thin and minute; interior hinge line crenulated." The description applies to the right valve only. The species is represented in North Carolina by three specimens, and on these the following description is based. Shell subcircular to broadly subovate in outline, the height in one specimen being slightly greater than the length. Valves depressed convex, the two valves probably subequal in convexity: shell subequilateral. Beaks small, depressed, not projecting above the hinge line and situated slightly back of the middle of the hinge. Dimensions of the largest specimen;

Length 35 mm., height 35 mm., convexity 4 mm. Posterior ear of right valve sharply delimited below by a deeply excavated sulcus slightly overhung by the body of the shell. Hinge straight. Internal characters not observed. The upper margins of the antero- and postero-dorsal slopes diverge from the beak at an angle of about 100 degrees; both margins are slightly concave upward. Surface marked by fine concentric growth lines, and by numerous crowded, radiating, bifurcating ribs which, though depressed, are distinct and readily seen macroscopically; the ribs are separated by much narrower depressions. Under the magnifying glass the surface in places appears slightly cancellated due to the crossing of the radiating and concentric markings. Owing to the frequent bifurcations the width of the ribs increases but slightly away from the beak. The posterior ear of the right valve shown in Plate 54, figure 11, is marked by fine growth lines and by fine, irregular radiating ribs which cross surface a little obliquely, rising slightly posteriorly. The dorsal portions of two of the three valves are so poorly preserved that it cannot be determined whether they are right or left valves." – Stephenson (1923) p. 194.

FIGURE 76: CAMPTONECTES BELLISCUPTUS (CONRAD, 1869)
A-C: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 8 FIG. 3,5,9; D: WELLER (1907)
PL. 49 F. 1 (KNS) (NOT P. ARGILLENSIS CONRAD, 1869); E:
ANSP 80491 (KWB)

***Camptonectes burlingtonensis* (Gabb, 1860)**

Pecten burlingtonensis Gabb, 1860A: p. 304, pl 48, f. 25; Gabb, 1861A: p. 213; Meek, 1864: p. 7; Johnson, 1905: p. 11; Weller, 1907: p. 470, pl. 49, f. 5-10; Wade, 1926: p. 63, pl 20, f. 5, 6, 10, 11; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 200-201; Richards, 1958: p. 129, pl. 23, f. 6; Richards, 1968: p. 26; Andres, 1995: p. 300; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Syncyclonema burlingtonensis (Gabb, 1860A). Conrad, 1868: p. 725.

Camptonectes burlingtonensis (Gabb, 1860A). Conrad, 1871: p. 76; Gabb, 1876A: p. 318; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156; Kuehne, 1993: p. 61; Elder, 1996: p. 254, f. 3.8-3.10; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 136, f. 108; Hall, 2005: p. 49.

Camptonectes (Amusium) burlingtonensis (Gabb, 1860A). Whitfield, 1885: p. 53-56, pl. 8, f. 7 (not pl. 8, f. 3-6 = *Camptonectes bellisculptus* (Conrad, 1869F)); Whitfield, 1886: p. 53-56, pl. 8, f. 7 (not pl. 8, f. 3-6 = *Camptonectes bellisculptus* (Conrad, 1869F)).

Pecten (Syncyclonema) perlamellosus Whitfield, 1885: p. 50, pl. 7, f. 7; Whitfield, 1886: p. 50, pl. 7, f. 7.

Pecten perlamellosus Whitfield, 1885; Johnson, 1905: p. 12.

Camptonectes cf. burlingtonensis (Gabb, 1860A). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40.

Chlamys (Pecten) burlingtonensis (Gabb, 1860A). Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54.

Neithea (Pecten) burlingtonensis (Gabb, 1860A). Brister and Young, 2007: p. 58.

Types – *Pecten burlingtonensis* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP 18756.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 470; Richards (1958) p. 129; Kuehne (1999) p. 64; ANSP 81024.

Description – "Shell, in large individuals, attaining a height of 57 mm., and a width of 62 mm.; the hinge-line straight, one half or a little less than one-half the width of the shell, with a central triangular cartilage pit; the body of the shell broadly subovate in outline,

the auriculations moderately large and nearly equal in size; the cardinal slopes a little concave, diverging from the beak at an angle of 90 or more, the shoulders of the valves prominent and above the middle of the height of the shell. Left valve depressed convex with the auriculations sharply differentiated. Right valve nearly flat, with a moderately deep byssal sinus. Surface of the valves marked by concentric bands which are continuous across the auriculations, and by exceedingly fine, impressed, radiating striae which are continuous upon the auriculations and the umbo, where they are about equal in width with the interspaces, but on the outer portion of the shell they become more or less discontinuous, the inner portion of the concentric bands often being nearly smooth, while on the outer portion they are completely striate, but with the interspaces between the striae broader than the striae themselves." – Weller (1907) p. 471

FIGURE 77: *CAMPTONECTES BURLINGTONENSIS* (GABB, 1860)
 A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 8 FIG. 7-8 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); C-D: WELLER (1907) PL. 49 FIG. 708 (KMV); E: WELLER (1907) PL. 49 FIG. 9 (KWB); F: ANSP 81024 (KW)

***Camptonectes conradi* (Whitfield, 1885)**

Amusium conradi Whitfield, 1885: p. 52, pl 7, f. 8-10; Whitfield, 1886: p. 52, pl 7, f. 8-10; Boyle, 1893: p.

37; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 154.

Pecten conradi (Whitfield, 1885). Johnson, 1905: p. 12; Weller, 1907: p. 474, pl. 50, f. 1-4; Gardner, 1916: p. 593-595; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 203-205; Richards, 1958: p. 130, pl. 23, f. 7, 11; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Syncyclonema conradi (Whitfield, 1885). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 65.

Camptonectes conradi (Whitfield, 1885). Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016; p. 9, f. 14, 16.

Types – *Amusium conradi* Whitfield, 1885; Holotype: ANSP 18757

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2501f.

Description - "Shell small, seldom exceeding half an inch in height; erect-ovate, becoming more elongate proportionally with increased growth. Valves slightly convex. Hinge short, from half to two-thirds as long as the width of the body of the shell, strongly and distinctly auriculated. Beaks of the valves small and pointed, and the cardinal slopes long, straight or slightly concave, extending to near the point of greatest width of the body of the shell. Left valve smooth or but faintly marked by fine concentric lines, and a few (five or six) very faint radii. Ears smaller than in the opposite valve, both sloping toward the beak on the outer margin. Right valve marked with crowded concentric folds or elevated lines; also, by five or six radiating lines; not always present. On most specimens there are distinctly rounded concentric folds or varices, but on some they are thin, sharp lines, always more crowded and usually finer toward the front, in adult specimens. Ears very distinct; that of the posterior side sloping toward the beak and the anterior one rounded at the extremity and deeply notched." - Whitfield (1886) p. 52

FIGURE 78: CAMPTONECTES CONRADI (WHITFIELD, 1885) A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 7 FIG. 8-9 ("LOWER MARL BEDS"); C: WELLER (1907) PL. 50 FIG. 1 (KWB); D: NJSM 23026 (KMV); E: MAPS A2501F (KW)

***Camptonectes* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Reported by Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30.

GENUS PECTEN MULLER, 1776
***Pecten simplicius* CONRAD, 1860**

Pecten simplicius Conrad, 1860: p. 283, pl. 46, f. 44; Gabb, 1861A: p. 216; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Conrad, 1868: p. 725; Stephenson, 1907: p. 143, 156, 157; Weller, 1907: p. 480, pl. 51, f. 6; Gardner, 1916: p. 595, pl. 34, f. 8, 9; Stephenson, 1923: p. 199, pl. 55, f. 6-11; Wade, 1926: p. 62, pl. 20, f. 7; Adkins, 1928: p. 124; Dane, 1929: p. 133; Shimer and Shrock, 1942: p. 405, pl. 161, f. 11, 12; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 212-213; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 44; Richards, 1958: p. 134, pl. 23, f. 12; Black, 1980: p. 73; Kuehne, 1994: p. 61; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 58; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 7; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Syncyclonema simplicius (Conrad, 1860). Meek, 1864: p. 7; Conrad, 1871: p. 99, pl. 9, f. 20; Gabb, 1876A: p. 319; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 46; Sohl and Christopher, 1984: p. 135, 137, 139, 141, 143, 146, 150, 153, 156, 156, 159; Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Kuehne, 1999: p. 71, 72, 74, 76, 77, 79.

Pseudamusium simplica (Conrad, 1860). Stoliczka, 1871: p. 420.

Amusium simplicium (Conrad, 1860). Whitfield, 1885: p. 51, pl. 7, f. 11-12; Whitfield, 1886: p. 51, pl. 7, f. 11-12; Boyle, 1893: p. 37; Whitfield, 1899: p. 154; Whitfield and Hovey, 1901: p. 416, cat. 5280.

Pecten (Syncyclonema) simplicius Conrad, 1860. Stephenson, 1941: p. 133, pl. 20, f. 10-11.

Syncyclonema cf. simplicius (Conrad, 1860). Kuehne, 1999: p. 65.

Types – *Pecten simplicius* Conrad, 1860; Holotype: Lost.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 65.

Description - "Shell small, barely half an inch in extreme height, and of equal width; discoid or very depressed convex, nearly or quite equilateral; margins of the shell somewhat regularly rounded; hinge-line a little less than half the width of the shell, and slightly rising from the center toward the extremities. Auricularations moderately large, the anterior side largest, slightly rounded on the outer margin and forming a slight byssal notch at its junction with the body of the shell on the right valve. Cardinal slopes on the right valve straight to near the point of greatest width of the valve and forming an angle of about fifty to fifty-five degrees with each other and very strongly impressed. Beak small and pointed. On the left valve the posterior ear is the smallest of the two, and the cardinal slopes less strongly marked, not so straight, and extend down the valve not so far as on the opposite valve. Surface of the valves smooth and shining to the naked eye, but under a lens is seen to be marked by fine concentric lines of growth, and on the left valve by faint, incipient, radiating lines." - Whitfield (1886) p. 51.

FIGURE 79: *PECTEN SIMPLICIUS* CONRAD, 1860 A-B:
WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 7 FIG. 11-12

Pecten sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2561a

FIGURE 80: *PECTEN* SP. A: MAPS A2561A (KW)

GENUS *RADIOPECTEN* STEPHENSON, 1941

Radiopecten quinquenarius (Conrad, 1853)

Pecten quinquearia Conrad, 1853A: p. 275, pl. 24, f. 10; Johnson, 1905: p.11; Weller, 1907: p. 476, pl. 50, f. 10-12 (not f. 13 = *Pecten mississippiensis* Stephenson, 1923).

Neithea quinquearia (Conrad, 1853A). Gabb, 1861A: p. 204; Meek, 1864: p. 7.

Pecten quinquenarius Conrad, 1853A. Whitfield, 1885: p. 47, pl. 7, f. 13-16; Whitfield, 1886: p. 47, pl.

7, f. 13-16; Whitfield, 1899: p. 163; Wade, 1926: p. 65, 66, pl. 21, f. 6-9; Stephenson, 1941: p. 138, 139; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 210-211; Richards, 1958: p. 131, pl. 23, f. 5.

Non *Pecten planicostatus* Whitfield, 1885. Crickmay, 1930: p. 48, pl. 8, f. 10, 11.

Radiopecten cf. *quinquenarius* (Conrad, 1853A). Dhondt, 1982: p. 853.

Radiopecten quinquenarius (Conrad, 1853A). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8, t. 2; Gallagher, 1986: p. 30

Chlamys quinquenarius (Conrad, 1853A). Kuehne, 1999: p. 64, 65.

Neithea (Pecten) quinquenarius (Conrad, 1853A). Brister and Young, 2007: p. 58.

Types – *Pecten quinquearia* Conrad, 1853; Holotype: ANSP 18805

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 476 pl. 50, f. 10-12; Richards (1958) p. 131; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65; MAPS A2453b; MAPS A2453c.

Description - "Shell of medium size, slightly oval transversely; in outline a little wider than high. Valves plano-convex in profile when united. Hinge line much shorter than the width of the shell below. Ears large, slightly unequal; that of the flat valve (right) somewhat sinuate on the anterior side. Cardinal slope of the valves somewhat concave between the beaks and the lateral margins of the body of the shell. Surface of the valves marked by strong, wide, rounded, radiating ribs, about five on the flat valve and six on the convex valve. On the convex valve, as shown upon the impression left in the fine blue marl, there have been fine, even, and closely arranged concentric lines crossing the folds and passing up over the auriculations; in fact, covering the entire surface of the valve. The opposite flat valve has not been marked by concentric lines, as was the convex valve, the surface of the cast, both inside and outside impressions, being apparently smooth. No remains of radiating lines on the folds can be seen." – Whitfield (1886) p. 47.

FIGURE 81: *RADIOPECTEN QUINQUENARIUS* (CONRAD, 1853)
A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 7 FIG. 14-15 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); C-D: WELLER (1907) PL. 50 FIG. 10, 12 (Kw); E: MAPS A2453B (Kw); F: MAPS A2453C (Kw)

ORDER **PHOLADOMYIDA** Newell, 1965
 FAMILY **PHOLADOMYIDAE** KING, 1844
 GENUS **PHOLADOMYA** SOWERBY, 1823
Pholadomya roemeri Whitfield, 1885

Pholadomya roemeri Whitfield, 1885: p. 176, pl. 24, f. 4; Whitfield, 1886: p. 176, pl. 24, f. 4; Whitfield, 1899, p. 163; Weller, 1907: p. 515, pl. 56, f. 4-5; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 249-251; Richards, 1958: p. 159, pl. 26, f. 5; Gallagher, 1986: p. 30; Kuehne, 1993: p. 69.

Types – *Pholadomya roemeri* Whitfield, 1885; Holotype: NJSM 9735.

Wenonah Specimens – Whitfield (1886) p. 176 pl. 24, f. 4; Weller (1907) p. 515 pl. 56, f. 4,5; Richards (1958) p. 159 pl. 26, f. 5; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64,65; NJSM 9735; MAPS A2451a; MAPS A2451b.

Description - The approximate dimensions of a rather small specimen are length, 38 mm.; height, 22 mm.; thickness, 18 mm. Shell very oblique and

inequilateral, elongate subovate in outline, widest back of the middle. Beaks small, incurved and nearly in contact, situated far forward. Hinge-line straight, rather long; anterior margin rounding from the anterior cardinal extremity into the basal margin; basal margin gently convex, curving upward posteriorly; posterior margin rather sharply rounded above the mid-height of the shell. Valves strongly convex or ventricose, the surface curving rather abruptly from the prominent umbones to the 'dorsal, anterior and ventral margins, much more gently to the posterior margin. Surface of each valve marked by about 13 narrow angular, radiating costae, separated by broad, concave interspaces: the most anterior costae curve slightly forward in passing from the beak to the margin of the shell. The surface is also marked by more or less irregular concentric lines of growth." – Weller (1907) p. 515.

FIGURE 82: *PHOLADOMYA ROEMERI* WHITFIELD, 1885 **A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 24 F. 4 ("LOWER GREEN SANDS"); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 56 FIG. 5 (Kw); C-D: MAPS A2451A (Kw); E-G: MAPS A2451B (Kw)**

Pholadomya sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64

ORDER POROMYIDA Ridgewood, 1903

FAMILY CUSPIDARIIDAE DALL, 1886

GENUS CUSPIDARIA Nardo, 1840

Cuspidaria ventricosa (Meek and Hayden, 1856)

Corbula ventricosa Meek and Hayden, 1856: p. 83; Gabb, 1861A: p. 167.

Neaera ventricosa (Meek and Hayden, 1856). Meek and Hay, 1860: p. 185; Gabb, 1861A: p. 204; Meek, 1864: p. 15; Meek, 1876: p. 238, pl. 30, f. 3a-e.

Cuspidaria ventricosa (Meek and Hayden, 1856). Weller, 1907: p. 533, pl. 58, f. 16-17; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 254-255; Richards, 1958: p. 172, pl. 28, f. 2.

Types – *Corbula ventricosa* Meek and Hayden, 1856; Holotype: USNM 419.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 533; Richards (1958) p. 172.

Description - "Shell small, nearly or quite equivalve, rather thin, very ventricose in the anterior and central regions; anterior margin somewhat narrowly rounded; base very deeply rounded toward the front, contracted behind; posterior side longer than the other, narrow, compressed and rostriform; dorsum sloping gradually with a concave outline behind the beaks, declining more abruptly in front; beaks prominent, apparently equal not oblique, located a little in advance of the middle; pallial border smooth; surface marked by rather concentric striae." - Meek and Hayden (1856) p. 83.

"The dimensions of a single valve are length, 13 mm.; height, 7 mm.; convexity, 2.7 mm." – Weller (1907) p. 533.

FIGURE 83: CUSPIDARIA VENTRICOSA (MEEK AND HAYDEN, 1856) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 58 FIG. 16 (KRB); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 28 FIG. 2 (KRB)

FAMILY POROMYIDAE DALL, 1886

GENUS CYMELLA MEEK, 1864

Cymella bella texana Stephenson, 1941

Non *Cymella meeki* Whitfield, 1877. Whitfield, 1885: p. 142 pl. 20, f. 6, 7; Whitfield, 1886: p. 142, pl. 20, f. 6, 7; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156.

Non *Cymella bella* Conrad, 1875A. Weller, 1905: p. 333; Weller, 1905A1: p. 333; Weller, 1905A2: p. 140; Weller, 1907: p. 530, pl. 58, f. 10-12; Kummel, 1908; Miller, 1911: pl. 5, f. 10; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 255-256; Owens, Minard, 1966; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 37, 40; Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 8, f. 3; Gallagher, 1984: p. 15; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54.

Cymella bella texana Stephenson, 1941: p. 165, pl. 26, f. 21-23; Richards, 1958: 9. 170, pl. 26, f. 9; Gallagher, Parris and Spammer, 1986: p. 30; Kuehne, 1994: p. 61; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Elder, 1996: p. 263; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 64, 69; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 385, f. 368.

Cymella bella var. Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 46, pl. 5, f. 3.

Types – *Cymella bella texana* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 76517.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 530; Richards (1958) p. 170; Gallagher (1984) p. 15; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64; MAPS A2425a; MAPS A2425b.

Description – "Shell subovate in outline, subequivalve, inequilateral, moderately ventricose, most inflated above the midheight and somewhat in advance of the midlength, becoming compressed posteriorly, probably slightly gaping posteriorly; shell wall thin. Beaks moderately prominent, broad, strongly incurved, approximate, slightly prosogyrate, situated a little in advance of the midlength. Lunule about 8 mm. long in the holotype, rather broad, smooth, and excavated. Escutcheon long, narrow, rather deep, separated from the main surface of the shell by a pronounced, dull-crested carina, outside of and parallel to which is a shallow channel against which the concentric ridges of the main surface end. Hinge and internal features not uncovered. Anterior margin regularly rounded, curving sharply into the dorsal margin above; ventral margin broadly and regularly rounded; posterior margin sharply rounded with a short subtruncation above the extremity; dorsal

margins sloping gently away from the beaks, the anterior one slightly arched. Surface ornamented with about 22 rather strong, broad, concentric ridges with narrow interspaces; the ridges become progressively broader from the beak toward the ventral margin, the last one being about 1.5 mm. wide; each of these ridges terminates above at the edge of these ridges terminates above at the edge of narrow, unribbed area bordering the dorsal margins. A group of a dozen or more rather broad, round crested radiating ribs, with narrower interspaces, extend from the beak down over the central part of the shell, leaving a little more than the anterior fourth and the posterior fourth, unribbed; the channels between the concentric ridges cut the radiating ribs, giving to the central part of the shell checkered appearance; the radiating ribs exhibit considerable variation in their number and spacing on different individuals." – Stephenson (1941) p. 165.

Stephenson (1923 p. 254) called attention to the fact that the New Jersey specimens had broader costae and narrower interspaces than the true *C. bella*. The varietal name *texana* was given to very similar forms in Texas and it seems desirable to use this name for the New Jersey specimens.

FIGURE 84: *CYMELLA BELLA TEXANUS* STEPHENSON, 1941 A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 20 FIG. 6-7; C: WELLER (1907) PL. 58 FIG. 11 (Kw); D-E: MAPS A2425A (Kw); F: MAPS A2425A (Kw)

Cymella ironensis (Stephenson, 1923)

Liopistha (Cymella) ironensis Stephenson, 1923: p. 255, pl. 65, f. 9.

Cymella ironensis (Stephenson, 1923). Vestal, 1946: p. 61.

Cymella cf. ironensis (Stephenson, 1923). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 37; Elder, 1996: p. 263, f. 7.1,7.2; Akers and Akers, 2002: p 385, f. 368.

Types – *Liopistha (Cymella) ironensis* Stephenson, 1923; Holotype: USNM 31727.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2428a; MAPS A2428b; MAPS A2428c.

Description – "Shell subovate in outline, very thin, inequilateral, moderately convex, fullest centrally and anteriorly, becoming compressed posteriorly. Beaks prominent, strongly incurved, prosogyrate, approximate, situated a little in advance of the midlength. Dimensions of the type: Length. 27 mm., height about 20 mm., convexity 7 mm. Lunule and escutcheon-like areas outlined rather sharply. Anterior margin regularly rounded; ventral margin broadly rounded posterior margin narrower than the anterior margin and subtruncated. Surface marked by 20 or more regular, broadly rounded, concentric ridges separated by narrow, moderately deep depressions. Radiating from the beaks down over the central and postero-central portions of the shell are numerous ribs which back of the midlength on the type alternate in size between relatively broad, round-topped ridges and narrow, less prominent intercalated ridges. This radiating sculpture fades out both anteriorly and posteriorly. The distinctness of the alternations in size of the radiating ribs differs in different individuals and on different parts of the shell, but they all agree in that the ribs are numerous and closely spaced." – Stephenson (1923) p. 255.

FIGURE 85: *CYMELLA IRONENSIS* STEPHENSON, 1923 A: MAPS A2482A (Kw) B-C: MAPS A2482B (Kw) D: MAPS A2482c (Kw)

***Cymella undata* (Meek and Hayden, 1856)**

- Pholadomya undata* Meek and Hayden, 1856: p. 81
- Pholadomya (Cymella) undata* Meek and Hayden, 1856. Meek 1864: p. 14, 34.
- Leiopistha (Cymella) undata* (Meek and Hayden, 1856). White, 1875: p. 187, pl. 18, f. 15a; Meek, 1876: p. 236, pl. 39, f. 1a-1b; Boyle, 1893: p. 165.
- Not Leiopistha (Psiloyma) meekii* White, 1874: p. 26.
- Leiopistha (Cymella) meeki* White, 1877: p. 187, pl. 18, f. 15a; Whitfield, 1877: p. 35, 36, pl. 11, f. 27, 28; Whitfield, 1880: p. 418, 419, pl. 11, f. 27, 28; Boyle, 1893: p. 165.
- Liopistha (Cymella) undata* (Meek and Hayden, 1856). Dawson, 1884: p. 44; Whiteaves, 1885: p. 80; Marcou, 1886: p. 312; Boyle, 1893: p. 170; Stanton, 1905: p. 112; Darton and Seibenthal, 1909: p. 39, 42; Peale, 1912: p. 645; Stephenson, 1923: p. 254.
- Liopistha undata* (Meek and Hayden, 1856). Whiteaves, 1889: p. 178; Boyle, 1893: p. 170; Sealey and Lucas, 2009: p. 70,75.
- Cymella meeki* (Whitfield, 1877). Boyle, 1893: p. 107.
- Cymella undata* (Meek and Hayden, 1856). Boyle, 1893: p. 108; Weller, 1907: p. 531, pl. 58, f. 13; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 256-257; Richards, 1958: p. 171, pl. 27, f. 9; Dhondt and Jagt, 1988: p. 188.

Liopistha (Cymella) meeki (Whitfield, 1877). Boyle, 1893: p. 170

Types – *Pholadomya undata* Meek and Hayden, 1856; Holotype: USNM 187.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 531 pl. 58, f. 13; Richards (1958) p. 171 pl. 27, f. 9 (NJSM 9746).

Description - "Shell transversely broad-ovate, approaching subtrigonal, moderately gibbous; anterior end rounded; posterior side narrower and a little more compressed, rounded chiefly from below; base forming a regular semiovate curve; dorsal margin sloping rather abruptly in front of the beaks, straighter and declining more gradually behind; hinge-margins straight, and inflected so as to form, a well-defined false area both behind and a little in front of the beaks, which are somewhat elevated, incurved at right angles to the hinge-line, and located a little in advance of the middle of the shell. Surface ornamented by about 17 to 20 of the simple, rounded, rather strong, regular, concentric undulations, which are broader than the depressions between, and, as it were, cut by the radiating linear furrows, on the central region of each valve, into about the same number of much smaller, simple, radiating costae, less than, or nearly equaling, the furrows by which they are separated." (Meek.) The dimensions of the only specimen observed, a left valve, are length, 16.5 mm.; height, 12 mm.; convexity, 3.5 mm." - Weller (1907) p. 531.

FIGURE 86: *CYMELLA UNDATA* (MEEK AND HAYDEN, 1856) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 58 FIG. 13 (Kw); B: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 27 FIG. 9 (NJSM 9746) (Kw); C: NJSM 9746 (Kw)

GENUS **LIPISTHA** MEEK, 1864***Liopistha protexta* (Conrad, 1853)**

Cardium protextum Conrad, 1853A: p. 275, pl. 24, f. 12; Gabb, 1859: p. 10; Gabb, 1861A: p. 164; Boyle, 1893: p. 79

Fragilia protexta (Conrad, 1853A). Conrad, 1860: p. 275

Non *Papyridea elegantula* (Roemer, 1852). Gabb, 1861A: p. 164, 218.

Papyridea (Liopistha) protexta (Conrad, 1853A). Meek, 1864: p. 12.

Liopistha protexta (Conrad, 1853A). Kerry, 1875: p. 28; Meek, 1876: p. 277, text f. 20-24; Boyle, 1893: p. 70; Weller, 1907: p. 526, pl. 58, f. 4-6; Stephenson, 1911: p. 178-180; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2-8; Clark, Berry and Gardner, 1916: p. 182; Gardner, 1916: p. 636, pl. 36, f. 15; Stephenson, 1923: p. 250, pl. 65, f. 3; Stephenson, 1926: p. 248, pl. 91, f. 7; Wade, 1926: p. 75, pl. 24, f. 6; Adkins, 1928: p. 149; Dane, 1929: p. 109, 133; Thomas and Rice, 1931: p. 318; Stephenson, 1941: p. 162, pl. 26, f. 27-30; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 261-263; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 46, pl. 5, f. 2; Stephenson, 1955: p. 116, pl. 19, f. 17-21; Richards, 1958: p. 167, pl. 27, f. 7-8; Richards and Shapiro 1963: p. 7; Swift, 1966: p. 32, f. 7; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40, 46; Carey, 1976: p. 218, pl. 7 f 2; Black, 1980: p. 73; Gallagher, 1984: p. 14; Sohl and Koch 1984: p. 137, 142, 144, 147, 151, 154, 157, 160, 162; Hartstein, 1986: p. 89; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 21, f. 9; Dhondt and Jagt, 1988: p. 188, 191, text f. 1; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 69, 70, 77, 79; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 386, f. 369; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59; Gallagher, Camburn, Camburn and Hanczaryk, 2014: p. 67; Lauginiger, Parris and Pellegrini, 2014: p. 176; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B. pl. 1; Farke and Phillips, 2017: p. 5, f. 3b, p. 6, table 1; Gallagher, Hanczaryk, 2019: p. 51.

Leiopistha protexta (Conrad, 1853A). Whitfield, 1885: p. 140-142, pl. 20, f. 1-3; Whitfield, 1886: p. 140-142, pl. 20, f. 1-3; Boyle, 1893: p. 165; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 335; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 185; Whitfield, 1899: p. 159; Johnson, 1905: p. 13.

Leiopistha inflata Whitfield, 1885: p. 142, pl. 20, f. 4-5; Whitfield, 1886: p. 142, pl. 20, f. 4-5; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer 1986: p. 16.

Liopistha aff. Liopistha protexta (Conrad, 1853A). Stetson, 1949: p. 9.

Liopistha cf. protexta (Conrad, 1853A). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 37.

Types – *Cardium protextum* Conrad, 1853; Holotype: ANSP 16871.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 526; Richards (1958) p. 167; MAPS A2439i.

Description - “The dimensions of a large individual are length, 30.5 mm.; height, 22 mm.; thickness, 16.5 mm. Shell, exclusive of the projecting beaks, subelliptical in outline. Beaks prominent, situated a little in advance of the middle of the shell, their apices pointed, incurved and nearly in contact. Anterocardinal slope slightly concave; anterior margin sharply rounded; basal margin regularly convex throughout; posterior margin rather short, obliquely subtruncate, straight or slightly convex; posterior cardinal slope more concave than the anterior. Valves ventricose in the umbonal region, the surface curving regularly to the margin all around, being more abrupt to the cardinal margin, and often somewhat compressed towards the postero-cardinal extremity; slightly gaping behind. Surface marked by 25 to 30, and in very large individuals as many as 35, angular, radiating costae with concave interspaces, a small area at the posterior extremity being nearly or wholly destitute of ribs. External impressions of the shell show these ribs to be crossed by fine concentric lines of growth, and to be surmounted along the summit by a row of small tubercles appearing almost like spine bases, whose distance apart is less than the distance between adjacent costae, the radiating rows of tubercles also continue across the posterior non-costate portion of the shell.” – Weller (1907) p. 527.

FIGURE 87: *LIPISTHA PROTEXTA* (CONRAD, 1853) A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 20 FIG. 1-2 (“LOWER GREEN MARLS”); C-D: WELLER (1907) PL. 58 FIG. 5-6 (KNS); E-F: MAPS A2439B (KS); G: MAPS A2439I (KW)

ORDER SOLENIDA DALL, 1889

FAMILY PHARIDAE ADAMS AND ADAMS, 1858

GENUS LEPTOSOLEN CONRAD, 1865

***Leptosolen biplicata* (Conrad, 1858)**

Siliquaria biplicata Conrad, 1858A: p. 324, 325, pl. 34, f. 17; Gabb, 1861A: p. 226; Lea, 1862: p. 150; Meek, 1864: p. 15; Conrad, 1867A: p. 15; Boyle, 1893: p. 264; Richards, 1968: p. 35.

Leptosolen biplicata (Conrad, 1858). Gabb, 1862A: p. 304; Gabb, 1876A: p. 30; Whitfield, 1885: p. 183, pl. 24, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1886: p. 183, pl. 24, f. 1-2; Boyle, 1893: p. 166; Whitfield, 1899: p. 159; Weller, 1905A1: p. 333; Weller, 1905A2: p. 140; Weller, 1905B1: p. 78; Weller, 1905B2: p. 153; Johnson, 1905: p. 17; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Stephenson, 1907: p. 126, 130, 136, 140; Weller, 1907: p. 624, pl. 70, f. 30-31; Kummel, 1908: p. 69; Stephenson, 1911: p. 129, 137, 160, 177, 180, 185; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2 & 8; Gardner, 1916: p. 703-704, pl. 42, f. 8; Wade, 1916: p. 94, pl. 31, f. 4, 7; Richards, 1958: p. 239, pl. 37, f. 1; Toots and Cutler, 1962B: p. 8; Sohl

and Christopher, 1983: p. 8; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 141, 143, 147, 150, 156, 160; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Hall, 2005: p. 49 t. 8, p. 44 t. 5; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59; Ebersole, 2009: p. 134; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 91; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54 App. B pl. 1; Shankle and Johnson, 2018: p. 26.

Solena (Leptosolen) biplicata (Conrad, 1858): Conrad, 1865C: p. 184.

Leptosolen biplicatus (Conrad, 1858). Conard, 1868: p. 727; Stephenson, 1923: p. 332, pl. 85, f. 10, 11; Adkins, 1928: p. 167; Dane, 1929: p. 40 pl. 8, f. 7; Stephenson and Monroe, 1940: p. 290, pl. 15, f. 5; Stephenson, 1941: p. 226, pl. 43, f. 4-5; Cooke, 1943: p. 29, 36; Bergquist, 1944: p. 23; Stephenson, 1955: p. 123, pl. 20, f. 15, 16; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40; Elder, 1996: p. 260, f. 6.11; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64, 73, 77; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 279, f. 253, p. 281, f. 255;

Leptosolen aff. Leptosolen biplicatus (Conrad, 1858). Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 279, f. 253, p. 281, f. 255.

Non *Legumen biplicata* (Conrad). Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54.

Types – *Siliquaria biplicata* Conrad, 1858 – Conrad (1858) p. 324, pl. 34, f. 17; Holotype: ANSP 16326 (MSKr); Topotype: USNM 128167.

Wenonah Specimens - *Leptosolen biplicata* Weller (1905) p. 333; Weller (1907) p. 624 pl. 70, f. 30-31; Richards (1958) p. 239 pl. 37, f.1, (NJSM 7682); Kuehne (1999) p. 64.

Description - “The dimensions of an average specimen are length, 35 mm.; height, n mm.; convexity, 3 mm. The largest example observed is” nearly 60 mm. in length. Shell elongate, with straight, subparallel dorsal and ventral margins, the anterior and posterior margins rounded, the anterior usually a little more sharply rounded than the posterior, the greatest anterior extension at or above the mid-height of the shell. Gaping at both ends, more widely so posteriorly. Beaks small, scarcely elevated above the hinge-line, situated a little more than one-fourth the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Valves nearly regularly convex from the dorsal to the ventral margin, the slope to the cardinal margin

usually a little more abrupt; the anterior extremity of the shell compressed, with two obscure, sometimes obsolete plications extending obliquely forward and downward from the beak. In the casts a strong furrow passes from the beak downward towards the ventral margin, with a slight posterior obliquity, growing shallower below and becoming obsolete at a point about three-fourths the height of the shell from the dorsal margin. Surface of the casts marked by more or less inconspicuous concentric lines of growth." - Weller (1907) p. 624.

FIGURE 88: *LEPTOSOLEN BIPLICATA* A-B: WELLER 1907 PL. 70 F. 30, 31 (Kw)

Leptosolen sp.

Wenonah Specimens: *Leptosolen* sp.; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2424c

FIGURE 89: *LEPTOSOLEN* SP. A-B: MAPS A2424c (Kw)

ORDER TRIGONIIDA DALL, 1889

FAMILY PTEROTRIGONIIDAE VAN HOEPEN, 1929

GENUS GABBIGONIA COOPER, 2015

Gabbigonia eufalensis (Gabb, 1860)

Trigonia eufalensis Gabb, 1860B: p. 396, pl. 68, f. 32; Gabb, 1861A: p. 232; Lea, 1862: p. 15; Meek, 1864: p. 9; Conrad, 1868: p. 725; Boyle, 1893: p. 287; Johnson, 1905: p. 11; Gardner, 1916: p. 582, pl. 34, f. 1,2; Wade, 1926: p. 61, pl. 20, f. 3-4.

Trigonia eufaulensis Gabb, 1860B. Whitfield, 1885: p. 113, 114, pl. 14, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1886: p. 113, 114, pl. 14, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1899: p. 165, pl. 14, f. 3, 4; Harris, 1900: p. 295, pl. 50, f. 9; Stephenson, 1907: p. 127, 143, 149, 154; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2-8; Weller, 1907: p. 462, pl. 48, f. 5, 6; Stephenson, 1911: 136, 138, 139,, 176, 180, 182 Stephenson, 1923: p. 189, pl. 34, f. 1-6; Adkins, 1928: p. 122; Shimmer and Shrock, 1942: p. 401, pl. 159, f. 12,13; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 44; Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957: p. 193; Richards, 1958: p. 123, pl. 21, f. 7, pl. 22, f. 1; Swift, 1966: p. 32, f. 7; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46; Gallagher, 1984: p. 16; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer, 1986: p. 11; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Kuehne, 1993: p. 60; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 225, 226, f. 196, 197; Hall, 2005: p. 49, t. 8; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 58; Brooks, Danilova and Garg, 2012: f. 9; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p 54, App. B, pl. 1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 61, 62, 70, pl. 3.

Trigonia aff. *Trigonia eufalensis* Gabb, 1860. Dane, 1929: p. 133; Vestal, 1946: p. 63; Black, 1980: p. 73.

Scabrotrigonia eufaulensis (Gabb, 1860). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8, t. 2.

Pterotrighonia (*Scabrotrighonia*) *eufaulensis* (Gabb, 1860). Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 137, 139, 143, 146, 150, 153, 156, 159; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 77, 79

Pterotrighonia eufaulensis (Gabb, 1860). Kuehne, 1995: p. 84; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 61, 64, 70, 71, 76, 77, 79

Pterotrighonia cf. *eufaulensis* (Gabb, 1860). Kuehne, 1999: p. 67; Farke and Phillips, 2017: p. 6, t. 1.

Gabbigonia eufalensis (Gabb, 1860). Cooper, 2015: p. 31, f. 6R, 6S.

Types – *Trigonia eufalensis* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP 19578

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 462 pl. 48, f. 5; Richards (1958) p. 123; MAPS A2442c; MAPS A2442h.

Description – “Shell small, the dimensions of an average specimen being length, 21 mm.; height 15 mm.; convexity, 4 mm. The largest specimen observed is under 30 mm. in length. Ovate subtrigonal in outline, somewhat alate posteriorly, moderately convex in front, compressed behind. Beaks almost anterior, slightly recurved. Anterior and antero-basal margin broadly rounded, postero-basal margin nearly straight, sloping upward towards the posterior hinge extremity, posterior extremity rounding sharply into the dorsal margin; dorsal margin nearly, straight behind, becoming more strongly concave as it approaches the beak. Surface of the valves divided into two portions by a ridge passing with a concave curve from the posterior side of the beak to the posterior margin of the shell just below the posterior extremity of the hinge-line. The lower portion of the valve is marked by 12 or 14 strong, angular, non-nodose ridges, narrower than the interspaces, the more anterior ones of which curve strongly forward in passing from the bounding ridge to the shell margin, the more posterior ones becoming straighter, in some cases having a slightly sigmoidal curve. The upper portion of the shell is inflected above the bounding ridge for about one-half the distance to the hinge-margin, above which it is again deflected into nearly a plane with the valve, the ribs of the lower portion of the shell are continued backwards in crossing the bounding ridge, the more posterior ones being more strongly bent than those in front. Besides the ribs, the shell is marked by inconspicuous lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 463.

FIGURE 90 GABBIIGNIA EUFALENSIS (GABB, 1860) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 14 FIG. 1-2 (“LOWER GREEN MARLS”); B: MAPS A2442H (KW); C: MAPS A2442E (KWB); D: MAPS A2442A (KS)

GENUS KAUFFMANELLA COOPER, 2015
***Kauffmanella cerulia* (Whitfield, 1885)**

Trigonia cerulia Whitfield, 1885: p. 114, 115, pl. 14, f. 7; Whitfield, 1886: p. 114, 115, pl. 14, f. 7; Boyle, 1983: p. 286; Clark, 1897: p. 335; Clark, 1898: p. 185; Whitfield, 1899: p. 165; Weller, 1907: p. 464, pl. 48, f. 13; Gardner, 1916: p. 584; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 170-171; Richards, 1958: p. 124, pl. 48, f. 13; Gallagher, 1984: p. 30.

Pterotrigoia cerulia (Whitfield, 1885). Kuehne, 1999: p.67.

Kauffmanella cerulia (Whitfield, 1885). Kauffmanella, 2015: p. 31, f. 6x, 6y.

Types – *Trigonia cerulia* Whitfield, 1885; Holotype: NJSM 7508

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher (1984) p. 30.

Description—The material on which this species is based is all more or less Imperfect or fragmentary. The best specimen is the right valve shown in Stephenson (1923) plate 52, fig. 1-3 and designated the type by Stephenson (1923), p. 186. Shell large, equivalve, inequilateral, subtrigonal, moderately ventrianteriorly, becoming compressed posteriorly. Beak small, incurved, opisthogyrate, situated about

one-fifth the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Dimensions of the type: Length 90 mm., height 80 mm., convexity about 25 mm.

The hinge of the right valve is composed of the following parts: Two prominent teeth, the anterior one of which inclines obliquely forward and downward from the tip of the beak, curving slightly with the convex side upward, and the posterior one extending from slightly back of the beak obliquely downward and backward, and curving slightly with the concave side upward, diverging from the anterior tooth; both teeth become thicker away from the beak and both are crossed laterally by numerous small ridges which trend approximately at right angles to the plane of contact between the valves, but which are slightly curved with the concave side upward; the two teeth are separated by a wide gap which opens into the interior of the shell; in front of the anterior tooth and parallel to it is a canal-like socket sunk below the level of the margin, and back of the posterior tooth is a narrow deep socket. The teeth of the right valve fit into corresponding sockets in the left valve, which are separated by a massive buttress; in front of the anterior socket and back of the posterior socket are small teeth which fit into the corresponding sockets of the right valve. Ligament al grooves deeply impressed extending about one-third the length of the dorsal area from the beak.

Anterior adductor scar deeply impressed, smaller than the posterior scar, subelliptical in outline, about half of its area being above the lower extremity of the main teeth and sockets; supported below by a massive buttress. Posterior adductor scar subtriangular, strongly impressed, situated just below the dorsal margin and slightly back of the midlength; above this scar is a small deeply impressed muscle scar. Pallial line nearly simple but becoming slightly sinuous and deeply impressed where it passes up to meet the posterior adductor scar. A well-defined ridge extends from a short distance back of the posterior adductor, backward and upward to a point a little above the middle of the posterior margin of the shell.

Dorsal margin strongly concave; anterior margin broadly rounded; ventral margin broadly rounded, fullest anteriorly, and notched, the notches corresponding to the interspaces between the surface ribs; posterior margin short, truncated, and strongly inclined forward. Dorsal surface of each valve deeply concave and ornamented with a series of small, tuberculated, slightly curved ridges spaced 2 to

2% mm. apart and trending transverse to the dorsal margin of the shell. Dorsal area separated from the main shell surface by an unribbed area which extends from the beak backward to the posterior margin in a broad curve with the convex side upward; a shallow sulcus extends along the center of the unribbed area and growth lines, and undulations cross it transversely. Main surface of shell ornamented with prominent ribs, numbering about 22 in the adult, which originate along the lower margin of the unribbed area, trending first in a slight curve downward and backward, but toward the anterior or ventral margin, as the case may be, curving rather strongly forward; each of these slightly sinuous ribs presents on its crest a series of rounded, more or less irregular nodes." – Stephenson (1923) p. 186.

FIGURE 91: KAUFFMANELLA CERULIA WHITFIELD, 1885 A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 14 FIG. 7 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 48 FIG. 13 (Kt); C: MAPS A2528C – CAST AND IMPRESSION (Kt)

GENUS PRAESCABROTRIGONIA COOPER, 2015
***Praescabrotrigonia bartrami* (Stephenson, 1923)**

Trigonia bartrami Stephenson, 1923: p. 40,45,46,186-187, pl. 52, f. 1-3, pl. 53, f. 1-4; Hall, 2005: p. 54, t. 11; Wick, 2021: p. 118 t. 2.

Trigonia (Pterotrigoia) cf. bartrami (Stephenson, 1923). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40.

Scabrotrigonia bartrami (Stephenson, 1923). Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 8.

Pterotrigonia cf. bartrami (Stephenson, 1923).
Kuehne, 1999: p. 76.

Praescabrotrigonia bartrami (Stephenson, 1923).
Cooper, 2015: p. 29.

Types – *Trigonia bartrami* Stephenson, 1923;
Holotype: USNM 31637

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2562b, MAPS A2562d.

Description - The material on which this species is based is all more or less imperfect or fragmentary. The best specimen is the right valve shown in Plate 52, and here designated the type. Shell large, equivalve, inequilateral, subtrigonal, moderately ventri-anteriorly, becoming compressed posteriorly. Beak small, incurved, opisthogyrate, situated about one-fifth the length of the shell from the anterior extremity (as oriented in figure 1, Plate 52). Dimensions of the type: Length 90 mm., height 80 mm., convexity about 25 mm. The hinge of the right valve is composed of the following parts: Two prominent teeth, the anterior one of which inclines obliquely forward and downward from the tip of the beak, curving slightly with the convex side upward, and the posterior one extending from slightly back of the beak obliquely downward and backward, and curving slightly with the concave side upward, diverging from the anterior tooth; both teeth become thicker away from the beak and both are crossed laterally by numerous small ridges which trend approximately at right angles to the plane of contact between the valves, but which are slightly curved with the concave side upward; the two teeth are separated by a wide gap which opens into the interior of the shell; in front of the anterior tooth and parallel to it is a canal-like socket sunk below the level of the margin, and back of the posterior tooth is a narrow deep socket. The teeth of the right valve fit into corresponding sockets in the left valve, which are separated by a massive buttress; in front of the anterior socket and back of the posterior socket are small teeth which fit into the corresponding sockets of the right valve. Ligamental grooves deeply impressed extending about one-third the length of the dorsal area from the beak. Anterior adductor scar deeply impressed, smaller than the posterior scar, subelliptical in outline, about half of its area being above the lower extremity of the main teeth and sockets; supported below by a massive buttress. Posterior adductor scar subtriangular, strongly impressed, situated just below the dorsal margin and slightly back of the midlength; above this scar is a

small deeply impressed muscle scar. Pallial line nearly simple but becoming slightly sinuous and deeply impressed where it passes up to meet the posterior adductor scar. A well defined ridge extends from a short distance back of the posterior adductor, backward and upward to a point a little above the middle of the posterior margin of the shell. Dorsal margin strongly concave; anterior margin broadly rounded; ventral margin broadly rounded, fullest anteriorly, and notched, the notches corresponding to the interspaces between the surface ribs; posterior margin short, truncated, and strongly inclined forward. Dorsal surface of each valve deeply concave and ornamented with a series of small, tuberculated, slightly curved ridges spaced 2 to 2mm. apart and trending transverse to the dorsal margin of the shell. Dorsal area separated from the main shell surface by an unribbed area which extends from the beak backward to the posterior margin in a broad curve with the convex side upward; a shallow sulcus extends along the center of the unribbed area and growth lines and undulations cross it transversely. Main surface of shell ornamented with prominent ribs, numbering about 22 in the adult, which originate along the lower margin of the unribbed area, trending first in a slight curve downward and backward, but toward the anterior or ventral margin, as the case may be, curving rather strongly forward; each of these slightly sinuous ribs presents on its crest a series of rounded, more or less irregular nodes. – Stephenson (1923) p. 186.

FIGURE 92: *PRAESCABROTRIGONIA BARTRAMI* (STEPHENSON, 1923) A: MAPS A2652B – INTERNAL CAST (KW) B: MAPS A2652A (KW) C: CCPM (KET)

GENUS **PTEROTRIGONIA** VAN HOEPEN, 1929*Pterotrigonia* sp.

Wenonah Specimens –Kuehne (1999) p. 6.5

FAMILY **TRIGONIIDAE** LAMARCK, 1819GENUS **TRIGONIA** BRUGUIERE, 1789*Trigonia mortoni* Whitfield, 1885

Trigonia mortoni Whitfield, 1885: 112,113, pl. 14, f. 5-6; Boyle, 1893: p. 288; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 43; Richards, 1956: p. 71, 80; Richards, 1958: p. 122, pl. 21, f. 4, 8; Richards and Shapiro, 1963; Gallagher, 1984: p. 14, 16, 18, 20, 25; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Gallagher, Camburn, Camburn and Hanczaryk, 2014: p. 67; Cooper 2015: p. 31; Gallagher and Hanczaryk, 2019: p. 52.

Trigonia cf. *mortoni* Whitfield, 1885. Richards, 1958: p. 122.

Types – *Trigonia mortoni* Whitfield, 1885; Holotype: ANSP 19346

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 466 (*T. thoracica*); Richards (1958) p. 122.

Description - "Shell large, the dimensions, of an average sized individual being length, 48 mm.; height, 42 mm.; convexity, 11 mm. Ovate subtrigonal in outline, the valves moderately convex in front, becoming compressed posteriorly; the beaks nearly anterior, slightly recurved. Anterior margin broadly rounded, passing into the ventral margin; ventral margin broadly rounded, often becoming a little straightened as it approaches the posterior extremity of the shell; posterior margin obliquely subtruncate above; dorsal margin gently concave from the beak to the posterior hinge extremity. Surface of the valve divided into two portions by an angular, curved furrow, passing backward from just behind the beak sub-parallel with the dorsal margin, to a point in the posterior margin of the shell a short distance below the posterior hinge extremity; the lower portion of the valve constitutes much the greater part and is marked by about fifteen ribs, about ten of which are very strong, subangular, more or less nodose, with broad concave interspaces, and occupying the greater portion of the shell, the more anterior of these ribs are shorter and curve strongly forward, the more posterior ones curve slightly downward ; between these strong ribs and the curved divisional

furrow is a subtriangular area occupied by much smaller somewhat nodose furrows, which usually have a more or less distinct upward curvature as they approach the posterior border. The upper portion of the valves is divided into two regions, being nearly in the plane of the valve below and abruptly inflected above to the hinge-line, to form a long and rather broad escutcheon, this region is marked with 12 or 14 subangular ribs which originate along the divisional furrow, curving backward and upward across the escutcheon to the hinge-line. The entire surface is also marked by more or less irregular concentric lines of growth." - Weller (1907) p. 460.

FIGURE 93: *TRIGONIA MORTONI* WHITFIELD, 1885 A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 14 FIG. 6; B: WELLER (1907) PL. 48 FIG. 2 (KMT); C-D: MAPS A2504A (KMT); E-F: MAPS A2504B – INTERNAL MOLDS (KNS); G-H: MAPS A2504B (KNS)

ORDER **UNIONIDA** Gray, 1854
 FAMILY **MARGARITIFERIDAE** HENDERSON, 1929
 GENUS **MARGARITIFERA** SCHUMACKER, 1815
Margaritifera sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2566a.

FIGURE 94: *MARGARTIFERA* SP. A: MAPS A2566A (KW)

ORDER **VENERIDA** Gray, 1854
 FAMILY **ARCTICIDAE** NEWTON, 1891
 GENUS **ETEA** CONRAD, 1875
Etea carolinensis Conrad, 1875

Etea carolinensis Conrad, 1875A: A6, pl. 1, f. 14; Conrad, 1875B: p. A15; Boyle, 1893: p. 120; Johnson, 1905: p. 14; Stephenson, 1907: p. 127, 130, 136, 138, 140, 148; Stephenson, 1911: p. 129, 132-134, 136, 137, 140, 180; Wade, 1926: p. 81, pl. 25, f. 9, 10; Popenoe, 1937: p. 385; Vestal, 1946: p. 56; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 40; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 141, 144, 147; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 63, 64, 73; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 298, f. 272; Hall, 2005: p. 44, t. 5, p. 49, t. 8; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54, 59; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 91; Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 14, 15; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: 61, 62, 72; Shankle and Johnson, 2018: p. 26, App. B pl. 1.

Crassatellina carolinensis (Conrad, 1875). Meek, 1876: p. 119, 120; Gardner, 1916: p. 646; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59.

Non *Etea carolinensis* Conrad, 1875. Weller, 1907: p. 541, pl. 59, f. 4-6 = *Etea carolinensis asper* Stephenson, 1923.

Veniella (Etea) carolinensis (Conrad, 1875). Stephenson, 1923: p. 264. pl. 56, f. 9-12; Stephenson, 1927: p. 17; Adkins, 1928: p. 154; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 7.

Veniella carolinensis (Conrad, 1875). Eley, 1938; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Wick, 2021: p. 118, t. 2.

Etea aff. Etea carolinensis Conrad, 1875. Vestal, 1946: p. 61.

Types – *Etea carolinensis* Conrad, 1875; Holotype: UNSM 31929

Wenonah Specimens – ANSP 80770.

Description – “The dimensions of a shell of average size, preserving both valves, are length, 33 mm.; height, 22.5 mm.; thickness, 14 mm. Length of the largest individual observed, 14 mm. Shell very oblique and inequilateral, the beaks obtuse, slightly incurved, situated about three-eighths of the entire length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Anterior margin somewhat narrowly rounded and passing into the basal margin; basal margin moderately convex anteriorly, becoming straight or usually slightly concave posteriorly; posterior-basal extremity acutely angular; posterior margin rather short, obliquely truncate; postero-dorsal margin straight except near the beak where it becomes slightly convex, making an angle of about 136 with the truncate posterior margin. Surface of the shell marked with a sharply angular or subcarinate, usually straight, umbonal ridge passing from the beak to the posterobasal extremity of the shell; postero-dorsal slope concave from the umbonal ridge to the cardinal margin, where the shell is sharply inflected to form a large and nearly flat escutcheon; in front of the umbonal ridge a broad, more or less indefinite depression passes from the beak to the sinuosity in the posterior portion of the ventral margin; in front of the beak the surface is inflected to form a rather large and broad lunule. Entire surface of the shell covered with strong, concentric lines of growth, which are more or less irregular in the strength of their development. Hinge of right valve with a large bifid cardinal tooth directed obliquely backwards from beneath the beak, and a much smaller simple one

directed forward; between these two teeth is a deep triangular pit, and behind the posterior one is a much narrower pit; two large lateral teeth are present, one in front and one behind the beak, the anterior one is nearer the beak with a broad and deep pit between it and the hinge-line, the posterior one is more elongate and slender, and is also separated from the hinge-line by a deep pit. The hinge of the left valve has two cardinal teeth, a large bifid one immediately beneath the beak and a thin, very oblique one behind, with a large, oblique, triangular pit between the two; there are two strong lateral teeth, one in front and one behind, the anterior one being nearer the beak and usually stronger but not so much extended longitudinally as the posterior one. Muscular impressions large and strong 1, of about equal size; pallial line parallel with the truncated posterior margin for a short distance below the posterior muscular impression, then bending abruptly forward and continuing subparallel with the shell margin." – Weller (1907) p. 541.

FIGURE 95: *ETE CAROLINENSIS* CONRAD, 1875 A: WELLER (1907) PL. 59 FIG. 5-6 (KMT); B: ANSP 80502 (KWB); C: ANSP 80770 (Kw)

***Etea carolinensis aspera* Stephenson, 1923**

Non *Etea carolinensis* Conrad, 1875. Weller, 1907: p. 541, pl. 59, f. 4-6 = *Etea carolinensis asper* Conrad, 1875.

Veniella (Etea) carolinensis aspera Stephenson, 1923: p. 266, pl. 66, f. 13-15; Richards, 1958: p. 175, pl. 28, f. 6, 7.

Etea carolinensis asper Conrad, 1875. Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 62, 64, 65, 69.

Types – *Etea carolinensis aspera* Stephenson, 1923; Holotype: UNSM 7715

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64, 65.

Description – “Associated with *Veniella (Etea) carolinensis* at several localities are individuals which are proportionately shorter and higher, have more prominent umbones, more sharply defined umbonal ridges, coarser surface sculpture, and are more strongly sinuous on the posterobasal margin than the typical representatives of the species. So far as can be determined with the available collections, these characters are constant, and perhaps deserve to be regarded as of specific importance. Larger collections, however, may reveal a gradation between the longer and shorter forms, and for this reason it seems best to regard the latter as a variety.” – Stephenson (1923) p. 266

FIGURE 96: *ETE CAROLINENSIS ASPERA* STEPHENSON, 1923 A: NJSM 21962 (Kw)

***Etea trapezoidea* (Conrad, 1860)**

Veniella trapezoidea Conrad, 1860: p. 282, pl. 47, f. 7; Gabb, 1861A: p. 234; Meek, 1864: p. 13; Stoliczka, 1866: p. 189; Conrad, 1868: p. 727; Whitfield, 1885: p. 151, pl. 19, f. 3; Whitfield, 1886: p. 151, pl. 19, f. 3; Boyle, 1894: p. 306; Whitfield, 1899: p. 162; Johnson, 1905: p. 13; Richards, 1968: p. 91.

Crassatella monmouthensis Gabb, 1860: p. 302; pl. 48, f. 19 (text lists f. 20); Gabb, 1861A: p. 168; Meek, 1864: p. 11; Conrad, 1868: p. 726; Whitfield, 1885: p. 119, pl. 17, f. 21, 22; Whitfield, 1886: p. 119, pl. 17, f. 21, 22; Boyle, 1893: p. 101; Whitfield, 1899: p. 156; Wingard, 1993: p. 58.

Crassatella lintea Shumard, 1862: p. 201.

Etea monmouthensis (Gabb, 1860). Conrad, 1876.

Veniella subovalis Whitfield, 1885: p. 150, pl. 19, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1886: p. 150, pl. 19, f. 1-2; Johnson, 1905: p. 13.

Crassatellites monmouthensis (Gabb, 1860). Johnson, 1905: p. 14.

Etea trapezoidea (Conrad, 1860). Weller, 1907: p. 543, pl. 58, f. 20-21, pl. 59, f. 7; Rindsberg, 1998.

Veniella (Etea) trapezoidea Conrad, 1860. Richards, 1958: p. 175, pl. 28, f. 8, 9, pl. 29, f. 7, 15.

Types – *Veniella trapezoidea* Conrad, 1860; Holotype: ANSP 18789

Wenonah Specimens –MAPS A2422b.

Description – “The dimensions of an average specimen are length, 26 mm.; height, 18 mm. The specimens sometimes attain a length of 30 mm. or more. Shell very oblique and inequilateral, subtrapezoidal to subelliptical in outline, the beaks situated about one-third the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Anterior margin rounding into the basal margin; basal margin convex anteriorly and sometimes throughout, often somewhat gibbous in the middle, and usually slightly sinuate posteriorly; posterobasal extremity acutely subangular, posterior margin obliquely truncate, the postero-dorsal margin straight or slightly curved, sloping from the beak to the posterior hinge extremity, where it meets the truncated posterior margin in an obtuse angle. Valves with an angular or subcarinate umbonal ridge passing from the beak to the postero-ventral extremity of the

shell; in front of the umbonal ridge is a more or less obscure depression or broad shallow sinus, which passes obliquely backward from the beak to the sinuosity in the ventral margin. The postero-dorsal slope concave to the cardinal margin, where the surface is inflected to form the escutcheon. In front of the beak the surface of the shell is inflected to form the rather large lunule. In the casts the muscular impressions are of moderate size, inconspicuous or somewhat strongly marked, and the free margins are not crenate. Surface of the shell marked by concentric lines of growth which vary in the strength of their development.” - Weller (1907) p. 543.

FIGURE 97: *Etea trapezoidea* (CONRAD, 1860) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 17 FIG. 21; B WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 19 F. 3; C: MAPS 2422B (KW); D: NJSM 19413 (KMV); E: NJSM 21146

***Etea* sp**

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30

GENUS *Tenea* CONRAD, 1870

***Tenea parilis* (Conrad, 1860)**

Mysia parilis Conrad, 1860: p. 278, pl. 46, f. 16 (listed as *Diplodonta parilis* in plate explanation p. 298); Gabb, 1861A: p. 200; Boyle, 1893: p. 188.

Tenea parilis (Conrad, 1860). Conrad, 1871: p. 73. pl. 3, f. 12; Conrad, 1875A: p. A8, pl. 2, f. 25; Boyle, 1893: p. 276; Johnson, 1905: p. 15; Stephenson, 1907: p. 140; Weller, 1907: p. 572, pl. 63, f. 1-6; Gardner, 1916: p. 661; Wade, 1926: p. 83, pl. 26, f. 1; Popenoe, 1937: p. 391; Stephenson, 1941: p. 217, pl. 42, f. 9-12; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 47; Stephenson, 1955: p. 121, pl. 20, f. 8-11; Richards, 1958: p. 218, pl. 31, f. 12, 13; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 141, 144, 147, 150, 154, 156, 160, 162; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65, 69; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 70,73, 79; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 290, f. 264; Sava, 2007: p. 47, pl. 6, f. 5,6; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54, 59; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 91.

Mysia (Tenea) parilis Conrad, 1860. Tyron, 1884: p. 216, pl. 119, f. 72.

Dosinia gabbi Whitfield, 1885: p. 161, 162, pl. 22, f. 4-5; Whitfield, 1886: p. 161, 162, pl. 22, f. 4-5; Boyle, 1893: p. 117; Whitfield, 1899: p. 157; Weller, 1905: p. 333.

Non *Tenea pinguis* (Conrad, 1853). Whitfield, 1885: p. 163, pl. 22, f. 1-2 (f. 3 = *Tenea pinguis* (Conrad, 1853)); Whitfield, 1886: p. 163, pl. 22, f. 1-2 (f. 3 = *Tenea pinguis* (Conrad, 1853)).

Tenea cf. parilis (Conrad, 1860). Kuehne, 1999: p. 64.

Types – *Mysia parilis* Conrad, 1860; Cotype: ANSP 18747

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 572; Richards (1958) p. 218; Kuehne (1999) p. 64; MAPS A2445c.

Description – “Shell in large examples attaining a length and height of 38 mm.; the depth of each valve being 13 mm. The valves more or less strongly and evenly convex, subcircular, obscurely subquadrangular or subovate in outline, beaks prominent, directed forward, slightly incurved. The post-cardinal margin deeply inflected. Each valve furnished with two cardinal teeth and no laterals. Muscular impressions rather large but not deeply impressed, pallial line with a deep, narrow, acutely subangular sinus, whose inner extremity is directed towards a point between the beak and the anterior muscular impression. Surface of the shell nearly smooth, marked only by fine lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 572.

FIGURE 98: *TENEA PARILUS* (CONRAD, 1860) A-C: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 22 FIG. 2,4,5; D: MAPS A24445C (KW); E: ANSP 80438 (KWB)

***Tenea pinguis* (Conrad, 1853)**

Lucinia pinguis Conrad, 1853: p. 275, pl. 24, f. 18; Gabb, 1861A: p. 195; Meek, 1864: p. 12; Conrad, 1868: p. 726.

Mysia gibbosa Gabb, 1860: p. 302, f. 1-2 (not f. 3); Conrad, 1868: p. 726; Boyle, 1893: p. 188.

Tenea pinguis (Conrad, 1853). Gabb, 1876A: p. 307; Whitfield, 1885: p. 163, 164, pl. 22, f. 3 (not figs 1-2); Whitfield, 1886: p. 163, 164, pl. 22, f. 3 (not figs 1-2); Woolman, 1893B: p. 221; Boyle, 1893: p. 276; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 165; Johnson, 1905: p. 15; Weller, 1907: p. 574, pl. 63, f. 7; Stephenson, 1911: p. 176, 180, 182, 185; Dane, 1929: p. 133; Richards, 1958: p. 219, pl. 31, f. 5; Black, 1980: p. 73; Harstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65, 69; Kuehne, 1999, p. 69, 77; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B pl. 1.

Types – *Lucinia pinguis* Conrad, 1853, Holotype: ANSP 18745; *Mysia gibbosa* Gabb, 1860, Holotype: ANSP 18746.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2427e.

Description – “Shell small, the dimensions of one specimen being height, 7 mm.; width, 8 mm.; thickness, 6 mm.; subcircular or obscurely subquadrangular in outline. Valves extremely ventricose or gibbous, giving to the entire shell a nearly globular form. Umbones very prominent, the beaks incurved and directed forward. Surface of the shell marked by somewhat prominent concentric lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 575.

FIGURE 99: *TENEA PINGUIS* (CONRAD, 1853) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 63 F. 7 (KNS) B: MAPS A2427B (KS); C-E: MAPS A2427E (KW)

**GENUS *VENIELLA* STOLICZKA, 1870
Veniella conradi (Morton, 1833)**

Veniella conradi Morton, 1833: p. 294, pl. 8, f. 1-2; Morton, 1834: p. 67, pl. 8, f. 1-2; Gabb, 1859: p. 17; Gabb, 1861A: p. 177 (233); Meek, 1864: p. 13; Conrad, 1868: p. 727; Conard, 1875B: p. A16.

Veniella trigona Gabb, 1862A: p. 324; Meek, 1864: p. 13; Conrad, 1868: p. 727.

Goniosoma inflata Conrad, 1869D: p. 44, pl. 1, f. 10.

Veniella elevata Conrad, 1871: p. 74, pl. 3, f. 7-7a.

Veniella conradi (Morton, 1833). Stoliczka, 1871: p. 190; Meek, 1876: p. 148, text f. 9-11; Whitfield, 1885: p. 144, pl. 19, f. 8-10; Whitfield, 1886: p. 144, pl. 19, f. 8-10; Woolman, 1893B: p. 222; Boyle, 1893: p. 305; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 186; Whitfield, 1899: p. 166; Whitfield, 1901: p. 426; Johnson, 1905: p. 13; Stephenson, 1907: p. 127-129, 130, 135, 136, 140, 143; Weller, 1907: p. 534, pl. 59, f. 1-3; Stephenson, 1911: p. 134, 136, 138, 140, 158, 174, 176, 180, 182; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, table 2-8; Gardner, 1916: p. 643, pl. 38, f. 2-7; Stephenson, 1923: p. 257, pl. 66, f. 1-5; Stephenson, 1926: p. 250, pl. 92, f. 13; Wade, 1926: p. 77, pl. 24, f. 14-16; Adkins, 1928: p. 153; Dane, 1929: p. 109, 133, 147; Thomas and Rice, 1931: p. 318, 321; Stephenson, 1941: p. 168, pl. 27, f. 6-8; Vestal, 1946: p. 56, 59, 63; Vokes, 1954: p. 36-44; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 46; Richards, 1958: p. 173, pl. 26, f. 11, pl. 29, f.14; Stephenson, 1960: p. 18, 22; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 7; Sohl, 1969B: p. 730, f. 6; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36, 42, 46; Black, 1980: p. 73; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 9 t. 2; Gallagher, 1984: p. 27; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 139, 144, 147, 150, 154, 160, 162; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer 1986: p. 17, 30; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65, 66, 69; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Kirby and Saul, 1995: p. 29, 35, pl. 2, f. 2-4; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60-64, 66, 69-73, 76, 77; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 299, 300, f. 273, 274; Gallagher, 2003; p. 27; Hall, 2005: p. 49, t. 8; Lacovara and Gallagher, 2006: p. 18 App. A; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 13, t. 1, t. 1, f. 111; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59; Carter, et. al., 2002: p. 184, f. 323; Gallagher, Camburn, Camburn and Hanczaryk, 2014: p. 67; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 91; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitely, 2016: p. 111, t. 1, pl. 2, f. 15 a-b; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: 61, 62, 72, pl. 4; Witts, Landman, et. al, 2018: f. 10L-M; Gallagher and Hanczaryk, 2019” p. 52; Wick, 2021: p. 118, t. 2.

Veniella elevata (Conrad, 1871): p. 74, pl. 3, f. 7, 7a; Whitfield, 1885: p. 148, pl. 19, f. 6-7; Whitfield, 1886: p. 148, pl. 19, f. 6-7; Boyle, 1893: p. 306; Whitfield, 1899: p. 166; Johnson, 1905: p. 13

Veniella trigona (Gabb, 1862): Whitfield, 1885: p. 149, pl. 19, f. 11-14; Whitfield, 1886: p. 149, pl. 19, f. 11-14; Boyle, 1893: p. 306; Whitfield, 1899: p. 166;

Johnson, 1905: p. 13; Weller, 1907: p. 537, pl. 59, f. 1-3; Richards, 1956: p. 79.

Veniella inflata (Gabb, 1869). Whitfield, 1885: p. 147, pl. 19, f. 4-5; Whitfield, 1886: p. 147, pl. 19, f. 4-5; Boyle, 1893: p. 306; Whitfield, 1899: p. 166; Johnson, 1905: p. 13; Richards, 1958: p. 173, pl. 28, f. 3.

Types – *Veniella conradi* (Morton, 1833); Holotype: ANSP 18787

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 534; Richards (1958) p. 173; Gallagher, et. al. (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64.

Description – “The dimensions of an average sized left valve are length, 26 mm.; height, 23 mm.; convexity, 12 mm. Shell subtrapezoidal in outline. Hinge-line rather strongly curved. Anterior margin straight above, sloping obliquely forward, sharply rounding into the basal margin below; basal margin gently convex, becoming straighter posteriorly; postero-basal extremity angular; posterior margin obliquely truncate; posterior cardinal extremity obtusely angular, becoming rounder in the larger individuals; postero-cardinal margin rather long, straight or slightly convex. Valves very ventricose, with a sharply angular, curved umbonal ridge. Beaks situated nearly as far front as the anterior extremity of the shell, incurved and directed forward. Post-umbonal slope abrupt, with a shallow sinus extending from the beak to the posterior margin of the shell, and a low subangular ridge curving from the beak to the posterior cardinal extremity; anterior slope convex from the umbonal ridge forward, the curvature of the surface becoming much more abrupt as it approaches the anterior margin. Surface of the shell marked by several, strong, concentric varices which become more remote away from the beak, and upon very large individuals become obsolete upon the outer portion of the shell; they are produced into broad, lamellar extensions of the shell and do not continue across the post-umbonal slope. The shell surface is also marked by more or less irregular concentric lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 536.

FIGURE 97A: *Veniella conradi* (Morton, 1833) A-B: Whitfield (1886) pl. 19, f. 9-10; C-D: MAPS A2436a (Kns); E: MAPS A2436b (Ks) ; F: MAPS A2436d (Internal Mold) (Ks); G-H: NJSM 21961 (Kwb)

Veniella sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2535a; MAPS A2535b

FIGURE 100: *VENIELLA* SP. A: MAPS A2535A (Kw); B: MAPS A2535B (Kw)

FAMILY **GLOSSIDAE** GRAY, 1847 (1840)

GENUS **GLOSSUS** POLI, 1795

World Register of Marine Species states *Isocardia* is not an accepted genus and is replaced by *Glossus*. See MOORE 1969 (Treatise Invert Paleo), N657 for *Glossidae* description.

Glossus bulbosa (Stephenson, 1941)

Isocardia bulbosa Stephenson, 1941: 206, pl. 37, f. 4-5; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 7, pl. 2, f. 10; Carey, 1976: p. 228, pl. 13, f. 10; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 7.

Types – *Isocardia bulbosa* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: UNSM 76653; Paratype USNM 76554.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2542b.

Description – “Shell broadly subovate in outline, a little longer than high, strongly convex. Shell wall very thin. A weak, shallow, radial sulcus extends from the beak to the middle of the posterior margin. Beaks prominent, strongly incurved, slightly separated, moderately prosogyrate, situated about two-fifths the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. The anterior part of the shell is strongly bulbous, descending steeply to the anterior margin, and more gently to the posterior margin. Dorsal margin arched; anterior margin sharply rounded; ventral margin

broadly rounded; posterior margin rather sharply rounded below, slightly subtruncated above; posterodorsal margin broadly rounded and much longer than the anterodorsal margin. Lunule and escutcheon wanting; the anterodorsal slope is very steep to slightly overhanging. The surface is nearly smooth with the exception of very fine concentric lines which are a little stronger on the dorsal slopes, and very faint radial lines, best seen in the umbonal region, which are spaced about three to the millimeter and are formed of closely spaced pores visible only under a magnifying glass. The hinge and internal features are not exposed, and the generic identification is made on the basis of the general form, and the characteristic forward twist of the beaks. Dimensions of the holotype, an internal mold with shell attached over more than half of the surface; length 11.6 mm., height 11 mm., thickness 8.5 mm.” – Stephenson (1941) p. 206.

FIGURE 101: *GLOSSUS BULBOSA* (STEPHENSON, 1941) A: MAPS A2524B (Kw)

Glossus cliffwoodensis (Weller, 1905)

Isocardia cliffwoodensis Weller, 1905A1: p. 333, text f. 1-3; Weller, 1905A2: p. 140, text f. 1-3; Weller, 1905B1: p. 135, pl. 15, f. 1-3; Weller, 1905B2: p. 135, pl. 15, f. 1-3; Shattuck, Miller, Bibbins and Walcott: 1907: p. 4; Stephenson, 1907: p. 126, 130; Weller, 1907: p. 598, pl. 66, f. 10-12; Stephenson, 1911: p. 158; Miller, 1911: p. 96; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, 28, 30, 31; Stephenson, 1923: p. 304, pl. 74, f. 1; Richards, 1958: p. 216, pl. 33, f. 18.

Isocardia cf. cliffwoodensis Weller, 1905. Stephenson, 1907: p. 136.

Glossus cliffwoodensis (Weller, 1905). Young, 1977: p. 130.

Types – *Isocardia cliffwoodensis* Weller, 1905; Cotypes: NJSM 9570; 7778.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 598; Richards (1958) p. 216.

Description – “Shell subovate in outline, the dimensions of two type specimens being length, 18.5 mm. and 15.5 mm.; height, 14.5 mm. and 14 mm.; convexity of one valve, 6.5 mm. and 6.5 mm. Anterior margin rounding regularly from beneath the beak into the ventral margin or sometimes a little more sharply rounded in the middle; ventral margin broadly rounded; posterior margin rather sharply rounded below, sloping forward above to the posterior extremity of the hinge-line with a gently convex curvature. Valves ventricose on the umbo, the most prominent portion situated anterior to the middle of the shell, the beaks small, situated anteriorly, strongly incurved and directed forward; the antero-umbonal slope abrupt, the posterior slope convex, becoming more abrupt as it approaches the posterior margin. Surface of the shell smooth.” – Weller (1907) p. 598.

FIGURE 102: *GLOSSUS CLIFFWOODENSIS* (WELLER, 1907) A-C: WELLER (1907) (KMG)

FAMILY MACTRIDAE LAMARCK, 1809

GENUS CYMBOPHORA GABB, 1869

Cymbophora appressa (Gabb, 1876)

Schizodesma appressa Gabb, 1876: p. 306, 307; Boyle, 1893: p. 262; Johnson, 1905: p. 17; Stephenson, 1907: p. 87; Weller, 1907: p. 634, pl. 71, f. 14-16, 20, 21; Stephenson, 1911: p. 137, 139, 140; Stephenson, 1923: p. 339; Richards, 1958: p. 246, pl. 37, f. 8.

Veleda transversa Whitfield, 1885: p. 174, pl. 23, f. 22; Whitfield, 1886: p. 174, pl. 23, f. 22.

Cymbophora appressa (Gabb, 1876). Stephenson, 1923: p. 229, 339; Cooke, 1943: p. 23; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 137, 143, 147, 150, 162; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 30; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89, pl. 1, f. 10; Rindsberg, 1998: Kuehne, 1999: p. 64, 65, 68, 77, 79; Hall, 2005: p. 49, t. 8.

Schizodesma appressa? Gabb, 1876: Cooke, 1943: p. 19.

Types – *Schizodesma appressa* Gabb, 1876; Holotype: USNM 76715.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 634 (*Schizodesma appressa*); Richards (1958) p. 246; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 65; MAPS A2511d.

Description – “The dimensions of an average right valve are length, 23 mm.; height, 15.5 mm., convexity, 4 mm. Shell inequilateral, subovate or ovate-subcuneate in outline. Anterior and posterior cardinal margins meeting at the beak at an angle of about 125; anterior margin regularly rounding from the antero-cardinal margin above into the basal margin below; basal margin gently convex throughout, becoming a little straighter posteriorly; postero-basal extremity subangular; posterior margin shorter than the anterior, obliquely truncate; posterior cardinal extremity obtusely subangular. Beaks prominent, nearly erect, slightly incurved, situated a little in front of the middle of the shell. Valves most prominent on the umbo, sloping rather abruptly to the cardinal margins, the most gentle slope being to the postero-basal extremity; a more or less obscure rounded or subangular umbonal ridge passes from the beak obliquely backward to the postero-basal extremity. Surface of the shell marked by regular, fine, concentric lines, which become regularly

stronger in passing from the beak to the shell margin and becoming nearly obsolete upon the post-umbonal slope.” – Weller (1907) p. 635.

FIGURE 103: CYMBOPHORA APPRESA (GABB, 1876) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 23 FIG. 22; B: WELLER (1907) PL. 71 FIG. 15 (KMG); C: MAPS A2511C (KS); D: MAPS A2511A (Kw); E: MAPS A2511D (Kw)

***Cymbophora lintea* (Conrad, 1860)**

Cardium (Protocardium) linteum Conrad, 1860: p.278, pl. 46, f. 17.

Cardium lintea (Conrad, 1860). Gabb, 1861A: p. 163.

Veleda lintea (Conrad, 1860). Conrad, 1871: p. 74; Conrad, 1875A: p. A9, pl. 1, f. 26; Whitfield, 1885: p. 172, 173, pl. 23, f. 18-21; Whitfield, 1886: p. 172, 173, pl. 23, f. 18-21; Boyle, 1893: p. 305; Clark, 1897: Clark, 1898; Whitfield, 1899: p. 165; Weller, 1905A1: p. 333; Weller, 1905A2: p. 140; Johnson, 1905: p.17; Shattuck, Miller, Bibbins and Walcott, 1907: p. 4; Miller, 1911: p. 96.

Cymbophora lintea (Conrad, 1860). Gabb, 1876A: p. 306; Conrad, 1877: p. 24; Boyle, 1893P. 107; Johnson, 1905: p. 17; Weller, 1907: p. 632, pl. 71, f. 12-13 (not pl. 71, f. 9-11 = *Cymbophora trigonalis*); Stephenson, 1907: p. 136, 140, 143; Stephenson, 1911: p. 120, 129, 133, 134, 139, 156, 158, 177, 179, 180, 182, 185, 192; Stephenson, 1914: p. 27, 29, 30,

35; Dorf and Fox, 1957: p. 4; Richards, 1958: p. 244, pl. 35, f. 15, 16; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 31, 68, 182; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60; Hall, 2005: p. 44, t. 5, p. 54, t. 11; Ebersole, 2009: p. 53, 134.

Cymbophora cf. lintea (Conrad, 1860). Kuehne, 1995: p. 85.

Types – *Cardium (Protocardium) linteum* Conrad, 1860; Holotype?

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 632; Richards (1958) p. 244.

Description – “The dimensions of two separate valves of this species, the larger specimen a right and the smaller a left valve, are length, 18.5 mm. and 16 mm.; height, 15 mm. and 13 mm.; convexity, 5 mm. and 3.5 mm. Shell ovate-subtriangular in outline. The anterior and posterior cardinal margins meeting at the beak in an angle of about 110, curving regularly into the anterior and posterior margins below; anterior margin rather sharply rounded, its greatest extent below the mid-height of the shell; ventral margin broadly convex; posterior margin more or less sharply rounded or somewhat pointed below, oblique above, subtruncate or gently convex. Beaks a little in front of the middle of the shell or sometimes nearly central in position, slightly incurved, pointing forward, elevated a little above the hinge-line. Valves moderately convex, with a more or less obscure umbonal ridge extending obliquely from the beak to the postero-basal extremity; post-umbonal slope rather abrupt, central portion of the valve gently convex, the anterior and posterior cardinal slopes about equally abrupt. In the casts the umbonal ridge is usually rounded, while in the shell itself it is often slightly angular. Surface of the shell marked with regular concentric lines, which are very fine in the young shells, becoming much stronger with the increased size of the shell. In the larger shells the surface markings seem sometimes to have been nearly or quite eroded, leaving the shell nearly smooth.” – Weller (1907) p. 632.

FIGURE 104: *CYMBOPHORA LINTEA* (CONRAD, 1860) A-C: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 23 FIG. 18,19,21 ("LOWER GREEN MARLS"); D: ANSP 16258 (KWB)

Cymbophora tellinoides (Whitfield, 1885)

Veleda tellinoides Whitfield, 1885: p. 173, pl. 23, f. 23;
Whitfield, 1886: p. 1732, pl. 23, f. 23.

Cymbophora tellinoides (Whitfield, 1885). Weller, 1907: p. 633, pl. 71, f. 22; Richards, 1958: p. 245, pl. 37, f. 7.

Types – *Veleda tellinoides* Whitfield, 1885; Holotype: NJSM 9768

Wenonah Specimens – Whitfield (1885) p. 173, pl. 23, f. 2; Weller (1907) p. 633 pl. 71, f. 2; Richards (1958) p. 245 pl. 37, f. 7; NJSM 9768.

Description - "Shell large for the genus, the cast, the only form under which it is known, being fully one and a quarter inch in length; form transversely ovate, largest at the anterior end, and two-thirds as high as long. Valves depressed convex with small appressed beaks and a slight angulation passing from the beak to the posterior extremity, forming a narrow posterior cardinal slope. Surface, as shown on the cast, marked by fine concentric lines of growth. Muscular scars proportionally large and moderately distinct, and an indication of a rather deep sinus in the pallial line." – Whitfield (1886) p. 173.

FIGURE 105: *CYMBOPHORA TELLINOIDES* (WHITFIELD, 1885) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 23 FIG. 23; B: NJSM 9768 (KW)

FAMILY TRAPEZIDAE LAMY, 1920

GENUS TRAPEZIUM VON MUHLFELD, 1811

Trapezium truncata Stephenson, 1923

Trapezium truncatum Stephenson, 1923: p. 267, pl. 74, f. 2-5; Eley, 1938; Wick, 2021 p. 118, t. 2.

Types – *Trapezium truncatum* Stephenson, 1923; Holotype: USNM 31780.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2518c.

Description – "Shell very thin, fragile and easily shattered; moderately large, strongly ventricose, suboval in general outline. Beaks prominent, small, strongly incurved, the tips moderately distant, prosogyrate, situated a little in advance of the midlength. An angular umbonal ridge extends from the beak to the lower posterior extremity, separating the steeply inclined, deeply concave postero-dorsal slope from the main body of the shell. A broad, shallow depression originates on the umbo and extends radially to the postero-ventral margin, parallel to and just in front of the umbonal ridge. Antero-dorsal slope abrupt, deeply excavated toward the beak. Dimensions of the type: length 36 mm., height 33 mm., convexity 14

mm. 85 268 Cretaceous Formations of North Carolina Ligamental groove external, snort (5 or 6 mm.). Anterodorsal and posterodorsal margins diverging from the apex at an angle of about 130 degrees, the former nearly straight, the latter long and gently convex away from the apex. Anterior margin regularly and rather sharply rounded; ventral margin broadly rounded anteriorly, becoming a little concave posteriorly, meeting the posterior margin almost at a right angle; posterior margin squarely truncated vertically. Surface smooth with the exception of fine concentric incremental lines." – Stephenson (1923) p. 267

FIGURE 106: *TRAPEZIUM TRUNCATUM* (MEEK, 1871) A-D: MAPS A2518c (Kw)

FAMILY VENERIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815
GENUS APHRODINA CONRAD, 1869B
***Aphrodina eufaulensis* (Conrad, 1860)**

Callista eufaulensis Conrad, 1860: p. 282, pl. 46, f. 24; Gabb, 1861A: p. 161; Whitfield, 1901: p. 413 (cat. 5285).

Callista delawarensis Gabb. 1861A: p. 161; Gabb, 1862C: p. 105; Whitfield, 1885: p. 153, pl. 22, f. 10 (not pl. 22, f. 8-9 = *Dione delawarensis*); Whitfield, 1886: p. 153, pl. 22, f. 10 (not pl. 22, f. 8-9 = *Dione delawarensis*); Woolman, 1893B: p. 221; Boyle, 1893: p. 70; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 186.

Dione eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Meek, 1864: p. 13.

Meretrix eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Weller, 1907: 609, pl. 68, f. 8-10; Wade, 1926: p. 89, pl. 28, f. 3-4; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 59.

Aphrodina eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Richards, 1958: p. 226, pl. 34, f. 6, 7; Kuehne, 1999: p. 62; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 91; Groves and Squires, 2018: p. 31.

Aphrodina cf. eufaulensis (Conrad, 1860). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 46.

Types – *Callista eufaulensis* Conrad, 1860; Holotype: AMNH 5285.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 609; Richards (1958) p. 46; ANSP 81026.

Description - "The dimensions of a very perfect left valve are height, 1.6 mm.; length, 19 mm.; convexity, 4 mm. Shell subovate in outline; the beaks at about the anterior third, rather small, directed anteriorly, scarcely incurved. Antero-cardinal margin concave just in front of the beak; anterior, ventral, posterocardinal margins convex; the posterior margin broader than the anterior. Valves regularly convex, the surface sloping more abruptly to the cardinal margins; in front of the beaks is a narrow, scarcely impressed lunule. Hinge of the left valve with two cardinal teeth diverging from beneath the beak, leaving a triangular pit between, and a much thinner, more elongate tooth directed obliquely backward close up to the ligamental area; in front of the cardinal teeth is a single strong lateral tooth beneath the lunule, parallel with the shell margin. Surface of the shell marked by fine, concentric striae of growth, those covering the area from the beak downward about 10 or 12 millimeters are very regular, the interspaces gradually increasing until the outer ones are about one-half millimeter apart. Beyond this regularly marked area the lines of growth are less conspicuous and not so regular." – Weller (1907) p. 609.

FIGURE 107: *APHRODINA EUFULENSIS* (CONRAD, 1860) A: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 23 FIG. 2, 3; B: WELLER (1907) PL. 68 FIG. 9-10 (KMT); C: ANSP 81026 (KW)

***Aphrodina tippana* (Conrad, 1858)**

Meretrix tippana Conrad, 1858A: p. 326, pl. 34, f. 18; Gabb, 1859; p. 13; Gabb, 1861A: p. 142; Whiteaves, 1879: p. 149; Boyle, 1893: p. 183; Weller, 1907: p. 607, pl. 68, f. 1-2 (not pl. 68, f. 3 = *Aphrodina tippana jerseyensis* Richards, 1958); Jukes-Brown, 1908: p. 156; Saul, 1993: p. 972.

Dione tippana (Conrad, 1858). Meek, 1864: p. 13.

Aphrodina tippana (Conrad, 1858). Conrad, 1868: p. 727; Conrad, 1869B: p. 246, pl. 18, f. 5; Whiteaves, 1879: p. 149; not Whitfield, 1885: p. 154, f. 6, 7 = *Aphrodina tippana jerseyensis* Richards, 1958; not Whitfield, 1886: p. 154, f. 6, 7 = *Aphrodina tippana jerseyensis* Richards, 1958: p. 154; Woolman, 1893B: p. 221; Boyle, 1893: p. 47; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 186; Johnson, 1905: p. 16; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Stephenson, 1907: p. 138; Condra, 1908: p. 91; Stephenson, 1911: p. 177, 180, 182; Stephenson, 1923: p. 314, pl. 79, f. 1-6; Wade, 1926: p. 89, pl. 28, f. 5-7; Adkins, 1928: p. 163; Wrather, 1933: p. 163; Frizzell, 1936: p. 23; Stephenson and Monroe, 1940: pl. 12, f.5-6; Stephenson, 1941: p. 208, pl. 39, f. 1-3, pl. 40, f. 5-6; Cooke, 1943B: p. 29, 36; Stephenson, 1955: p. 120, pl. 20, f. 2-4; Katto and Hattori, 1961: p. 8;

Swift, 1966: p. 32, f. 7; Richards, 1968: p. 90; Wolleben, 1977: p. 387; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 13, 15, 24, 30, 49, 121; Saul, 1993: p. 972; Rindsberg, 1998; Kuehne, 1999: p. 69, 74, 77, 79; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 54, 59; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 13, t. 1, f. 11L, p. 20, f. 11M; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 7; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 91; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 53, App. B, pl. 1; Witts, Landman, Garb, Boas, Larina, Rovelli, Edwards, Sherrell and Cochran, 2018: f. 10 I-J; Wick, 2021: p. 113, t. 2.

Antigona (Aphrodina) tippana (Conrad, 1858). Gardner, 1916: p. 681, pl. 40, f. 3, 4; Akers and Akers, 2002: p. 312, f. 286, p. 313, f. 287.

Meretrix cf. tippana Conrad, 1858A. Whitfield, 1885: p. 154; Whitfield, 1886: p. 154; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 47.

Aphrodina cf. tippana (Conrad, 1858). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 42.

Types – *Meretrix tippana* Conrad, 1858; Holotype: ANSP 4135.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 607.

Description – “The dimensions of a specimen from Ripley Mississippi, preserving the shell are height, 28 mm.; length, 35 mm.; convexity, 8 mm. Shell subovate in outline. Anterocardinal margin concave in front of the beak, from in front of this concave portion entirely around the shell to the posterior side of the beak, the margin is convex. Beaks nearly central or in front of the center of the shell, directed forward, scarcely incurved. Valves regularly convex, the surface curving more abruptly to the cardinal margin, with a rather broad, scarcely impressed lunule in front of the beak. Hinge of the left valve with three cardinal teeth diverging from beneath the beak, the anterior one curving forward and becoming thickened below, the posterior one much more oblique than the others and more elongate. In front of the cardinal teeth is a single weak lateral beneath the lunule, parallel with the shell margin. In the right valve are two divergent, cardinal teeth, the posterior one becoming thickened below with a longitudinal sinus, beneath the lunule is a pit for the reception of the anterior lateral tooth of the opposite valve. Surface of the shell marked by fine, more or less regular, concentric lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 607.

FIGURE 108: *APHRODINA TIPPANA* (CONRAD, 1869) A: WELLER (1907) PL. 68 FIG. 1-2 (USNM 20690, TNKr); B: ANSP 80471 (KWB)

***Aphrodina tippana jerseyensis* Richards, 1958**

Non *Aphrodina tippana* (Conrad, 1858). Whitfield, 1885: p. 154, f. 6, 7; Whitfield, 1886: p. 154, f. 6, 7.

Non *Meretrix tippana* (Conrad, 1858). Weller, 1907: p. 607 (part) pl. 68, f. 3 (not pl. 68, f. 1, 2 = *Aphrodina tippana* (Conrad, 1858)).

Aphrodina tippana jerseyensis Richards, 1958: p. 224, pl. 34, f. 5; Kuehne, 1993: p. 64; Kuehne, 1995: p. 85; Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 61, 64.

Types – *Aphrodina tippana jerseyensis* Richards, 1958; Syntype: ANSP 19408.

Wenonah Specimens – ANSP 56698.

Description – “Various poorly preserved casts have been referred to *A. tippana* Conrad, but as pointed out by Gardner and others, the New Jersey specimens seem to show at least a subspecific difference. The subspecific name *jerseyensis* is therefore proposed for these specimens. They differ from the typical *A. tippana* in their shorter, relatively higher outline and the less produced, more broadly rounded posterior end. The type specimen measures 33.0 mm by 26.5 mm. and was collected by T. A. Conrad” – Richards (1958) p. 224.

FIGURE 109: *APHRODINA TIPPANA JERSEYENSIS* RICHARDS, 1958 A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 22 FIG. 6-7; WELLER (1907) PL. 68 F. 3 (KMW)

***Aphrodina* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64

GENUS *CYPRIMERIA* CONRAD, 1864

***Cyprimeria welleri* Stephenson, 1923**

Non *Cyprimeria cretacensis* (Conrad, 1860 = *Sanguinolaria cretacensis*). Weller, 1907: p. 604, pl. 67, f. 7-8.

Cyprimeria welleri Stephenson, 1923: p. 304, pl. 74, f. 14; Richards, 1958: p. 223, pl. 34, f. 1, 2; Kuehne, 1999: p. 64.

Types – *Cyprimeria welleri* Stephenson, 1923; Holotype: USNM 31787.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 604; Richards (1958) p. 223.

Description – “Shell moderately thick, broadly subovate in outline, depressed convex, bent a little to the left posteriorly. Beak very small, not prominent, pointing forward, situated about 0.45 the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Dimensions of the type: Length 42 mm., height 35 mm. Hinge normal. Antero-dorsal margin broadly arched; anterior margin broadly and regularly curved; ventral margin very broadly and regularly curved; posterior extremity slightly narrower than the anterior and slightly truncated, the truncation inclining slightly forward; postero-dorsal margin truncated or only slightly convex, inclined at a small angle from the

horizontal. Surface slightly waterworn, but apparently marked by fine incremental lines which become a little coarse toward the base.” – Stephenson (1923) p. 304.

FIGURE 110: *CYPRIMERIA WELLERI* STEPHENSON, 1923 A-B: WELLER (1907) PL. 68 FIG. 7 (KWB); C-D: RICHARDS (1958) PL. 34 F. 1-2 (KWB)

Cyprimeria sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer, (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2496f

FIGURE 111: *CYPRIMERIA* SP. A-C: MAPS A2496F (KW)

GENUS **LEGUMEN** CONRAD, 1858

Legumen concentricum Stephenson, 1923

Legumen appressum Whitfield, 1885: p. 185, pl. 25, f. 6-8; Whitfield, 1886: p. 185, pl. 25, f. 6-8.

Non Legumen planulatum (Conrad, 1853). Weller, 1907: p. 612, pl. 69, f. 7, questionably f. 5, 6 (not f. 3, 4 = *L. ellipticum* Conrad, 1858).

Legumen concentricum Stephenson, 1923: p. 319-321: pl. 80, f. 6-9; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 48; Richards, 1958: p. 227, pl. 36, f. 1, 2; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 36; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 8; Gallagher, 1984: p. 15; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 77; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016; p. 54, App B, pl. 1.

Types – *Legumen concentricum* Stephenson, 1923; Holotype: USNM 31798.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2401e; ANSP 81025.

Description – “Shell thin, greatly elongated, subelliptical, inequilateral, compressed; beaks not prominent, approximate, somewhat variable in position on different individuals, but as a rule situated about one-fourth the length of the shell from the anterior extremity. Dimensions of the type: Length 43 mm., height 16 mm., 3 mm. Dimensions of another larger specimen: Length 71 mm., height 22 mm., convexity 3.5 mm. Dental formula L. 10101 / R. 010101. The posterior cardinal tooth of the right valve is narrowly bifid and very oblique, being nearly parallel to the postero-dorsal margin; the two anterior cardinals are close together, prominent, nearly vertical, and separated from the posterior cardinal by a wide, deep socket with floor sloping to the interior of the shell. Lateral teeth wanting. The anterior cardinal tooth of the left valve is set between two profound sockets; the two posterior cardinals are long, oblique, narrow, and are separated by a narrow socket not as deep as the two anterior sockets. Neither lunule nor escutcheon is present. Ligamental groove deeply impressed, extending about one third the distance to the posterior extremity. Postero-dorsal margin long, straight, nearly horizontal; posterior margin sharply rounded; ventral margin long, slightly convex, nearly parallel with the postero-dorsal margin; anterior margin more sharply rounded than the posterior; antero-dorsal margin descending, slightly convex. The outline of the shell varies somewhat in form on different individuals. Surface

marked by strong, nearly regular, concentric ridges, separated by narrow, rather deeply impressed depressions; the ridges are wider on the posterior portion of the shell and on the posterodorsal slope of the large individuals assume the form of imbricating lamellae." – Stephenson (1923) p. 320.

FIGURE 112: *LEGUMEN CONCENTRICUM* STEPHENSON, 1923
A-B: WHITFIELD (1886) PL. 25 FIG. 6-7; C-D: WELLER (1907)
PL. 69 F. 3-4 (KNS); E: MAPS A2401E (KW); F: ANSP
81025 (KW)

Legumen sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2403c

FIGURE 113: *LEGUMEN* SP. A: MAPS A2403c (KW)

Class **GASTROPODA** Cuvier, 1795
 SUBCLASS **CAENOGASTROPODA** Cox, 1960
 FAMILY **EPITONIIDAE** BERRY, 1910
 GENUS **ACIRSA (HEMIACIRSA)** DE BOURY, 1890
Acirsa (Hemiacirsa) cretacea (Wade, 1917)

Hemiacirsa cretacea Wade, 1917: p. 301, pl 19, f. 3;
 Cossman, 1918: p. 21; Wade, 1926: p. 170, pl. 55, f.
 9.

Acirsa (Hemiacirsa) cretacea (Wade, 1917). Cossman,
 1925: p. 280, pl. 8, f. 1; Sohl, 1964: p. 313, pl. 51, f.
 22; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 64; Bandel and
 Dockery, 2016: p. 47.

Types – *Hemiacirsa cretacea* Wade, 1917; Holotype:
 USNM 32951

Synonyms – *Hemiacirsa cretacea* Wade, 1917

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2592a.

Description – “Shell fairly large for the group, slender,
 turreted and conical in outline; spire acuminate; spire
 of the type slightly curved, possibly an individual
 characteristic due to three accidents in the life of the
 animal, each of which resulted in the breaking of the
 shell (as scars on the type specimen show) on the
 same side of the spire or possibly a specific character
 of this many whorled form; whorls flattened, very
 closely appressed posteriorly, less tightly coiled
 toward the aperture; whorls twelve and a half on the
 imperfect type, at least two have been broken away,
 volutions increasing gradually in size; protoconch
 unknown; sculpture dominantly axial, axial costae
 abruptly elevated and subangular on the crests,
 somewhat flexuous, costae sixteen in number on the
 body of the type, regularly spaced, persistent from
 suture to suture on the whorls of the spire, interaxial
 spaces concave and a little wider than the costae;
 spiral sculpture subdued but well defined in the
 interaxial depressions, consisting of eleven on the
 body whorl and about the same number on the
 whorls of the spire; spiral lines on base of body very
 faint; suture impressed; base of body nearly flat;
 angular edge between base and sides of body well
 rounded; aperture ovate; margin of outer lip broken
 away; inner lip strongly and smoothly excavated
 medially; parietal wall washed with thin glaze of
 callus; columella smooth. Dimensions (apex of
 individual broken away) – Altitude 39.4mm.;
 maximum diameter 11.1 mm.” – Wade (1917) p. 301.

1 cm

FIGURE 114: *ACIRSA (HEMIACIRSA) CRETACEA* WADE, 1917
 A: MAPS A2592A (Kw)

GENUS **BELLISCALA** STEPHENSON, 1941
Belliscala sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2888d

2 cm

FIGURE 115: IMPRESSION OF *BELLISCALA* SP. A:
 MAPS A2888D (Kw)

GENUS **STRIATICOSTATUS** SOHL, 1963**Striaticostatus** sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30

Striaticostatus sillimani (Morton, 1834)

Scalaria sillimani Morton, 1834: p. 47, pl. 13, f. 9; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 138, pl. 18, f. 2; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 138, pl. 18, f. 2; Woolman, 1893: p. 221; Boyle, 1893: p. 258; Clark, 1897: p.331; Clark, 1898: p. 180; Whitfield, 1899: p. 175; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Richards, 1968: p. 187.

Scala sillimani (Morton, 1834). Gabb, 1859: p. 6; Gabb, 1861: p. 138; Meek, 1864: p. 20; Johnson, 1905: p. 20; Crider, 1906: p. 17; Weller, 1907: p. 672, pl. 76, f. 2-3; Stephenson, 1911: p. 182; Stephenson, 1914: tab. 2, 4, 5, 6, 8; Richards and Ramsell, 1962: p. 6, pl. 50, f. 3

Scalaria? sillimani Morton, 1834. Owen, 1860: pl. 8, f. 7.

Non Scala sillimani (Morton, 1834). Wade, 1926: 168 (= *Epitonium pondi* Stephenson, 1941).

Non Scalaria spillmani Aldrich, 1885: p. 154.

Striaticostatium sillimani (Morton, 1834). Sohl, 1964A: p. 319, pl. 52, f. 11,17,22; Kuehne, 1999: p. 72.

Types – *Scalaria sillimani* Morton, 1834; Holotype: ANSP 15498

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 672; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 6.

Description.—"Shell of medium size, measuring nearly one inch in length and rapidly tapering, the apical angle being about 30° or 35°; volutions five or more, very round and full, hut closely compacted; the suture line deep and sharp, but close; aperture (as shown on the only specimen in hand, which is a matrix containing the shell of one side of the specimen in place and from which a gutta-percha cast is taken for description and figure), is round, but the margin is not preserved; surface of the shell marked by oblique varices, which have a slightly backward direction in crossing from the upper to the lower side of the volution; the varices are thin and recurved, and number eight on one-half of the circumference of the last volution, but decrease somewhat in number toward the apex of the spire; axis imperforate: the base of the last volution bordered by a raised carina, below which the varices do not appear to extend. So

far as can be ascertained from the specimen, I should judge that the varices were slightly produced in the upper part to form subspines around the base of the preceding volution. The minute surface character of the shell cannot be ascertained from the specimen in use, as only the inside of the substance is revealed, but Dr. Morton describes it as marked by 'very minute spiral striae,' which one would suppose would naturally be the case. Mr. Gabb also speaks of it having 'much finer' revolving striae than his *Scala (Opalia) Thomasi*, which is also a New Jersey species, and says that 'each rib is reflected back into a little lip or notch at the angle of the basal varina.'" – Whitfield (1892) p. 138.

"The dimensions of a large specimen are height, 31 mm.; maximum diameter, 18 mm." – Richards (1962) p. 7.

"Diagnosis – Medium-sized shells with short whorls; pleural angle 26 – 28 degrees. Whorls bear 16-18 thin close spaced transverse ribs per whorl." – Sohl (1964) p. 319.

FIGURE 116: STRIATICOSTATUS SILLIMANI SP. A: NJSM 18425 (Kns)

FAMILY **TURRITELLIDAE** LOVEN, 1847GENUS **SOHLITELLA** SERNA, 1979

Species of *Turritella* were described by Sohl (1960, pls. 7, 8), but Sohl (1964b) later placed *T. bilira* and *T. trilira* in the genus *Haustator*. Serna (1979) p. 24

placed *T. quadrilira*, *T. trilira* and *T. bilira* species recognized as *Haustator* by Sohl (1964b) in a new genus *Sohlitella*.

***Sohlitella bilira* (Stephenson, 1941)**

Turritella bilira Stephenson, 1941: p. 288, pl. 52, f. 9-16; Sohl, 1960: p. 73, pl. 7, f. 16, 23; Minard, 1974: tb. 4; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89, pl. 2, f. 21; Dockery, 1993: p. 48; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 85, 281; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 14, t. 1, p. 20, f. 9A, 9B.

Sohlitella bilira (Stephenson, 1941). Serna, 1979: p. 23; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 42.

Turritella (Sohlitella) bilira Stephenson, 1941. Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 12, 14, 21, 34, 44, 46, 89, 96, 127, 130, 144-151, 153-156, 161, 163, 177, 178, 183, 189, 192, 194, 196, 204, 208, 217, 220, 225, 227, 230, 234, 235, 239; Sohl and Koch, 1984B: p. 135, 137, 142, 144, 151, 154, 157, 160, 162.

Haustator bilira (Stephenson, 1941). Kuehne, 1999: p. 71, 72, 76, 77.

Types – *Turritella bilira* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 76867, Paratype: USNM 76868; Hypotype: 76870.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2838d.

Description – “Shell of small to medium size for the genus. Apical angle 28 to 30 degrees, decreasing to about 20 degrees on the larger whorls below. Whorls about 12 (estimated) in a specimen the size of the incomplete holotype. Protoconch not preserved, but obviously very small. Suture closely appressed lying a little below the middle of a deep, broadly U-shaped channel; this channel is noticeably wider on then some individuals than on others. The ornamentation consists of two prominent spiral lirae which vary in thickness on different individuals from thin and sharp to nearly three-quarters of a millimeter, with rounded crests. The interspace between the two lirae is broadly U-shaped to flattish on the bottom. The periphery of the body whorl is marked by a narrow carina, against which the succeeding whorl fits tightly as growth proceeds, in such a manner that the carina is not apparent in the bottom of the sutural depression. The growth lines are strongly concave in trend toward the aperture, the deepest part of the curve being at the intersection of the upper of the two lirae. Base on body whorl broadly excavated. Aperture subcircular, peristome entire, slightly flaring

in the adult. Dimensions of the slightly incomplete medium-sized holotype: Height 19.2 mm., diameter 6.7 mm.; the larger shells reach diameters of 12 mm. or more.” – Stephenson (1941) p. 288.

FIGURE 117: *SOHLITELLA BILIRA* (STEPHENSON, 1941) A: MAPS A2838d (Kw)

***Sohlitella trilira* (Conrad, 1860)**

Turritella trilira Conrad, 1860: p. 285; Gabb, 1861A: p. 147; Meek, 1864: p. 18; Boyle, 1893: p. 295; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Veatch, 1906: pl. 11, f. 4; Stephenson, 1907: p. 122, 130, 154; Weller, 1907: p. 699, pl. 79, f. 4-5; Stephenson, 1911: p. 138, 140, 174, 177, 178, 185, 187, 191, 192; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2,5,6,8; Gardner, 1916: p. 489; Stephenson, 1923: p. 360, pl. 90, f. 2-9; Stephenson, 1926: p. 250, pl. 92, f. 15; Wade, 1926: p. 161, pl. 56, f. 3; Adkins, 1928: p. 181, 184; Dane, 1929: p. 109, 133; Thomas and Rice, 1931; Stephenson and Monroe, 1940: pl. 15, f. 7; Stephenson, 1941: p. 286, pl. 52, f. 1-5; Cooke, 1943: p. 20, 30, 33; Shimer and Shrock, 1944: p. 493, pl. 201, f. 13; Vestal, 1946: p. 62; Stephenson, 1960: p. 18,22; Sohl, 1960: p. 71, pl. 7, f. 8, 10, 17, 20, 27, 28; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 23, pl. 51, f. 11; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 9; Myers, 1968: p. 71, pl. 14, f. 8; Carey, 1976: p. 220, pl. 9, f. 3; Wollenben, 1977: p. 393, pl. 3, f. 17; Black, 1980: p. 74; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65, 69; Dockery, 1993: p. 49, pl. 8, f. 1-4; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 87,283; Perrilliat, Vega and Corona, 200: p. 12, f. 5.22; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 61; Ebersole,

2009: p. 52; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1; Wick, 2021: p. 119, t. 2.

Turritella corsicanna Shumard, 1861: p. 196; Meek, 1864: p. 18; Hill, 1887: p. 295; Boyle, 1893: p. 294.

Turritella trilineata Smith, 1817. Hill, 1901: pt. 7, pl. 48, f. 3; Hill and Vaughn, 1902: f. 47.

Haustator trilira (Conrad, 1860). Sohl, 1964B: p. 361, pl. 54, f. 15; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 47; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 19, f. 8; Kuehne, 1999: p. 70, 73, 75, 79.

Turritella (*Sohlitella*) *trilira* Conrad, 1860: Serna, 1979: p. 23; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 12, 14-17, 21, 25, 28, 31, 41, 44, 56, 57, 61, 71, 73, 84, 87, 88, 100, 107, 117, 119, 126, 130, 133, 140, 141, 145, 151, 153, 163, 166-169, 171, 173, 175, 177, 178, 180, 189, 193, 196-199, 201, 206, 208, 218, 225, 227, 230, 232; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 10, t. 2; Sohl and Koch, 1984B: p. 135, 137, 140, 142, 144, 147, 151, 154, 157, 160; Elder, 1996: p. 264, f. 7, 8.

Sohlitella trilira Conrad, 1860: Serna, 1979: p. 23; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 42.

Types – *Turritella trilira* Conrad, 1860; Holotype: ANSP? Plesiotypes: USNM 76864- 76866; Hypotypes: 73637, 76865-76866, 128422-128423, 1315601.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 699 pl. 79, f. 5; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 23 pl. 51, f. 11 (NJSM 7698).

Description – “Shell with an apical angle of about 27 degrees; the figured specimen 36 mm. in length, with a maximum diameter of 13.5 mm., and showing seven volutions. The specimen is incomplete at both ends, and when complete it must have been 60 mm. or more in length, with 14 or more volutions. Suture situated near the middle of a rather broad, depressed, concave channel of moderate depth, the lower slope of the channel being less abrupt than the upper and with a slight revolving rib midway of the slope; the greatest depth of the sutural furrow lies a little above the suture itself. Surface of the volutions, between the margins of the sutural furrow, flat and marked by three strong, revolving, angular ribs of equal strength, with rounded interspaces.” – Weller (1907) p. 699.

FIGURE 118: SOHLITELLA TRILIRA (CONRAD, 1860) A: ANSP 80455 (KWB); B: WELLER (1907) PL. 79 FIG. 5 (KWB); C-D: NJSM 7698 (Kw)

GENUS TURRITELLA LAMARCK, 1799
***Turritella austini* Stephenson, 1941**

Turritella austini Stephenson, 1941: p. 291, 292, pl. 54, f. 4-6; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 85, 281; Brooks, Danilova and Garb, 2012: f. 9.

Types – *Turritella austini* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 76883; Paratypes: 76884-76885

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2880b.

Description – “Shell thin, of moderate size, elongate conical, with an apical angle of about 18 degrees. Sides of whorls plumply rounded, fullest below. Suture closely appressed and occupying a deep depression, the upper or posterior slope of which is the steeper. The ornamentation consists of 8 or 9 narrow, sharp non-prominent, spiral primary ribs, with smaller, equally sharp, secondary ribs in the interspaces; the obscure beginnings of tertiary ribs

may be faintly seen in places in the smaller subspaces; fine, sharp ribs of secondary and tertiary strength produce a fine lining on the opposing slopes of the sutural depression; there is some unevenness in the spacing of the spirals, the anterior ones being a little more widely spaced than the posterior ones. The base is flattish, descending abruptly to the columella, and appears to be nearly smooth, although fine, obscure, microscopic, spiral lines may be faintly seen on one specimen; the base is bounded at the angular periphery by a sharp, moderately prominent carina. The aperture is not well preserved. The dimension of the holotype, an incomplete specimen slightly distorted by a calcite vein, are, Height 23+ mm., diameter 11.5mm. The largest paratype has a diameter of 13 mm. The species is characterized by the plumpness of the whorls, and by the fine, sharp, subregular system of spiral lirae." – Stephenson (1941) p. 291.

FIGURE 119: *TURRITELLA AUSTINI* STEPHENSON, 1941 A: MAPS A2880B (CAST) (Kw); B-D: MAPS A2880B (MOLD) (Kw)

***Turritella vertebroides* Morton, 1834**

Turritella vertebroides Morton, 1834: p. 47, pl. 3, f. 13; Gabb, 1859: p. 9; Lea 1861: p. 15; Gabb, 1861: p. 148; Meek, 1864: p. 19; Conrad, 1868: p. 729; Woolman, 1892: p. 146; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 146, pl. 18, f. 13-15; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 146, pl. 18, f. 13-15; Clark, 1893B: p. 197; Woolman, 1893B: p. 220; Clark, 1897: p. 331, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 180, 186; Whitfield, 1899: p. 176; Johnson, 1905: p. 21; Crider 1906: p. 21; Weller, 1907: p. 693, pl. 78, f. 15-16; Stephenson, 1907: p. 127-128; Miller, 1911: pl. 5, f. 5; Stephenson, 1911: p. 177, 178, 211; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2, 3, 5, 6, 8; Clark, Berry and Gardner, 1916: p. 182; Stephenson, 1923: p. 367, pl. 91 f. 12-14; Wade, 1926: p. 160, pl. 56, f. 1, 5; Adkins, 1928: p. 183-184; Dane, 1929: p. 133; Cooke, 1943: p. 30; Shimmer and Shrock, 1944: p. 491, pl. 202 f. 9-12; Stephenson, 1955A: p. 126, pl. 22 f. 16-19; Richards, 1956: p. 79; Sohl, 1960: p. 75, pl. 8 f. 1-4, 12; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 19, pl. 49, f. 9, pl. 50, f. 5; Toots and Cutler, 1962B: p. 9, pl. 2, f. 6, 7; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 9; Swift, 1966: p. 32, f. 7; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 47; Feldman, 1977: p. 90; Wollenben, 1977: p. 393, pl. 3, f. 14-15; Black, 1980: p. 74; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 11, 14, 15, 19, 21, 23, 25, 26, 28, 31, 39, 40-42, 56, 57, 60, 61, 66, 68, 71, 73, 78, 82, 84, 87-89, 93, 98, 100, 101, 110, 113, 117, 119, 122, 123, 130, 133, 135, 140, 141, 145-149, 151, 155, 158, 160, 161, 165, 168, 169, 171, 173-175, 177, 178, 180, 184-187, 189, 192, 201, 218, 220, 222, 232, 235; Gallagher, 1984: p. 25, 27; Sohl and Koch, 1984A: p. 12, 13, 17, 18, 26, 31, 46, 47, 49, 51, 52, 67, 74, 76, 78, 82, 84-86, 97, 101, 102, 109, 111, 113, 114, 116, 119, 130, 137, 143, 146, 147, 157, 198, 245, 281; Sohl and Koch, 1984B: p. 135, 140, 154, 160; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 17; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Dockery, 1993: p. 50, pl. 8, f. 5; Dunagan and Gibson, 1993: p. 89; Vega, Feldman and Sour-Tovar, 1995: p. 347, t. 1, 2; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 86, 283; Kuehne, 1999: p. 69-71, 77; Finsley, 1999: p. 59; Perrilliat, Vega and Corona, 2000: p. 12, f. 5.27, 5.28; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Hall, 2005: p. 44, t. 5; Lacovara and Gallagher, 2006: p. 18, App. A; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 61; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 109, t. 1, pl. 1, f. 15; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 42; Boas, Garb, Landman, Rovelli and Larina, 2016; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 63, 72, pl. 4.

Turritella cf. vertebroides Morton, 1834. Sohl and Koch, 1984B: p. 154; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Lacovara and Gallagher, 2006: p. 16, App. A.

Non *Turritella vertebroides* Morton, 1834. Whitfield, 1892A: p. 144, f. 16-18; Whitfield, 1892B: pl. 144, f. 16-18; Weller, 1907: p. 693, pl. 18, f. 14

Types – *Turritella vertebroides* Morton, 1834; Holotype: ANSP 2287.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2830i

Description – “Shell acutely angular, the apical angle about 20 ; the dimensions of a large individual from Alabama are : maximum diameter, 20 mm. ; length with the apex broken, 64 mm. ; number of volutions preserved, 10. Suture moderately impressed, situated a little below the center of a rounded, revolving furrow ; surface of the volutions depressed convex from suture to suture. Surface marked by four or five subequal, angular, revolving costae, with several much finer ones occupying each of the interspaces, and by fine transverse lines of growth which describe a concave curve in passing downward from the suture. In the casts the volutions are moderately close, the surface is smooth and rounded curving rather abruptly into the sutures above and below.” – Weller (1907) p. 693-694.

**FIGURE 116A: *TURRITELLA VERTEBROIDES* MORTON, 1834
A: MAPS A2830A – IMPRESSION (Kns) B: MAPS A2830A
(Kns) C: MAPS A2830B (Ksv) D: MAPS A2830D –
IMPRESSION (KMR) E: MAPS A2830D (KMR)**

ORDER **CEPHALASPIDEA** Fischer, 1883

FAMILY **CYLICHNIDAE** ADAMS AND ADAMS, 1854

GENUS **CYLICHNA** LOVEN, 1846

***Cylichna recta* (Gabb, 1860)**

Bulla recta Gabb, 1860: p. 302, pl. 48, f. 16; Richards, 1968: p. 181.

Cylichna recta (Gabb, 1860). Gabb, 1861A: p. 103; Meek, 1864: p. 16; Conrad, 1868: p. 728; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 164, pl. 20, f. 10-11; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 164, pl. 20, f. 10-11; Whitfield, 1899: p. 169; Johnson, 1905: p. 19; Weller, 1907: p. 814, pl. 99, f. 17-18; Stephenson, 1911: p. 185; Gardner, 1916: 411, pl. 18, f. 10-11; Stephenson, 1923: p. 389; Cooke, 1943: p. 30; Stephenson, 1955A: p. 134; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 96, pl. 64, f. 5,7; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 9; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 45; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 19, f. 8.

Non Cylichna recta (Gabb, 1860). Wade, 1926: p. 106, pl. 34, f. 18 = *Cylindrotruncatum demersum*, Sohl, 1964.

Types – *Bulla recta* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP 18782

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 814 pl. 99, f. 18; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 96.

Description - "Shell small, measuring only about half an inch in extreme length, form cylindrical, largest below, with nearly straight sides; spire deeply sunken in the cast; aperture large and the lip nearly straight on the sides, but gradually expanding below; columella curved; surface unknown." - Whitfield (1892) p. 164

FIGURE 117: CYLICHNA RECTA (GABB, 1860) A-B: WHITFIELD (1892) ("LOWER GREEN SANDS"); C: WELLER (1907) PL. 99 FIG. 18 (KW); D-E: GARDNER (1916) PL. 18 FIG. 10-11 (KS); F-G: RICHARDS AND RAMSDELL (1962) PL. 64 F. 5, 7 (ANSP 18782) (KML)

SUBCLASS HETEROBRANCHIA Burmeister, 1837

FAMILY ACTEONIDAE D'ORBIGNY, 1842

GENUS ACTEON MONTFORT, 1810

Acteon cretacea Gabb, 1862

Tornatella sp. Forbes, 1845: p. 63 text f. c.

Acteon cretacea Gabb, 1862: p. 318; Meek, 1864: p. 17; Conrad, 1868: p. 728; Conard, 1869A: p. 360; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 158, pl. 19, f. 9-12; Whitfield,

1892B: p. 158, pl. 19, f. 9-12; Boyle, 1893: p. 24; Whitfield, 1899: p. 167; Johnson, 1905: p. 19; Weller, 1907: p. 805: pl. 99, f. 1-6 (part).

Actaeon ovoidea Gabb, 1862: p. 319; Meek, 1864: p. 17; Conrad, 1868: p. 728; Conard, 1869A: p. 360; Boyle, 1893: p. 24; Johnson, 1905: p. 19.

Actaeon subovooides Whitfield, 1892A: p. 155, pl. 19, f. 14-16; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 155, pl. 19, f. 14-16; Whitfield, 1899: p. 167; Cunha and Salvador, 2018: p. 511.

Cinulia ovoidea Whitfield, 1892A: p. 162, pl. 20, f. 5-6; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 162, pl. 20, f. 5-6.

Acteon cretacea Gabb, 1861. Gardner, 1916: p. 411; Wade, 1926: p. 102; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 90, pl. 63, f. 3; Richards, 1968: p. 120; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 43; Gallagher, 1984: p. 27; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 17; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Lacovara and Gallagher, 2006: p. 18, App. A; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: App. pl. 1; Shankle and Johnson, 2018: p. 26; Cunha and Salvador, 2018: p. 508, f. 1Q, 1R, p. 511, f. 2I, 2J, 2K, 2L.

Types – *Actaeon cretacea* Gabb, 1862; Holotype: ANSP 18778; Syntype: ANSP 18779 (type of *Actaeon ovoidea* and *A. subovooides*), ANSP 56166.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 805 pl. 99, f. 3-6; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 90.

Description – "Shell variable in size, subovoid in general form, with a moderately elevated spire; the dimensions of two individuals are height, 39 mm. and 20 mm.; maximum diameter, 25 mm. and 11.5 mm.; height of spire, 10 mm. and 7 mm.; height of aperture, 29 mm. and 13 mm. Volutions four or five, with distinctly marked sutures in the cast; body volution large, forming the greater bulk of the shell, moderately convex in the middle and slightly pointed below; aperture large, about two-thirds of the total height of the shell, pointed at the upper end, and moderately increasing in width anteriorly, its greatest width considerably below the middle, obtusely pointed below. The columellar cavity in the casts rather wide and furnished with a single moderately strong tooth at about the broadest part of the aperture, which is often but weakly developed; surface of the shell obscurely marked on the cast by a few rather broad spiral lines, which externally, as

indicated by impressions, are narrow impressed lines.” – Weller (1907) p. 806.

FIGURE 118: *ACTEON CRETACEA* GABB, 1861 A: WELLER, 1907 PL. 99 FIG. 3-4 (2 LATERAL VIEWS OF SAME SPECIMEN) (KW); B: WELLER, 1907 PL. 99 FIG. 5-6 (2 LATERAL VIEWS OF SAME SPECIMEN) (KW); C: WELLER, 1907 PL. 99 FIG. 1-2 (2 LATERAL VIEWS OF SAME SPECIMEN) (KNS)

Acteon sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2802f

FIGURE 119: *ACTEON* SP. A: MAPS 2802f (KW)

FAMILY ARCHITECTONICIDAE GRAY, 1850

GENUS *GRANOSOLARIUM* SACCO, 1892

Granosolarium voragiformis (Stephenson, 1941)

Architectonica voragiformis Stephenson, 1941: p. 271, pl. 48, f. 12-14; Carey, 1976: p. 232, pl. 15, f. 5; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 19, f. 8.

Architectonica cf. *voragiformis* Stephenson, 1941. Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 8, pl. 3, f. 5a-c; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 47.

Architectonica (*Granosolarium*) *voragiformis* Stephenson, 1941. Sohl, 1964B: p. 360; Wolleben, 1977: p. 393, pl. 3, f. 18; Vega, Feldman and Sour-Tovar, 1995: p. 47, t. 1.

Granosolarium voragiformis Stephenson, 1941. Dockery, 1993: p. 37, 38, 91; Ackers and Ackers, 1997: p. 232, 306, f. 246; Kiel, 2001: p. 118; Kiel, Bandel and Perrilliat, 2002: p. 331.

Types – *Architectonica voragiformis* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 76819.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2883c.

Remarks - Sohl, 1964B placed *A. voragiformis* in the sub genus *A. (Granoslarium) voragiformis*. Dockery 1993 elevated this to *Granosolarium voragiformis* (Stephenson, 1941)

Description – “Shell of medium size and thickness, depressed conical, umbilicate; spiral angle about 95 degrees. Whorls 5 or 6, flattish on the side, with a spiral sulcus toward the lower edges. Suture closely appressed, sharply but not deeply impressed. Protoconch not preserved. Base flattish with, however, a broad, shallow, spiral sulcus near the periphery; this sulcus opposite to the sulcus near the lower boarder of the outer side of the whorl and the two constrictions together produce a thin; projecting, flange-like carina on the periphery of the body whorl. Umbilicus wide and deep. Starting from the rim of the umbilicus the growth lines cross the base trending obliquely forward and curving broadly forward as they cross the peripheral sulcus and flange; on the lateral surface of the whorl the growth lines continue upward and somewhat obliquely forward to the suture. The lateral surface of the body whorl near the aperture is ornamented with 7 primary, beaded, spiral lirae, the last two of which are on the peripheral flange; in each of the interspaces except between the fourth and fifth (counting from suture downward) is a small, obscurely beaded secondary; the seven

primary spirals are traceable backward on the whorls toward the apex to the place where the surface is too badly corroded to count them; the secondaries fade out posteriorly, the last trace of them disappearing at about the beginning of the penultimate whorl. The base is covered with about 15 closely crowded, beaded spiral lirae which are coarsest near the rim of the umbilicus, but become regularly smaller toward the periphery, fading out on the peripheral flange. The rim of the umbilicus is relatively coarsely nodose, the nodes being elongated in the direction of the growth lines. The whole of the umbilicus appears to be covered with spiral lirae which are not clearly uncovered. The lips are broken but the aperture is subsquarish with a slight obliquity in the direction of the peripheral flange. Dimensions of the holotype: Height 8.8 mm., diameter 14.4 mm." – Stephenson (1941) p. 271.

FIGURE 120: *GRANOSOLARIUM VORAGIFORMIS* (STEPHENSON, 1941) A-B: MAPS 2883A (KW); C-D: EML C-064 (KML)

FAMILY MATHILDIDAE DALL, 1889

GENUS *GEGANIA* JEFFREYS, 1884

Gegania bella (Conrad, 1860)

Tuba bella Conrad, 1860: p. 289, 290, pl. 46, f. 38; Gabb, 1861A: p. 140; Boyle, 1893: p. 291; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 47.

Gegania bella (Conrad, 1860). Sohl, 1960: p. 135, pl. 18, f. 37, 38; Sohl, 1964B: p. 363; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 98; Dockery, 1993: p. 90.

Tuba aff. Tuba bella Conrad, 1860. Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40.

Types – *Tuba bella* Conrad, 1860; Topotype: USNM 21162.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2852b.

Description – "Turritid; whorls nine, rapidly increasing in size, convex, excavated at suture; whorls of spire have three revolving ribs, and the body whorl, which is ventricose, about fourteen; a fine line revolves between the ribs; ribs and lines elegantly crenulated by regular, closely arranged, fine lines; body whorl regularly rounded at base. Length 1 1/8 inches; diameter 3/8 inch." – Conrad (1860) p. 289.

Remarks – "The type of *Gegania bella* (Conrad) unfortunately is lost, but a topotype (?) in the U.S. National Museum (USNM 21162) from the Ripley formation at Eufaula, Barbour County, Ala., is well preserved and could serve as a neotype..." – Sohl (1960) p. 135 in the description of *Gegania bella prodiga* Sohl (1960).

FIGURE 121: *GEGANIA BELLA* (CONRAD, 1860) A-C: MAPS A2852c (Kt)

ORDER LITTORINIMORPHA Golikov and
Starobogatov, 1975

FAMILY APORRHAIIDAE GRAY, 1850

GENUS ANCHURA CONRAD, 1860

Anchura substriata Wade, 1926

Anchura substriata Wade, 1926: p. 149, pl. 52, f. 10; Sohl, 1960: p. 106, pl. 12, f. 2, 3, 10, 11, 13; Dockery, 1993: p. 62; Elder and Saul, 1996: p. 382; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 108, f. 94, 95; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 61; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 50, 63.

Non Anchura substriata Wade, 1926: Sohl, 1964B: p. 366, pl. 54, f. 2, 3 = *Anchura coffea* Dockery, 1993.

Anchura? *substriata* Wade, 1926: Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 13, t. 1, p. 20, f. 9 Q, 9O, 9P.

Types – *Anchura substriata* Wade, 1926; Holotype: USNM 32924; Hypotype: USNM 128514-128516.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2905g.

Description – “Shell large, outer lip abnormally expanded; spire very acuminate, its elevation greater than half the total altitude of the shell; spiral angle low at the apex and increasing in size with age; whorls 13 or 14, feebly convex, increasing in size gradually; protoconch small and elevated, coiled three times, its whorls well rounded and regular; sculpture elaborate, consisting of both axial and spiral elements; axial elevations low and broadly sinuous, best developed on the whorls of the spire and disappearing almost entirely on the body; axial elevations overridden by spirals; low, irregular-shaped nodules developed at their intersections on the later whorls; primary spiral fillets 12 or 14 on the body and 6 on the whorls of the spire; spiral depressions marked by 3 to 6 fine secondary spiral threads; the fourth spiral fillet from the suture persists as an elevation to the most posterior point of the expanded outer lip, and the adjacent four spiral ridges break up into secondary lirae and spread out with the secondary threads in the interspaces in fan shape over the expanded outer lip; suture impressed; body very slightly constricted posteriorly and abruptly constricted in front, where it merges into a narrow, smooth, and straight anterior canal aperture glazed with callus; inner aperture broadly lenticular, produced in front into a narrow open canal, slightly notched posteriorly and extending in a curved groove on the inner side of the outer lip to the most posterior

point of this lip; this groove is obscured by callus in old-age stages; outer lip very widely expanded into a wide abnormal lip, which near the outer margin is slightly lobed in front and produced backward into a long, sharp, slightly curved, spur-shaped projection; extreme outer margin broadly arcuate; outer lip thin in young adults but very much thickened on the inner side of old adults; inner lip excavated medially; columella smooth; parietal wash thin and extending far out on the adjacent body region. A slightly imperfect individual measures in altitude, 81.6 millimeters; elevation of spire, 43 millimeters; maximum diameter, including the expanded outer lip, 50 millimeters. This species is characterized by its high, very acute spire and further by the well-developed broadly sinuous axial ribs. Its pillar is feeble and smooth. The outer margin of the outer lip is arcuate. In general aspect it resembles *Anchura convexa*, but it differs from that form in size and detail of external sculpture. In many respects it greatly resembles *Anchura haydeni* White, which occurs in the Pierre shale of Colorado. It differs from *Anchura abrupta* Conrad mainly in the shape of the outer lip. The species *Rostellaria noneliana* CD' Orbigny), from the Turonian of France, and *Aporrhais securifera* Forbes, from the Trichinopoly group of southern India, are probably related ancestral forms of the Senonian species of this group. The shells of *Anchura substriata* are very common at Coon Creek, but perfect specimens are rarely obtained, not only because the shells are very fragile but also because the high spire, the slender pillar, and the expanded outer lip are so extended that they break away easily, and for these reasons many of the individuals were imperfect before they were covered up in the sediments.” – Wade (1926) p. 149.

FIGURE 122: *ANCHURA SUBSTRIATA* WADE, 1926 A-B: MAPS A2905G (KW); C-E: MAPS A2905A (KS)

GENUS *APORRHAI*S DA COSTA, 1778

Aporrhais sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2909d.

FIGURE 123: *APORRHAI*S SP. A-B: MAPS A2909D (KW)

GENUS *ARRHOGES* (LATALIA) SOHL, 1960

Arrhoges (Latalia) lobata (Wade, 1926)

Anchura lobata Wade, 1926: p. 150, pl. 52, f. 11; Sohl, 1960: p. 47.

Anchura? lobata Wade, 1926. Stephenson, 1941: p. 298, pl. 56, f. 15.

Anchura? lobata media Stephenson, 1941: p. 299, pl. 55, f. 8-10.

Anchura aff. Anchura lobata Wade, 1926. Vestal, 1946: p. 62.

Arrhoges (Latalia) lobata (Wade, 1926). Sohl, 1960: p. 101, pl. 11, f. 9, 13-15; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kiel and Bandel, 2002: p. 84; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 61; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 49; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1.

Arrhoges (Latalia) cf. lobata (Wade, 1926). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 37; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 17, 56, 71, 152; Sohl and Koch, 1984B: p. 144, 157, 162.

Arrhoges lobata (Wade, 1926). Kuehne, 1999: p. 60, 61.

Arrhoges cf. lobata (Wade, 1926). Kuehne, 1999: p. 71, 72.

Types – *Anchura lobata* Wade, 1926; Holotype: USNM 32925; Plesiotype: 76908; *Anchura lobata media* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 76912; Paratype: USNM 20988.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2836i.

Description – “Shell of more than medium size; thin but tough and strong; spire turreted, its elevation a little greater than half the total altitude of the shell; whorls seven, increasing gradually in size, convex, and closely appressed; protoconch small and smooth, trochoid, and coiled three times; sculpture dominantly axial; axial costae abruptly elevated but low, angular on the crest, and protractive, more widely spaced on the body and disappearing near the aperture; low varicose ribs appear at irregular intervals; varices not protractive but parallel to the axis; spiral sculpture consists of fine, crowded, slightly impressed lines on the spire but absent on the body; suture impressed; body inflated and very abruptly constricted in front, where it merges into a narrow, sharp anterior canal: inner aperture lenticular and produced in front into a narrow, straight canal; outer lip expanded into a broad wing-shaped appendage, lobed anteriorly and produced backward into a pointed spur-shaped projection; outer margin slightly thickened; posterior commissure extended backward upon the penultima; inner lip excavated; columella smooth; parietal wall washed with a thin, wide

brilliant glaze of callus. Altitude, 48.4 millimeters; maximum diameter, including the expanded outer lip, 27.2 millimeters. This species is characterized by its low, angular protractive axial ribs, which are varicose at irregular intervals, and further by its faint microscopic spiral sculpture." – Wade (1926) p. 150.

FIGURE 124: *ARRHOGES (LATILA) LOBATA* (WADE, 1926) A-B: MAPS A2836i (Kw); C-D: MAPS A2836A (Ks); E: ANSP 80412 (Kw)

***Arrhoges (Latiala) rostrata* (Gabb, 1860)**

Rostellaria rostrata Gabb, 1860B: p. 390, pl. 68, f. 7; Boyle, 1893: p. 256; Richards, 1968: p. 183.

Gladius rostrata (Gabb, 1860). Gabb, 1861A: p. 111; Conrad, 1868: p. 729.

Anchura (Drepanochilus) rostrata (Gabb, 1860). Meek, 1864: p. 19.

Anchura rostrata (Gabb, 1860). Conrad, 1868: p. 729; Boyle, 1893: p. 39; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Weller, 1907: p. 709, pl. 81, f. 7-9; Darton and Siebenthal, 1909: p. 39, 42; Gardner, 1916: p. 471; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 51; Richards, 1956: p. 71, 72; Sohl, 1960: p. 47; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 32, pl. 50, f. 11, pl. 53, f. 1; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 9; Gallagher, 1984: p. 13, 14; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 67; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 63, 74, pl. 5.

Non Anchura rostrata (Gabb, 1860). Conrad, 1875A: p. A17; Conrad, 1875B: p. A17.

Alaria rostrata (Gabb, 1860). Whitfield, 1892A: p. 119, pl. 14, f. 5, 6; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 119, pl. 14, f. 5, 6; Woolman, 1893B: p. 220; Clark, 1897: p. 331; Clark, 1898: p. 180; Whitfield, 1899: p. 167.

Arrhoges (Latiala) rostrata (Gabb, 1860). Soh, 1960: p. 47; Gallagher, 1986: p. 30.

Types – *Rostellaria rostrata* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP 15048.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 709 pl. 81, f. 9; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 32.

Description - Description. "Shell of only moderate size; spire elevated, forming an apical angle of about 35; but somewhat variable in different specimens; whorls about six in number, very slightly convex between the sutures, which are not very strongly marked, and are ornamented by rather closely arranged vertical folds, smaller, more numerous, and more closely arranged on the upper than on the body whorl; those on the last whorl become smaller, shorter, and more indistinct toward the expanded lip, on the back of which they become obsolete; on all the upper whorls the folds extend from suture to suture, but on the last one they are marked only on the upper or larger parts; outer lip expanded, forming a broad, wing-like extension which is prolonged below along the moderately long rostral beak, and above is extended into an obtusely pointed hook-like process from its outer upper border. This feature I have seen entire only on the type specimen, though several are before me which show the expansion of the lip. No keel-like ridge marks the back of the lip, as in most of the species of this group from the Cretaceous beds of the Upper Missouri region." - Whitfield (1892) p. 119.

Remarks - Weller, 1907 p. 709 lists *Rostellaria rostrata* Gabb, 1860, *Gladius rostrata* Gabb, 1861, *Anchura (Drepanochilus) rostrata* (Gabb, 1860), *Alaria rostrata* Whitfield, 1892 all as *Anchura rostrata* (Gabb, 1860). Sohl, 1960 p. 47, 101 places *Anchura lobata* in the genus *Arrhoges (Latiala)*.

FIGURE 125: *ARRHOGES (LATIALA) ROSTRATA* (GABB, 1860)
A-B: WELLER (1907) PL. 81 FIG. 7-8 (KMT); C: WELLER (1907) PL. 81 F. 9 (KW); D-E: NJSM 21015 (KMT)

GENUS PTEROCERELLA MEEK, 1864
Pterocerella tippana (Conrad, 1858)

Harpago tippanus Conrad, 1858A: p. 331, pl. 35, f.25; Gabb, 1859: p. 6; Gabb, 1861A: p. 112; Boyle, 1893: p. 145.

Pterocerella tippana (Conrad, 1858). Meek, 1864: p. 20, 36; Gabb, 1868: p. 146-147, pl. 14, f. 20; Tyron, 1883: p. 195, pl. 60, f. 90; Boyle, 1893: p. 248; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Weller, 1907: p. 718: pl. 83, f. 2 (not pl. 83, f. 1 = *Pterocerella poinsettiformis* Stephenson, 1941); Stephenson, 1911: p. 134, 137, 185; Stephenson, 1914: t. 1, 8; Stephenson and Monroe, 1940: pl. 13, f. 3; Stephenson, 1941: p. 310; Shrock, 1947: p. 495-496; Sohl, 1960: p. 109, pl. 13, f. 3, 5, 19; Richard and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 40; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 32, 107, 110, 133, 142, 144, 147, 157, 160, 230; Dockery, 1993: p. 64; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 113, 286, f. 99; Hall, 2005: p. 49, t. 8; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 50.

Non Pterocerella tippana (Conrad, 1858). Weller, 1907: p. 718, pl. 83, f. 1; Wade, 1916: p. 152, pl. 53, f. 6, 7.

Chenopus (Pterocerella) tippana (Conrad, 1858). Cossman, 1904: p. 70, f. 3.

Aporrhais (Pterocerella) tippana (Conrad, 1858). Wenz, 1940: p. 920, f. 2697; Sohl, 1967A: p. B19.

Types – *Harpago tippana* Conrad, 1858; Holotype: Lost; Topotype USNM 128525; Hypotypes: USNM 20435, 128525, 128526.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 718 pl. 83, f. 2.

Description – “Shell with a spire of moderate height, with about six volutions, having an apical angle of about 48. The dimensions of a nearly perfect specimen from Texas are total height, exclusive of the wing-like extensions of the aperture, 35 mm.; height of spire, 18 mm.; maximum diameter of body volution, 23 mm.; extension of the processes on the border of the outer lip from 18 mm. to 33 mm. The volutions of the spire are marked by a revolving keel a little below the mid-height of each volution, the sutures not impressed below the surface of the spiral, concave band between the carinae of succeeding volutions. Greatest height of the body volution, exclusive of its wing-like extensions, about equal to the greatest height of the spire, marked by a second less sharply angular revolving rib, which is situated about as far below the upper carina as that is below the upper suture, and by three or less distinctly marked ones near the anterior margin, the two lower of which are distinctly recurved. When the outer lip of the aperture is complete it is produced into six elongate, divergent, conspicuous, wing-like processes, which are strengthened along their median lines by thickened ribs or carinae, the median carinae of five of these processes being continuations of the ribs upon the body volution of the shell. The most posterior of the processes is a branch from near the base of the one next to it, and its median line is subparallel to the axis of the spire. Surface of the shell marked only by fine, inconspicuous lines of growth.” – Weller (1907) p. 718

FIGURE 126: *PTEROCERELLA TIPPANA* (CONRAD, 1858) A: WELLER, 1907 PL. 83 FIG. 2 (KW)

Pterocerella sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 40 pl. 52, f. 10 (NJSM 7692); MAPS A2877e, MAPS 2877g

FIGURE 127: *PTEROCERELLA* SP. A: RICHARDS AND RAMSDELL (1962) PL. 52 FIG. 10 (NJSM 7692) (KW); B: MAPS A2877E (KW); C: MAPS A2877C (Ks); D: MAPS A2877A (Kmv); E: MAPS A2877C (Ks)

GENUS **PUGNELLUS** CONRAD, 1860

Pugnellus densatus (Conrad, 1858)

Strombus densatus Conrad, 1858: p. 330, pl. 25, f. 14; Gabb, 1859: p. 6; Gabb, 1861A: p. 138.

Pugnellus densatus (Conrad, 1858). Conrad, 1860: p. 284, pl. 46, f. 32; Gabb, 1961A: 128; Meek, 1864: p. 20; Stoliczka, 1868: p. 18; Gabb, 1876A: p. 298; Hill, 1887: p. 295; Boyle, 1893: p. 249; Hill, 1901: p. 342, pl. 48, f. 2; Cossman, 1904: p. 37, pl. 7, f. 4, 5; Johnson, 1905: p. 23; Veatch, 1906: pl. 10, f. 3; Crider, 1906: p. 17, 21; Stephenson, 1991: p. 158, 177; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 2, 8, 9; Gardner, 1916: p. 468; Deussen, 1924: pl. 11, f. 1; Wade, 1926: p. 148, pl. 52, f. 4-5; Adkins, 1928: p. 192; Stephenson, 1940: pl. 13, f. 1, 2; Shimer and Shrock, 1944: p. 497, pl. 203, f. 27, 28; Sohl, 1960: p. 112-113, pl. 14, f. 4, 5, 9, 10, 13-16, 19, 20; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 43, pl. 53, f. 8; Popenoe, 1983: p. 742-743; f. 6E-H; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 147; Dockery, 1993: p. 89; Dunagan and Gibson, 1993: p. 89; Vega, Feldman and Sour-Tovar, 1995: p. 347, t. 1; p. 348, t. 2; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 116, 286; Kiel and Bandel, 1999: p. 49, 50, 56; Kuehne, 1999: p. 49, 50, 56; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 61; Kollman, 2009: pl. 2, f. 6; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 51.

Pugnellus cf. densatus (Conrad, 1858). Stephenson, 1907: p. 140; Weller, 1907: p. 720, pl. 83, f. 6; Sohl, 1964B: p. 368.

Pugnellus typicus Gabb, 1876A: p. 298; Popenoe, 1983: p. 743; Popenoe, 1983: p. 743.

Pugnellus pauciplicatus Stephenson, 1923: p. 373, pl. 92, f. 10-12.

Pugnellus (Pugnellus) densatus (Conrad, 1858). Wenz, 1940: p. 940, f. 2748, 2747; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 16, 21, 25, 27, 29, 32, 44, 49, 51, 56, 60, 61, 104, 152, 172, 177, 189, 194, 200; Perrilliat, Vega and Corona, 2000: p. 13, f. 6.2, 6.3.

Pugnellus densatus nacatochanus Stephenson, 1941: p. 310-311, pl. 58, f. 5-8; Sohl, 1960: p. 113.

Types – *Strombus densatus* Conrad, 1858; Holotype: ANSP 15016; Hyptotypes: 128535-128540; *Pugnellus pauciplicatus* Stephenson, 1923; Holotype: USNM 31864; *Pugnellus densatus*

nacatochanus; Holotype: USNM 76971, Paratypes: 76972-76974

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 720 pl. pl. 83, f. 6; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 43 pl. 53, f. 8 (NJSM 7693).

Description – “Internal casts of median size, subovate in form, the dimensions of a nearly complete one being height, 35 mm.; greatest diameter, 20 mm.; height of aperture, about 22 mm.; width of aperture, 7.5 mm. Volutions about four in number, the suture well denned, the height of the spire less than one-half the total height of the shell. Volutions of the spire gently convex and nearly vertical for two-thirds of this height from the suture below, curving much more strongly above to the upper suture. Surface of the cast without well-defined markings.” – Weller (1907) p. 720

FIGURE 128: *PUGNELLUS DENSATUS* (CONRAD, 1858) A-B: NJSM 7693 (KW); C-D: MAPS A2839A (KS); E-F: MAPS A2839B (KS); G: WELLER 1907 PL. 83 F. 6 (KW)

***Pugnellus goldmani* Gardner, 1916**

Pugnellus goldmani Gardner, 1916: p. 468, pl. 17, f. 5, 6; Stephenson, 1927: p. 22; Dockery, 1993: p. 68; Kiel and Bandel, 1999: p. 56.

Pugnellus robustus Stephenson, 1941: p. 312, pl. 58

Pugnellus (Pugnellus) goldmani Gardner, 1916. Sohl, 1960: p. 114, pl. 14, pl. 14, f.11,12, 17, 18, pl. 15, f. 12, 14, 16; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 21, 32; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 116, 287, f. 102.

Types – *Pugnellus goldmani* Gardner, 1916; Holotype: USNM 131881; Hyptotypes: USNM 128542-128544; *Pugnellus robustus* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 76975; Paratypes: USNM 76976-76977

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2953a; MAPS A2953b; MAPS A2953c.

Description – “Shell of adult large, thick, robust, irregular, largely covered with callus of uneven thickness; on the outer surface of the body whorl back thickened outer lip the covering of callus is thin, and on different individuals is more or less completely scaled off. The stage of growth just preceding that in which old age characters begin to form is a smooth, plump shell similar to, though considerably larger than, that of *Pugnellus densatus nacatochana*. The apical angle is about 65 degrees. There is a flat narrow shoulder just below the suture; the side whorl is very broadly rounded but is modified above just below the shoulder by a shallow excavated band about one-fourth the width of the whorl. The growth lines extend first nearly vertically downward from the suture and then curve strongly forward becoming slightly sinuous as they approach the suture below; on the body whorl the growth lines are markedly sinuous as they pass downward over the broadly rounded periphery and the base below. The surface is nearly smooth except that on some specimens 4 or 5 faint revolving lines appear on the penultimate whorl between the excavated band and the suture below. On mature shells 4 or 5 obscure, but coarse, rather widely spaced longitudinal ribs are present on the upper part of the body whorl back of the aperture; these ribs are sinuous, following the trend of the growth lines. The uncallused surface of this part of the body whorl also shows a dozen or more very faint, fine spiral lines diverging from the convex part of the whorl toward the margins of the lip; apparently new lines are intercalated as the interspaces widen. The aperture of the adult is elongated with almost parallel

sides about 10 mm. apart in the upper three-fourths of its length; the anal chamber is broad and wide open with a broadly rounded bottom; the siphonal channel is of moderate length and nearly straight. The outer lip is very thick and widely expanded; its upper, outer extremity is formed by a heavy, blunt node which projects upward 10mm. or more, but which is incompletely preserved in the available material; on the margin a little more than halfway between this large node and the anterior extremity of the shell is another curious, smaller, but prominent, blunt node projects 6 or 7 mm. forward, a little downward and a little inward; this node is elongated in the direction of the margin, has a length of about 8mm., and a thickness of 4 or 5 mm. The base just in front of the aperture is made plump by a deposit of callus which spreads away from the aperture in a progressively thinning sheet, and the spire is completely callused over in such a manner as to present a twisted appearance.” – Stephenson (1941) p. 312.

FIGURE 129: *PUGNELLUS GOLDMANI* GARDNER, 1916 A-B: MAPS A2953A (Kw); C-D: MAPS A2953A; E-F: MAPS A2953B (Kw)

Pugnellus sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 64; MAPS A2815e, MAPS A2815l

FIGURE 130: *PUGNELLUS* SP. A-B: MAPS A2815E (Kw)

FAMILY **CAPULIDAE** FLEMING, 1822

GENUS **TURBINOPSIS** CONRAD, 1860

Turbinopsis depressa Gabb, 1862

Non Straparolus lapidosus Gabb, 1860A (in part): p. 300, pl. pl.48, f. 5.

Turbinopsis depressa Gabb, 1862: p. 321; Conard, 1869A: p. 360; Conard, 1869D: p. 43; Boyle, 1893: p. 292; Johnson, 1905: p. 123; Weller, 1907: p. 794, pl. 98, f. 6-11; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 28, pl. 62, f. 10-11; Richards, 1968: p. 123.

Non Delphinula? lapidosa (Gabb, 1860). Meek: 1864: p. 18; Conard, 1868: p. 728.

Turbinopsis depressus Gabb, 1862. Meek, 1864: p. 19; Conrad, 1868: p. 729.

Modulus lapidosa Whitfield, 1892A: p. 152, pl. 17, f. 6-8; Whitfield, 1892B: p, 152, pl. 17, f. 6-8; Clark, 1897: p. 331; Clark, 1898: p. 180; Whitfield, 1899: p. 172; Johnson, 1905: p. 149

Turbinopsis cf. depressa Gabb, 1862. Sohl, 1960: p. 91, pl. 10, f. 28; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 44, 56, 61, 82.

Types – *Turbinopsis depressa* Gabb, 1862; Holotype: USNM 14968; Hypotype: USNM 128477; *Modulus lapidosa* Whitfield, 1892; Holotype: ANSP 19456; Cotype: ANSP 29546.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 794 pl. 98, f. 10-11; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 28.

Description – “The dimensions of one of the specimens, an internal cast, are height, 14 mm.; maximum diameter of the outer volution, 14 mm. Shell broadly umbilicate, with two or three volutions, spire depressed, suture about flush with the surface. Outer volution gibbous, its greatest width above the middle, periphery rounded, the upper and lower surfaces both convex, the slope of the upper surface to the suture more abrupt than the slope of the lower surface, contracted below to a very short anterior canal. Surface of the outer volution marked with revolving costae, probably about seven or eight in number, and by transverse ribs of about equal strength, with interspaces about equal to those between the revolving costae; the points of intersection of the revolving and transverse ribs are elevated into low nodes. Internal casts smooth or marked by more or less indistinct revolving ribs, the surface rounded from the suture to the angular umbilical margin, the greatest thickness of the volution about its mid-height; columellar cavity very broad, marked by a single strong and sharp revolving fold situated near the anterior margin.” – Weller (1907) p. 794.

FIGURE 131: *TURBINOPSIS DEPRESSA* GABB, 1861 A: ANSP 14968 (TYPE); B: WELLER 1907 PL. 98 FIG. 10 (KW); C-E: WHITFIELD, 1892 “LOWER GREEN SANDS”

FAMILY NATICIDAE GUILDING, 1834

GENUS *EUSPIRA* AGASSIZ, 1837

***Euspira halli* (Gabb, 1860)**

Lunatia halli Gabb, 1860B: p. 391, pl. 68, f. 11; Gabb, 1861A: p.114; Stoliczka, 1863: p. 296; Meek, 1864: p. 20; Conrad, 1868: p. 729; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 130, pl. 15, f. 13-16, p. 175, pl. 21, f. 10, 11; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 130, pl. 15, f. 13-16, p. 175, pl. 21, f. 10, 11; Boyle, 1893: p. 174; Woolman, 1893: p.220; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 186; Whitfield, 1899: p. 171; Whitfield, 1891A: p. 428; Johnson, 1905: p. 21; Weller, 1907: p. 677, pl. 76, f. 9-19; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 49; Richards, 1956: p. 71, 79; Sohl, 1960: p. 123; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 10, pl. 47, f. 9-10; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 8; Richards, 1968: p. 140; Erickson, 1971: p. 116; Feldman, 1977: p. 90; Gallagher, 1984: p. 13, 14, 19-21, 25, 27; Gallagher, 1986: p. 16, 17; Olson and Parris, 1987: p. 20; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27, Lacovara and Gallagher, 2006: p. 16, 18; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 63, 72, pl. 4; Wick, 2021: p. 119, t. 2.

Non Gyrodes altispira Gabb, 1862A. Whitfield, 1892A: p. 128, pl. 16, f. 7-8; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 128, pl. 16, f. 7-8.

Euspira halli (Gabb, 1860). Kummel, 1908; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 19, f. 8; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 64, 66, 67; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1.

Polynices (Euspira) halli (Gabb, 1860). Gardner, 1916: p. 499, pl. 13, f. 1-2; Toots and Cutler, 1962B; Young, 1977: p. 130; Perrilliat, Vega and Corona, 2000: p. 14; Al-Duliami, 2020: p. 57, pl. 3, f. A-C, T. 2.

Non Polynices (Euspira) halli (Gabb, 1860). Wade, 1916: p. 163, pl. 56, f. 11, 12; Shimer and Shrock, 1944: p. 483, pl. 198, f. 23-24.

Types – *Lunatia halli* Gabb, 1860; Cotypes: ANSP 19640, ANSP 15119, ANSP 19637.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 677; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 10; KS2248.

Description - "Shell of moderate size, with an elevated spire composed of about four or four and a half volutions in entire specimen, and much resembling a *Paludina* in general appearance; elevation about once and a half as great as the

diameter of the last volution, and the last volution when measured on the apertural side forms about three-fourths of the entire height; volutions convex, not inflated, but regularly rounded, with a well-marked suture in the casts, the only condition in which they are known from. New Jersey, but which does not indicate a flattening at the top in the perfect shell; aperture elongate-ovate, acutely rounded below and somewhat sharper above than below, the greatest breadth being below the middle; base of the last volution sharply rounding into the umbilical cavity; umbilical opening in the cast small, not extending above the lowest volution, and showing no evidence of any thickening or callus of any kind; surface unknown." - Whitfield (1892) p. 130.

FIGURE 132: *EUSPIRA HALLI* (GABB, 1860) A-B: WHITFIELD, 1892 PL. 21 FIG. 10-11 ("MIDDLE GREEN SANDS"); C-D: WELLER, 1907 PL. 76 FIG. 12, 14 (KNS); ANSP 81295 (KNS) E: ANSP 81295 (KNS)

Euspira sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2809g.

FIGURE 133: *EUSPIRA* SP. A-B: MAPS A2809G (KW)

GENUS *GYRODES* CONRAD, 1860

Gyrodes petrosus (Morton, 1834)

Natica petrosa Morton, 1834: p. 46, 48, 49, pl. 19, f. 6; Boyle, 1893: p. 191; Richards, 1968: p. 173.

Gyrodes petrosa (Morton, 1834). Gabb, 1861A: p. 117; Meek, 1864: p. 21; Gabb, 1876A: p. 295 (in part); Boyle, 1893: p. 143; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 170; Crider, 1906: p. 17, 21.

Gyrodes petrosus (Morton, 1834). Conrad, 1868: p. 729; Whitfield, 1901: p. 428; Johnson, 1905: p. 21; Weller, 1907 (in part): p. 689, pl. 77, f. 13-15 (not pl. 77, f. 16-18); Stephenson, 1927: pl. 81, f. 10; Stephenson, 1941: p. 282, f. 1-7; Vestal, 1946: p. 59; Stetson, 1949: p. 9; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 49; Richards, 1956: p. 71, 79; Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957: p. 14; Sohl, 1960: p. 120, pl. 15, f. 2-5; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 14, pl. 49, f. 3; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 9; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 42; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 40, 42, 44, 52, 54, 56, 57, 59-61, 63-66, 68, 72, 73, 78, 80-82, 86, 92, 93, 97, 99-101, 104, 105, 107, 110, 111, 113, 116, 117, 119, 123, 126, 128, 130, 133, 140, 141, 147-149, 152, 162, 168; Gallagher, 1984: p. 13, 14, 21, Dunagan and Gibson, 1993: p. 89; Kuehne, 1999: p. 67; Gallagher, 2003: p. 27; Lacovara and Gallagher, 2006: p. 16, App. A; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 63, 74, pl. 5.

Non Gyrodes petrosus (Morton, 1834). Gardner, 1916: p. 496, pl. 13, f. 8 (= *G. subcarinatus* Stephenson, 1941); Whitfield, 1892A: p. 127, pl. 16, f. 1-4 (= *G. (S.) spillmani*, Gabb, 1862); Whitfield,

1892B: p. 127, pl. 16, f. 1-4 (= *G. (S.) spillmani*, Gabb, 1862).

Gyrodos aff. Gyrodos petrosus (Morton, 1834). Richards, 1943: p. 29, pl. 6, f. 4, 5; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 14, pl. 44, f. 4-5.

Gyrodos cf. petrosus (Morton, 1834). Kuehne, 1999: p. 60.

Types – *Natica petrosus* Morton, 1834; Holotype: ANSP 15140; Topotypes: USNM 76856, 76857; Hypotypes: 76858, 76857, 128554.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 689; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 14.

Description - "Shell (as seen in casts) of medium size or smaller, obliquely oval or depressed and somewhat patulose, with a low spire ; the entire adult shell having three to three and a half volutions, the last of which forms the greatest bulk of the shell ; volutions obliquely compressed from above, largest below the middle, often slightly flattened on the upper half and with a distinct flattened space bordering the suture ; aperture large, very oblique, strongly receding below as seen in profile on its edge; semilunate in outline, rounded below and slightly acute above, somewhat modified in the upper part by the intrusion of the preceding volution; umbilicus large, broadly patulose within, and apparently without callus; peristome thin, and the substance of the shell also apparently slight; surface of the shell unknown." - *Whitfield – (1892) p. 127*

"The dimensions of an average-sized adult specimen are maximum diameter, 25 mm.; height, 19 mm.; height of aperture, 23 mm.; width of aperture, 12 mm." – Weller (1907) p. 689.

FIGURE 134: *GYRODES PETROSUS* (MORTON, 1834) A-C: WELLER, 1907 PL. 77 F. 13-15 (KNS)

***Gyrodos (Gyrodos) supralicatus* (Conrad, 1858)**

Rapa supralicata Conrad, 1858: 332, pl. 35, f. 2; Gabb, 1859; p. 6; Gabb, 1861A: p. 130; Hill, 1887: p. 295; Boyle, 1893: p. 252.

Natica (Gyrodos) crenata Conrad, 1860: p. 289

Gyrodos crenata (Conrad, 1860). Gabb, 1861A: p. 116; Meek, 1864: p. 21; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 126, pl. 16, f. 5-6; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 126, pl. 16, f. 5-6; Whitfield, 1899, p. 170; Johnson, 1905: p. 21; Crider, 1906: p. 21; Stephenson, 1907: p. 127, 140; Weller, 1907: p. 685, pl. 77, f. 10-12; Stephenson, 1911: p. 158; Stephenson, 1914: t. 2, 7, 8; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 49, pl. 6, f. 1; Richards, 1956; Carey, 1976: p. 220, pl. 9, f. 1; Ward and Kennedy, 1983: p. 164, pl. 57, f. 1-2; Sessa, Larson, et. al. 2015: p. 1556, f. 1g.

Natica infracarinata Gabb, 1862: p. 319, 320; Boyle, 1893: p. 191.

Gyrodos infracarinata (Gabb, 1862). Conrad, 1868: p. 729; Conrad, 1869A: p. 360; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 125-126, pl. 16, f. 5-6; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 125-126, pl. 16, f. 5-6; Woolman, 1893: p. 220; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 186; Whitfield, 1899; p. 170; Richards, 1968: p. 145.

Gyrodos supralicatus (Conrad, 1858). Stephenson, 1923: p. 357, pl. 89, f. 3-6 (not pl. 89, f. 1, 2 = *Gyrodos major* Wade, 1926); Stephenson, 1941: p. 280, pl. 51, f. 13-16; Vestal, 1946: p. 62; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p.49; Stephenson, 1955: p. 125, pl. 21, f. 15, 16; Sohl, 1960: p. 117, pl. 16, f. 1-5, 9, 13, 19; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 13, pl. 48, f. 5, 7, 9, pl. 49, f. 1; Sohl, 1964A: p. 369; Sohl an Koch, 1983: p. 14, 21, 25, 32, 35, 189, 209, 234; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 140, 144, 147, 154, 160; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Vega, Feldman and Sour-Tovar; 1995: p. 348, t. 2; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 71, 77; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte: 2007: p. 13, 20, t. 1, f. 9K, 9J; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, Ap. B, pl. 1; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 55; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2018: p. 63, 72, pl. 4; Wick, 2021: p. 119, t. 2.

Gyrodos supralicata (Conrad, 1858). Adkins, 1928: p. 180.

Gyrodos cf. supralicatus (Conrad, 1858). Cooke, 1943: p. 26; Kuehne, 1999: p. 63, 64.

Gyrodos crenatus (Conrad, 1860). Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957: p. 49.

Natica crenata Conrad, 1860. Richards, 1968: p. 120.

Gyrodos (Gyrodos) supralicatus (Conrad, 1858). Popenoe, Saul and Susuki, 1987: p. 75; Darragh and Kennedy, 1994: p. 39, f. 8a-d; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 140, 141, 291, f. 130, 131; Perrilliat, Vega and Corona, 2000: p. 14, f. 6.8.

Types – *Gyrodos supralicatus* (Conrad, 1858): Topotype: USNM 20440, Plesiotype: USNM 20922, 128175, Topotype: USNM 128176; Hypotype: USNM 128545, 128546, 20992, 76851; *Gyrodos crenata* (Conrad, 1860): Holotype: ANSP 15133; *Natica infracarinata* Gabb, 1862: Holotype: ANSP 15132.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 685 Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 13.

Description – “Shell of medium size, the dimensions of a rather large internal cast being maximum width, 30 mm., height, 23 mm.; height of aperture, 20 mm.; width of aperture, 13.5. Depressed globular above with a depressed spire, broadly umbilicate below. Volutions about four in number, the outer one of which forms fully two-thirds of the bulk of the entire shell, largest below the middle, the casts slightly flattened on top adjacent to the suture, strongly angular on the base bordering the umbilicus. Aperture large, oblique; widest below the middle. In specimens preserving the shell, or in impressions of the exterior, a distinct band of elevated crenulations or transverse nodes marks the top of the volutions just below the suture and forms a decided ridge around the spiral portion of the shell. Surface of the shell marked by fine lines of growth parallel with the margin of the aperture and passing over the line of nodes on the upper surface of the volution.” – Weller (1907) p. 685.

FIGURE 135: *GYRODES (GYRODES) SUPRALICATUS* (CONRAD, 1858) A: ANSP 80475 (KWB); B: MAPS A2872A (KS)

***Gyrodos (Sohlella) spillmani* Gabb, 1862**

Natica (Gyrodos) alveata Conrad, 1860: p. 289, pl. 46, f. 45.

Natica alveata Conrad, 1860. Gabb, 1861A: p. 115; Boyle, 1893: p. 190.

Gyrodos alveata (Conrad, 1860). Meek, 1864: p. 21; Conrad, 1875B: p. A17; Gabb, 1876A; Tyron, 1883: p. 206, pl. 64, f. 70; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 127; Whitfield, 1829B: p. 127; Wade, 1926: p. 164, pl. 57, f. 6, 9; Young, 1977: p. 130.

Non Gyrodos petrosus (Morton, 1834). Whitfield, 1892A: p. 127, pl. 16, f. 1-4; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 127, pl. 16, f. 1-4; Weller, 1907: p. 689 (in part).

Gyrodos spillmani Gabb, 1862: p. 320, Boyle, 1893: p. 143; Johnson, 1905: p. 21; Stephenson, 1941: p.284; Stephenson, 1955: p.125, pl. 21, f. 13, 14; Sohl, 1960: p. 118-119, pl. 16, f. 14, 17, 18, 20, 21, pl. 17, f. 27; Sohl, 1964B: p. 369, pl. 54, f. 28-31, 33; Richards, 1968: p. 189; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 14, 21, 25, 32, 38, 42, 44, 48, 49, 56, 60, 68, 72, 100, 101, 110, 117, 135, 139, 168, 178, 189, 194, 201, 206, 231, 234; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 135, 138, 144, 147, 151, 154, 157, 160; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89, pl. 2, f. 3; Popenoe, Saul and Susuki, 1987: p. 79; Finsley, 1999: p. 60, f. 121; Kuehne, 1999: p. 77, 79; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 13, 20, t. 1, f. 9I, 9H.

Gyrodos alveatus (Conrad, 1860). Cooke, 1943: p. 30

Non Gyrodos petrosa (Morton, 1834). Shimer and Shrock, 1944: p. 483, pl. 198, f. 13-15.

Gyrodos cf. alveatus (Conrad, 1860). Vestal, 1946: p. 62.

Gyrodos cf. spillmani Gabb, 1862. Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 37.

Gyrodos (Sohlella) spillmani (Gabb, 1862) Dockery, 1993: p. 40, 75, pl. 20, f. 10, 11; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 142, 143, 291, f. 133, 134; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 55.

Types – *Natica (Gyrodos) alveata* Conrad, 1860; Cotype: ANSP 15162, ANSP 15313.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2873d; KS2246, KS2249.

Description – “Small to medium sized shell with low spire. Protoconch small, consists of two smooth raised whorls. Suture impressed, whorls number 4-5. Whorls broadly rounded on sides, developing a shoulder on second teloconch whorl; shoulder flat to excavated, variable in width and bordered by narrow commonly sharp carina. Sculpture lacking save for prosocline growth lines, which are most strongly developed on shoulder. Aperture subovate, inclined to axis, posteriorly angulated, anteriorly rounded; outer lip thin, simple; inner lip slightly sinuous over columellar area; parietal callus thin in small forms, thickening with increased shell size. Umbilicus flaring and open, has subangular margin in small specimens that rounds off with increased growth.” – Sohl (1960) p. 119.

FIGURE 136: *GYRODES (SOHLELLA) SPILLMANI* STEPHENSON, 1941 A-B: MAPS 2873B (Ks)

***Gyrodos* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30

FAMILY XENOPHORIDAE TROSCHEL, 1852

GENUS XENOPHORA FISCHER VON WALDHEIM, 1807

***Xenophora leprosa* (Morton, 1834)**

Trochus leprosa Morton, 1834: p. 46, pl. 15, f. 6; Morton, 1846: p. 39; Gabb, 1861A: p. 141; Boyle, 1893: p. 290; Richards, 1968: p. 151.

Onustus leprosus (Morton, 1834). D’Orbigny, 1850: p. 222; Conrad, 1868: p. 728.

Phorus leprosus (Morton, 1834). Gabb, 1859: p. 6; Gabb, 1861A: p. 124; Meek, 1864: p. 18.

Xenophora leprosa (Morton, 1834). Whitfield, 1892: p. 135, pl. 17 f. 16-19; Clark, 1897: p. 330, 336; Clark, 1898: p. 179, 186; Whitfield, 1899: p. 177; Kummel and Knapp, 1904: p. 77; Johnson, 1905: p. 21; Weller, 1907: p. 690, pl. 78, f. 1-3; Stephenson, 1914: p. 24, t. 4, 5; Gardner, 1916: p. 495; Stephenson, 1926: pl. 91, f. 9; Wade, 1926: p. 162, pl. 56, f. 7-8; Stephenson, 1941: p. 284, pl. 52, f. 17-19; Shimer and Shrock, 1944: p. 485, pl. 199, f. 10-11; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 50; Sohl, 1960: p. 96; pl. 10, f. 19, 23-27; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 16; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 9; Sohl and Kauffman, 1964: p. H19; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 44, 51, 56, 57, 59, 61-66, 71, 73, 76, 78, 82, 110, 117, 123, 127, 130, 133, 135, 139-141, 147-149, 152, 158, 161, 166, 168, 169, 173, 183; Webster, 1983: p. 1095; Ponder and Cooper, 1983: p. 4, 11, 30, 71; Gallagher, 1984: p. 14, 30; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 19, f. 8; Dockery, 1993: p. 71, pl. 20, f. 1-4; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 133, 289; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 69, 71; Squires and Saul, 2001: p. 52; Perrilliat and Vega, 2001: p. 75; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 14, 21, t. 1, f. 10A; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 61; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014; Oman, Manning, Badger and Whitley, 2016: p. 109, t. 1, pl. 1, f. 17a,b,c; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 51; Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 14.

Non Xenophora? conchyliophora Dall, 1892: p. 360 (in part).

Xenophora cf. leprosa (Morton, 1834). Sohl, 1967A: p. B5; Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 47.

Types – *Trochus leprosa* Morton, 1834; Holotype: ANSP 15361

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30.

Description. "Shell small or below a medium size, trochiform, or broad conical ; the spire having an apical angle of less than 90 ; base flat or concave, usually more or less depressed in the center, with the margin of the volution more or less rounded, and in old individuals sometimes distinctly rounded; casts showing a small umbilical perforation, but the axis probably solid in the shell; volutions probably seven or eight, but in the casts the upper ones are usually absent and seldom show more than four or four and a half; one small specimen retaining the upper whorls, to the number of four and a half, measures only five-eighths of an inch in diameter. This one, if continued below to the size of the larger one figured, would possess at least eight volutions; whorls obliquely flattened on their surfaces in the direction of the spire, with only a small portion of their edges rounded or vertical, and the surface deeply and abundantly scarred by the cicatrices of foreign substances which have been attached to the surface of the shell during life; aperture compressed, transversely ovate or trapezoidal, and the outer margin much prolonged." – Whitfield (1892) p. 135.

FIGURE 137: *XENOPHORA LEPROSA* (MORTON, 1834) A-B: MAPS A2801E (Ks) C: THREE VIEWS OF WOODBURY SPECIMEN, COURTESY OF JOHN WHITLEY (KWB)

ORDER NEOGASTROPODA WENZ, 1938

FAMILY BUCCINIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS BUCCINOPSIS CONRAD, 1857

(Not *Buccinopsis* Deshayes, 1865, not *Buccinopsis* Jefferys, 1867, not *Buccinopsis* (Bayle) Mayer, 1876)

***Buccinopsis globosa* (Gabb, 1876)**

Nassa globosa Gabb, 1876A: p. 282 (in part); Boyle, 1893: p. 190; Weller, 1907: p. 738, pl. 86, f. 1; Wade, 1926: p. 146.

Seminola globosa (Gabb, 1876). Stephenson, 1923: p. 375, pl. 93, f. 8-9; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 59, pl. 55, f. 6; Wick, 2021: p. 119, t. 2.

Buccinopsis globosa (Gabb, 1876). Sohl, 1964A: p. 171; Sohl and Christopher, 1983: p. 9, t. 2; Wick, 2021: p. 118, t. 2.

Types – *Nassa globosa* Gabb, 1876; Syntypes: ANSP 2304-2306.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 738 pl. 86, f. 1; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 59 pl. 55, f. 6 (NJSM 7684).

Description – "Shell subglobose, with a short anterior beak, spire moderately elevated, volutions six or more in number. The dimensions of a large, somewhat imperfect and distorted internal cast are total height, 45 mm.; greatest width after correcting for the distortion, about 37 mm. Volutions of the spire marked by rather broad, vertical nodes which reach nearly from suture to suture, their greatest prominence being somewhat above the mid-height; body volution marked by similar nodes which are continued anteriorly, dying out about two-thirds of the distance from the suture to the anterior extremity, these nodes are broad, separated by about equally broad depressions, and are most prominent a little below the suture. Surface of the shell marked throughout by moderately coarse, depressed, revolving ribs, the distance from center to center of the larger ones upon the example whose dimensions are given above being about 2 mm." - Weller (1907) p. 738.

FIGURE 138: *BUCCINOPSIS GLOBOSA* (GABB, 1876) A: NJSM 7684 (Kw)

GENUS *HYDROTRIBULUS* WADE, 1916
Hydrotribulus elegans Sohl, 1964

Hydrotribulus elegans Sohl, 1964A: p. 170, 246, pl. 36 f. 13-16, 18; Kuehne, 1999: p. 77; Bandel and Dockery, 2012: p. 100; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 76.

Types – *Hydrotribulus elegans* Sohl, 1964; Holotype: USNM 130458; Paratypes: USNM 130459-130461

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2882b.

Description – “Shell of medium size, spire somewhat less than half the total shell length; pleural angle 70 – 80 degrees. Protoconch consisting of about two regular smooth surfaced volutions; junction with conch gradual, accompanied by flattening of the upper whorl surface and addition of spiral cords to the whorl sides. Whorls shouldered with a well-rounded periphery and constricted posteriorly to a moderately strong collar and constricted anteriorly to a curved pillar. Suture impressed. Sculpture strong; two broad strong spiral cords are visible on the penultimate whorl between shoulder and suture, these are the upper two of the four equispaced primary cords of the periphery; sometimes a few faint spiral lirae occur above the shoulder; on the basal slope and the siphonal canal progressively weaker cords appear; transverse ribs number 13-15 on the body whorl, are strongest at the shoulder, and

pronouncedly diminish in vigor on the anterior slope. Growth lines prosocline between suture and shoulder, almost orthocline in trend over the rounded whorl sides with shallow minor sinuses formed where the lines cross the primary spiral cords. Aperture subovate, posterior notch broadly and shallow, bounded by a parietal tooth, siphonal canal of moderate length, twisted, and inclined to the left; outer lip thin at edge, thickening within on later stages, crenulate at edge and bearing several teeth above the siphonal canal; inner lip callus well defined, narrowing on columellar lip. Columella bearing a broad swelling immediately above the siphonal canal.” – Sohl (1964) p. 246.

FIGURE 139: *HYDROTRIBULUS ELEGANS* SOHL, 1964 A-B: MAPS A2882A (Ks) C: MAPS A2882B (Kw)

FAMILY *CANCELLARIIDAE* FORBES AND HANLEY, 1851

GENUS *MATAXA* WADE, 1916
Mataxa elegans Wade, 1916

Mataxa elegans Wade, 1916: p. 456, pl. 23, f. 1, 2, 3; Cossman, 1917: p. 99; Cossman, 1925: p. 255, pl. 11 f. 7, 8; Wade, 1926: p. 109, pl. 35, f. 9, 10; Wenz, 1943: p. 1271, f. 3617; Sohl, 1964A: p. 267, pl. 45, f. 20-27; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 219, 303, f. 227; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 64; Bandel and Dockery, 2012: p. 103; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 78.

Mataxa valida Stephenson, 1941: p. 365, pl. 70 f. 1-3, 6, 7.

Types – *Mataxa elegans* Wade, 1916; Holotype: USNM: 32846

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2924b.

Description —Shell of medium size, ovate in outline; spire less than half the entire length of the shell; whorls of conch three and a half in number; protoconch large, smooth and obtuse, thrice coiled, the first and second volutions for the most part immersed and coiled in a single plane, the final whorl of the protoconch moderately elevated, increasing rapidly in size; surface of conch slightly glazed and inconspicuously sculptured; axials reduced to fine incrementals and one or two exaggerated resting stages; spiral sculpture of low, broad, flattened bands, eight in number upon the penultima of the type, the two posterior the widest and separated from one another by a wide and rather deep sulcus; body spirals very obscure, increasingly so toward the aperture, more than 30 in number, interspaces wider than the spirals and very shallow, excepting directly in front of the suture; suture impressed; aperture more than half the entire length of the shell, lenticular in outline and produced anteriorly into a comparatively long canal; outer lip marked internally by 10 or 12 regularly spaced Urate denticles; columella reinforced with two rather strong oblique folds a little less than half way between the base of the body and the anterior extremity of the aperture and a less prominent marginal fold and occasionally a fourth feeble plication behind the margin; anterior fasciole rather short, moderately wide, emarginate at the extremity". – Wade (1916) p. 156.

FIGURE 140: *MATAXA ELEGANS* WADE, 1916 A-D: MAPS A2924b (KW): A: MOLD B-D: VIEWS OF THE SAME CAST

GENUS PALADMETE GARDNER, 1916

***Paladmete cancellaria* (Conrad, 1858)**

Trichotropis cancellaria Conrad, 1858: p. 333, pl. 35, f. 8; Gabb, 1859: p. 9; Boyle, 1893: p. 285; Crider, 1906: p. 21.

Cancellaria eufaulensis Gabb, 1960: p. 390, 391, pl. 68, f. 8; Gabb, 1861A: p. 98; Boyle, 1893: p. 74.

Paladmete cancellaria (Conrad, 1858). Gardner, 1916: p. 414, pl. 18, f. 14, 15; Cossman, 1925: p. 27, pl. 11, f. 15, 16; Wade, 1926: p. 107; Conant, 1942: p. 25; Sohl, 1964A: p. 171, 271, pl. 45, f. 29-34; Sohl, 1964B: p.382, pl. 56, f. 4; Vermeij and Dudley, 1982: p. 400; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 14, 22, 23-25, 32, 34, 97, 144-146, 152, 155, 163, 177, 179, 180, 183-187, 190, 192, 194, 196, 197, 213, 215, 225, 227, 231, 239; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 136, 138, 140, 142, 145, 148, 151, 154, 157, 160, 162; Gallagher, 1986: p. 30; Harstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Elder, 1996: p. 266, f. 7.21; Akers and Akers, 1997: p. 223, 224, 304, f. 233, 234; Kuehne, 1999: p. 71, 77; Kosnick, 2005: App.; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 64; Bandel and Dockery, 2012: p. 103; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 60; Witts, Landman, et. al., 2018: f. 10Z.

Paladmete densata Wade, 1926: p. 108, pl. 35, f. 7, 8; Sohl, 1964A: p. 272

Trichotropis (Palaeadmete) cancellaria Conrad, 1858.
Wenz, 1940: p. 891, f. 2621.

Paladmete peocilma Haribson, 1945: p. 87, pl. 3, f. 17-18; Sohl, 1964A: p. 171, pl. 45, f. 28.

Paladmete cf. cancellaria (Conrad, 1858). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 37; Elder, 1994: p. 18, 22.

Paladmete aff. Paladmete cancellaria (Conrad, 1858). Sohl and Mello, 1970: p. 40, 42.

Types – *Trichotropis cancellaria* Conrad, 1858; Holotype ANSP 14692.

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; MAPS A2849b.

Description – “Acutely subovate; volutions five; spire subscalariform; body whorl ventricose; longitudinal ribs. narrow, prominent, distant; revolving lines prominent, distant, with an occasional minute intermediate line; columella profoundly incurved; labium reflected; base subumbilicated; shoulder of body volution with minute revolving lines, and one larger than the others.” – Conrad (1858) p. 333.

“Shell small, nassoid in outline, spire a little higher than the aperture; whorls seven in number, the earlier turns increasing regularly in size, broadly convex, the later tabulated posteriorly; nuclear turns approximately three in number, the initial whorl and a half very small and largely immersed in the succeeding volution, the final nuclear turn relatively elevated and broadly convex; external surface cancellated, axial sculpture of about 15 narrow, rounded, sharply pinched costals, separated by wider concave intercostals; axials tending to become irregular and to evanesce upon the final half turn and upon the base of the pillar; axials overridden by narrow, flattened, equisized and equispaced spiral fillets, uniform in character upon the costal and intercostal areas, separated by channeled interspaces, slightly wider than the spirals; primaries four in number upon the penultima and five or six on the ultima; two or three secondaries developed upon the shoulder and three or four at the base of the body; body whorl evenly rounded anteriorly; aperture holostomous, ovate to lenticular, outer lip thin, simple, broadly arcuate; inner lip excavated at the base; aperture constricted at its anterior extremity to form an incipient canal; parietal wall calloused; umbilicus closed by the reverted labium; area directly behind it feebly depressed. Conrad's description implies a perforate shell, but there has

been not even a chink of an umbilical opening in any of the numerous individuals examined from the Gulf as well as from Maryland” – Gardner (1916) p. 414.

FIGURE 141: PALADMETE CANCELLARIA (CONRAD, 1858) A-C: MAPS A2849B (Kw)

FAMILY FASCIOLARIIDAE GRAY, 1853

GENUS ORNOPSIS WADE, 1916

***Ornopsis glenni* Wade, 1916**

Ornopsis glenni Wade, 1916: p. 463, pl. 24, f. 1; Cossman, 1917: p. 99; Cossman, 1925: p. 251, pl. 10, f. 33; Wade, 1926: p. 126: p. pl. 44, f. 8, 9, 12, 13; Vermeij and Dudley, 1982: p. 400; Saul and Popenoe, 1993: p. 371, 372; Brister and Young, 2007: p. 63.

Ornopsis (Ornopsis) glenni Wade, 1916. Sohl, 1964A: p. 215, pl. 29, f. 8-10, 15, 16; Squires and Saul, 2006: p. 66, 67, 71.

Types – *Ornopsis glenni* Wade, 1916; Holotype: USNM 32883; Hypotypes: USNM 130354, 130355.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2843a, KS2396.

Description – “Description.—Shell fairly large and strong; elevation of spire less than length of aperture;

protoconch very small, smooth, paucispiral and trochoid; volutions of conch six in number, increasing in size from a very small apical whorl to an inflated body whorl; external ornamentation well-defined, axials elevated, well rounded and short, beginning at shoulder and quickly evanescent in front of the periphery of body, becoming less prominent toward aperture and disappearing almost entirely in some individuals, costae of varying size and spacing, twelve on body of type; spiral lines sharply impressed, more than thirty on body whorl, becoming fine and oblique on pillar; shoulder broad, feebly convex; suture impressed; body whorl abruptly constricted into a slender pillar; aperture pyriform, produced anteriorly into a narrow canal sinistrally inclined; outer lip sharp and marginally crenate; parietal wall washed with a callus thickest at posterior extremity of aperture; columella flattened at the entrance of the canal into a shelf-like fold." – Wade (1916) p. 463

FIGURE 142: *ORNOPSIS GLENNI* WADE, 1916 A: MAPS A2843A (KW)

GENUS *PIESTOCHILUS* MEEK, 1864

Piestochilus kanei (Gabb, 1862)

Voluta kanei Gabb, 1862A: p. 323; Meek, 1864: p. 21; Conrad, 1868: p. 730; Boyle, 1893: p. 312

Volutomorpha kanei (Gabb, 1862). Gabb, 1876A: p. 293; Boyle, 1893: p. 313; Johnson, 1905: p. 25; Sohl, 1964A: p. 253.

Volutomorpha (Piestochilus) kanei (Gabb, 1862). Whitfield, 1892A: p. 76, pl. 6, f. 19-20; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 76, pl. 6, f. 19-20.

Piestochilus kanei (Gabb, 1862). Weller, 1907: p. 784, pl. 96, f. 5-9; Richards and Ramsdell, 1976: p. 76, pl. 61, f. 4-5.

Types – *Voluta kanei* Gabb, 1862; Holotype; ANSP 14381

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 748 pl. 96, f. 5-6.

Description – "Shell small, short elliptical in outline, with a short, pointed spire and proportionally long body volution; volutions probably about four, ventricose, largest above the middle and attenuate below; aperture large, elongate elliptical, widest above the middle and narrow below. Columella moderately strong, marked by two distinct and distant plications below the middle of the aperture; surface of the shell so far as can be seen on the inside of the case of the outer volution in one of the type specimens, marked by a few spiral ridges and by distant vertical plications or folds, but which are not transmitted to the internal cast in any of the individuals seen." - Whitfield (1892) p. 76.

FIGURE 143: *PIESTOCHILUS KANEI* (GABB, 1861) A-B: WELLER, 1907 PL. 96 F. 5,6 (KW)

GENUS *REMERA* STEPHENSON, 1941*Remera flexicostata* Sohl, 1964

Remera flexicostata Sohl, 1964A: p. 170, 227, pl. 31 f. 1-2; Sohl and Koch, 1983: p. 32, 187, 213, 239; Sohl and Koch, 1984: p. 142, 144, 148, 151, 154, 157, 162; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 89; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 77; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1.

Types – *Remera flexicostata* Sohl, 1964; Holotype; USNM 130392; Paratypes: 130393, 130394.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2858c.

Description – “Medium-sized fusiform shells; spire high, evenly tapering; pleural angle 20-25 degrees. Protoconch unknown, sutures impressed. Whorl sides gently convex, rounding over base to a tapering pillar. Sculpture of moderately strong collabral ribs that become lower and more sinuous in latest growth stages; ribs number 18-20 per whorl. Spiral ornament consists of low close-spaced spiral ribbons on whorl sides that are weaker where they override the transverse ribs and become wider spaced lirae on the base. Growth lines almost orthocline near suture, becoming decidedly opisthocline over periphery, swinging arcuately to strongly known; lenticular in outline as preserved, posteriorly angulated, siphonal canal of moderate length and straight. Inner lip callus best developed over upper part of columellar lip. Columella straight and smooth.” – Sohl (1964A) p. 227.

FIGURE 144: *REMERA FLEXICOSTATA* SOHL, 1964 A: MAPS A2858c (Kw) B-C: MAPS A2858B (Ks)

FAMILY MURICIDAE RAFINESQUE, 1815

GENUS *SARGANA* STEPHENSON, 1923

Description – “Low, almost flat spire, the broad, deep spiral sulcus which emerges from beneath the inner lip about midway of the aperture and extends around to the lower end of the outer lip and pronounced fold or ridge at the angle separating the columella from the canal.” – Stephenson (1923) p. 377.

Sargana sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2816d.

FIGURE 145: *SARGANA* SP. A-B: MAPS A2816c (Kns)

FAMILY PERISSITYIDAE POPENOE, SAUL 1987

GENUS *PYROPSIS* CONRAD, 1860

Description – “Medium to large-sized subpyriform shells having low to very low spires, peripherally expanded whorls that are shouldered and strongly constricted anteriorly, and a long, tapering, siphonal canal. Sculpture ornate, dominated by noded to spinose spiral cords. Aperture thickened within, inner lip heavily callused, columella smooth, except for a broad weak to strong swelling above the siphonal canal that leaves an umbilical chink at the upper edge of the columella lip.” – Sohl (1964A) p. 234.

Pyropsis sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 30; KS2244.

FAMILY PHOLIDOTOMIDAE COSSMAN, 1896

GENUS *BELLIFUSUS* STEPHENSON, 1941

Description – “Medium-sized fusiform shells; spire a little more than one-third total shell height. Whorls generally inflated above midheight, constricted posteriorly to a transversely wrinkled collar, and bearing a sharp to well-rounded shoulder. Ornament of strong collabral transverse ribs that die out on

basal slope and spiral cords and lirae that cover surface or are restricted to lower body slope. Aperture sublenticular, siphonal canal moderately long and open. Columella slightly twisted with a strong plication anterior to a weaker fold." – Sohl (1964A) p. 202.

Bellifusus sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2889j; KS2250.

FIGURE 146: *BELLIFUSUS* SP. A-B: MAPS A2889J (KW)

GENUS *VOLUTODERMA* GABB, 1877
Volutoderma biplicata (Gabb, 1860)

Volutilithes biplicata Gabb, 1860A: p. 300, 301, pl. 48, f. 6; Gabb, 1861A: p. 149; Conard, 1868: p. 730; Boyle, 1893: p. 313; Richards, 1968: p. 107.

Rostellites biplicata (Gabb, 1860). Meek, 1864: p. 21, Conrad, 1868: p. 729.

Volutoderma biplicata (Gabb, 1860). Gabb, 1876A: p. 292; Whitfield, 1829A: p. 90, pl. 10, f. 1-2; Whitfield, 1829B: p. 90, pl. 10, f. 1-2; Boyle, 1893: p. 313; Whitfield, 1899: p. 177; Johnson, 1905: p. 25; Weller, 1907: p. 775, pl. 91 f. 13-17; Richards and Ramsdell, 1956: p. 71, 78, pl. 59, f. 8, 11; Gallagher, 1984: p. 14, 19.

Types – *Volutilithes biplicata* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP: 14420

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 775 pl. 91, f. 13-14; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 78.

Description - "Shell of medium size, robust, pyriform in outline, with a low spire and very large body volution; whorls three to four, ventricose, largest above the middle and narrowed below; aperture very large, elongate, two-thirds the length of the shell and

semielliptical, straightened on the inner side and rounded on the outer margin; columella strong, marked by two strong oblique folds near the middle of its length.; surface unknown, but on the inner volution of the type there are a few distant vertical plications, faintly indicated, but which do not extend below the most ventricose part of the whorl." - Whitfield (1892) p. 90.

FIGURE 147: *VOLUTODERMA BIPLICATA* (GABB, 1860) A-B: WELLER, 1907 PL. 91 F. 13-14 (KW)

FAMILY *TURBINELLIDAE* SWAINSON, 1840

GENUS *NAPULUS* STEPHENSON, 1941
Napulus retifer (Gabb, 1860)

Fusus retifer Gabb, 1860A: p. 301, pl. 48, f. 11; Gabb, 1861A: p. 108; Meek, 1864: p. 22; Conrad, 1868: p.730; Richards, 1968: p. 182.

Perissolax retifer (Gabb, 1860). Conrad, 1868: p. 730; Squires, 2011: p. 1202.

Dolium (Doliopsis) multiliratum Whitfield, 1892A: p. 121, pl. 15, f. 4-6; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 121, pl. 15, f. 4-6; Whitfield, 1899: p. 169.

Pyropsis retifer (Gabb, 1860). Whitfield, 1892A: p. 38, pl. 2, f. 1-4; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 38, pl. 2, f. 1-4; Clark, 1893: p. 196; Clark, 1897: p. 336; Clark, 1898: p. 186; Woolman, 1898: p. 38, pl. 2, f. 1-4; Whitfield, 1899: p. 174; Johnson, 1905: p. 24; Weller, 1907: p. 749, pl. 88, f. 7-13; Gardner, 1916: p. 452, pl. 15, f. 9-10; Sohl, 1964A: p. 235.

Napulus retifer (Gabb, 1860). Stephenson, 1941: p. 318; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 48, pl. 54, f. 13; Squires, 2011: p. 1204, t. 2.

Types – *Fusus retifer* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP: 13936

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 749 pl. 88, f. 12-13; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 48.

Description – “Shell small, pyriform, or without the anterior canal subglobular in form, the dimensions of a large individual being height, 22 mm., or probably 25 mm., if the anterior beak were complete; maximum diameter, 18 mm.; height of spire, 6 mm. Volutions about three, rounded, ventricose and rapidly increasing in size, rapidly contracting below to the short anterior beak, spire low, conical, sutures well marked in the cast; aperture large, subcircular on the outer margin, about two-thirds as high as the total height of the shell; columellar cavity in the cast rather narrow. Surface of the casts marked by 8 or 10 spiral ridges upon the body volution, placed at nearly equal intervals, also by fainter vertical ridges which appear usually to have been placed at nearly equal intervals to those of the spiral ridges, though occasionally they are somewhat closer. Upon the external surface, as shown in impressions of the outside, the revolving and vertical ribs are much more conspicuous than on the casts, their intersections being marked by small, rounded nodes.” – Weller (1907) p. 749.

FIGURE 148: *NAPULUS RETIFER* (GABB, 1860) A-B: WELLER, 1907 PL. 88 FIG. 12, 13 (Kw)

Napulus sp.

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kuehne (1999) p. 64; MAPS A2859i

FIGURE 149: *NAPULUS* SP. A: MAPS A2859i (Kw)

GENUS **TURBINELLA** LAMARCK, 1799
Turbinella alabamensis (Gabb, 1860)

Cancellaria alabamensis Gabb, 1860B: p. 301, pl. 48, f. 14, (f. 26 on plate); Gabb, 1861A: p. 98; Boyle, 1893: p. 74; Richards, 1968: p. 98.

Turbinopsis alabamensis (Gabb, 1860). Gabb, 1862A: p. 321.

Turbinopsis? *alabamensis* (Gabb, 1860). Meek, 1864: p. 19.

Pyropsis alabamensis (Gabb, 1860). Gabb, 1876A: p. 285, 286; Woolman, 1893: p. 221; Boyle, 1893: p. 251; Johnson, 1905: p. 24; Sohl, 1964A: p. 235.

Turbinella? *verticalis* Whitfield, 1892A: p. 82, pl. 3, f. 13-14; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 82, pl. 3, f. 13-14; Clark, 1897: p. 330; Clark, 1898: p. 179; Whitfield, 1899: p. 176.

Turbinella alabamensis (Gabb, 1860). Weller, 1907: p. 769, pl. 91, f. 1-6; Richards and Ramsdell, 1962: p. 65, pl. 56, f. 5; pl. 59, f. 1; Squires, 2011: p. 1204, t. 2.

Xancus alabamensis (Gabb, 1860). Gardner, 1916: p. 435.

Types – *Cancellaria alabamensis* Gabb, 1860; Holotype: ANSP: 30777

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 769 pl. 91, f. 6; Richards and Ramsdell (1962) p. 65.

Description – “Internal casts, exclusive of the anterior canal, subglobose in form, with a moderately elevated spire, which has an apical angle of about 85, consisting of about three and one-half volutions; the dimensions of a nearly complete internal cast are height, 36 mm.; height of spire, 9 mm.; greatest

diameter, 26 mm. Volutions increasing rather rapidly in size, the last one ventricose in the upper part, rapidly contracted below and produced anteriorly in an elongate anterior canal; aperture elliptical in form, pointed above and prolonged below; columellar cavity of moderate size, with three slender, oblique plications opposite the middle of the aperture; surface of the volutions marked by strong, rounded, vertical plications or folds, which become obsolete a little below the periphery and are also less distinct upon the outer half of the last volution. About 11 of these folds are present upon the outer volution of an average example. A plaster cast of the upper half of a shell from a natural mold has about five volutions, the spire is conical and turritid with an apical angle of about 75; suture well defined; the volutions of the spire strongly angular a little below the middle of the distance between the sutures, the upper surface flattened or slightly concave, the angle marked with strong nodes, of which there are about 12 on each volution. Upper surface of the body volution nearly flat, sloping downward from the suture to the angular periphery, which is marked by strong nodes similar to those of the upper volutions; below the periphery the surface is gently convex as far as the specimen continues, Surface marked by fine revolving costae, and by lines of growth which, just below the suture, are as strong or stronger than the revolving costae. The direction of the lines of growth indicate that the outer lip of the aperture was broadly sinuate in its upper part." – Weller (1907) p. 769.

FIGURE 149A: *Turbinella alabamensis* (Gabb, 1860).
A-C: ANSP 3077 (Type: Prairie Bluff Chalk); D -
Richards, 1962, pl. 56. f. 1 (Kns); E – Whitfield, 1892,
pl. 3, f. 14 (“Lower Green Marls”)

FAMILY VASIDAE ADAMS & ADAMS, 1853

GENUS LUPIRA STEPHENSON, 1941

Lupira pyriformis Stephenson, 1941

Lupira pyriformis Stephenson, 1941: p. 360, pl. 69, f. 1, 2; Haribson, 1945: p. 87; Sohl, 1964A: p. 233, pl. 32, f. 10-11; Bandel and Dockery, 2016: p. 75.

Lupira polycyma Haribson, 1945: p. 86-87, pl. 5, f. 31, 32.

Types – *Lupira pyriformis* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: ANSP: 20895. Hypotypes: USNM 130416-130418. Paratype: USNM 103758. *Lupira polycyma* Haribson, 1945: Holotype: USNM 20895.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2956a.

Description – “The species is based on one shell, probably juvenile. Shell small, pyriform, with 4 or 5 volutions. Spire low; spiral angle about 98 degrees. Whorls increasing rapidly in size. Body whorl greatly inflated in the upper half, constricted to a narrow canal below. Protoconch broken away, but the scar is small. Suture narrowly but not deeply impressed.

Shoulder of medium width and moderately excavated. Body whorl with 12 strong axials, narrower than the interspaces, extending well down the basal slope, represented across the shoulder by gentle swells, oblique forward. From the shoulder down the body whorl is ornamented with about 16 rather weak spiral ridges narrower than the interspaces, coarsest low on the base and most obscure on the steepest part of the slope; they override the axials. The shoulder is covered with small, closely crowded obscure spiral lirae. The upper ends of the axials are exposed on the penultimate and antepenultimate whorls. Aperture widest above, very narrow anteriorly where it forms an elongated, slightly twisted canal; anal canal very small, not well preserved. Outer lip broken away, but is strongly arched at the inflation. Inner lip broadly excavated above the middle, forming a thin callus on the parietal wall. Columella twisted, bearing a broad swell above the canal; the swell is paralleled by a broad depression above which the ends of two moderately strong columellar folds are visible; additional small folds are surmised to be present farther back in the matrix-filled cavity, as on the topotype of *Lupira variabilis* (Wade).” – Stephenson (1941) p. 360-361.

FIGURE 150: *LUPIRA PYRIFORMIS* STEPHENSON, 1941 A-B: MAPS A2956A (Kw) INTERNAL MOLDS C: INTERNAL CAST

Gastropoda incertae sedis

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS Site 105a

FIGURE 151: GASTROPODA INCERTAE SEDIS A-C: THREE VIEWS OF AN UNIDENTIFIED WENONAH FORMATION GASTROPOD

CLASS **CEPHALOPODA** Cuvier, 1795

ORDER **AMMONITIDA** Hyatt, 1889

FAMILY **BACULITIDAE** GILL, 1871

GENUS **BACULITES** LAMARCK, 1799

***Baculites texanus* Kennedy and Cobban, 1999**

Types – *Baculites texanus* Kennedy and Cobban, 1999; Holotype: ANSP: 475059

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30 (*Baculites scotti*); Kennedy, Cobban (1994A) p. 107, f. 8.1-8.3 USNM 445188; f. 8,12, f. 8.17-8.19 USNM 445189 (*Baculites scotti*); MAPS A2003a; MAPS A2003b, MAPS A2003c.

Description – “A moderate sized baculite that has a robust cross section, rather high angle of taper in early adult growth stage, and strong ornament of broad, arcuate flank swellings and weak, irregular ventral ribbing.

The holotype, a young adult or possibly a microconch, consists of the adapical half of a body chamber attached to the last four chambers of the phragmocone. The specimen has a length of 91 mm and an angle of taper of 7 degrees. The intercostal cross section is oval; dimensions at the large end are height 29.3 mm and breadth 22.0 mm; at the small end, height 20.4 mm and breadth 14.1 mm. Flanks very broadly rounded, the dorsum is broadly rounded, and the venter more narrowly rounded. Large, broad, high, crescentic ribs that occupy most of the flank are the dominant ornament. They are spaced at two in a distance equal to the whorl height. Weak ribs of irregular strength and spacing are present on the venter. ... The suture of *B. texanus* sp. n. is moderately digitate and is typical of the genus in having symmetrically bifid lobes and saddles.” – Kennedy and Cobban (1999) p. 76.

FIGURE 152: *BACULITES TEXANUS* KENNEDY, COBBAN, 1999
A-D: MAPS A2003B (Kw)

FIGURE 153: *BACULITES TEXANUS* KENNEDY, COBBAN, 1999
SUTURE PATTERN A: HOLOTYPE, USNM 475059; B:
PARATYPE, USNM 475061

***Baculites* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Kennedy, Cobban (1994A) p. 107 f. 8.4-8.6,8.14-8.16,10 USNM 445183, 445184, 445200; MAPS A2042a

FAMILY **DIPLOMOCERATIDAE** SPATH, 1926

GENUS **GLYPTOXOCERAS** SPATH, 1925

Description – “Initial helix followed by loose, regular or elliptical coiling, normally with more or less straight shaft and hook in questionable microconchs; section circular to oval; ribs annular, sharp, straight, close or

distant; a few collared constrictions present” - Wright, Calloman and Howarth (1996) p. 250.

Glyptoxoceras sp.

Wenonah Specimens –MAPS A2043b

The table below lists all NACP occurrences of the Genus *Glyptoxoceras*.

FIGURE 154: GLYPTOXOCERAS SP. A: MAPS A2043B (KW)

GENUS PARASOLENOCERAS COLLIGNON, 1969

Description – “All ribs with outer ventrolateral tubercles only, but there may be slight swellings at inner ventrolateral position; several ribs may be united at slightly enlarged ventrolateral spine, but ribs are not markedly enlarged” - Wright, Calloman and Howarth (1996) p. 253.

***Parasolenoceras* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Kennedy, Cobban (1994A) p. 107; USNM 445158

GENUS SOLENOCERAS CONRAD, 1860

Description – “Generally small; initial few spiral whorls followed by 2, straight or slightly curved, parallel shafts; section circular to oval; first shaft normally constricted; aperture constricted and collared; ribs straight, radial or rursiradiate, with small ventrolateral spines; ribs may be weak or interrupted on venter” - Wright, Calloman and Howarth (1996) p. 253.

***Solenoceras annulifer* (Morton, 1843)**

Hamites annulifer Morton, 1843A (1841) p. 109, 110; Morton, 1842: p. 213, pl. 11 f. 4; Gabb, 1869: p. 143; Johnson, 1905; Kennedy, Landman, Cobban and Scott, 2000.

Solenoceras annulifer (Morton, 1843). Conrad, 1860: p. 284; Gabb, 1861A: p. 81; Conrad, 1869A: p. 360; Boyle, 1893: p. 265; Johnson, 1905: p. 27; Stephenson, 1941: p.398; Reeside, 1962: p. 121, pl. 70, f. 8-10; Cobban, 1974A: p. 81-83; Kennedy and Cobban, 1994B: p. 1295, f. 11.1-11.11, 13.2; Jagt and Neumann, 2006: p. 572; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014: p. 167.

Ptychoceras (Solenoceras) annulifer (Morton, 1843). Meek, 1864: p. 23; Clark, 1892A: p. 198; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 273, pl. 45, f. 6-8; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 273, pl. 45, f. 6-8; Clark, 1893B: p. 198; Weller, 1907: pl. 107, f. 7-9.

Types – *Hamites annulifer* Morton, 1843; Holotype: ANSP 4789.

Wenonah Specimens - MAPS A2039c.

Description – “Holotype is complete body chamber of 21 mm long and 5 mm in diameter, and only specimen known to previous authors. Ten specimens present in collections from Biggs Farm. Adult shell small consisting of two closely adpressed shafts. Largest body chamber known is holotype. A number of fragments show curved section and parts of two limbs. Whorl section of smaller shaft depressed reniform and expands slowly. Fine, dense, concave ribs on dorsum strengthen markedly across dorsolateral area, where they are slightly convex; they then become markedly prorsiradiate on flanks, where rib index is 5-6. Ribs pass across venter and bear delicate transversely elongated ventral tubercles. Larger shaft has depressed reniform whorl section with whorl breadth to height ration of 0.8 and deep dorsal sulcus to accommodate dorsum of smaller shaft. Rib direction changes from prorsi- to recti- to rursiradiate around curved portion of shell. Ribs sharp and narrow on flank, where rib index is 5-6; ribs pass straight across venter ornamented by minute ventral tubercles. Periodic constrictions first appear on curved portion; there are two on body chamber of holotype, one perhaps marking proximity of aperture. Suture simple with little-incised bifid lobes and saddles.” – Kennedy and Cobban (1994) p. 1295.

FIGURE 155: *SOLENOCERAS ANNULIFER* (MORTON, 1843) A-E: MAPS A2039c (Kw)

FAMILY NOSTOCERATIDAE HYATT, 1894

GENUS *DIDYMO CERAS* HYATT, 1900

Description – “Loosely and irregularly coiled at first, even hamitoid; then helicoid with whorls just or not touching; body chamber pendent, U-shaped; ribs numerous, irregularly branching and looped, some with 2 rows of ventral tubercles.” – *Wright, Calloman and Howarth (1996) p. 247.*

Didymoceras binodosum (Kennedy and Cobban, 1993)

Bostrychoceras socoense Young, 1963: p. 42 (pars), pl. 4, f. 8 only.

Didymoceras cf. secoenes [sic] (Young, 1963). Blaszkiwicz, 1980: p. 24, pl. 5, f. 4, 6, pl. 7, f. 16, 19.

Didymoceratoides binodosum Kennedy and Cobban, 1993. Kennedy and Cobban (1993D), p. 92, f. 8.1, 8.2, 8.5, 8.6, 8.13-8.15, 8.22-8.24, 8.28, 8.29, 8.32, 8.33, 8.35-39, 9.1-9.3, 12.1; Emerson, Emerson, Akers and Akers (1994), p. 314, unnumbered figures.

Didymoceras binodosum (Kennedy and Cobban, 1993). Larson, Johnson, Farrar and Larson (1997); Kennedy and Cobban (1997): p. 67; Kennedy and Cobban (1999): p. 72, pl. 1-4, pl. 5 f. 11-20, text-f. 3-4; Kennedy, Cobban and Scott (2000): p. 228, pl. 1,

2; pl. 3, f. 4-7, pl. 4, 5; pl. 10 f. 2-4, pl. 12 f. 14,15; text f. 2, 3; Garb, Johnson and Chamberlin (2007); Kennedy, Tunoglu, Walaszczyk and Ertekin (2007): p. 870, f. 3A, 3D, 7H, 7D-F, 8A-F; Jorgensen, Larson, Landman and Cobban (2010).

Nostoceras (Didymoceras) cf. binodosum (Kennedy and Cobban, 1993). Summersberger and Kennedy (2004): p. 176.

Types – *Didymoceratoides binodosum* Kennedy and Cobban, 1993A; Holotype: USNM 441521.

Wenonah Specimens- MAPS A2022a, MAPS A2022c.

Description - Holotype from Pierre Shale is a nearly complete adult, whereas Annona specimens are all fragments that overlap in size with type or are larger. Protoconch not preserved, but an initial half whorl progressively develops ribs. This is succeeded by 1.5 whorls that form a low spire with whorls just in contact, followed by an elliptical nearly planispiral criocone of 1.5 whorls. Whorl section depressed oval. Ornament on phragmocone and adapical parts of body chamber consists of simple ribs; weak and transverse on dorsum but strengthen on dorsolateral area and cross flanks in a slightly rursiradiate course; sharp, high and narrower than interspaces; rib index four or five. All ribs bear sharp septate ventral spines, represented by a rounded tubercle on mold; linked across venter by strong, high rib. Ribbing differentiates on largest fragments with appearance of weaker nontuberculate ribs that alternate with tuberculate ones. Ribs weaken somewhat and may become slightly flexed; nontuberculate ones efface over venter. Yancy material includes juveniles identical with type as well as larger ones with differentiated ribbing that may join in pairs at tubercles, and efface across venter, which seems to be variable adult features. Suture has broad bifid lobes and saddles.” – Kennedy and Cobban (1993) p. 93.

FIGURE 156: *DIDYMO CERAS BINODOSUM* (KENNEDY AND COBBAN, 1993) A-C: MAPS A2022C

Didymoceras sp

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kennedy, Cobban (1994A) p. 106 fig. 9.1-9.29; Kuehne (1999) p. 64. Kenny, Cobban (1994) state there are two undescribed species of *Didymoceras* in f. 9.1-9.29: USNM 445185-445187, 445190-445192, 445195-445199 representing one new species and USNM 445193, USNM 445194.

GENUS *NOSTOCERAS* HYATT, 1894

Description – “Apical angle rather to very obtuse; whorls circular to polygonal in section, in contact until body chamber; body chamber U-shaped, hanging free; 2 or more rows of distinct, small or large tubercles throughout on simple or looped, close or distant ribs. “- Wright, Calloman and Howarth (1996) p. 247.

Nostoceras colubriformis Stephenson, 1941

Nostoceras colubriformis Stephenson, 1941: p. 412, pl. 8, f. 1-3; Scott and Cobban, 1965: p. 3; Cobban, 1974B: p. 8; Kennedy and Cobban, 1993B: p. 9; Kennedy and Cobban, 1993E: p. 431, text-figs. 7.1-4, 7.8-9; Kennedy, Landman, Cobban and Scott, 2000: p. 49; Kennedy, Cobban and Scott, 2000B: p. 8; Ifrim, Stinnesbeck and Lopez-Olivia, 2004: p. 35, 39, pl. 4, f. 1-4; text-fig. 14c; Ifrim, Stinnesbeck and Schafhauser, 2005: p. 51; Stinnesbeck, Ifrim and Salazar, 2012: p. 722.

Nostoceras aff. *Nostoceras colubriformis* Stephenson, 1941. Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A: p. 103, f. 8.13.

Types – *Nostoceras colubriformis* Stephenson, 1941; Holotype: USNM 77265; Paratype: USNM 77266.

Wenonah Specimens – Kennedy and Cobban (1994A) USNM 445176; MAPS A2047a; MAPS A2047d.

Description – “External mold of spire 37.5 mm high consists of parts of seven whorls that have apical angle of 20-25 degrees. Translation rate high and whorls in tight contact. Outer whorl face strongly convex. Ornament of narrow, sharp, prorsiradiate, number about 34-35 per whorl, and bear row of minute tubercles in middle of outer whorl face.” – Kennedy and Cobban (1994A) p. 103.

FIGURE 157: *NOSTOCERAS COLUBRIFORMIS* STEPHENSON, 1941 A-C: MAPS A2407A (Kw)

Nostoceras monotuberculatum Kennedy and Cobban, 1993

Nostoceras monotuberculatum Kennedy and Cobban, 1993D: p. 86, f. 6.14-6.18, 6.22-6.24, 6.26, 6.27, 7.1,7.4,7.5,7.21,7.22, 7.33-7.35, 12.4; Larson, Jorgensen, Farrar, and Larson, 1997: p. 57, unnumbered figures; Kennedy and Cobban, 1997: p. 65, 68, f. 3-3,3-4, 5-12, 5-16,5-17; Kennedy, Landman, Cobban and Scott, 2000: p. 50, f. 19A-C; Serna and Narvaez, 2003; Gallagher, Camburn, Camburn and Hanczaryk, 2014: p. 67; Gallagher and Hanczaryk, 2019: p. 41.

Types – *Nostoceras monotuberculatum* Kennedy and Cobban, 1993; Holotype: USNM 441493; Paratype: USNM 441494-441501.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2038b.

Description – “Coiling both dextral and sinistral with a high spire. Whorls tightly in contact throughout with

a wide concave impressed zone that extends across all of upper whorl face. Outer whorl face high and broadly convex, shoulder between upper and outer whorl faces narrowly rounded, but outer and convex lower whorl faces merge imperceptibly. Umbilicus very narrow. Forty to fifty markedly prorsiradiate ribs on upper part of outer whorl face; ribs cross outer whorl face obliquely and may be concave on upper two-thirds of face, but flex back across juncture of outer and lower whorl faces, then cross lower whorl face in a slight convexity. A single row of transversely elongate weak tubercles present at mid-flank. Precise relationship between ribs and tubercles varies both within and between specimens. All ribs may be tuberculate; a single nontuberculate rib may

alternate with a single tuberculate one, or there may be two nontuberculate ribs between tuberculate ones. Single ribs generally link to tubercles, but a pair of ribs occasionally links at a tubercle or a pair may arise at a tubercle and pass down across lower part of outer whorl face; 16-20 tubercles per whorl. Ribs slant forward across lower whorl face and may join in pairs close to the umbilicus. Two or three strong deep constrictions per whorl with or without weak collar-ribs. Suture has broad, plump elements; E/L asymmetrically bifid, L deep and bifid, U2 large and bifid with shallow incisions." – Kennedy and Cobban (1993) p. 86.

FIGURE 158: *NOSTOCERAS MONOTUBERCULATUM* KENNEDY AND COBBAN 1993 A-C: MAPS A2038B

***Nostoceras puzosiforme* Kennedy and Cobban, 1994**

Nostoceras puzosiforme Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A: p. 103, f. 8.8-8.10.

Types – *Nostoceras puzosiforme* Kennedy and Cobban, 1994; Holotype: USNM: 445177

Wenonah Specimens – Kennedy, Cobban (1994) p. 103, f. 8.8-8.10; USNM 445177.

Description – “Holotype is small fragment of two whorls with maximum preserved whorl height of 10 mm. Translation rate very high with low apical angle of 15.5 degrees. Whorls in tight contact and all of upper whorl face occupied by deep impressed zone to accommodate lower part of preceding whorl.

Juncture of upper and outer whorl faces very narrowly rounded. Upper part of outer whorl face only slightly convex, and remainder of face flattened so that interwhorl suture is associated with only a shallow depression in spire profile. An estimated 30 ribs per whorl at top of exposed whorl face; these may bifurcate, and additional ribs may intercalate, so that just below whorl suture there are about 50 ribs per whorl. Ribs are delicate, prorsiradiate and slightly concave; they sweep across outer whorl face to spiral depression just above lower whorl suture where they weaken markedly before linking, either singly or in pairs, at small obliquely placed bullae at contact of outer and lower whorl faces. On lower whorl face, ribs are much coarser, convex and prorsiradiate. Periodic constrictions, two per whorl, deep and

prorsiradiate and flanked by strong collar ribs. Suture not seen." – Kennedy and Cobban (1994A) p. 103.

FIGURE 159: *NOSTOCERAS PUZOSIFORME* KENNEDY AND COBBAN, 1994 A-C: USNM 445177(KW)

***Nostoceras* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30

FAMILY PACHYDISCIDAE SPATH, 1922

GENUS MENUITES SPATH, 1922

***Menuites portlocki* (Sharpe, 1855) *complexus* (Hall and Meek, 1856)**

Ammonites complexus Hall and Meek, 1856: p. 394, pl. 4, f. 1a-1f; Meek, 1864: p. 24; Conrad, 1868: p. 730; Meek, 1876: p.447, pl. 24, f. 1a-1c; Marcou, 1886: p. 298; Whitfield, 1892A: p. 249, 250, pl. 41, f. 5-7; Whitfield, 1892B: p. 249, 250, pl. 41, f. 5-7; Clark, 1893: p. 198; Whitfield, 1899: p. 177; Diener, 1925: p. 25;

Ammonites complexis [sic] Hall and Meek, 1856. Gabb, 1861A: p. 65.

Pachydiscus complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Cragin, 1893: p. 237; Darton and Siebenthal, 1909" p. 39; Grabau and Shimer, 1910: p. 174; Gardner, 1916: p.378; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 274-278; Cobban and Reeside, 1952: p. 1020; Collignon, 1952: p. 90

Pachydiscus? complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Weller, 1907: p. 819, pl. 101, f. 3, 4

Parapachydiscus complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Spath, 1922: p. 122; Dane, Pierce and Reeside, 1937: p. 230

Anapachydiscus complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Scott and Cobban, 1959: p. 126; Schultz, 1965: p. B2; Scott and Cobban. 1975, listed on map; Kennedy and Cobban, 1976B.

Menuites aff. Menuites complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Reeside, 1962: p. 122, pl. 69, f. 1-6.

Anapachydiscus? complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Scott, 1963: p. 101 (parts).

Menuites n. sp. Scott, 1963: p. 101; Gill, Mereweather and Cobban, 1970: p. 23; Scott and Cobban, 1975: listed on map; Bernstein, 1988; p. 208.

Anapachydiscus n. sp. Gill, Mereweather and Cobban, 1970: p. 23.

Menuites complexus (Hall and Meek, 1856). Gallagher, 1986: p. 30

Menuites portlocki (Sharpe, 1855) *complexus* (Hall and Mee, 1856). Cobban and Kennedy, 1993B: p. 2, pl. 1-3, pl. 4, f. 4-10, pl. 5, f. 1, 5-7, pl. 6, f. 9-15, pl. 7, f. 5, pl. 8 f. 3, 4, text f. 2; Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A: p. 98, f. 3.1 – 3.6; Kennedy and Cobban, 1997: p. 64, f. 3.1, 3.2, 3.5-3.13.

Types – *Ammonites portlocki* (Sharpe, 1855) *complexus* (Hall and Meek, 1856); Lectotype: ANSP 9531/1; Hypotypes USNM 445157, 445159-445161.

Wenonah Specimens – Weller (1907) p. 819 pl. 101, f. 3,4; Reeside 1962 p. 122, pl.69, f. 4-6 (not 1-3=M. *portlocki*) Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; Kennedy, Cobban (1994B) p. 98 fig 3.1-3.12 USNM 445156, USNM 445157, USNM 445159-445161; MAPS A2015a; MAPS A2015b; MAPS A2015c; KS1333.

Description – "Lectotype (Sharpe, 1855, p. 30 pl. 13, f. 2), nearly complete specimen about 82 mm in diameter, has umbilicus of 22 mm (27% of diameter) and a breadth at the adoral end of about 54 mm (66% of diameter) (measurements from plaster cast). Umbilicus has sloping walls and narrowly rounded shoulder. Flanks and venter well rounded. Most of outer whorl has strong, rectiradiate, narrow, widely spaced ribs that number 13 per half whorl at diameter of 62 mm. On this half whorl for strong, nodate umbilical tubercles give rise to pairs of ribs, and two other ribs arise on umbilical shoulder between umbilical tubercles. Ribs decline abruptly near large end of specimen where prominent, rounded ventrolateral tubercles appear at base of body chamber. Paralectotype (Sharpe, 1855, p. 30 pl. 13, f. 2a-c) is septate coil of about 50 mm in diameter with an umbilicus of 15 mm (30%) and breadth of 33 mm (66%) (measurements from plaster cast). Last half

whorl (diameter of 50 mm) has 11 strong, narrow, rectiradiate ribs that arise singly or in pairs from five prominent, bullate umbilical tubercles.

Specimens from the Wenonah Formation are a little smaller and less robust than lectotype, but all have sparsely ribbed phragmocones like paralectotype. Phragmocones stout with rounded flanks and venters. Coiling moderately involute with deep umbilicus; umbilical wall broadly rounded. Whorl section depressed, reniform, with greatest intercostal breadth just outside umbilical shoulder and greatest costal breadth at umbilical bullae. Four to six bullate to nodate umbilical tubercles per half whorl give rise to narrow, sharp ribs either single or in pairs; occasional ribs arise low on flank. All ribs widely separated (9-12 per half whorl), slightly prorsiradiate

to rectiradiate on flanks, and strengthen on crossing venter in broad convexity.

Complete body chambers not present. Intercostal section lunate with greatest width at umbilical shoulder; flanks slightly flattened and venter well rounded. Ribs weaken on older part. Umbilical bullae move out to lower lateral position where they are connected to umbilical shoulder by low, narrow rib. Either pair of weak ribs or single rib loop to ventrolateral tubercles that are weak at beginning of body chamber but large and massive toward aperture. Weak, delicate, irregular ribs are present on flank and venter between major tuberculate ribs. Sutures poorly preserved." – Kennedy and Cobban (1994A) p. 98.

FIGURE 160: *MENUITES PORTLOCKI* (SHARPE, 1855) COMPLEXUS (HALL AND MEEK, 1856) A-C: MAPS A2015B

FAMILY PLACENTICERATIDAE HYATT, 1900

GENUS PLACENTICERAS MEEK, 1876

Placenticerus minor Kennedy and Cobban, 1994

Non Placenticerus placenta (Dekay, 1828). Weller, 1905A1: p. 333; Weller, 1905A2: p. 141; Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A: p. 98-99, f. 4.1-4.5, 4.17-4.18, 4.21, 5.2.

Placenticerus minor Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A: p. 99-103, f. 4.6-4.16, 4.19, 4.20, 5.1, 5.3, 6.1-6.7; Garb, Johnson and Chamberlin, 2007.

Types – *Placenticerus minor* Kennedy and Cobban, 1994; Holotype USNM 445167; Paratype USNM 4454168.

Wenonah Specimens – Kennedy, Cobban (1994) p. 99 figs 4.6-4.16, 4.19, 4.20, 5.1, 5.3, 6.1-6.7; USNM 445167 (Holotype); USNM 445168–445174; MAPS A2001a; MAPS A2001b; MAPS A2001c; MAPS A2001d; MAPS A2001e; KS 1326, KS 1545-1548.

Description – “On phragmocone, coiling involute, with up to 70 % of previous whorl covered. Umbilicus small (15-19% of diameter), shallow, crater-like, with flattened, outward inclined wall. Umbilical shoulder broadly rounded; compressed whorl section (whorl breadth to height ratio about 0.6), has broadly rounded inner flanks and flattened, convergent outer flanks, sharp ventrolateral shoulders, and narrow, concave venter. Four or five small, slightly bullate

umbilical tubercles per half whorl give rise to pairs of very weak prorsiradiate ribs that efface around midflank or may link to small, slightly bullate outer lateral tubercles that number about eight or nine per half whorl. Lateral tubercles give rise to low, concave ribs separated by concave lirae and striae that sweep forward to ventrolateral shoulder. Delicate ventral clavi that number 16-18 per half whorl alternately placed on either side of venter. Twice as many ventral clavi as outer lateral tubercles. Ventral clavi disappear at end of adult phragmocone, and venter is virtually flat, then broadens and ultimately rounds at adult aperture. Umbilical bullae weaken and become elongate giving rise to pairs of prorsiradiate riblets that are convex across inner to middle flank. Riblets may link to lone crescentic outer lateral bullae and then flex forward to become concave on outer flank. Riblets intercalate at various points on flank so that body chamber is covered in dense, weak ornament. Toward adult aperture, where venter rounds, ornament becomes stronger on venter and seeps forward to cross it transversely. Suture has narrow lobes and broadly stemmed saddles. Small adults, interpreted as microconchs, are much as 100 mm in diameter; large adults, interpreted as microconchs, are up to 150 mm diameter.” - Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A. p. 101.

FIGURE 162: *PLACENTICERAS MINOR* KENNEDY AND COBBAN A-C: MAPS A2001D

***Placenticerias* sp.**

Wenonah Specimens – Kuehne (1999) p. 30

FAMILY SCAPHITIDAE GILL, 1871

GENUS TRACHYSCAPHITIES COBBAN AND SCOTT,
1964

***Trachyscaphities pulcherrimus* (Roemer, 1841)**

Scaphites pulcherrimus Roemer, 1841: p. 91 (pars) not pl. 14, f. 4; Schluter, 1872: p. 85, pl. 26, f. 1-5; Grossouvre, 1984: p. 250, pl. 32, f. 6, 9a, b; Arnold, 1968: p. 314, text-fig. 36.

Scaphites multinodosus Hauer, 1866: p. 306, pl. 1 f. 7, 8; Summesberger and Zorn, 2012: p. 103, pl. 5 f. 2a-d.

Scaphites spinosissimus Frech, 1915: p. 564, text-fig. 12.

Acanthoscaphites pulcherrimus (Roemer, 1841). Nowak, 1916: p. 63; Reeside, 1928: p. 33; Mikhailov, 1951: p. 96, pl. 18, f. 83, 84; Naidin and Shimanski, 1959: p. 195, pl. 6, f. 14; Reeside, 1962: p. 33.

Scaphites (Acanthoscaphites) pulcherrimus (Roemer, 1841). Diener, 1925: p. 206; Schormann, 1995: p. 81, t. 2, f. 4.

Trachyscaphites pulcherrimus (Roemer, 1841). Cobban and Scott, 1964: p. E1, E5-E9; Khakhimov, 1972: p. 160, t. 1, f. 3; Cobban, 1973A: p. 695-700, f. 1a-1l, 2a-2g, f. 3; Naidin, 1974: p. 171, pl. 58, f. 5; Atabekian and Khakhimov, 1976: p. 68, pl. 8, f. 3, pl. 12, f. 1; Klinger and Kennedy, 1997: p. 160, pl. 1, f.

3; Blaszkiewicz, 1980: p. 33, pl. 15, f. 1, 4-11; Martinez, 1982: p. 173, pl. 30, f. 7; Kennedy and Summesberger, 1984: p. 171, pl. 11, f. 1,2, pl. 12, f. 1-7, 10-22, pl. 13, f. 2-6; Kennedy, 1986A: p. 132, pl. 13, f. 4, pl. 15, f. 4, pl. 16, f. 8, 9, 12-17; Kennedy and Summesberger, 1986: p. 171, pl. 11, f. 1, 2; pl. 12, f. 1- 7, 10- 22, pl. 13, f. 2- 6; Kennedy and Cobban, 1994A: p. 108, f. 8.7, 8.11, 11.1-11.12; Sugarman, Miller, Burky and Fiegeson, 1995: p. 21; Niebuhr, 1996: p. 275, t. 4, f. 1-5; Kennedy and Kaplan, 1997: p. 65, pl. 69 f. 1, pl. 77 f. 1-5,7-10; Kennedy and Cobban, 1999: p. 77, text-f. 8-9; Kuchler, Kutz and Wagreich, 2001; Kennedy and Summesberger, 2001: p. 90, t. 1; Sugarman, Stanford, Owens and Brenner, 2005; Jagt and Nuemann, 2006: p. 567, 568, 572, 574.

Scaphites (Trachyscaphites) pulcherrimus (Roemer, 1841). Niebuhr, 1995: p. 32, t. 9 f. 8-9.

Types – *Scaphites pulcherrimus* Roemer, 1841; Holotype?; *Scaphites multinodosus* Hauer, 1866; Holotype GBA 1866/001/004 (former coll. no. 3480).

Wenonah Specimens – Cobban (1973) p. 695, f.2a-c, g; Gallagher, Parris, Spamer (1986) p. 30; – Kennedy, Cobban (1994A) p. 108, f. 8.7, 8.11; MAPS A2021a; MAPS A2021b; MAPS A2021c.

Description - Coiled phragmocone compressed; umbilicus small, deep, umbilical shoulder narrowly rounded, inner flank broadly rounded, outer flank flattened and convergent, ventrolateral shoulder faceted, venter flat in costal section, rounded intercostally. Elongate bullae perch on umbilical shoulder and give rise to one or two narrow flexuous prorsiradiate primary ribs which branch irregularly once or twice and increase by intercalation, so that rib spacing is constant across flanks. There are small conical inner and outer lateral and small feebly clavate inner and outer ventrolateral tubercles. The latter alternate on either side of the venter and are linked by irregular zig-zag ribs with a small siphonal tubercle. The straight part of the shaft bears a full complement of lateral and ventrolateral tubercles and shows ribs looping between the tubercles in some cases. The siphonal tubercle may decline or persist. The final hook shows a coarsening of ribs at the expense of tubercles and becomes much more markedly prorsiradiate; umbilical, inner and outer ventrolateral tubercles (the latter alternating when viewed in ventral profile) persist, but the laterals are ultimately lost.”- Kennedy (1986) p. 134.

FIGURE 164: *TRACHYSCAPHITES PULCHERRIMUS* (ROEMER, 1841) A-C: MAPS A2021A

Class **SCAPHOPODA** Bronn, 1862
ORDER **DENTALIIDA** Starobogatov, 1974
FAMILY **DENTALIIDAE** CHILDREN, 1834
GENUS **DENTALIUM** LINNAEUS, 1758

Description – “Shell curved and tapering, longitudinally sculptured or smooth, diameter greatest at aperture. Animal has conical foot with an encircling sheath expanded laterally and interrupted dorsally.” -Ludbrook (1960) p. 37.

Dentalium sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2375f.

FIGURE 165: DENTALIUM SP. A: MAPS 2375f

PHYLUM ARTHROPODA von Siebold, 1848
 CLASS THEOCOSTRACA GRUVEL, 1905
 ORDER SCALPHELLOMORPHA BUCKERIDGE,
 NEWMAN, 2006
 FAMILY SCALPELLIDAE PILSBRY, 1907
 GENUS ARCOSCALPELLUM HOEK, 1907
Arcoscalpellum withersi Collins and Mellen, 1973

Arcoscalpellum withersi Collins and Mellen, 1973: p. 371, pl. 3 f. 17,18, pl. 4 f. 5-15; Zullo, 1976: p. 338, f. 3.17-3.29; Canis and Zullo, 1986: p. 186, 188, f. 3.7-3.11; Weisbord, 1980: p. 144, pl. 15, f. 1-10.

Types – *Arcoscalpellum withersi* Collins and Mellen, 1973; Holotype: BMNH 64456; Hypotypes USNM 401567- 401568, MSU 3299-3301.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3775a.

Description – “Carina slightly bowed inward; tectum slightly arched apically, becoming flattened towards the base; parietes and intraparietes well developed in line with one another and inclined almost at right angles to the tectum. Other valves generally robust and much thickened.” – Collins and Mellen (1973) p. 371.

FIGURE 166: ARCOSCALPELLUM WITHERSI A-C: MAPS A3775A (KW)

CLASS MALACOSTRACA Latreille, 1802
 ORDER DECAPODA Latreille, 1802
 FAMILY CALLIANASSIDAE DANA, 1852
 GENUS MESOSTYLUS BRONN AND ROEMER, 1852
Mesostylus mortoni (Pilsbry, 1901)

Callianassa? antiqua Credner, 1870: p. 241.

Callianassa mortoni Pilsbry, 1901. p. 112-114, pl. 1, f. 1-7; Johnson, 1905: p. 28; Weller, 1907: p. 849-851, pl. 111, f. 1-15; Pilsbry, 1916: p. 363, pl. 11, f. 1-3;

Rathbun, 1926: p. 188, pl. 67, f. 1, 2, 4-9; Hayes, 1933: p. 49; Rathbun, 1935: p. 4, 29, t. 1; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 308-312; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 54; Richards, 1956: p. 71, 72; Dorf and Fox, 1957: p. 8; Carey, 1976: p. 222, pl. 10, f. 3, 4; Gallagher, 1984: p. 13, 14, 19, 20; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 23, f. 12; Spamer and Forster, 1988: p. 75; Gallagher, Camburn, Camburn and Hanczaryk, 2014: p. 67; Gallagher and Hanczaryk, 2019: p. 53.

Callianassa conradi Pilsbry, 1901: p. 114, pl. 8-10; Weller, 1907: p. 851, pl. 110 f. 18-22; Pilsbry, 1916: p. 368, pl. 10, f. 5; Hayes, 1933: p. 49; Schweitzer and Feldmann, 2010: p. 34.

Callianassa mortoni marylandica Pilsbry, 1916: p. 366, pl. 11, f. 9-10.

Callianassa conradi punctimanus Pilsbry, 1916: p. 368, pl. 11, f. 4-5; Rathbun, 1935: p. 4, 30, t. 1; Spamer and Forster, 1988: p. 74.

Callianassa clarki Pilsbry, 1916: p. 368, pl. 11 f. 6-8.

Protocallianassa mortoni (Pilsbry, 1901). Mertin, 1941: p. 208; Roberts, 1962: p. 169, pl. 81 f. 8, pl. 83, f. 1-6; Gallagher, Parris and Spamer, 1986: p. 29; Hartstein and Decina, 1986: p. 90; Bishop, 1991: p. 12-13; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehn, 1999: p. 61, 69, 78, 79; Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 14, 29, t. 1, f. 14P; Schweitzer and Feldmann, 2010: p. 39; Feldmann, Schweitzer and Baltzly, 2013: p. 13; Hyzny and Klompaker, 2015: p. 412, 415, t. 1; Boas, Garb, Landman, Rovelli and Larina, 2016; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App B, pl. 1;

Mesostylus mortoni (Pilsbry, 1901). Toolson and Kues, 1996: p. 113, 114, f. 1.2-1.4; Schweitzer and Feldmann, 2012: p. 18-19, f. 3.1-3.5; Feldmann, Schweitzer and Baltzly, 2013: p. 12, f. 4; Lauginiger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014: p. 176; Callahan, Mehling, Denton and Parris, 2014: p. 168, t. 1; Kornecki, 2014: p. 9, 29-31, f. 10.1, 10.6; Tandon, Moyer and Garb, 2016: p. 9, f. 14; Kornecki, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2017: p. 283, f. 6A, 6B.

Mesostylus (sensu lato), cf. M. mortoni (Pilsbry, 1901). Feldmann, Schweitzer and Portell, 2014: p. 35.

Types – *Protocallianassa mortoni* Pilsbury, 1901; Hypotype: WFIS 4059, USNM 335153, USNM 379310, USNM 335833, USNM 335834, USNM 335152; Syntype: WFIS 5478W, ANSP 19669.

Wenonah Specimens – Roberts (1962) p. 169; ANSP 81160; ANSP 81161; MAPS A3205a.

Description – Major palm of the first pair of chelipeds smooth, rectangular, lower proximal angle narrowly rounded, upper and lower edges acute, closely and minutely crenulated and bordered on either side by a row of sockets. Upper edge very oblique, trending inward from front to back almost cristate and strongly deflexed at the proximal angle. Outer surface more convex than the inner, abruptly depressed before the oblique posterior margin and with a papillose prominence high on the palm near the depression. Below the prominence a curved row of four papillae descends to the root of the fixed finger; above the prominence a horizontal row of 3- rarely 4 or 5- papillae extend forward to the distal margin of the palm. Two papillae situated near the median line mark off the inner surface longitudinally into thirds.

Fixed finger curved inward, its lateral angles and the acute crenulated lower edge bordered by sockets. On the occludent surface of the fixed finger there is a low dentelated carina bears a blunt median tooth. Dactylus suddenly attenuated at the tip, which is bent downward at the right angle to the occludent margin; on the occludent surface behind the tip there is a prominent notch followed successively by a dentelated ridge, a hiatus, and a low proximal tooth. The tips of the fingers cross closed, that of the fixed finger outermost and engaging the notch behind the tip of the dactylus.

Wrist more than three-quarters the length of the palm; upper and lower edges acute and crenulated; a forward pointing spine just below the upper distal angle. On the outer surface near the lower distal corner there is a short oblique groove with beaded margins. Merus slightly shorter than the wrist: lower margin straight posteriorly, upper margin convex. Outer surface transversely angulated, coarsely papillated along the angulation and provided with a large tubercle behind the distal articular node. Lower edge of merus acute and serrate. Ischium about three

times longer than its distal height; upper and lower margins slightly convergent proximally, the upper margin with a serrate distal lobe; outer surface moderately convex in a vertical direction and with a longitudinal sulcus below the median line. M

Minor palm of first pair of chelipeds squarish; posterior margin oblique in lateral profile, the lower corner rounded; upper and lower edges acute, crenulate and erect throughout their entire length. Outer surface slightly more convex than the inner, shallowly depressed longitudinally along the upper quarter, the depression marked with 4 to 6 rather evenly spaced papillae. From the proximal papilla of this row of 3 to 6 papillae descend to the root of the finger. Two papillae near the median line of the inner surface divide the palm into thirds longitudinally. Fixed finger slightly shorter than palm, slender. the lateral edges beaded and socketed; outer edge intersected anterior to the half-length by a sharp oblique carina which occupies the proximal portion of the occludent surface. Upper surface of dactylus papillated. The papillated strip narrowing distally to a single row of papillae. Outer surface of dactylus with two subparallel grooves that are separated posteriorly by a double row of papillae. The lower groove bears a line of prominent sockets. Lateral margins of the otherwise smooth occludent surface beaded. Wrist shorter and higher than the major wrist." – Roberts (1962) p. 169.

FIGURE 167: *MESOSTYLUS MORTONI* (PILSBURY, 1901) A-C: MAPS A3205A (Kw)

FAMILY DAKOTICANCRIDAE RATHBURN, 1917

GENUS TETRACARCINUS WELLER, 1905

Tetracarcinus subquadratus Weller, 1905

Tetracarcinus subquadratus Weller 1905A1: p. 328, pl. 15 f. 4-6; Weller, 1905A2, p. 136, pl. 15 f. 4-6; Miller, 1906: p. 3; Shattuck, Miller, Bibbins and Walcott, 1907: p. 4; Weller, 1907: p. 852-853, pl. 111, f. 16-19; Miller, 1911: p. 96; Rathbun, 1935: p. 41, pl. 10, f. 16-18; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 313-314; Holland and Cvancara, 1958: p. 496; Bishop, 1983: p. 419, f. 3I, 3J; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 23, f. 12; Bishop, 1991: p. 13; Kuehne, 1993: p. 69; Bishop, Feldmann and Vega, 1998: p. 244, 250, f. 2.1; White, 2010: p. 15; Schweitzer and Feldmann, 2010: p. 58; Karasawa, Schweitzer and Feldmann, 2011: p. 524; Feldmann, Schweitzer, Baltzly, et. al., 2013: p. 28; Kornecki., 2014: p. 55, f. 12.1, f. 12.2; Kornecki, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2017: p. 300, f. 8A, 8B; Trochessett, 2002: p. 79, t. A1.

Types – *Tetracarcinus subquadratus* Weller 1905; Holotype: NJSM 7788.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3203c.

Description – “Carapace subquadrangular, length and breadth nearly equal, the dimensions of two individuals are: length, 12.3 mm. and 14.4 mm.; breadth, 12.5 mm., and 14 mm. Dorsal surface convex longitudinally and transversely, the sides curving abruptly downward to a nearly vertical position, marked by two longitudinal and two transverse furrows. Rostrum short, with a deep, longitudinal, median furrow. Extending backward from the posterior extremity of the median furrow of the rostrum, the two longitudinal dorsal furrows diverge from their anterior point of origin to the junction with the anterior transverse furrow, and then converge until they nearly meet again at the posterior margin of the carapace, enclosing a longitudinal, median area, which is not crossed by the anterior transverse furrow, and across which the posterior transverse furrow is less strongly defined than in its lateral limbs. The lateral limbs of the transverse furrows become less well defined towards the margin of the carapace, the anterior ones curve slightly backward toward their distal extremities, while the posterior ones have a slight forward curve, so that the two together, with the longitudinal furrows, enclose a pair of slightly convex, subovate areas. From the antero-lateral margins of each of these subovate areas two slight,

gently curved tuberclose ridges or lines of tubercles extend forward, diverging slightly, to the anterolateral margins of the carapace.” – Weller (1907) p. 852.

FIGURE 168: *TETRACARCINUS SUBQUADRATUS* WELLER, 1905
A-B: MAPS A3203C (Kw)

FAMILY DROMIIDAE RATHBURN, 1917

GENUS COSTADROMIA FELDMANN, SCHWEITZER
2019*Costadromia hajzeri* Feldmann, Schweitzer 2019

Costadromia hajzeri Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2019: p. 2, f. 1; Guinot, 2019: p. 762; Luque, Bracken-Grissom, Ortega-Hernandez and Wolfe, 2023: p. 12.

Types – *Costadromia hajzeri* Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2019; Holotype: NJSM: 24329

Wenonah Specimens – NJSM 24329.

Description – “Strongly ornamented carapace; wider, 37.6 mm measured at midlength, than long, 30.5 mm; L/W = 0.81; moderately vaulted transversely; strongly arched anteriorly in longitudinal view and less so posteriorly; highest position on carapace at mesogastric region. Front triangular, downturned, axially sulcate; marginal rim finely granular extending in continuous arc to form granular orbital rim. Orbits ovate, ca. 3.7 mm in diameter, outer orbital corner projected, blunt suborbital spine visible when viewed dorsally. Fronto-orbital width 17.6 mm; FOW/W = 0.47. Anterolateral and posterolateral margins form convex arc. Posterior margin broken. Sulcate rostral surface bounded by divergent epigastric regions bearing longitudinal granular ridges terminating posteriorly in large granular tubercle bounding anterior projection of mesogastric region bearing single row of four granules. Posterior part of mesogastric region strongly inflated, wider than long, surface with granular tubercles. Protogastric region

depressed below axial region, granular with one larger granular tubercle at posterior corner. Hepatic region a single, granular tubercle. Metagastric region a concave-forward granular arc as wide as mesogastric region, narrowing posteriorly. Urogastric region depressed, smooth. Cardiac region an isosceles triangle bounded by smooth depressions, longer than wide, widest posteriorly, with granular tubercles in concave forward arcs. Intestinal region depressed, smooth. Cervical groove weakly convex-forward, extending from base of hepatic region to mesogastric region as depressed, oblique, smooth surface, turning strongly posteriorly to cross midline in poorly defined V-shaped surface. Epibranchial region large with granular surface laterally, becoming tubercular axially. Small, longitudinally arcuate, tubercular branchial swellings situated parallel to cardiac region. Mesobranchial and metabranchial regions undifferentiated, with three prominent concave forward ridges with granular tubercles on crests. Sternum, pleon, and appendages not preserved.” – Feldmann and Schweitzer (2019) p. 2.

FIGURE 169: *COSTODROMIA HAJZERI* FELDMANN AND SCHWEITZER 2019 A-B: NJSM 24329 (KW): A - DORSAL VIEW; B- FRONTAL VIEW FROM FELDMANN AND SCHWEITZER 2019, FIG. 1

FAMILY ETYIDAE GUINOT AND TAVARES, 2001

GENUS *XANTHOSIA* BELL, 1863

Xanthosia elegans Roberts 1962

Xanthosia elegans Roberts, 1962: p. 177, pl. 89, f. 1, 3; Bishop, 1985: p. 622; Bishop, 1999: p. 311;

Schweitzer, Hopkins, Salva and Feldmann, 1999: p. 80, 87, 88, 90; Guinot and Tavares, 2001: p. 516; Fraaije, Van Beckel, Jagt and Artal, 2008: p. 199; Collins and Brenton, 2009: p. 48; Klompmaker, Artal, Van Beckel, Fraaije and Jagt, 2011: p. 1204, t. 2; Schweitzer, Feldmann, Frantescu and Klompmaker, 2012: p. 131, 133, f. 4.4; Charbonnier, Garassino and Pasini, 2012: p. 352; Frantescu, 2013: p. 174, f. 4.4; Feldmann, Schweitzer, Baltzly, Bennett, Jones, Weaver and Yost, 2013: p. 20, f. 8.

Xanthosia cf. *Xanthosia elegans* Roberts, 1962. Schweitzer, Feldmann, Garassino, Karasawa and Schweigert, 2010: p. 131.

Non Xanthosia elegans Secretan, 1964: p. 178-182, pl. 20, f. 4-6 = *Xanthosia robertsi* (Secretan, 1964).

Types – *Xanthosia elegans* Roberts, 1962; Holotype: WFIS: 17108

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3213b.

Description – “Carapace nearly twice as wide as long; granulation of the dorsal surface coarser on the protogastric field and branchial ridges than elsewhere; ventral surface minutely punctate; proximal half of posterolateral margin concave. Front orbital distance about one-half the carapacal width. Front low-triangular, moderately deflexed, its dorsal sulcus broadly V-shaped and continued postad between the submedian pair of epigastric tubercles to the base of the mesogastric process. Orbit about half the width of the front, subcircular and oblique; superior margin curved upward to form a concave rim which bears a stout triangular tooth near the inner angle and a closed fissure near the outer; inferior margin bifissured. Anterolateral margin thin, crenulate; teeth triangular with rounded apices; the first (outer orbital) tooth hollowed dorsally, the others bisected by a dorsal ridge. The proximal tooth is situated posterior to the widest part of the carapace. Mesogastric process long and slender, reaching forward to a point slightly beyond the level of the inner orbital angles and clearly separated from the distal half of each protogastric lobe by a broad sulcus. Proximal half of each protogastric lobe swollen parallel to the cervical groove. Cardiac field oval and domed. Urogastric and metagastric fields separated by an impressed line which bears a submedian pair of deep punctures. Branchial groove broad, deep and transverse, intersecting the lateral margin of the carapace at a point opposite to the urogastric

punctures and bordered above and below by broad ridges. Inner angle of the branchial field elevated into a low boss from which two subparallel ridges extend obliquely postad to the lateral margin of the carapace. The inner ridge intersects the lateral margin at the middle. The outer ridge is situated halfway between the middle of the lateral margin and the proximal lateral tooth. Subhepatic suture and edge of mouth field each marked by a raised line. Subhepatic surface ornamented with two elongated tubercles which lie side by side and subparallel to the subhepatic suture.

Measurement of holotype: length 10.4, width 19.4: depth 4.4, front orbital distance 9 mm." – Roberts (1962) p. 177.

FIGURE 170: *XANTHOSIA ELEGANS* ROBERTS 1962 A: MAPS A3213A (Kmv) B-C: MAPS A3213B (Kw)

FAMILY GALATHEIDAE SAMOUELLE, 1819

GENUS LUISOGALATHEA KARASAWA AND

HAYAKAWA, 2000

Luisogalatea cretacea (Stenzel, 1945)

Galatea cretacea Stenzel, 1945: p. 430, pl. 43 f. 3; Bishop, 1985: p. 603; Karasawa, Hayakawa, 2000: p. 143.

Luisogalatea cretacea (Stenzel, 1945). Karasawa, Hayakawa, 2000: p. 143; Schweitzer, Feldmann, Garassino, Karasawa and Schweigert, 2010: p. 50; Klompmaker, Robbins, Jakobsen and Sheldon, 2022: p. 1094.

Munida cretacea (Stenzel, 1945). Frantescu, 2014: p. 225, f. 3A-3E.

Non *Luisogalatea cretacea* (Stenzel, 1945). Vega, Gonzalez-Leon, Morena-Bedmar, 2019: f. 3.1-3.7, 3-9 = *Eomunidopsis texcalaensis* Klompmaker, 2022.

Types – *Galatea cretacea* Stenzel, 1945; Holotype?:

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3224a.

Description – “Carapace small, elongate rectangular in outline; the length to width proportion is 6 to 5. Carapace depressed, nearly straight along midline, but convex from side to side. Rostrum 1/3, to V2 the length of the carapace, elongate triangular in outline with the sides concave in outline and the broad base as wide as the length of the rostrum, dorsoventrally strongly compressed, and thin; dorsally with a broad, V-shaped median groove, ventrally with a corresponding V-shaped keel; dorsal surface of rostrum with many short, arcuate rugae to each side of the median groove. Some of these rugae produce small denticles at the margins of the rostrum. Greatest width of the carapace at the posterior quarter; lateral margins slightly convergent to the anterior of the greatest width, to the posterior rapidly curving inward. Posterior margin concave as seen from above. Cervical, antennar, and hepatic grooves smooth and deep. Cervical groove curved, antennar groove sinuous, hepatic groove nearly straight. Hepatic groove meets the lateral margin at a right angle. The median groove of the rostrum extends backward in a pair of short and shallow gastro-orbital grooves, which enclose an acute angle. Entire carapace covered with transverse rugae, some of which are short while others are long enough to extend across the entire width of the carapace or at least from groove to groove. There are 7 precervical entire rugae; of these 2 abut against the cervical groove and 5 against the antennar grooves; two entire precervical rugae are cut by the gastroorbital grooves; there are 5 rugae between the hepatic and the antennar grooves; of the postcervical rugae only the last 3 reach across the entire width of the carapace; those anterior to the last three rugae are arranged in three tiers, one of which is median or cardiac; the other two are lateral or branchial in position. There are 4 rugae in the cardiac tier and 5 in the branchial tiers; the ends of the cardiac rugae are not in line with the branchial rugae. All rugae have a row of innumerable and very fine pits along their crest. The rugae which lie anterior to the greatest

width of the carapace, and which reach the lateral carapace margins produce spinules at the margins. Six spinules are posterior to the hepatic groove, 5 spinules are between the hepatic and antennar groove, about 3 spinules are interior to the antennar groove. The first 3 abdominal segments are visible; they are simple, transversely grooved. The abdomen is curved under the carapace. The small, pyritized nodule containing the monotype specimen shows also traces of the legs.” – Stenzel (1945) p. 430.

FIGURE 171: *LUISOGALATHEA CRETACEA* (STENZEL, 1945) A: MAPS A3224A (KW)

FAMILY LYREIDIDAE GUINOT, 1993

GENUS *MACROACAENA* TUCKER, 1998

Macroacaena tridens (Roberts, 1962)

Raninella tridens Roberts, 1962: p. 187, pl. 88 f. 5, 6; Gore and Heck, 1988: p. 125; Spamer and Forster, 1988: p. 76; Schweitzer and Feldmann, 2010: p. 75; Klompaker, 2012: p. 333; Kornecki, 2014: p. 76; Kornecki, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2017: p. 311; Trochesset, 2022: p. 48, t. A1.

Non *Raninella tridens* Roberts, 1962. Bishop, 1991: p. 13 = *Bournelyreidus ericksoni* Kornecki, et. al. 2017.

Notopocorystes cf. *Notopocorystes tridens* (Roberts, 1962). Landman, Johnson, Garb, Edwards and Kyte, 2007: p. 14, 29, t. 1, f. 15 N, 15 O.

Bournelyreidus tridens (Roberts, 1962). Klompaker, 2012: p. 402; Van Bakel, Guinot, Fraaije and Jagt, 2012: p. 83, 118 (pars) not f. 38C-D; Feldmann, Schweitzer, Baltzly, Bennett, Jones, Mathias,

Weaver and Yost, 2013: p. 27, f. 12; Karasawa, Schweitzer, Feldmann and Luque, 2014: p. 218, 247, 249, t. 1; Kornecki, 2014: p. 76; Kornecki, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2017: p. 311.

Macroacaena tridens (Roberts, 1962). Karasawa, Schweitzer, Feldmann and Luque, 2014: p. 246, S5, t. S2; Kornecki, 2014: p. 76-78.

Types – *Macroacaena tridens* (Roberts, 1962); Holotype: ANSP 19737.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3217c.

Description - “Carapace obovate; strongly arched from side to side; greatest width and the highest point on the dorsal surface at the distal third. Immediately in front of this high point, on the dorsal surface of the carapace and extending forward to the orbital borders, there is a median triangular facet which points postad. Running backward from the high point, there is a low median convexity which dies out in the cardiac field. Front two-thirds as wide as the carapace and almost transverse exterior to the rostrum. Rostrum triangular; excavated dorsally, the middle of the excavation occupied by a short longitudinal ridge. Tip of rostrum bluntly rounded and curved slightly downward. Orbit about one-fifth the width of the front; subcircular; directed obliquely outward and upward, its upper and lower margins each pierced by a closed fissure. Anterolateral teeth three, including the outer orbital tooth. The teeth are triangular in dorsal profile, moderately compressed dorsoventrally. with submucronate tips. First tooth larger and less compressed than the others, pointed obliquely forward, acute but nearly equilateral and separated from the second tooth by a broadly U-shaped sinus. Second tooth broad and low, inclined slightly forward, smaller than the third tooth and situated midway between the latter and the first tooth. The third tooth is placed at the widest part of the carapace. It is directed obliquely forward and is more acutely triangular than the first tooth. The posterior margin of the third tooth is distinctly concave and is provided with a carinate edge which becomes continuous with the lateral edge of the carapace posteriorly. Cardiac field barrel-shaped, limited laterally by faint branchiocardiac grooves which connect distally with a pair of deep thumbnail muscle scars. Hepatic area slightly concave. Mouth

field nearly half as long as the carapace, its lateral edges parallel and outwardly arcuate. When viewed from the ventral surface, the subhepatic furrow and the prominent subhepatic carina exterior to it are parallel to each other and to the lateral margin of the carapace. Surface of carapace minutely and evenly granulate “– Roberts (1962) p. 187.

FIGURE 172: *MACROACAENA TRIDENS* (ROBERTS, 1962) A:
MAPS A3217C (Kw)

FAMILY NECROCARCINIDAE FORSTER, 1968

GENUS NECROCARCINUS BELL, 1863

Description – “Carapace ovate, hexagonal, or subquadrate, wider than long; rostrum downturned, weakly projecting beyond orbits, with three or four small spines; orbits round, forwardly directed, often with intraorbital and outerorbital spines and two fissures; anterolateral margin with two or more spines; posterolateral margin sometimes with spines; protogastric region well-marked, wider than long; cervical groove deep, sinuous, notches at lateral margin where it intersects it; branchiocardiac groove less well-developed; postcervical groove deep, short, straight across midline, then with segments at each end at nearly right angles to axial segment; axial regions well-marked, cardiac region elongate-ovate; dorsal carapace with large tubercles or spines often arranged into longitudinal rows, sometimes not arranged into rows.” – Feldmann, et.al. (2013) p. 21

Necrocarcinus sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3226c

FIGURE 173: *NECROCARCINUS* SP. A: MAPS A3226c (Kw)

FAMILY NEPHROPIDAE DANA, 1852

FIGURE 174: INDETERMINATE SPECIMEN OF NEPHROPIDAE A-
B: MAPS A3204B (Kw)

GENUS HOPLOPARIA M’COY, 1849

Hoploparia gabbi Pilsbry, 1901

Hoploparia gabbi Pilsbry, 1901: p. 115, 116, pl. 1, f. 11-14; Johnson, 1905: p. 28; Weller, 1907: p. 846, pl. 110, f. 12-15; Pilsbry, 1916: p. 90, 91, 361, pl. 10, f. 1-4, 8-9; Rathbun, 1935: p. 24, pl. 5, f. 10, 11;

Ramsdell, 1948: p. 305-306; Groot, Organist and Richards, 1954: p. 53; Richards, 1956: p. 71-72; Richards, Groot and Germouth, 1957; p. 11; Roberts, 1962: p. 166, pl. 5-7; Richards and Shapiro, 1963: p. 10; Gallagher, 1984: p. 14; Lauginiger, 1988: p. 24, f. 12; Kuehne, 1993: p. 65; Kuehne, 1999: p. 61, 69; Tshudy and Sorhannus, 2003: p. 708, f. 1, App. 1; Tshudy, Donaldson, Collom, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2005: p. 965-966, f. 5, App. 1; Feldmann, Schweitzer, Baltzly, Bennett, Jones, Mathias, Weaver and Yost, 2013: p. 9, 10, f. 1; Lauginiger, Parris, Pelligrini, 2014; Kornecki, 2014: p. 21; Kuehne and Kuehne, 2016: p. 54, App. B, pl. 1; Kornecki, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2017: p. 277; Ando, Hirose, Ugai and Shimada, 2020: p. 28, t. 2.

Non *Hoploparia gabbi* Pilsbry, 1901. Davis and Leng, 1927: p. 47, f. 2, 3; Roberts, 1962: p. 165, pl. 81, f. 1-4 (= *Hoploparia gladiator* Pilsbry, 1901).

Hoploparia gladiator Pilsbry, 1901. Roberts, 1962: p. 166, pl. 82, f. 1-2 (not of *H. gladiator* Pilsbry, 1901).

Hoploparia cf. gabbi Pilsbry, 1901. White, 1996: p. 10.

Types – *Hoploparia gabbi* Pilsbry, 1901; Cotypes: WFIS 5941, ANSP 527; Syntype: YPM 17903.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3200a, A3200.

Description – “Carapace about one and four-fifths longer than high; branchial and pterygostomial fields roughened with adpressed conical granules. Median groove of rostrum narrow, lateral carinae transversely rounded, spinulate above, and continued backward on the gastric field by two steadily diverging rows of oblique conical granules. Proximal slope of supraorbital spine long, spinulate, followed by a row of granules which parallels the row behind the lateral carina of the rostrum. Antennal field inconspicuously trilobed, the lobes convex vertically; distal edge of anterior lobe beaded, the

two posterior lobes granulated medially. The antennal spine is replaced by a blunt tubercle at the antennal angle. Postcervical groove broader and deeper than the other carapacial grooves. Cervical groove barely arcuate, rising to a point slightly below the level of the infraorbital spine. Anterior arm of hepatic groove deep and straight, posterior and lower arms shallow, the latter ascending. Antennal groove angulated before the prominence omega, its proximal arm straight equilateral, lower border marked by a shallow groove. Abdominal terga dotted with small widely spaced punctae; pleurons roughened with crowded sockets. A broad thickened rim borders the posterior margin of each pleuron; along the upper border of the pleuron, extending forward from the rim to the distal margin, there is a rounded and closely pitted ridge. Major chelae equal and symmetrical, elongate elliptical in lateral profile; about one and one-fifth times the length of the carapace. Palm highest between the anterior quarter and third; outer side of upper edge armed with an arcuate row of four curved and laterally compressed spines; between spines 2 and 3 of this row but situated near the inner side of the palm there is a fifth spine similar to the other four. Lower surface of palm bluntly rounded the distal two-thirds with a narrow median groove which continues onto the fixed finger. Fingers slightly shorter than palm; section of fixed finger obovate, concave on either side of the occludent surface except near the insertion of the finger, where it is convex. Dactylus flattened-elliptical, armed with a strong dorsoproximal spine which is in line with the row of spines on the outer side of the palm. Occludent teeth of both fingers contiguously arranged so that the larger teeth of one finger oppose groups of smaller teeth of the other. Wrist spinous; its hinge process longer than wide, rounded apically, the longitudinal axis curved.” – Roberts (1962) p. 165.

FIGURE 174A: *HOPLOPARIA GABBI* PILSBRY, 1901 A-C: MAPS A3200A (Kw); D: MAPS A3200G (Kmv)

***Hoploparia gladiator* Pilsbry, 1901**

Hoploparia gladiator Pilsbry, 1901: p. 116, 117, pl. 1, f. 15, 16; Weller, 1907: p. 848, pl. 110, f. 16,17; Pilsbry, 1916: p. 90, 91, 362, pl. 10, f. 6; Rathbun, 1935: p. 4, 8, 24, 25; Ramsdell, 1948: p. 307-308; Roberts, 1962: p. 166, pl. 80 f. 7-8, pl. 82 f. 3-8, (not pl. 82, f. 1-2 = *Hoploparia gabbi* Pilsbry, 1901); Gallagher, 1984: p. 14; Spamer and Forster, 1988: p. 74; Tshudy and Sorhannus, 2003: p. 708, App. 1; Tshudy, Donaldson, Collom, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2005: p. 968, App. 1; Klomp maker, 2014: p. 410; Feldmann, Schweitzer, Baltzly, Bennett, Jones, Mathias, Weaver and Yost, 2013: p. 10, f. 2; Lauinger, Parris and Pelligrini, 2014: p. 176; Kornecki, Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2017: p. 277.

Non *Hoploparia gabbi* Pilsbry, 1916. Roberts, 1962: p. 165, pl. 81, f. 1-4.

Types – *Hoploparia gladiator* Pilsbry, 1901; Syntype: WFIS 10120.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3200a, A3201d.

Description – “Carapace about twice as long as high. Rostrum half the length of carapace; rostrum groove wide, broadly U-shaped; lateral carinae smooth above, triangular in section. The two rows of conical tubercles which continue the carinae backward on the gastric field are parallel to the dorsal median line of the carapace. Supraorbital spine carinated and followed by a short row of tubercles. A longitudinal row of three equally spaced conical tubercles on the antenna1 field. Cervical groove broad and deep, ascending to or slightly above the inconspicuous gastroorbital groove. Anterior and posterior arms of the hepatic groove shorter than the distinctly oblique inferior arm. Prominence omega an acute triangle with apes pointing upward and slightly backward. Palms of the first pair of ehelipeds almost three times longer than their distal height; the one palm of the pair rectangular in lateral profile, the other subcuneiform, otherwise the two are similar. Inner

and outer surfaces equally and evenly convex, each with a row of 4 or 5 compressed elongated teeth along the median convexity; a similar row of 4 teeth on the subacute upper edge. Lower edge transversely flat and narrow, bounded laterally by two parallel rows of minute, conical tubercles which point obliquely forward and downward. Fingers slender; the fixed finger pyriform in section near the insertion, a wide hiatus separating the anterior and posterior teeth. On the subcuneiform hand, the proximal teeth of the fixed finger are large, quadrate and contiguous. On the rectangular hand, they are small, circular and separated. Dactylus broadly elliptical, the occludent surface not set off from the lateral surfaces by

grooves or angles. Merus elongated, produced into a long spine at the outer distal margin. Integument polished; minutely punctate when examined under the lens.

Palms under 25 mm. in length have a granular surface, an arcuate lower edge, and are proportionately higher and shorter than large palms. Apparently, they are major palms, but their morphological relations will be uncertain until the second and third pair of ehelipeds of the species become known.”—Roberts (1962) p. 166.

FIGURE 175: *HOPLOPARIA GLADIATOR* PILSBRY, 1901 A: MAPS A3201C (Kw); B: MAPS A3201B (Kmv)

FAMILY PAGURIDAE LATREILLE, 1802

GENUS PALAEOPAGURUS VAN STRAELEN, 1924

Palaeopagurus pilsbryi Roberts, 1962.

Palaeopagurus pilsbryi Roberts, 1962: p. 174, pl. 85 f. 1-4; Richards, 1968: p. 217; Spamer and Forster, 1988: p. 75; Klompmaker, 2012: p. 410.

Types – *Palaeopagurus pilsbryi* Roberts, 1962; Holotype: WFIS 17095; Paratype: ANSP 19705.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3208a.

Description – “Palm subrectangular, somewhat swollen, proximal corners abruptly angled, posterior margin broadly lobed at the hinge. Outer surface is evenly convex lengthwise, vertically angulate at the lower third and less convex above than below the rounded angulation. On the inner face an oblique longitudinal convexity rises at the dactylar hinge node and extends postad to a smooth lunate groove before the proximal margin. The palm is faceted below this convexity, concave above it. Upper edge acute, almost straight, its crest bluntly rounded and closely granulated, the granules becoming larger on the proximal two-thirds where they form a single irregular row. Lower edge sigmoidal, subcarinate; the crest deflected inward distally and not visible on the fixed finger from below. Upper margin of fixed finger almost straight on the outer side, concavely arcuate on the inner; tip blunt, curved inward and upward. Dactylus triangular in section near the articulation, becoming elliptical at the tip; outer surface broadly channeled longitudinally below the coarsely papillose upper margin. The closed fingers have a slight gape posteriorly. Chela covered with acorn shaped granules with roughened tips. On the outer surface of the granules are small and close together becoming larger along the upper margin. On the inner surface they are coarser and farther apart but become more crowded toward the distal end.

Palms less than 9mm. in length have a single row of granules extending the full length of the sharp upper edge. The lower edge is clearly carinate under the base of the fixed finger.” – Roberts (1962) p. 174.

FIGURE 176: *PALAEOPAGURUS PILSBRYI* ROBERTS, 1962 A: MAPS A3208A (KW)

FAMILY PALAEOCORYSTIDAE LORENTHEY IN LORENTHEY AND BEURLEN, 1929

GENUS CRETACORANINA MERTIN, 1941

Description – “The distinguishing characteristics of *Cretacorantina* include an oval to oblong carapace with a non-tuberculate, finely granulated to smooth surface; a distinct medial keel for almost the entire length of the carapace which may be faint to absent in some species; a lobed line that crosses the frontal area; and cervical and branchial furrows, often with just the medial portions represented; toothed anterolateral margins; a slightly produced and bifid rostrum; and strongly grooved pterygostomial region.” – Haj and Feldmann (2002) p. 477.

Cretacorantina sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3210a

FIGURE 177: *CRETACORANINA* SP. A-B: MAPS A3210A (KW) - A: -VENTRAL VIEW, B – DORSAL VIEW

FAMILY **RANINIDAE** DE HAAN, 1839
 GENUS **RANINELLA** MILNE-EDWARDS, 1862
Raninella sp.

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3219a

FIGURE 178: *RANINELLA* SP. A-B: MAPS A3217C (KW)

ICHNO SPECIES

ICHNO FACIES DOMINCHINA

ICHOGENUS GASTROCHAENOLITIES Leymerie, 1842

Gastrochaenolities isp.

Description – “Clavate borings; aperture narrower than main chamber and may be circular, oval, or dumb-bell shaped; main chamber may vary from subspherical to elongate. Usually made by bivalves which may be preserved in situ.”

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A2511k

FIGURE 179: A-C: GASTROCHAENOLITIES, POSSIBLE BORINGS OF LITHOPHAGIC, MAPS A2411k (Kw)

ICHOGENUS OPHIOMORPHA Lundgren, 1891

Ophiomorpha nodosa Lundgren, 1891

Description – “Ophiomorpha with burrow walls consisting predominantly of dense, regularly distributed discoid, ovoid, or irregular polygonal pellets.” Frey, Howard and Pryor (1978).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS IC1a, IC1b, IC1c, IC1d, IC1e.

FIGURE 180: OPHIOMORPHA NODOSA LUNDGREN, 1891 A: MAPS 1C1E

Indeterminate Burrow Fillings

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS A3207a

ICHOGENUS PHYCODES Richter, 1850

Phycodes palmatus (Hall, 1852)

Description – “Horizontal hypichnial burrow system at the interface of a fine-grained sandstone and claystone with a slightly curved stem, 12mm in diameter, from which four gently curved and closely spaced burrows branch out. The distal parts of the branches are not preserved. Their oval cross-sections probably result from compaction. Burrow diameter is 8–10mm in the horizontal and 3–5mm in the vertical axis.” – Knaust (2004).

Synonyms - *Phycodes (Buthrolepis) palmatum* Crimes and Anderson, 1985; *Buthotrephis palmata* Clausen and Vilhjalmsen 1986; *Phycodes palmatum* Orlowski 1989

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS IC3b

ICHNOGENUS RHIZOCORALLIUM Zenker 1836
Rhizocorallium sp.

Description - Horizontal to oblique, U-shaped spreite burrow." Knaust (2013).

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS IC2a.

FIGURE 181: *RHIZOCORALLIUM* SP. A: MAPS 1C2A

ICHNOGENUS ROSSELIA Dahmer, 1937
Rosselia socialis Dahmer, 1937

Description – “*Rosselia socialis* burrows are cylindrical, 2 to 3 cm in diameter, and extending up to 60 cm in length. The burrows consist of concentrically laminated, clay rich sediment with a sand filled central tube.”

Wenonah Specimens – Martino and Curran, 1990 p. 127, 133

ICHNO FACIES NEREITES
ICHNOGENUS NEREITES
Invertebrate Trails

Wenonah Specimens – MAPS IC4a, IC4b, IC4c.

ICHNO FACIES ZOOPHYCOS
ICHNOGENUS ZOOPHYCOS Massalongo, 1855
Zoophycos sp.

Description – “Burrows of deposit feeders planar form of Zoophycos consists of horizontal to gently inclined, clay-rich spreiten with a thickness of about 1.5 cm.”

Wenonah Specimens Martino and Curran, 1990 p. 127.

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WENONAH FORMATION SPECIES LIST

Specimens marked with a '#' indicate the first reported occurrence of the species from the Late Cretaceous Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain (NACP) and those specimens marked with a '&' indicate the first reported occurrence from the Wenonah formation based on the MAPS collection. Those specimens marked with an 'X' have been previously reported in those formations. The systematic paleontology is based primarily on the online database MolluscaBase (2020). Tht – Hornerstown, Kt – Tinton, Kne – New Egypt, Krb – Red Bank, Ksv – Severn, Kns – Navesink, Kml – Mount Laurel, Kw – Wenonah, Kmt – Marshalltown, Ket – Englishtown, Kwb – Woodbury, Kmv – Merchantville, Kcq – Cheesapeake, Kmg – Magothy, Kr – Raritan.

		MONMOUTH GROUP						MATAWAN GROUP						
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence						
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq
Bryozoa														
<i>Basslerinella prismatica</i> (Canu & Bassler, 1926)	pg. 5								#					
<i>Basslerinella</i> sp.	pg. 5								&					
<i>Dynsoetopora celleporoides</i> Canu & Bassler, 1926	pg. 6								#					
<i>Heteroconopeum ovatum</i> (Canu & Bassler, 1926)	pg. 5								#					
Annelida														
<i>Diploconcha harbisonae</i> Howell, 1943	pg. 7								X			X		
<i>Pyrgoipoion wenonahanus</i> Howell, 1943	pg. 7	X							X		X			
Cnidaria														
<i>Micrabacia cribraria</i> Stephenson, 1916	pg. 9						X	X	X	X		X	X	
<i>Micrabacia hilgardi</i> Stephenson, 1916	pg. 10							X	X					
<i>Trochocyathus woolmani</i> Vaughan, 1900	pg. 9							X	X	X		X	X	
Echinodermata														
<i>Domechinus chelonium</i> (Cooke, 1953)	pg. 12							X	X	X	X		X	
<i>Hardouinia mortonis emmonsii</i> (Stephenson, 1927)	pg. 12							X	X					
Bivalvia														
<i>Agerostrea falcata</i> (Morton, 1830)	pg. 52	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		
<i>Anatimya anteradiata</i> Conrad, 1860	pg. 55					X			X			X	X	
<i>Anatimya lata</i> (Whitfield, 1885)	pg. 56		X			X	X		X			X	X	
<i>Anomia argentaria</i> Morton, 1833	pg. 58				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Aphrodina eufaulensis</i> (Conrad, 1860)	pg. 85						X	X	X	X		X		
<i>Aphrodina tippiana</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 86		X			X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X

		MONMOUTH GROUP					MATAWAN GROUP								
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence							
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq	Kr
<i>Etea trapezoidea</i> (CONRAD, 1860)	pg. 77						X	&			X	X			
<i>Ethmocardium welleri</i> (Stephenson, 1941)	pg. 25		X					X			X	X			
<i>Exogyra ponderosa erraticostata</i> Stephenson, 1914	pg. 49						X	&	X		X				
<i>Flemingostrea subspatulata</i> (Forbes, 1845)	pg. 51				X			X							
<i>Fulvia tenuis</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 26			X			X	X	&						
<i>Gabbioigna eufalensis</i> Gabb, 1860	pg. 70			X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		
<i>Gervillioopsis ensiformis</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 48	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
<i>Glossus bulbosa</i> (Stephenson, 1941)	pg. 81							X	&						
<i>Glossus cliffwoodensis</i> (Weller, 1907)	pg. 81								X			X		X	
<i>Glycymeris microdentus</i> (Weller, 1907)	pg. 18			X				X	X						
<i>Granocardium dumosum</i> (Conrad, 1870)	pg. 26		X		X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
<i>Inoceramus proximus</i> Toumey, 1854	pg. 39							X	X		X	X	X	X	
<i>Inoperna carolinensis</i> Conrad, 1875	pg. 42					X	X		&		X	X	X		
<i>Laternula jerseyensis</i> (Weller, 1907)	pg. 57							X	X		X	X	X		
<i>Laternula robusta</i> Stephenson, 1941	pg. 57					X	X		&						
<i>Legumen concentricum</i> Stephenson, 1923	pg. 88					X	X	X	X			X	X	X	
<i>Leptosolen biplicata</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 69				X	X		X	X		X	X	X	X	
<i>Lima monmouthensis</i> (Whitfield, 1885)	pg. 37							X	X				X		
<i>Lima reticulata</i> (Lyell, Forbes, 1845)	pg. 37		X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
<i>Lima whitfieldi</i> (Weller, 1907)	pg. 38			X			X	X	X	X					
<i>Linearia metastrata</i> Conrad, 1860	pg. 28				X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>Liopistha protexta</i> (Conrad, 1853)	pg. 68		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
<i>Margaritifera</i> sp.	pg. 75								#						
<i>Modiolus wenonah</i> (Weller, 1907)	pg. 42								X						
<i>Mytilus oblivius</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 43						X		X					X	
<i>Nemoarca cretacea</i> Conrad, 1869	pg. 16	X			X				X			X	X		
<i>Nemodon angulatum</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 20						X		&	X	X	X	X		

		MONMOUTH GROUP					MATAWAN GROUP							
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence						
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq
<i>Nemodon brevifrons</i> Conrad, 1875	pg. 20					X		X	X	X	X			
<i>Nucula percrassa</i> Conrad, 1858	pg. 46				X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>Nucula whitfieldi</i> Weller, 1907	pg. 47			X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	
<i>Nuculana marlboroensis</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 44							X		X				
<i>Nuculana rostratruncata</i> (Gardner, 1916)	pg. 44				X			&		X				
<i>Nuculana stephensoni</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 45		X		X		X	X		X	X			
<i>Nuculana whitfieldi</i> (Gardner, 1916)	pg. 45				X	X			X		X	X		
<i>Panopea decisa</i> Conrad, 1853	pg. 15	X		X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	
<i>Pecten simplicius</i> Conrad, 1860	pg. 62	X			X	X		X	X		X	X	X	
<i>Pholadomya roemeri</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 64								X			X		
<i>Postligata crenata</i> Wade, 1916	pg. 19			X		X	X	X	&				X	
<i>Pteria petrosa</i> (Conrad, 1853)	pg. 54								X		X	X	X	
<i>Praescabrotrigonia bartrami</i> (Stephenson, 1923)	pg. 72					X			&		X		X	
<i>Radiopecten quinquenarius</i> (CONRAD, 1853)	pg. 63				X				X	X				
<i>Scambula perplana</i> Conrad, 1869	pg. 36					X			X		X	X		
<i>Solyma lineolatus</i> Conrad, 1870	pg. 30		X	X	X		X	X	X			X	X	
<i>Striarca congesta</i> (Conrad, 1875)	pg. 19				X				X			X	X	
<i>Striostrea plumosa</i> (Morton, 1833)	pg. 53		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	
<i>Tellina gabbi</i> Gardner, 1916	pg. 30				X	X		X	X		X	X	X	
<i>Tellina georgiana</i> Gabb, 1876	pg. 31					X	X	X	X			X		
<i>Tellinimera eborea</i> Conrad, 1860	pg. 32				X	X			X			X	X	
<i>Tenea parilis</i> (CONRAD, 1860)	pg. 77		X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	
<i>Tenea pinguis</i> (CONRAD, 1853)	pg. 78					X	X	X	&			X	X	
<i>Tenea pinguis</i> (CONRAD, 1853)	pg. 78					X	X	X	&			X	X	
<i>Trachycardium longstreeti</i> (Weller, 1907)	pg. 27							X	X		X		X	
<i>Trapezium truncata</i> (Meek, 1871)	pg. 84							X	&					
<i>Trigonia cerulia</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 71								X					

		MONMOUTH GROUP						MATAWAN GROUP							
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence							
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq	Kr
<i>Trigonia mortoni</i> Whitfield, 1885	pg. 74	X	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	X		
<i>Unicardium umbonata</i> (Whitfield, 1886)	pg. 15			X		X		X	&			X	X		
<i>Veniella conradi</i> Morton, 1833	pg. 79	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
<i>Veniella</i> sp.	pg. 80		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Gastropoda															
<i>Acirsa (Hemiacirsa) cretacea</i> (Wade, 1917)	pg. 90								&						
<i>Acteon cretacea</i> Gabb, 1861	pg. 96	X					X	X	X	X		X			
<i>Anchura substriata</i> Wade, 1926	pg. 99		X	X		X	X		&				X		
<i>Aporrhais</i> sp	pg. 100		X				X		X						
<i>Arrhoges (Latiola) lobata</i> (Wade, 1926)	pg. 100		X	X	X	X	X	X	&			X	X		
<i>Arrhoges (Latiola) rostrata</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 101						X	X	X			X	X		
<i>Bellifusus</i> sp	pg. 117		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			
<i>Belliscala</i> sp	pg. 90		X			X		X	X						
<i>Buccinopsis globosa</i> (Gabb, 1876)	pg. 111								X						
<i>Cylichna recta</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 95					X		X	X			X			
<i>Euspira halli</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 106	X		X			X	X	X	X		X	X		
<i>Gegania bella</i> (Conrad, 1860)	pg. 98		X	X			X	X	&						
<i>Granosolarium voragiformis</i> (Stephenson, 1941)	pg. 97						X	X	&						
<i>Gyrodes petrosus</i> (Morton, 1834)	pg. 107	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		
<i>Gyrodes (Gyrodes) supraplicatus</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 108		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		
<i>Gyrodes (Sohlella) spillmani</i> Stephenson, 1941	pg. 109		X				X	X	&	X					
<i>Hydrotribulus elegans</i> Sohl, 1964	pg. 112					X			&						

		MONMOUTH GROUP						MATAWAN GROUP							
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence							
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq	Kr
<i>Lupira pyriformis</i> Stephenson, 1941	pg. 119					X		X	&						
<i>Mataxa elegans</i> Wade, 1916	pg. 112							X	&						
<i>Napulus retifer</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 117					X	X	X	X						
<i>Ornopsis glenni</i> Wade, 1916	pg. 114								&						
<i>Paladmete cancellaria</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 113				X	X		X	X	X			X		
<i>Piestochilus kanei</i> (Gabb, 1861)	pg. 115						X		X			X		X	
<i>Pteroceralla tippiana</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 102					X			X						
<i>Pugnellus densatus</i> (Conrad, 1858)	pg. 103					X			X			X			
<i>Pugnellus goldmani</i> Gardner, 1916	pg. 104					X			X						
<i>Pyropsis</i> sp.	pg. 116	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
<i>Remera flexicostata</i> Sohl, 1964	pg. 116					X			&			X			
<i>Sargana</i> sp	pg. 116				X	X	X	X	X	X					
<i>Sohlitella biliria</i> (Stephenson, 1941)	pg. 92		X	X		X	X		&						
<i>Sohlitella triliria</i> (Conrad, 1860)	pg. 92				X	X		X	X	X	X	X			
<i>Striaticostatus sillimani</i> (Morton, 1834)	pg. 91		X		X		X		X	X		X	X		
<i>Turbinella alabamensis</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 118					X	X		X						
<i>Turbinopsis depressa</i> Gabb, 1861	pg. 105						X	X	X			X	X		
<i>Turritella austini</i> Stephenson, 1941	pg. 94							X	&				X		
<i>Turritella vertebroides</i> Morton, 1834	pg. 93		X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X		

		MONMOUTH GROUP						MATAWAN GROUP						
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence						
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq
<i>Volutoderma biplicata</i> (Gabb, 1860)	pg. 117						X	X	X		X	X		
<i>Xenophora leprosa</i> (Morton, 1834)	pg. 110		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		
Cephalopoda														
<i>Baculites</i> sp.	pg. 121	X		X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X
<i>Baculites texanus</i> Kennedy & Cobban, 1999	pg. 121								X					
<i>Didymoceras binodosum</i> (Kennedy & Cobban, 1993)	pg. 123								&	X				
<i>Didymoceras</i> sp.	pg. 124					X	X	X	X					
<i>Glyptoxoceras</i> sp	pg. 122				X			X				X		
<i>Menuites portlocki</i> (Sharpe, 1855) complex (Hall & Meek, 1856)	pg. 126					X		X	X	X				
<i>Nostoceras colubriformis</i> Stephenson, 1941	pg. 124					X	X	X	X					
<i>Nostoceras monotuberculatum</i> Kennedy & Cobban, 1993	pg. 124							X	&	X				
<i>Nostoceras puzosiforme</i> Kennedy & Cobban, 1994	pg. 125								X					
<i>Parasolenoceras</i> sp.	pg. 122								X					
<i>Placentoceras minor</i> Kennedy & Cobban, 1994	pg. 128								X					
<i>Solenoceras annulifer</i> (Morton, 1843)	pg. 122							X	&	X				
<i>Trachyscaphites pulcherrimus</i> (Roemer, 1841)	pg. 129								X					
Scaphopoda														
<i>Dentalium</i> sp.	pg. 131			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Arthropoda														

		MONMOUTH GROUP						MATAWAN GROUP							
		Tht						Marshalltown Sequence							
			Kt	Kne	Krb	Ksv	Kns	Kml	Kw	Kmt	Ket	Kwb	Kmv	Kmg / Kcq	Kr
<i>Arcoscalpellum withersi</i> Collins, 1973	pg. 132							&							
<i>Costadromia hajzeri</i> Feldmann and Schweitzer, 2019	pg. 134							X							
<i>Cretacoranina</i> sp.	pg. 142				X	X		X							
<i>Hoploparia gabbi</i> Pilsbry, 1901	pg. 138		X			X	X	X	X		X	X			
<i>Hoploparia gladiator</i> Pilsbry, 1901	pg. 140							X		X		X			
<i>Luisogalatea cretacea</i> (Stenzel, 1945)	pg. 136							&							
<i>Macroacaena tridens</i> (Roberts, 1962)	pg. 137							&			X	X			
<i>Mesostylus mortoni</i> (Pilsbury, 1901)	pg. 132		X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X			
<i>Necrocarcinus</i> sp.	pg. 138					X		X			X	X			
<i>Paleopagurus pilsbryi</i> Roberts, 1962	pg. 142							X				X	X		
<i>Raninella</i> sp.	pg. 143							X			X				
<i>Tetracarcinus subquadratus</i> Weller, 1905	pg. 134							&		X	X	X	X		
<i>Xanthosia elegans</i> Roberts, 1962	pg. 135							&				X			
Ichno Species															
<i>Gastrochochaenolites isp.</i>	pg. 144							X	X	X					
<i>Ophiomorpha nodosa</i> Lundgren, 1891	pg. 144							X	X	X	X	X			
<i>Phycodes palmatum</i> (Hall, 1852)	pg. 144							&	X			X			
<i>Rhizocorallium</i> sp.	pg. 145							&							

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